

Causes of spatiotemporal variation in
reproductive performance
of Eurasian oystercatchers
in a human-dominated landscape

Magali Frauendorf

This thesis should be cited as:

Frauendorf, M. (2022). Causes of spatiotemporal variation in reproductive performance of Eurasian oystercatchers in a human-dominated landscape. NIOO Thesis 194. PhD Thesis, Radboud University, Nijmegen, The Netherlands.

ISBN: 978-90-832556-3-7

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6837142

Lay-out: Magali Frauendorf

Cover design & pictures: Luzie Lage (Luzie.Lage@gmx.de)

Cover photographs: Andrew Allen, Matthijs Bokje, Magali Frauendorf, Marc Griesheimer, Adu Wijnhard

Photographs & artwork: Luzie Lage (headings), Marc Griesheimer (p. 8), Iryna Litovska (p. 26, p. 62, p. 102, p. 372), Bruno Ens (p. 62, p. 372), Andrew Allen (p. 62), Katrin Schifferle (p. 62), Barbara Rodenburg-Geertsema (p. 124), Ferran Fitó (p. 174, p. 360), Audrey Dunn (p. 266), Helmut Bähr (p. 282), Adu Wijnhard (p. 7, p. 300), Bert Dijkstra (p. 370), Koos Minnaar (p. 370), Wim Tijssen (p. 362, p. 370), Matthijs Bokje (p. 370), Magali Frauendorf/CHIRP project (others)

Printed by: Print Service Ede – www.proefschriftenprinten.nl

The research presented in this thesis was carried out at the Department of Animal Ecology at the Netherlands Institute of Ecology (NIOO-KNAW) in Wageningen and at the Radboud Institute for Biological and Environmental Sciences (RIBES) at Radboud University in Nijmegen, with support of NWO-TTW (formerly STW) grant 14638.

© 2022, Magali Frauendorf (magalifrauendorf@gmail.com)

Causes of spatiotemporal variation in reproductive performance of Eurasian
oystercatchers in a human-dominated landscape

Proefschrift ter verkrijging van de graad van doctor
aan de Radboud Universiteit Nijmegen
op gezag van de rector magnificus prof. dr. J.H.J.M. van Krieken,
volgens besluit van het college voor promoties
in het openbaar te verdedigen op

woensdag 14 september 2022
om 10.30 uur precies

door

Magali Frauendorf
geboren op 29 april 1988
te Eckernförde (Duitsland)

Promotor:

Prof. dr. J.C.J.M. de Kroon

Copromotoren:

Dr. B.J. Ens (Sovon)

Dr. ir. E. Jongejans

Dr. M. van de Pol (Nederlands Instituut voor Ecologie)

Manuscriptcommissie:

Prof. dr. R.P.B. Foppen

Prof. dr. R. Norris (University of Guelph, Canada)

Prof. dr. B.I. Tieleman (Rijksuniversiteit Groningen)

Causes of spatiotemporal variation in reproductive performance of Eurasian
oystercatchers in a human-dominated landscape

Dissertation to obtain the degree of doctor
from Radboud University Nijmegen
on the authority of the Rector Magnificus prof. dr. J.H.J.M. van Krieken,
according to the decision of the Doctorate Board
to be defended in public on

Wednesday, September 14, 2022
at 10:30

by

Magali Frauendorf
born on April 29, 1988
in Eckernförde (Germany)

PhD supervisor:

Prof. dr. J.C.J.M. de Kroon

PhD co-supervisors:

Dr. B.J. Ens (Sovon)

Dr. ir. E. Jongejans

Dr. M. van de Pol (Netherlands Institute of Ecology)

Manuscript Committee:

Prof. dr. R.P.B. Foppen

Prof. dr. R. Norris (University of Guelph, Canada)

Prof. dr. B.I. Tieleman (University of Groningen)

CONTENTS

Chapter 1	General introduction	9
Chapter 2	Conceptualizing and quantifying body condition using structural equation modelling: A user guide	27
Chapter 3	Body condition mediates carry-over effects of overwintering environment on reproductive success in a shorebird population	63
Chapter 4	Love thy neighbour? – Spatial variation in density dependence of nest survival in relation to predator community	103
Chapter 5	The synergistic effects of environmental drivers of declining reproduction of a threatened meadow bird across the Netherlands	125
Chapter 6	Synthesis	157
	Appendix A - Supplementary material chapter 2	175
	Appendix B - Supplementary material chapter 3	239
	Appendix C - Supplementary material chapter 4	267
	Appendix D - Supplementary material chapter 5	283
	Appendix E - Supplementary material chapter 6	301
	Bibliography	306
	Research data management	351
	Summary	352
	Samenvatting	356
	Curriculum Vitae	362
	List of publications	364
	PE&RC Training and Education Statement	366
	Acknowledgements	371

CHAPTER 1

General introduction

'A hundred years ago, there were one and a half billion people on Earth. Now, over six billion crowd our fragile planet.' – Sir David Attenborough.

To fulfil their growing needs humans altered their environment drastically (Foley et al., 2011; Steffen et al., 2007), putting the natural ecosystems all over the globe under enormous pressure. The impact by humans leads to habitat destruction, agriculture intensification, overexploitation of natural resources and a changing climate (Barnosky et al., 2012; Ellis et al., 2013; Feddema et al., 2005; Foley et al., 2011; Rockström et al., 2009). Ultimately, this results in biodiversity loss and reduced resilience of ecosystems to cope with the changing environment.

Consequences of environmental change

Within an ecosystem, populations are forced to adapt to environmental change, but not all succeed. Climate change for instance affects community composition by increasing the dominance of generalist taxa and larger basal prey species, whereas habitat specialists, rare species, and species with more northerly distributions are threatened with extinction (Moritz & Agudo, 2013). One of the central problems in population biology, ecology and conservation is to understand spatiotemporal fluctuations in population abundance. Population dynamics (e.g. changes in abundance over time) are a function of three fundamental demographic variables: reproduction, survival and dispersion (Rothschild et al., 1997; Townsend et al., 2008). For instance, a population can increase because of higher reproductive success, but also due to high immigration rates into the area or due to low mortality.

Therefore, understanding how anthropogenic factors affect population dynamics is crucial to be able to explain why species are threatened, and also to be able to turn the tide (Cardillo et al., 2005). Since management actions to conserve a species have to influence one or more of these three demographic variables, it is relevant to quantify the impact of these variables on the population dynamic, how they interrelate as well as their link with environmental variables (Nichols et al., 2004). However, conservation actions that only target single-threat drivers risk of being inadequate because multiple drivers may interact to mitigate or intensify global environmental change (Darling & Cote, 2008; Didham et al., 2007; Mora et al., 2007). For example, habitat loss might increase the vulnerability of some species to global warming by further stressing their

physiological tolerance and making range shifts impossible (Brook et al., 2008). Ignoring these synergistic effects increases the uncertainties of models that predict the impact of environmental change (Darling & Cote, 2008). Especially specialized species are at greater risk to experience negative synergistic effects threatening its extinction (Davies et al., 2004).

Given that the impact of environmental conditions may differ at large spatial scale and therefore changes of the environment likely cover a large spatial extent, ecological research should be addressed on a broad scale (Noon & Dale, 2002). This requires a considerable amount of data collected over a large spatial and/or temporal extents (Devictor et al., 2010). Citizen science is perhaps the only practical way (Box 1.1) to achieve the geographic range required to document ecological patterns and address ecological questions at scales relevant to species range shifts, migration patterns, spread of infectious disease, broad-scale population trends and impacts of environmental processes like landscape and climate change (Dickinson et al., 2010; Kobori et al., 2016).

The role of intrinsic factors

Next to extrinsic (environmental) factors, intrinsic (density-regulated) factors may influence population dynamics. Density dependence can take positive or negative directions. At high population densities close to the carrying capacity, population density and growth are generally negatively related due to increased competition for resources (Dunn et al., 2015), predator attraction (Gunnarsson & Elmberg, 2008) or parasite transmission (Deredec & Curchamp, 2006), which prevents populations from growing further (Mayer et al., 2019). On the other hand, at low population size, density dependence can be positive due to problems in, for example, finding mates or deterring predators (Kramer et al., 2011). If declining populations reach low densities, positive density dependence could lead to an acceleration of decline, ultimately causing an extinction vortex (Luque et al., 2016). This process, also known as Allee effect (Allee, 1927), may occur even if the original (extrinsic) factor that caused the initial population decline is no longer present.

One challenge for ecological research is that intrinsic factors can have direct influence on demographic variables, but they can also affect population dynamics in a

synergistic manner, by interacting with extrinsic factors (Sæther, 1997). For example, de Little et al. (2007) show a complex interplay between density and weather condition on juvenile survival in southern elephant seals (*Mirounga leonina*). They emphasize the importance to evaluate both, intrinsic and extrinsic, factors rather than examining these factors in isolation. By ignoring those potential synergistic effects, erroneous conclusions may be drawn that can have substantial impact on implications on population regulations.

Full annual cycle research

The ecology of many vertebrates is organized into annual cycles that consist of different stages e.g. the reproductive phase, the non-breeding residency, and (for migratory species) a migratory phase in between (Calvert et al., 2009). Different seasonal environments can influence seasonal vital rates in a direct way: wintering area influences winter survival, migration affects migratory survival and the breeding area impacts the survival in breeding season and the reproductive success (Calvert et al., 2009; Fig. 1.1). However, these stages are not only linked physiologically and ecologically in a direct way, but preceding events may have profound consequences on the following life history phases (Norris & Marra, 2007). For migratory species, these stages are not only temporally separated, but also spatially. For example, residing in sub-optimal habitat at non-breeding areas can result in delayed spring migration, consequently negatively affecting breeding performance the following season (Cтры et al., 2013; Low et al., 2015; Marra et al., 1998; Norris et al., 2004).

Several taxa include migrating species. Various bird species migrate from breeding to wintering areas and back to breeding grounds. African ungulates follow the rain to ensure high food availability (Leuthold, 2012). Marine mammals like for instance grey whale (*Eschrichtius robustus*) nurse in the Arctic (Boyd, 2004). The well-known monarch butterfly (*Danaus plexippus*) covers thousands of kilometres during fall migration from the northern and central United States and southern Canada to Florida and Mexico (Reppert & de Roode, 2018). European eel (*Anguilla anguilla*) begin their life cycle in the ocean and spend most of their lives in fresh inland water, or brackish coastal water, returning to the Bermuda Triangle to spawn and then die (Tamario et al., 2019).

Thus, even though several species migrate and, therefore, the stages of their annual

cycle are geographically and temporally distinct, still, our understanding of the fundamental ecology of four vertebrate classes (birds, mammals, amphibians, reptiles) has been limited by a severe single (breeding) season research bias (Marra et al., 2015). The authors show in a review that up to 75% of research considered only the breeding season and only 5.5% of the studies investigated seasonal interactions. Recent emergence of new analytical and technological tools for studying individual and population-level animal movement already helped to double the number of studies on seasonal interaction (in almost two decades) (Marra et al., 2015). Probably, this positive development will continue in the future.

Carry over effects and body condition

Seasonal interactions are also called carry-over effects. Carry-over effects, i.e. when processes in one season influence processes in the next season, are believed to have important effects on the behaviour and fitness in animals. Most studies investigate carry-over effects by linking environmental conditions in one season to the individual performance (reproduction, survival) in the subsequent season (Harrison et al., 2011).

Carry-over effects in migratory species are particularly challenging because migrants not only live in different areas in different seasons, but individuals from the same breeding (or overwintering) area may overwinter (or breed) in different areas (Gunnarsson et al., 2005; Norris et al., 2004). For example, the carry-over effect on reproduction could be mediated by winter condition in different places, which in turn are affected by spatially varying environmental conditions. This complexity emphasizes the need to study carry-over effects on a large spatial scale.

In addition, in the presence of carry-over effects in migratory species, we can search for causes of decline in one season (e.g. in breeding grounds for reproduction), but the cause may lie in another season (wintering grounds). Ignoring such a relationship may lead to a misclassification of the mechanism underlying the individual variation.

Short-distance migrants may suffer less from direct reduced survival during the migration event itself where long-distance migrants experience huge challenges (Both et al., 2010). However, they also have to deal with spatially distinct events that may influence the subsequent annual cycle stage and should not be ignored when trying to understand population dynamics. Nevertheless, only few studies suggest that seasonal

Figure 1.1: Schematic illustration of the thesis (and CHIRP project). Arrows represent the direct seasonal fitness impacts (solid lines) and seasonal interaction (dashed line). Blue coloured boxes and lines indicate the wintering ground (stationary, non-breeding habitat), whereas the yellow coloured boxes and arrows indicate the breeding area (also illustrated by the profile drawings). Chapter numbers indicate in which chapter the relationships are investigated. Grey boxes indicate the potential extrinsic (environmental) and intrinsic (density-related) drivers occurring in the wintering and/or breeding area. Dark grey boxes show the drivers that were studied in this thesis; light grey and green boxes were studied in other sub-projects of the CHIRP project. Note that potential interactive effects between the drivers are not visualized here, but mentioned in the text.

interactions may also impact short-distance migrants (Duriez et al., 2012).

To get a better understanding of the mechanistic link between non-breeding and breeding season and its consequences for the individual performance, it is essential to use traits that reflect the state of an individual (e.g. condition, arrival/departure date) that link habitat quality or climate conditions in one season to the performance in the next season (Fig. 1.1; Harrison et al., 2011; Swift et al., 2020). If the mechanistic link of a potential carry-over effect is not taken into account, one may draw erroneous conclusions. This may be the case when, for instance, the individual performance superficially appears to be affected through an individual trait, but in reality it is the result of environmental conditions in two subsequent seasons that affect each other.

Body condition is an important determinant of an individuals' fitness and its implications are of great interest to ecologists. Many authors have addressed the relationship between condition and performance variables such as reproductive investment, survivorship, parasite loads or investment in characters used in sexual display. However, most authors are either (i) not explicit about what they mean by 'body condition' or (ii) they use restrictive definition of body condition by usually referring to the relative size of energy stores compared with structural components of the body (Green, 2001).

Simple metrics such as body size or mass may not be enough to predict and measure the strength of carry-over effects (Harrison et al., 2011). Two individuals could be of similar body mass, and thus appear superficially to be in similar condition, but in practice may still have different abilities to deal with systematic challenges such as oxidative stress or disease. Additionally, whether there is an underlying physiological mechanism within carry-over effects remains unclear (Harrison et al., 2011; McNamara & Houston, 2008b). In fact, in the last decade it has become clear that different metrics of body condition other than body mass (e.g. hormonal or physiological state) appear to be appropriate predictors, at least in species with determinate growth strategy (Barry & Wilder, 2013; Nie et al., 2014). In addition, a few studies have suggested that hormones and the immune system may be involved in carry-over effects as well (Crossin et al., 2012; Hegemann et al., 2015). For instance, Schultner et al. (2014) experimentally elevated the stress hormone corticosterone in chick rearing black-legged kittiwakes (*Rissa tridactyla*). Higher secretion of corticosterone is often

associated with a response to food shortages. Corticosterone-treated females left the breeding grounds earlier and spent a longer period at the wintering grounds than control birds.

Therefore, to identify the mechanism of a carry-over effect, it is essential to measure a state variable (e.g. nutritional, hormonal, immune state) in one season, ideally link it to environmental drivers in that season, and relate it to its performance in the next season, which is rarely done.

Study system: The Eurasian oystercatcher in the Netherlands

With about 518 residents per square kilometre, the Netherlands is the second most densely-populated country in Europe (World Bank Group, 2021). Consequently, in the Dutch landscape, ecosystems are experiencing very strong human pressure, and it is the expectation that some species profit, whereas others are threatened (van Turnhout, 2010).

The number of meadow birds strongly decreased in the last decades all over Western Europe (BirdLife International, 2021). Breeding bird counts from Sovon (Dutch Centre for Field Ornithology) indicate that the Eurasian oystercatcher (*Haematopus ostralegus*, hereafter “oystercatcher”) population show the steepest decline compared to other meadow bird species (Fig. 1.2) in the Netherlands.

The North Sea (specifically United Kingdom, the Netherlands and Germany) comprises most of the global breeding (69%) and overwintering (78%) population of this species of oystercatchers, with 30% of the European population breeding in the Netherlands (van de Pol et al., 2014).

Oystercatcher life history

The oystercatcher historically breeds on saltmarshes and dunes along the coastline of Europe, where it feeds on intertidal mudflats. Since the 1950s, it colonized inland breeding areas up to a few hundred kilometres from the coast, and it now predominantly (75% of the Dutch population) breeds on agricultural land in many parts of Europe (Ens et al., 2011; Goss-Custard, 1996). A new trend in more recent years is the colonization of cities as breeding habitat (Ens & Underhill, 2014). Thus, although

oystercatchers are historically and taxonomically shorebirds, they are nowadays often meadow birds or even city-dwellers.

Figure 1.2: Relative national population trend from 1990 to 2019 for five meadow bird species. The population size from 1990 is set to 100. The indices are calculated from breeding bird monitoring programs. Data source: Netwerk Ecologische Monitoring (NEM), Sovon, provinces & CBS, www.sovon.nl; images: Vogelbescherming Nederland.

With a maximum recorded lifespan of 43 years (Fransson et al., 2017), oystercatchers are one of the longest-living breeding birds in the Netherlands. In line with life history theory of long-lived species, oystercatchers likely prioritise their own survival over reproduction, suggesting, on a population level, higher sensitivity to reduced survival than to reduced reproduction (Sæther & Bakke, 2000). However, the present population declines in meadow birds across Europe are caused by a decrease in reproduction rather than in adult survival, from a demographic perspective (Plard et al., 2019; Roodbergen et al., 2012). The reproductive output is presently too low to compensate for adult mortality. This emphasizes the necessity to focus on investigating the causes for the reduced reproductive success on a large national scale.

During the breeding season (April to July), pairs lay from one to four (on average three) eggs in a shallow nest scrape on the ground which they incubate for 27 days. Vegetation around clutches and cryptic egg colours as well as markings provide the

Chapter 1

major source of nest concealment, as they use little nesting material. Oystercatchers are single brooded, but (multiple) replacement clutches are common when the first clutch failed. Young fledge after about 30-35 days. Breeding success showed a strong decline from before 1980s to 2006, reaching a low level of about 0.2-0.5 fledglings per pair in more recent years, highly depending on breeding habitat (Allen et al., 2021; Koffijberg et al., 2021; Roodbergen et al., 2012; van de Pol et al., 2014).

The oystercatcher population in the Netherlands is partial migrant, but over relatively short distances. Partial migration, where a fraction of the population is migratory and the other sedentary, is observed in many animal taxa (Lundberg, 1988). About one-third of the Dutch oystercatcher population migrates to inland breeding areas after having spent the winter in the Dutch Wadden Sea or Delta area estuary (Allen et al., 2019a). The remaining two-thirds of the population stays on coastal breeding grounds (on the islands and mainland coasts) for breeding.

The decision to migrate or not to migrate is typically not a completely random event, but shaped by natural selection (Lundberg, 1988). One explanation often mentioned for the two behavioural alternatives is fitness balancing, where it is the question if migrants and residents within a population are equally fit or if one of the categories is inferior (Lundberg, 1988). It is not clear yet, which characteristics shape the distinction between migrants and residents in the Dutch population. In addition, the wintering population can be seen as a 'mixed' one. Breeding birds from higher latitudes (e.g. Norway) winter together with the Dutch population, and Dutch breeding birds are also recorded in winter at lower latitudes (e.g. France).

A substantial effort has been made in the last decade to engage citizen scientists with the oystercatcher project in the Netherlands (see Box 1.1). Oystercatchers are marked with individual recognizable colour rings (containing letters or numbers) across a large spatial scale and numerous resightings occur year-round. Individuals have been marked in both organized captures (e.g. using mist nets, cannon nets, traps on the nest) and opportunistically by volunteers (e.g. trapping individuals on the nest during the breeding season). Since the 'The Year of the Oystercatcher' in 2008, organized by BirdLife Netherlands and Sovon (Ens et al., 2011), and the launch of an online portal (Wadertrack, now CR-birding submit), where captures and subsequent observations are entered, the engagement of citizen scientists showed a substantial increase. In

addition, 'RAS-projects' (Retrapping Adults for Survival) and 'Nestkaart-project' (with an online portal and more recently also a mobile application) initiated by Sovon, resulted in a large spatial cover of the monitoring of the breeding success of oystercatchers. All these data obtained by citizen scientists are crucial to quantify seasonal movement, survival and reproductive output.

Potential causes of oystercatcher decline

The decline of the population may be caused by several threats throughout the annual life cycle of an oystercatcher varying on spatial and temporal scale (van de Pol et al., 2014). During summer, agricultural intensification (e.g. destruction of clutches through mowing, reduced earthworm biomass; Beintema & Muskens, 1987; Onrust et al., 2019) and drought (earthworm being deeper in the soil) may impact inland breeding birds; with earthworms being an important food source. Local observations from roof-breeding urban oystercatchers report higher reproductive success, maybe due to lower impacts of mammalian predators (Ens & Underhill, 2014). For coastal breeding birds, however, an increasing incidence of flooding events is a threat (van de Pol et al., 2014). Predation is often reported as one of the most important risks that negatively affect the reproductive success (Teunissen et al., 2005).

All those drivers might interact. For instance, birds that breed on less suitable land (e.g. intensively managed fields) with lower ground water level, where earthworms are already rare, suffer probably even more from dry weather condition during chick rearing when worms are even less available.

However, since density-dependence (as intrinsic factor) could also drive population dynamics, there is reasonable concern that a nation-wide Allee effect may cause the decline of the population. This concern originated from experiments conducted (on local scale) on a Dutch island that showed that predation on oystercatcher clutches decreased at higher breeding oystercatcher density (Bailey et al., 2017). The authors suggest that a higher number of neighbours helps in predator deterrence through mobbing behaviour. With a declining population and, consequently, lower breeding density, an Allee effect could cause an acceleration of the decline. In addition, since breeding densities in inland breeding grounds are lower compared to coastal breeding habitats, the question arises to what extent the breeding density in inland breeding

grounds affects the reproductive success.

Moreover, it is important to get insight if the density-dependent effect from the local population can be generalized on a large national scale. If so, that would mean, that the effectiveness of the anti-predator behaviour of oystercatchers (e.g. mobbing) that is observed on the island does not vary over space. However, the type of predator species for oystercatcher nests vary spatially. Therefore, we may expect that whether aggregation during the reproductive season (i.e. breeding at high density) incurs a benefit or a cost in birds, and thus results in a positive or negative density effect on nest survival, may depend on how predators and prey interact (Forsman et al., 1998; Ringelman, 2014) and on the presence and behaviour (e.g. cognitive and perceptual ability) of nest predators (Auger-Methe et al., 2016; Blanco & Bertellotti, 2002; Rangen et al., 2001). Anti-predator behaviour by the parents, like predator mobbing (Krams et al., 2009), can reduce nest predation rates if birds nest close to each other and help in protecting neighbouring nests (Larsen & Grundetjern, 1997; Quinn & Ueta, 2008). However, if the anti-predator behaviour of the prey species is ineffective, for example if densities become too low for group defence to be effective (Sönnichsen et al., 2013), spacing out to avoid predators may be a more efficient predator avoidance strategy (Picman, 1988). If predators can learn to exploit areas with higher nest densities (Larivière & Messier, 1998; Ringelman, 2014; Yahner & Mahan, 1996) or by exhibiting “area-restricted searching” behaviour once they find a nest (Bernard, 2004), this will increase the predation risk of nests at high densities. Thus, quantifying how extrinsic and intrinsic factors interact (during breeding season) on a large national scale can give important insights on the causes for the population decline.

During winter, climate change, human disturbance or competition with shellfisheries impacts the wintering birds (Linssen et al., 2019; van de Pol et al., 2014; van der Kolk et al., 2020; Verhulst et al., 2004). The invasive Pacific oyster (*Crassostrea gigas*) has become abundant in the Dutch Delta and is increasing in the Dutch Wadden Sea (van de Pol et al., 2014). Oystercatchers generally do not feed on this oyster species but it is reported to invade mussel beds and may compete with cockles and mussels, consequently reducing oystercatcher food availability (Waser et al., 2016).

Until now, studies on oystercatcher population dynamics have either focussed on what happens in winter and how this affects survival, or have focussed on what

happens in summer and how this affects reproduction (van de Pol et al., 2014). In addition, even though we observe differences in habitat types in the reproductive success, the oystercatcher individuals share their (common) wintering ground being much more clustered in winter than in summer. Therefore, it seems obvious that there may be some common threats in winter that may carry over to the subsequent breeding season influencing the reproductive output. Identifying potential carry-over effects may help in understanding the population dynamics of the Dutch oystercatcher population.

Therefore, to get better insights in the population decline, it is important to identify the relative importance of all these different threats (including their synergies) that (a) occur at different stages of their annual life cycle and (b) depend on where the individual is located in space and time.

Research outline

The above introduction points to several knowledge gaps in ecological research that are important to consider to better understand the temporal and spatial variation in reproductive performance; ultimately resulting in a better understanding of the causes for the Dutch population decline:

- 1) The study of multiple threats and their synergistic effects on a large spatial scale.
- 2) An appropriate quantification of body condition (including physiological measures).
- 3) Research on seasonal interactions between different parts of the annual life cycle, especially with a focus on a mechanistic understanding via a state variable (e.g. body condition) (Fig. 1.1).

With the help of a large and passionate citizen science network and advanced statistical approaches, I aim to fill the above-mentioned knowledge gaps concerning the Dutch oystercatcher population. This research is part of the CHIRP (Cumulative Human Impact on biRd Populations) project that aims to quantify the cumulative impact of all potential human pressures on reproductive success and survival of oystercatchers in the Netherlands.

In this thesis, we investigate the environmental impact at two stages of the annual cycle of the oystercatcher: at the wintering ground (chapter 2 and 3) and at the

breeding ground (chapter 4 and 5) while also studying the seasonal interaction (chapter 3) between winter and summer (Fig. 1.1). In more detail, in chapter 2 we introduce a conceptual framework to quantify body condition for a wide range of ecological questions. We provide a statistical user guide where we use the oystercatcher as a model species to quantify the winter body condition (including nutritional, hormonal and physiological state) within the framework of Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). In chapter 3 we apply and integrate the body condition quantification method described in chapter 2 in a Bayesian mark-recapture framework to investigate if we can identify a carry-over effect and how environmental variables in winter affect the individual body condition. Then, we move on to the breeding area and identify how the relationship of nest density in combination with different predator composition affects the clutch survival in oystercatchers (chapter 4). Finally, we study how predator density, food availability, weather condition and land use intensity and their synergistic effects impact the clutch and hatchling survival of oystercatchers on a national scale (chapter 5). Chapter 6 synthesizes the major findings of this dissertation and outlines perspectives for future research and management implications.

Box 1.1: Citizen science - Chances and challenges

Citizen science is the process whereby citizens participate in scientific research by collecting data, monitoring sites and even taking part in the whole process of scientific inquiry (Aceves-Bueno et al., 2017; Kruger & Shannon, 2000). Citizen scientists contribute to science for the love of it, not for the payment. They usually have no formal qualifications but a high level of expertise, appropriate to the studies in which they participate, often gained through extensive field experience (Greenwood, 2007).

Among others due to advancing technologies (e.g. mobile applications), citizen science has increased, covering a wide range of research fields. So far, citizen science projects have contributed to investigate many different targets, like identifying the mechanisms driving species responses to land-use changes or global warming (Jiguet et al., 2007; Rosenberg et al., 1999) and quantifying changes in plant phenology (e.g. Phenoclim program in the European Alps; Bison et al. 2019). Citizen science data have also been used to assist with the conservation of various organisms and to assess protected area efficiency (Devictor et al., 2010; Greenwood, 2007). Citizen science

programs are also very flexible so that they can be implemented for very different taxonomic groups (Devictor et al., 2010).

A major strength of using datasets from citizen science in large-scale analysis is precisely their large sample size (Greenwood, 2007) which ensures a great statistical power (e.g. the probability of detecting a trend) and high robustness (e.g. the stability of the trend to change in datasets) (Newman et al., 2003; Schmeller et al., 2009). Moreover, the strength of citizen science programs directly relies on the curiosity and pleasure of the citizen scientists to learn and observe their environment and share their observations with scientists (Devictor et al., 2010).

There are also limitations and challenges with citizen science. Scientists should inform participants about the progress of citizen science programs and communicate regularly (e.g. presenting results) (Devictor et al., 2010). Thus, projects often involve regular feedback moments, online visualization of data and newsletters. A positive side effect is that the involvement in citizen science makes sure that scientists clearly communicate the societal importance of their research.

Despite the growth in the number of citizen science projects, scientists remain concerned about the accuracy of citizen science data (Aceves-Bueno et al., 2017). Some studies that evaluated the data quality have found citizen science data to be more variable than professionally collected data (Moyer-Horner et al., 2012). On the other side, promisingly, other studies show that citizen scientists' performance is comparable to that of professionals (Bison et al., 2019; Oldekop et al., 2011). In addition, the often very large sample sizes will tend to increase precision (Dickinson et al., 2010). However, those data quality issues are not unique to citizen science. Citizen science data are not perfect, actually, no data are (Tulloch et al., 2013). Thus, this should not inhibit the use of this vital resource in broad ecological research. There are some ways to ensure high data quality:

- 1) A careful study design with appropriate training of citizen scientists and clear instructions (Greenwood, 2007; Weisshaupt et al., 2021).
- 2) Well-designed protocols with a standardized sampling procedure including sufficient temporal and spatial representation (Greenwood, 2007; Lukyanenko et al., 2016).
- 3) Automatic algorithms and filters to correct obvious erroneous entries (e.g. outside typical dates of occurrence, excessive bird numbers) (Weisshaupt et al., 2021). In

addition, manual corrections through direct contact with citizens can be useful to rectify potentially incorrect entries.

4) The development of advanced statistical approaches to minimize the effects of these biases (Dickinson et al., 2010). For instance, biases due to heterogeneous and imperfect observation processes (Johnston et al., 2018) or biases in the distribution of survey effort across space and time (Fink et al., 2020; Robinson et al., 2018; Szabo et al., 2010).

Of course, the issues of bias must be addressed in a question-specific way and it is important to realize that data being unbiased for one question are not necessarily unbiased for another (Dickinson et al., 2010). Overall, since citizen science driven questions do not usually aim to uncover mechanisms underlying ecological patterns, it is best viewed as complementary, hypothesis-driven, research. The increasing citizen science field has led to new, quantitative approaches to emerging questions about the distribution and abundance of species across space and time (Dickinson et al., 2010).

Citizen science is based on good partnership and expands opportunities for learning among citizens and scientists (Kruger & Shannon, 2000). For citizens the motivation is to contribute to “real” science, public information and conservation. For a scientist, citizen science offers a way to collect information that would otherwise be impossible on such a scale (Kruger & Shannon, 2000; Tulloch et al., 2013). Some scientists may become involved with citizen science merely in order to get hold of data for their own interests, using citizens merely as unpaid labour. However, scientists and citizens should work as partners (Greenwood, 2007). For a scientist, the citizen should be seen as “they know minimal as good as we do, in some cases even better” and “their perception is different from ours, therefore, let consult each other and work together, because what we study concerns us all!” (Greenwood, 2007). Of course, perspectives between citizens and scientists may differ, but with careful management (of feedback moments and good communication), long-term projects can become a success (Greenwood, 2007).

CHAPTER 2

Conceptualizing and quantifying body condition using structural equation modelling: A user guide

Magali Frauendorf, Andrew M. Allen, Simon Verhulst, Eelke Jongejans, Bruno J. Ens, Henk-Jan van der Kolk, Hans de Kroon, Jeroen Nienhuis, Martijn van de Pol

Abstract

Body condition is an important concept in behaviour, evolution and conservation, commonly used as a proxy of an individual's performance, for example in the assessment of environmental impacts. Although body condition potentially encompasses a wide range of health state dimensions (nutritional, immune or hormonal status), in practice most studies operationalize body condition using a single (univariate) measure, such as fat storage. One reason for excluding additional axes of variation may be that multivariate descriptors of body condition impose statistical and analytical challenges. Structural equation modelling (SEM) is used in many fields to study questions relating multidimensional concepts, and we here explain how SEM is a useful analytical tool to describe the multivariate nature of body condition. In this "Research Methods Guide" paper, we show how SEM can be used to resolve different challenges in analysing the multivariate nature of body condition, such as (i) variable reduction and conceptualization, (ii) specifying the relationship of condition to performance metrics, (iii) comparing competing causal hypothesis, and (iv) including many pathways in a single model to avoid stepwise modelling approaches. We illustrated the use of SEM on a real-world case study, and provide R-code of worked examples as a learning tool. We compared the predictive power of SEM with conventional statistical approaches that integrate multiple variables into one condition variable: multiple regression and principal component analysis. We show that model performance on our dataset is higher when using SEM, and led to more accurate and precise estimates compared to conventional approaches. We encourage researchers to consider SEM as a flexible framework to describe the multivariate nature of body condition and thus understand how it affects biological processes, thereby improving the value of body condition proxies for predicting organismal performance. Finally, we highlight that it can be useful for other multidimensional ecological concepts as well, such as immunocompetence, oxidative stress and environmental conditions.

Introduction

Body condition is (by definition) a key determinant of an individual's fitness (Wilder et al., 2016). Understanding how best to quantify body condition therefore has implications in behavioural (Kirk & Gosler, 1994), evolutionary (Aubry et al., 2013) and conservation (Stirling & Derocher, 2012) studies, but how to analyse and estimate body condition has remained a subject of debate for decades (Wilder et al., 2016). Notably, there is currently no consensus on a strict definition of body condition, although there is conceptual agreement that the term describes the degree to which an animal's health state influences its performance (e.g. reproduction) (Brown, 1996; Peig & Green, 2009). The concept of body condition can thus encompass a wide range of morphological and physiological metrics that describe the nutritional, immune and/or hormonal state of an individual. Which of such metrics are most relevant will depend on the study system and aims, and therefore also on the performance variable of interest (e.g. survival, reproduction, activity) (Table 2.1).

Despite the multidimensional nature of body condition, most ecological studies operationalize body condition by quantifying a single (univariate) measurable variable (Wilder et al., 2016). In studies in which the energy stores are thought to be important for the individual's performance, often it is approximated by the mass of an individual relative to its size, as this is assumed to reflect internal fat content (Durell et al. 2001; Janssen et al. 2011; Schulte-Hostedde et al. 2005; see van der Meer & Piersma (1994) for the distinction between energy reserves and energy stores). Well-known examples include the body mass index in humans (BMI, $\text{mass}/\text{length}^2$; Nuttall 2015), or the residuals of body mass regressed to one or more variables of structural size (e.g. tarsus or head length; Jakob et al. 1996), which are widely used in avian studies (Peig & Green, 2009). However, two individuals with similar BMI may still differ in various other aspects of their health, quality or vigour (Stevenson & Woods, 2006). The BMI in humans, for instance, reflects different body composition in men and women (e.g. women have more fat and men more muscles; Jackson et al. 2002) and therefore appears to be a poor predictor of morbidity and mortality, as people with similar BMI can have different metabolic health (Roberson et al., 2014). In fact, it has now become clear that different metrics of body condition are also related to aspects other than the

Table 2.1: An overview highlighting the diversity of studies investigating body condition with different aspects of an individual's health state and performance measures. Note that this overview is not based on an exhaustive search, as it only aims to illustrate the diversity in health status metrics considered for different performance metrics.

Performance \ Health status		Nutritional state	Immune state	Hormonal state
Reproduction	Reproductive output (eggs, fledglings)	- Abdominal profile index ¹ - Residual mass ¹ - Nutrients (protein content) ²	- Principal component of packed cell volume, haemoglobin, scaled mass, muscle score, fat score ²⁴ - Carotenoid ²⁵	- Corticosterone ^{26, 27, 28, 29, 30}
	Milk production	- Body condition scoring ^{3, 4, 5}		
	Lay date	- Abdominal profile index ¹		- Corticosterone ³¹
	Paternal investment (sexual selection, male attraction)	- Residual mass ^{6, 7} - Fulton index (weight/length ³) ⁷ - Nutrients (protein content) ²	- Lymphocyte ⁶ - Parasite load ⁷	- Testosterone ³²
Survival	Mortality risk through disease (e.g. obesities)	- Subcutaneous and abdominal fat ⁸ - Body Mass Index (mass/length ²) ⁹ - Scaled mass index ¹⁰		
	Survival (adult, juveniles)	- Principal component of haematocrit, buffy coat, residual mass ¹¹ Scaled mass index ¹²	- Principal component of haematocrit, buffy coat, residual mass ¹¹ - Parasite load ¹² - Carotenoid ²⁵	- Testosterone ³³ - Corticosterone ³⁴

Table 2.1: Continued.

Performance \ Health status		Nutritional state	Immune state	Hormonal state
Growth	Chick/nestling growth	- Ratio (mass/length) ¹³ - Residual mass (mass~pc1(body size)) ¹⁴		- Corticosterone ^{14, 35, 36} - Testosterone ³⁷
	Adult growth	- Muscle index ¹⁵ - Liver enzyme activity ¹⁶		
Foraging	Foraging efficiency/strategy	- Visible fat scores ¹⁷ - Ratio(mass/length) ¹⁷ - Residual mass ¹⁹		- Corticosterone ³⁵
	Foraging condition	- Subcutaneous fat ¹⁸ - Plasma parameters (e.g. protein, urea, cholesterol, carbohydrates) ²⁰ - Nutrients (e.g. calcium, phosphorus, nitrogen) ²¹ - Liver enzyme activity ¹⁶		- Corticosterone ^{38, 39, 40, 41, 42}
Migration	Migratory behaviour	- Subcutaneous or abdominal fat scoring ^{1, 17, 22}		
Response to environment	Response to ecotoxicologically polluted area	- Scaled mass index ²³		

¹Bêty et al. (2003) ²Barry & Wilder (2013) ³Russel et al. (1969) ⁴Edmonson et al. (1989) ⁵Roche et al. (2009) ⁶Gleeson et al. (2005) ⁷Neff & Cargnelli (2004) ⁸German et al. (2006) ⁹Nuttall (2015) ¹⁰MacCracken & Stebbings (2012) ¹¹Verhulst et al. (2004) ¹²Souchay et al. (2013) ¹³Beintema (1994) ¹⁴Williams et al. (2008) ¹⁵Brown & Murphy (2004) ¹⁶Metón et al. (1999) ¹⁷Swanson et al. (1999) ¹⁸Bearhop et al. (2004) ¹⁹Durell et al. (2001) ²⁰Alonso-Alvarez et al. (2002) ²¹Nie et al. (2014) ²²Wiersma & Piersma (1995) ²³Tête et al. (2013) ²⁴Milenkaya et al. (2015) ²⁵Simons et al. (2012) ²⁶Angelier et al. (2010) ²⁷Ouyang et al. (2011) ²⁸Kouwenberg et al. (2013) ²⁹Perez et al. (2016) ³⁰Montreuil-Spencer et al. (2019) ³¹Schoech et al. (2004) ³²Saino & Møller (1995) ³³Dufty (1989) ³⁴Rivers et al. (2012) ³⁵Kitaysky et al. (2003) ³⁶Sheriff et al. (2009) ³⁷von Engelhardt et al. (2006) ³⁸Jimeno, Briga, et al. (2017) ³⁹Jimeno et al. (2018) ⁴⁰Jimeno, Hau, et al. (2017) ⁴¹Marra & Holberton (1998) ⁴²Kitaysky et al. (1999)

energetic state of an individual (Table 2.1). Such non-energetic aspects can be an additional or even more appropriate predictor of fitness (Cox & Calsbeek 2015; McGuire et al. 2018; with fitness measuring the genetic contribution to future generations). For example, an animal can have high lipid content but have low reproductive success if it is deficient in other nutrients (e.g. protein, vitamins, minerals) that it needs to reproduce (Nie et al., 2014).

These examples indicate that operationalizing body condition via univariate descriptors of body energy stores is unsatisfactory for two reasons. Firstly, the underlying assumption that there is a (monotonic) positive association between energy stores and organismal performance has often been falsified. This suggests that it is important to also consider other measures of the health state beyond energy stores, such as physiological measures (Table 2.1; note that here our point is to emphasize that a variety of body condition measures can be and are used in ecological and (veterinary) health research and that no 'perfect' metric exists that is universally suitable for all studies, even though we appreciate that in specific studies some condition metrics can be more relevant than other metrics for biological reasons). Secondly, a univariate approach to body condition is unlikely to fully capture what is essentially a multivariate concept, at the expense of lower power to predict variation in performance. Indeed, efforts to combine several variables into one compositional measure have been able to better predict fitness variation than each of these condition variables separately (Sousa et al., 2007; Verhulst et al., 2004). A solution to these two problems may be to not operationalize condition as one or two major axes of variation among traits that are a priori assumed to be related to fitness (e.g. univariate metrics such as fat content), but rather operationalize condition as the axis of variation (i.e. a specific composite body condition metric) that best explains variance in individual fitness or performance. Such a view is quite similar to how Wilson & Nussey (2010) conceptualized 'individual quality', though body condition is always linked to a specific aspect of individual quality (i.e. health state) and is a much more dynamic concept as it fluctuates during lifetime, while individual quality is a less flexible characteristic (e.g. social dominance).

Adopting a multivariate description of body condition and identifying which condition index best explains variation in performance or fitness, imposes statistical and analytical challenges that have thus far not been fully addressed. Studies that aim

to describe the multivariate nature of body condition have used a variety of statistical methods (e.g., multiple regression, principal component analyses), which have limited flexibility and implicitly make specific assumptions that are not always recognized. Principal component analyses (PCA) identify axes of body condition based on the correlation patterns among condition variables (Abdi & Williams, 2010), while the weight of a variable in an estimate of condition instead ideally reflects how much it contributes to explaining variation in performance relative to other variables. Multiple regression (MR) models have low flexibility in that they cannot handle variables that are simultaneously response and explanatory variables, which is resolved using stepwise modelling approaches that can potentially cause bias in the parameter estimates (Darlington & Smulders, 2001; Freckleton, 2002). Thus, there is a need for an alternative analytical framework to integrate multiple variables in one condition estimate, with their relative weight depending on their power in explaining variation in fitness, or, more usually, fitness proxies such as survival or reproductive traits (e.g. lay date, egg volume, fledgling number).

To this end, we introduce structural equation modelling (SEM) and show how it can be used to overcome the above-mentioned challenges in quantifying a body condition index. SEM is a flexible conceptual framework, where statistical and mathematical tools, along with analytical principles are used to learn about a system (Grace, 2006; Shipley, 2016). SEM builds on path-analysis, which is a statistical regression analysis that allows one to investigate patterns of effect within a system of variables by examining the impact of a set of predictor variables on multiple, possibly interrelated, response variables. Moreover, SEM extends path analysis by including unmeasured variables. For example, 'latent variables' or 'composite variables' can be used to summarize multivariate concepts, like body condition, that are not directly measurable themselves. SEM can be used to evaluate competing multivariate models of body condition, and thus learn more about the study system, and quantify the relative importance of different pathways. Although SEM originates from the social sciences (Grace et al., 2010), the capacity for evaluating multivariate hypotheses has also attracted the interest of ecologists, with some aspects of SEM (e.g. latent variables, path analysis) being widely used in specific subfields of ecology (Grace, 2006; Shipley, 2016). Belovsky et al. (2004) suggested that the ecological sciences can be advanced by

a better integration of theory and empirical evidence and by studying multiple causes simultaneously, both of which can be addressed with SEM.

We emphasize that the SEM techniques we describe are not novel from a statistical perspective. Instead, our aim is to demonstrate in a comprehensive and educational way its usefulness for the quantification of body condition indices as well as for testing biological hypotheses concerning condition through worked empirical examples on a shorebird species. Data are from a large-scale study in which we measured a variety of morphological and physiological variables on Eurasian oystercatchers (*Haematopus ostralegus*). We provide R-code of all analyses with annotations to facilitate its usage and as a learning tool for those new to SEM.

Introducing the case study used to explain the conceptual framework

The case study system

The global Eurasian oystercatcher population has declined rapidly which can be caused either by reduced reproduction or reduced survival, and thus one aim is to identify the impact of potential environmental drivers in winter affecting survival. However, survival probabilities of individuals are not directly observable, as we have to infer them from the stochastic realizations of individuals dying or not, leading to information loss (this is even more problematic when there is imperfect detection and we have to rely on capture-mark-recapture analysis for inference, which also requires many years of data collection). An additional challenge in our long-lived study species is that mortality events are rare, with an average annual adult survival rate of ~ 0.9 (Allen et al., 2019a), meaning that there is little variation in this performance metric in a single year. Both challenges limit the opportunity to detect associations between environmental drivers and survival probabilities. Creating a body condition index that is closely related to survival gives the opportunity to use a more informative fitness proxy in the future based on data that are less time-consuming to collect in the field (compared to the long-term survival data).

Therefore, the overall aim of the case study is to use health status measurements on captured birds to derive an integrative body condition index that maximizes the

explained variation in a fitness component (survival) and helps to identify how environmental drivers (competitor density) affects body condition (Fig. 2.1).

To quantify body condition, 774 oystercatchers were caught with nets at high-tide roosts and colour-banded in the Netherlands during 19 catching events spanning two winters (2016-2017: 196 birds; 2017-2018: 578 birds) (Supplementary Fig. A1; Supplementary Table A1). Several morphological and physiological variables were measured that could potentially reflect the immune, hormonal and nutritional state of an individual. In addition, we measured (carotenoid based) bill colour that may serve as a visual status signal of an individual's body condition to conspecifics (Fig. 2.1). We considered these variables based on previous studies that have shown that they can be associated with either body mass or survival (Supplementary Text A1). Some variables that we are not primarily interested in may influence multiple condition variables (Norte et al., 2009), and thereby could explain some of the intercorrelation between various condition variables. Accounting for such confounding variables may clarify to what extent these condition variables are different axes of body condition (Fig. 2.1). By considering effects of handling time (proportion of time between capture and measuring) on condition variables, we aim to statistically account for time-dependent mass loss and possible effects on other physiological variables that we are not interested in. Similarly, we want to consider confounding effects of individual characteristics like age, sex and bill shape. The age of the birds was classified in 1st, 2nd, 3rd calendar year and adults (>3rd calendar year). We focussed only on sub-adults (2nd and 3rd calendar year) and adults (>3rd calendar year) in the analysis because the number of sampled juveniles (1st calendar year) was small (n=28; Supplementary Table A1). Adult oystercatchers cannot be accurately aged and therefore we do not consider any possible effect of senescence on body condition or survival. A long-term study population in the Netherlands, in which there are many known-age individuals (e.g. marked at birth), also did not reveal any evidence that survival or body condition vary systematically with age among adults. Bill tip height was used as a proxy for the type of individual's feeding specialization ranging from worm specialists (pointed bill characterized by a low bill tip height) to shellfish specialists (blunt bill characterized by a high bill tip height) (van de Pol et al., 2009a).

We relate the body condition index to survival in the year following capture. The

Figure 2.1: Conceptual framework of the case study and how we will develop the model in three sections. The numbers in the top left of each box with interrupted lines indicate the section where the analysis of those variables is discussed. Box 1 (dotted line): Summarizing the multidimensional nature of body condition by variable reduction; Box 2 (long dashed line): Quantify body condition based on a fitness trait; Box 3 (short-dashed line): High flexibility, comparing competing hypotheses, and model performance. The grey shaded area in box 2 zooms in on the specific condition variables used and discussed in the oystercatcher case study (see section 2) and the three axes of health status illustrated in Table 2.1.

survival estimates (mean (sd), min, max: 0.87 (0.06), 0.73, 0.92) used in the case study were generated from a multi-state live and dead recoveries model and therefore are on an area-level. See Supplementary Text A1 & Table A2 for details on data collection and capture-mark-recapture modelling.

The conceptual framework applied to the case study

In the following three sections, we describe step-by-step how we quantify body condition with SEM in the oystercatcher population. We first describe how to summarize the multidimensional nature of body condition by using a variable reduction approach (box 1 in Fig. 2.1). We then describe how to quantify body condition based on a fitness trait (box 2 in Fig. 2.1). The last section combines the first two steps, but also adds confounding variables to the model (box 3 in Fig. 2.1) to illustrate the high flexibility of SEM. For comparison, we start all sections by analysing the data with a conventional statistical approach before demonstrating the SEM approach. In the last section we compare the model performance between SEM and a conventional approach.

Section 1 - Summarizing the multidimensional nature of body condition: variable reduction

In this section we will illustrate how the multivariate concept of body condition can be summarized and compared to alternative models by considering two variables of health status, namely 'energy stores' and 'bill colour' (box 1 in Fig. 2.1).

Conventional method – principal component analysis (PCA)

A conventional method that combines several measures into one compositional measure is PCA, a multivariate statistical technique that is used in most scientific disciplines (Abdi & Williams, 2010). PCA has also been used to create condition indices (e.g. Bearhop et al. 2004; Milenkaya et al. 2015; Verhulst et al. 2004). PCA summarizes multiple variables by using the shared correlation structure to derive the principal components. If the first principal component (PC1) explains the majority of the

variation, the other principal components can be ignored without much information loss, and variable reduction is achieved through using PC1 as a single new condition variable. The use of PCA is suitable for the (adult) bill colour and energy stores examples, because the different (adult) bill colour and energy stores metrics are strongly linearly interrelated (Supplementary Fig. A2 & Table A3), and such intercorrelation is a requirement for PCA.

Concerning the energy stores, we considered two alternative variables in our analysis that reflect some of the diversity of measures used in the ecological literature (Peig & Green, 2009): (1) the residuals of mass regressed against structural size measures: head length, tarsus length and wing length and (2) the ratio of mass to size (tarsus length). Both variables are assumed to be positively related to fitness (Stevenson & Woods, 2006) and are highly intercorrelated ($r=0.91$, Supplementary Fig. A2). We note that using ratios sometimes introduces underlying hidden assumptions and mathematical limitations that may need consideration, for a full discussion see Atchley & Anderson (1978). PC1 explained 96.6% of the variation (residuals: 0.98; ratio: 0.98; $n=804$; Supplementary Fig. A3 & Table A4). We therefore can conclude that the PCA performs well in summarising both correlated traits into a single variable.

For bill colour, we ran a PCA with the variables hue, chroma and luminance (components of a colour; Quesada & Senar, 2006) for both age classes separately, as we clearly see differences between the intercorrelation of the variables between adults and sub-adults (Supplementary Table A3 & Fig. A6). The PC1 of bill colour explained 88.8% and 69.4% of the variation for adults and sub-adults, respectively, and loading was approximately equal for each of the three components, except for hue in sub-adults (adults: hue=0.99, chroma=-0.90, luminance=0.95, $n=599$; sub-adults: hue=-0.49, chroma=0.99, luminance=0.92, $n=163$; see Supplementary Fig. A4-A6 and Table A5-A6). For bill colour we therefore also can conclude that the PCA performs well in summarising all three correlated colour traits into a single variable.

SEM method – confirmatory factor analysis using latent variables

A closely related statistical approach to PCA that is available in the SEM framework is a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). CFA includes two types of variables: observed variables and latent variables which are graphically represented respectively by boxes

and circles (Fig. 2.2). The ‘confirmatory’ part speaks to the knowledge one has of the theory behind the relationship between the latent and their observed variables. Latent variables are hypothetical or theoretical variables (constructs) that we assume to exist but for which we have no direct measurements, and are therefore referred to as ‘unmeasured variables’ (Grace et al., 2010). Latent variables are used in models to represent an underlying process, while observed variables serve as indicators of the effects or manifestations of the latent factors (Grace & Bollen, 2008). Latent variables play an important role in SEM because they represent a bridge between observed data and theoretical generalization (Grace & Bollen, 2008), and a part of the concept of body condition is a prime example of a latent theoretical concept, as these are latent variables made up of typically correlated condition measures (e.g. ratio and residual body mass or BMI). CFA provides a conceptual advantage: we often choose a single indicator as a surrogate for a latent concept (e.g. hue representing the more general concept ‘colour’). Including more indicators (e.g. chroma, luminance) helps to generalize this phenomenon by testing that the result is not impacted by the choice of any single indicator. This emphasizes that CFA/SEM is a logical choice in the context of the multivariate nature of body condition. The purpose of CFA is to statistically test the ability of a hypothesized (factor) model to reproduce a set of sampled data (usually through a variance–covariance matrix) (Nusair & Hua, 2010). In a CFA the estimated values for all records can be extracted and used for instance for plotting in a similar way as is done with PCA.

The use of latent variables (as a variable reduction tool) is common in social sciences and psychology (Bollen, 2002; Grace et al., 2010) and also in ecological research there is growing interest. Latent variables are for instance used to quantify species performance in plant research (Grace et al., 2016; Travis & Grace, 2010; Visser et al., 2018), or morphometrics in birds (Araya-Ajoy et al., 2019; Cubaynes et al., 2012; Pugesek & Tomer, 1996) and mammals (MacKay et al., 2017; Nespolo et al., 2003), as well as to quantify environmental conditions (Guan et al., 2016; Souchay et al., 2018), behaviour in mammals (Dochtermann & Jenkins, 2007), fish (Sprenger et al., 2012) and birds (Araya-Ajoy & Dingemanse, 2014; Dingemanse et al., 2010; Jablonszky et al., 2018; Krams et al., 2013; Moiron et al., 2019).

We created the variable ‘energy stores’ as a latent variable construct in the SEM-

framework using CFA (Fig. 2.2a). The variable energy stores was defined by both (1) the ratio of mass to tarsus length and (2) the residual of mass regressed to three structural size measurements (head length, tarsus length, wing length). Model results (Supplementary Code A1) indicate that the ratio and residual variables are positively related to the latent variable energy stores (Fig. 2.2a).

Similarly, we can create a variable 'bill colour' as a latent variable in the SEM-framework (Fig. 2.2b; Supplementary Code A2), which on a more abstract level can be seen as a common factor of several observed variables (hue, chroma and luminance) so that its associated biological consequence can be viewed to occur at the level of a bill colour factor, rather than at the level of each observed variable. Hue values indicate a scale from orange to yellow, whereas luminance and chroma give information on the lightness and saturation of the colour (see Supplementary Fig. A7 for colour component interpretation). Since we expect that the relationship among the colour variables differs between the two age classes, we conduct a multi-group CFA. The structural equation model (Fig. 2.2b, Supplementary Code A2) shows that in adults, the hue and luminance are positively intercorrelated, whereas chroma is negatively intercorrelated. In accordance with the PCA results, the CFA for sub-adults shows low intercorrelation of hue with chroma and luminance and hue contributes less to the estimate of 'bill colour' in this group.

To conclude, CFA is a technique within SEM that is conceptually related to the variable reduction technique PCA, and in our case study the values from the latent variable and PC1 are highly correlated for the energy store ($r=0.98$) and the bill colour model (adults: $r=0.95$; sub-adults: $r=0.92$), showing linear relationships over the entire range (Supplementary Fig. A8). Note that at this point 'bill colour' and 'energy stores' are latent variables which are not yet related in any way to condition. This will follow in the next two sections.

Section 2 - Quantify body condition based on a fitness trait ...

PCA and CFA identify the body-condition-axes of 'bill colour' or 'energy stores' based on the correlation patterns among observed variables (Abdi & Williams, 2010), but not on how well the different observed variables explain variation in fitness. It is not

unlikely that different body condition variables explain different parts of the variation in fitness, as they may represent different aspects ('axes') of body condition. For example, energy stores may explain variation in survival due to starvation, while immunological measures may explain variation in survival due to disease. Arguably, ecologists may often have no clear reason to assume *a priori* that the shared correlation patterns among condition variables necessarily explain most variation in fitness. Thus, different observed variables may have different weights in explaining variation in fitness, and rather than making *a priori* assumptions about the weights, SEM can be used to build a model where the weights are part of the outcome. Furthermore, when researchers use PCA/CFA, it is often implicitly assumed that a relationship between the measured condition variable (e.g. mass corrected for size) and fitness prospects exists. However, the assumption that there is a monotonic positive association between energy stores and fitness prospects has often been falsified (e.g. Barry & Wilder, 2013; Verhulst, 1998) and it is therefore important to check this key assumption.

We will illustrate the quantification of a body condition index based on a fitness trait with our case study, where our overall goal is to create a body condition index that maximizes the explained variation in annual survival (box 2 in Fig. 2.1).

... with a conventional method - multiple regression analysis (MR)

MR estimates the relationships between a response variable (e.g. fitness component) and one or more predictor variables (condition variables) (Nusair & Hua, 2010). A key characteristic of MR analysis is that it aims to show how variation in one variable can be explained by others. A limitation of MR is that they cannot handle variables being both response and predictor at the same time and therefore are limited to the examination of single process at a time. The commonly-used work around is to take a multi-step approach of performing several MR analyses sequentially (e.g. Skarpaas et al., 2011). In our hypothesized conceptual model (box 2 and grey shaded area in Fig. 2.1), body mass is seen as a predictor variable when used to explain variation in the body condition index, but simultaneously as a response variable when regressed to different structural size measurements (e.g. tarsus length) (Fig. 2.4a).

Figure 2.2: Path diagrams of the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) for the latent variables (a) energy stores (determined by mass corrected for size (equivalent to residuals on the mass axis) and by the ratio of mass/tarsus length) and (b) bill colour (determined by hue, chroma and luminance) for the two age-classes. Boxes indicate measured variables; circles represent latent variables. Arrows indicate positive significant (solid line), negative significant (dashed line) or non-significant (dotted line) path strengths with values of standardized coefficients shown next to each line. Standardized coefficients are estimates expressed in equivalent units to make it possible to compare different path strengths in the model. Standardized coefficients (scale standardization) are estimated by multiplying the slope of the with the ratio of the standard deviation of the predictor and response variable (Lefcheck, 2019). Latent variables are described by arrows going away from the latent variable indicating that they are measured by the observed variables. (c) and (d) show the equations belonging to model (a) and (b), respectively. α , λ and ϵ illustrate the intercept, slope coefficients and residual error, respectively. See Supplementary Code A1 and A2 for detailed model results and specifications.

We aimed to quantify a body condition index that explains variation in survival and is based on six measured condition variables characterizing the nutritional state, immune state and hormonal state (box 2 in Fig. 2.1, Fig. 2.4a). With a MR approach, we would answer this question by conducting the following four sequential steps. We first need to regress mass on three structural sizes (tarsus length, head length and wing length) to account for individual variation in structural size that we are not interested in (step 1). Next, we extract the residuals of this model, and regress them together with the five other condition variables (buffy coat, etc.) on the survival variable (step 2). Then, we extract the predicted values of the survival model as a body condition index (step 3). Only now, in a final fourth step, can we tackle our main question by regressing the body condition index to the environmental variable 'competitor density' to determine the effect of density on 'condition', and thereby answer how competition (e.g. for food sources) affects survival through the condition of an individual. Conducting multiple steps by using the residuals of a model as input for another model (also called residual analysis) can lead to biased parameter estimates, especially if independent variables are not totally uncorrelated (Darlington & Smulders, 2001; Freckleton, 2002).

... with SEM method - Composite variable and MIMIC

The hypothesized conceptual model (box 2 in Fig. 2.1) can be fitted in a single model within the SEM framework using 'composite variables'. Whereas 'regular' latent variables represent an unmeasured variable that leads to correlation between the observed variables (Fig. 2.3a), composite variables represent the collective effect of a group of observed or latent variables (Fig. 2.3b) (Grace & Bollen, 2008). Composite variables can be seen as a special case of a latent variable and are represented by a latent variable with zero error, which signifies that it is completely specified by its causes (Grace, 2006). Thus, if condition variables are strongly correlated, we advise to use latent variables to integrate them, whereas in composite variables, the observed contributing condition variables do not necessarily need to be correlated, which is an important flexibility of its application (Nusair & Hua, 2010).

In contrast to the use of latent variables in ecology, composite variables have been long recognized as a potentially important element of SEM, but have received very

limited use in ecology among others because of a lack of theoretical consideration (Grace & Bollen, 2008; Hopcraft et al., 2012; Pugsek & Tomer, 1996). Composite variables come in two types. One is a fixed-weight composite, in which the loadings (Υ in Fig. 2.3d) from the causes are specified a priori (Grace, 2006). An example is the ‘importance value’ in plant ecology, which is defined as the unweighted sum of the relative density, relative abundance and relative frequency (usually for a species within a community). A second type of composite is the unknown-weight composite (Grace & Bollen, 2008). The unknown weight composite is related to a multiple regression predictor, where some weighted combinations of causal influences maximize variance explanation in one or more response variables, and weights are thus estimated from the data. The concept of body condition (box 2 in Fig. 2.1) is a prime example of an ‘unknown-weight composite’ as firstly, the six condition variables (Fig. 2.4a) show low inter-correlation (Supplementary Fig. A2) and secondly, we do not know a priori how important each condition measure is for our fitness proxy survival.

We created a condition index making use of a composite variable defined as a weighted sum of the condition variables, with the weights reflecting the dependency of survival on each of the condition variables (Fig. 2.4a). This step is basically the same as in a MR. The values of the condition index variable for each record can be extracted from the SEM-model (Fig. 2.4a) so that the relationship between condition index and density can be plotted (Fig. 2.4b). Furthermore, building a condition index as a composite variable can also be done by relating it to other fitness-traits like reproduction (see Discussion), or the weights can be used to quantify the condition of birds captured in future studies, without the need for measuring their survival. We note that the six condition variables were at most weakly correlated (e.g. correlation between cholesterol and corticosterone was $r=-0.02$; Supplementary Fig. A2), and using a latent variable as part of a CFA approach would thus not be an alternative to the composite variable approach taken here.

In a MR it is not possible to handle mass as a response variable and at the same time as an explanatory variable, forcing the use of other solutions such as using the residuals of mass (as illustrated in Fig. 2.2a). An advantage of the SEM approach is that there is no need to first extract the residuals (of body mass on size) and then summarize the variables; instead, we can include the size, mass and size-corrected-mass variables

in the same model (Fig. 2.2; see also next paragraph). In addition, in the same SEM we specify condition as a function of survival probability, and in a separate equation (but in the same model; Fig. 2.4c) regress density on the condition index (see Supplementary Code A3 for model specifications and R-code). This has the additional advantage that an overall model fit can be assessed, to quantify to what extent the hypothesized model fits the sample data (Musil et al., 1998) or to compare it with potential alternative models, which will be discussed in detail in the section 3.

Figure 2.3: Graphical representation of a model using a latent (a) and a composite (b) variable. The path diagram shows the relationships between observed variables (X 's in boxes) and (a) latent (L ; in circle) or (b) unknown-weight composite (C ; in hexagon) variable. Note that for the unknown-weight composite in (b), a response variable Y is required, while for defining a latent variable in (a) this is not a necessity, but could be added if useful. The equations for the latent and composite variable are shown in (c) and (d), respectively. (c) X is the result of the influence of the latent variable (L), proportional to λ (=loading), plus the error ε and the intercept α . For details on how L and λ are derived from data see chapter 4 in Grace (2006); (d) composite variable C is equal to the sum of the effects of X s plus the error which is fixed to 0. The response variable Y is a result of the intercept (α_Y), the slope coefficient γ , C and the error ε .

Since larger individuals may have a higher body weight, we want to account for the size when including mass as a condition measure in the model. This is often done by taking the residuals of mass regressed on structural size variables (Jakob et al., 1996; Peig & Green, 2010). SEM avoids using residuals (as in Fig. 2.2a) when considering mass corrected for size as a condition variable by using a technique called the multiple-

indicator, multiple-cause model (MIMIC). MIMIC incorporates covariates of interest which are modelled under a latent variable framework (Chang et al., 2020). Specifically, in our case study, we create a new latent variable ('Size-corrected-mass'; Fig. 2.4) affecting only one observed variable 'mass' with a default factor loading of 1. The structural size covariates (tarsus length, head length, wing length) affect the latent variable 'Size-corrected-mass', rather than the observed variable mass. By incorporating the size variables as covariates in this way in SEM, the latent construct 'Size-corrected-mass' allows for the model to estimate the relationship of mass on condition while simultaneously accounting for the effect of size-variables on mass, similar to taking the residuals of mass regressed on size when using a stepwise MR approach. In addition, there may be relationships between the size variables and other condition variables (e.g. cholesterol) that could be considered in the model.

So far, we only considered linear relationships, but often relationships are curvilinear in biology. To illustrate how to model non-linear relationships, we run the model from Fig. 2.4 with an additional variable 'squared mass' (Supplementary Code A4). By doing so, we can investigate a possible non-linear relationship of mass on condition. However, in this case study, squared mass does not show a significant effect on condition ($p=0.07$, Supplementary Code A4), and we henceforth ignore it for reasons of simplicity.

The model results show that size-corrected-mass and corticosterone have a negative effect on the condition index, while buffy coat, haematocrit, uric acid and cholesterol show smaller (non-significant) effects on condition (Fig. 2.4a). The condition has a path strength of 0.41 on survival, explaining 17% of the spatial variation in survival within the Netherlands (Supplementary Code A3 & Fig. A9). Oystercatcher density shows a strong (-0.57) negative association with the body condition index (Fig. 2.4b; Supplementary Fig. A10).

Section 3 - High flexibility, comparing competing hypotheses, and model performance of SEM

In this section we combine the two models from sections 1 and 2 and include confounding variables related to measurement procedure (handling time) and

individual characteristics (sex, feeding specialization and age class; box 3 in Fig. 2.1). Next, we compare the model performance of a SEM approach and a conventional statistical approach.

Model results and interpretation

To construct the full model (Fig. 2.5) we connect the latent variable ‘energy store’ (Fig. 2.2a) with the composite variable body condition (Fig. 2.4). In addition, by using MIMIC modelling, we correct for the effect of measurement procedure (handling time) and individual (sex, age) related confounding variables to account for its effect on the condition variables. The correlation structure of the three colour parameters (hue, chroma, luminance) differs strongly between the two age classes. The colour parameters are only highly correlated in adults and not in sub-adults (Supplementary Table A3) as illustrated in the multi-group CFA (Fig. 2.2b). Therefore, it is not useful to use a latent variable for bill colour in this example. Instead, for simplicity, we use only hue as a measure of bill colour (Fig. 2.5), which we expect to have more variation giving information on the colour in contrast to luminance and chroma, which reflects lightness (Supplementary Fig. A7). For completeness, we illustrate alternative model structures to handle the different correlation structures between age classes in Supplementary Fig. A11.

Whereas MR assumes independence of error terms, which may bias the estimates (James et al., 2013), it is possible to specify non-independence of error terms in SEM. For instance, in our example, we expect the error term of haematocrit and cholesterol to be correlated because cholesterol is quantified as a concentration in blood, which means that it is related to the proportion of haematocrit in the blood (Supplementary Code A5). Similarly, in the example of modelling non-linearity in mass using squared mass as additional variable, we can specify that the error terms of mass and its squared version are correlated.

The full model (Fig. 2.5) shows that the latent variable energy stores is a result of the positive influence of mass (corrected for structural size variables and handling time) as well as the ratio of mass divided by tarsus length. We also find that individuals with a higher bill tip height (blunter shaped bill) show a more yellowish bill (standardized

Figure 2.4: (a) SEM model of body condition based on a fitness trait for oystercatchers. Solid and dashed lines indicate a positive and negative significant ($p < 0.05$) path, respectively. Values indicate the standardized path strength (see Fig. 2.2 for explanation). Dotted lines indicate non-significant pathways ($p > 0.05$). (b) visualizes the relationship of density on the body condition index as estimated by the SEM. Dots indicate density data points and model estimate of body condition index for each individual, while the solid line shows fitted line of the model with the lower and upper 95% confidence interval as dashed lines. Note that individuals have the same density value when they were caught at the same location. (c) shows the equations of the SEM depicted in (a), emphasizing that oystercatcher density (dark grey box) does not shape the condition index, only the measured condition variables (light grey boxes) do (as can be seen from the two separate equations for C). The tilde-signs denotes the use of multiple regression within the SEM (e.g. mass as a function of size), while the 'equal'-signs denote the estimation of the composite and latent variables. The latent variable size-corrected-mass was included as part of the MIMIC subpart of the SEM (shaded area in a) to make sure that condition was affected by size corrected for mass and not by mass alone. For further explanation see the text. For R-code see Supplementary Code A3.

estimate=0.22, $p < 0.001$; Supplementary Code A5). In addition, males have a more orange than yellowish bill compared to females (standardized estimate=-0.25, $p < 0.001$; Supplementary Code A5). Most importantly, we find that energy stores and corticosterone have a negative effect on the condition whereas the other condition variables (buffy coat, haematocrit, cholesterol, uric acid and bill colour) show weaker

(non-significant) effects on the condition index.

These aforementioned results emphasize the point made in the introduction that we often assume positive relationships with performance or fitness (e.g. high energy stores benefit survival), but that those assumptions do not always hold true. We stress that the negative contribution of the latent construct 'energy stores' to body condition results from a negative correlation between mass (corrected for size) and survival (Supplementary Fig. A12), and is thus not a result of the (SEM) modelling procedure itself. A possible explanation for the negative relationship of energy stores with condition may be that birds with higher condition are mainly in areas with more food and therefore do not need to store that many resources, as the food source is more reliably available (Cuthill et al., 2000). Another possible reason may be that the number of predatory birds (e.g. peregrine falcon *Falco peregrinus*) in the oystercatcher wintering grounds increased during recent decades (Sovon Vogelonderzoek Nederland, 2018) which may increase the survival of lighter, more agile individuals by allowing them to escape predation. Lastly, it is important to keep in mind that we here analyse site level variation in mortality rather than individual level mortality, and between and within site (population) patterns need not be similar. Thus, the negative relationship between energy stores and condition does not exclude that energy stores in principle are important for starvation just that under conditions of high food stocks or predator abundance encountered in our study, energy stores may potentially be unrelated to starvation and instead reflect other aspects, such as foraging efficiency or agility.

We *a priori* hypothesized a positive relationship of body mass on the condition index, and therefore called the latent variable 'energy stores'. We can learn from the outcome of this model that our data is not consistent with the theoretical ideas that led us to model the concept of energy stores in the way we did. However, our latent variable 'energy stores' could be consistent with interpreting this latent variable as the concept 'mass-related agility' of an individual, but this hypothesis would require further testing. We note that the concept 'mass related agility' could still be thought of as a condition variable, as it reflects an aspect of health status (responsiveness to danger) and predicts performance (the fitness proxy survival).

Our results also confirmed the expected negative relationship between corticosterone and the condition index, meaning that birds at sites with higher survival

had lower corticosterone levels. Corticosterone fulfils its main functions by mobilizing stored resources to facilitate up-regulating metabolism for coping with increased energetic challenges (Jimeno et al., 2018). Thus, birds coping with harsh environmental conditions may show elevated corticosterone secretion (Angelier et al., 2010; Jimeno et al., 2017a), and our results are consistent with this idea.

We included bill colour as a potential variable affecting individuals' condition, as we hypothesized a priori that such a carotenoid based-trait is likely to be sensitive to nutritional state and may thus serve as a visual status signal of the individual condition to conspecifics meaning that individuals with a more reddish bill have higher condition. However, on the other hand, if bill colour would be an 'honest' signal for sexual selection, it may also be costly and could result in a negative relationship with survival. The pathway of bill colour on condition shows no significant effect on the condition index and survival. We can learn from the model that bill colour is not a useful condition variable that predicts variation in survival performance in this population.

Finally, we found that the body condition index shows a strong (-0.55) negative association with oystercatcher density, while body condition positively affected annual survival probability (0.45 standardized path coefficient; Fig. 2.5). This result suggests that that competition may affect the survival through body condition, and that this mediating effect of condition is quite strong: a one standard deviation decrease oystercatcher density at a site is associated with a quarter standard deviation increase in annual survival ($-0.55 \times 0.45 = -0.25$; rules of path tracing e.g. Grace, 2006).

Competing hypothesis and model fit comparison

Researchers may want to compare competing multivariate descriptions of a conceptual model (based on *a priori* hypotheses), but formal ways to compare such models and identify whether they are sufficient descriptions in the first place have rarely been considered. In SEM, we obtain one overall model fit and can compare model fits between models, which makes it possible to learn about a system. Various metrics of model fit exist for SEM, but we focus here on the comparative fit index (CFI; Bentler, 1990) that is mostly reported in ecological studies (see Supplementary Table A7 for other metrics). CFI, is a chi-square estimate using a maximum-likelihood solution, where values ≥ 0.90 and ≥ 0.95 indicate an acceptable and reasonably good fit,

respectively (Hooper et al., 2008; Hu & Bentler, 1999; Lefcheck, 2019). We constructed an alternative model to compare with the original one (Fig. 2.5) to explore whether we can improve the model. In the original model, by design, all effects of body size go indirectly through condition, whereas by adding a direct pathway of a latent construct 'body size' on survival, we can learn the relative role of body size and body condition (which is often understood as being independent; Schulte-Hostedde et al., 2005). Both models show good model fit with a CFI of 0.94 (Supplementary Code A6-A7). The alternative model reveals no direct effect of body size on survival, but only an indirect effect through mass and condition (Supplementary Fig. A13). Comparing both models with an ANOVA confirms that the alternative model (with an additional direct effect of body size on survival) does not show a significant improvement ($p=0.4$; Supplementary Table A8) compared to the original model. We have thus learned that effects of body size primarily affect survival through its effect on body condition. This model comparison also illustrates that if no direct arrow connects two variables, independence between variables is assumed (e.g. between size or sex and survival; Fig. 2.5). The decision on which pathways to include in a model or not, should be based on prior biological knowledge and the aim of the study, and thus requires careful thinking about hypotheses.

Model performance of SEM vs. Conventional approach

In the conventional approach, we can imitate latent variables using PCA and composite variable using residuals from MR (Fig. 2.6a vs. 2.6b). However, using conventional methods (MR and PCA) to create a condition index that predicts survival requires a large number of steps, especially when multiple condition variables are measured (Fig. 2.6b). We expected the SEM to perform better than the conventional approach, as in SEM we can estimate the joint likelihood of all the relations simultaneously (Fig. 2.6a), contrasting with the four steps in the conventional approach (Fig. 2.6b). The conventional approach involves using the residuals from a previous model in input in the actual model, which may cause bias in parameter estimation (Darlington & Smulders, 2001; Freckleton, 2002).

Figure 2.5: Full SEM model including latent (circles), composite (hexagon) and measured (squares) variables as well as confounding, predictor and response variables. Values indicate the standardized path strength (see Fig. 2.2 for explanation). Solid and dashed lines indicate a positive and negative significant ($p < 0.05$) path and are indicated by an asterisk next to the standardized path strength, respectively. Dotted lines indicate non-significant pathways ($p > 0.05$). For simplicity we only documented the path strength of the condition, predictor and response variables. The MIMIC part of the condition variables (buffy coat, haematocrit, cholesterol, uric acid and corticosterone) contains latent variables of the observed condition variables (indicated by an apostrophe) that are corrected for confounding variables (e.g. sex, age). 'Bill colour' and 'size-corrected mass' are also MIMIC parts (corrected for confounding variables) within the model, but have another biological meaningful name (rather than the name of the measured variable) and therefore are not noted without apostrophe.

We compared how well the body condition index could predict survival using either the SEM or the conventional method (Fig. 2.6). Model performance was quantified using a measure of prediction error (Root Mean Square Error; lower values imply less deviations between model predictions and observed survival estimates) and a measure of explanatory power (R²; higher values indicating more variation explained). We applied 10-fold cross-validation to the original dataset, with 80% of the dataset being used as training dataset to which the SEM (Fig. 2.6a) and conventional model (Fig. 2.6b) were fitted and 20% being used as test dataset to assess model performance of both methods. This process was repeated 3 times, meaning that in total 30 different training and test sets were used to estimate the performance (see Supplementary Code A8-A9).

The results of the cross validation show that the SEM approach has higher model performance which is indicated by a 1% reduction of the prediction error (RMSE) and an increase of the explained variation (R²) by 9% compared to the conventional (MR/PCA) approach (SEM: RMSE=0.438; R²=0.177; MR&PCA-approach: RMSE=0.442; R²=0.163; Fig. 2.6c).

In addition, we compared the bias and precision of estimators from both approaches. To this end, we simulated 1000 datasets with 1000 observations each, based on the covariance patterns found in the case study population using the ‘simulateData’ function in lavaan (Rosseel, 2012). Next, we estimated the effect of each condition variable on condition index using either a SEM (Fig. 2.6a; Supplementary Fig. A14) or conventional stepwise MR&PCA (Fig. 2.6b; Supplementary Fig. A15) approach. For each condition variable of both approaches we calculated the mean bias ($\hat{B} = \frac{1}{n_{sim}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{sim}} \hat{\theta}_i - \theta$) and the average empirical standard error ($\hat{E} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_{sim}-1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{sim}} (\hat{\theta}_i - \bar{\theta})^2}$) of the estimate, with θ being the parameter value used to simulate the data (‘true value’), $\hat{\theta}_i$ being the estimated parameter from the simulated i -th repetition, $\bar{\theta}$ being the mean of the estimated parameters and n_{sim} being the number of simulated datasets.

Simulation results indicate that the SEM method is practically unbiased, while the conventional method can have substantial bias and not consistently in the same direction (Fig. 2.7). For condition variables having a ‘true’ value not close to 0, we calculated the relative bias (Morris et al., 2019) which ranged from -85% to 50% and

Chapter 2

Figure 2.6: Comparison of two analysis approaches using either (a) structural equation modelling (SEM) and (b) conventional methods: multiple regression (MR) and principal component analysis (PCA). Arrows point from predictor to response variable within the model. a) SEM to quantify body condition in oystercatcher that is positively related to survival including latent and composite variables in one step. b) MR&PCA approach to quantify body condition which needs 4 steps (compared to 1 step in SEM). c) shows the root mean square error (RMSE) and R^2 for both models as a result from cross validation. Note that the variable ‘competitor density’ (from Fig. 2.5) was not included in the SEM model to compare the model performance of both approaches (a and b) since the aim was to create a proxy of body condition that best explains the variation in survival and therefore predicts the survival well with a train and test dataset (cross validation). See Supplementary Code A8 & Table A9 for model specifications and R-code as well as the details of each step of the MR&PCA approach, respectively.

0.8% to 3.5% for the conventional approach and SEM, respectively (Supplementary Fig. A16). The bias of the conventional estimators is largest in the variables having the strongest (significant) effect on the condition index (Fig. 2.7; Supplementary Fig. A17), ranging from -0.16 to +0.21 absolute bias (Supplementary Fig. A18). Overall, the estimator of the SEM approach was also more precise (with an empirical standard error around 0.056) than the conventional approach estimator (with an empirical standard error around 0.087), when considering estimators that were unbiased in both methods (e.g. uric acid; Supplementary Fig. A19-A20).

Figure 2.7: Results from the simulation comparing biases in the estimation of the slopes of the condition variables using the SEM and the conventional approach. Dots and triangles indicate the mean simulated estimate for the conventional method and SEM, respectively, with the empirical standard error. Grey horizontal line indicates the ‘true’ values used to generate the data. Note that standard error of the variable ‘energy store’ is really small and error bars are therefore hardly visible. Here we illustrate effect size estimates for the four condition variables that contributed most strongly to the condition index, see Supplementary Fig. A17 for the bias of all seven condition variables.

Discussion

We showed how to use structural equation modelling (SEM) to quantify body condition, comparing it with the conventional approaches of multiple regression and/or principal component analysis. We illustrated how latent variables can be used to summarize the multidimensional nature of body condition, yielding variable reduction. Next, we showed that composite variables make it possible to define the body condition index based on associations between observed condition variables and a fitness trait, even if the different condition variables contributing to body condition are uncorrelated (potentially reflecting different axes of condition). This is advantageous, because the direction of a relationship between a condition measure (e.g. body mass) and fitness is often assumed, but rarely known with certainty. Finally, we showed how it is possible in SEM to combine latent and composite variables in one model, which more realistically reflects complex natural situations, as it allows for summarizing both strongly correlated and less correlated measures of condition. A major advantage of SEM is that, in contrast to conventional methods, it can handle variables that are response and explanatory variables at the same time. As a consequence, SEM allows all the relationships to be estimated in a single model, resulting in one estimate for the model fit and generating the possibility to compare competing models, whereas in conventional methods several steps are required (e.g. extracting residuals of a model and use them as input for another model) that provide additional challenges (e.g. biased parameter estimates and carrying over the uncertainty from previous models). In addition, we showed how we can correct for the effect of confounding variables in SEM using MIMIC (multiple-indicator, multiple-cause) modelling. Overall, the high flexibility and integration of SEM makes it a powerful tool that might increase model predictability and result in unbiased and precise estimates, as illustrated by our worked examples on a case study, and therefore may also provide novel insights in ecological processes.

While we used SEM to quantify body condition, there are numerous other contexts in which it can be used to describe complex concepts. For example, in determining an immune response or experienced stress level of an individual, because usually multiple immunological, physiological or hormonal metrics are measured, which may also reflect

different aspects of the immune or stress response, and it is a challenge to derive an integrated immune estimate from these data. Similarly, climatic conditions are highly multivariate, and while most studies have for example detailed climatic data on various weather variables, studies tend to focus on a single weather variable such as temperature.

From a biological point of view: body condition related to different performance metrics

A condition index based on predicting survival does not necessarily mean that a high body condition of an individual indicates high fitness, because fitness also depends on the association between condition and other fitness components, such as reproductive success. Quantifying condition based on survival data may result in a different condition index than when it is based on the reproductive success of an individual, or a fitness metric that integrates survival and reproduction, such as reproductive value. This difference highlights that definitions of condition can be context dependent and may vary during the life-cycle, which may be particularly relevant when investigating species that alternate strategies (e.g. albatrosses prioritising reproduction in one year and survival in another year; Froy et al., 2013). Our SEM approach provides a framework for identifying how different condition measures define a successful survivor or a successful breeder and how they may differ from each other.

From a statistical point of view: additional techniques, challenges and limitations

We want to emphasize that in order to compare the two approaches, the data used to analyse the data and generating the data had the same model structure. However, in reality, this will rarely be the case. Different research questions require different statistical frameworks (model structures) and a thorough understanding of the definitions and components of the frameworks as well as of the study system is crucial for making biologically meaningful inferences (Bentham et al., 2017). Therefore, identifying a proper model structure (that fits the data well) and that addresses a biological question properly is by no means trivial and probably one of the largest

challenges in the art of modelling.

We considered confounding variables (e.g. sex and age) to illustrate how it can be modelled in SEM in general, but there may be many more confounding variables, and most will not have been measured (e.g. social dominance on foraging grounds). The presence of unmeasured confounders is a general challenge in observational studies (VanderWeele & Arah, 2011), but sensitivity-analysis and bias-modelling techniques can help handling uncontrolled confounding variables (Lin et al., 1998; McCandless et al., 2007).

In this paper, we used latent variables to achieve variable reduction (similar to PCA). However, latent variables can also be used to account for measurement errors of observed variables. Conventional statistical approaches like MR assume that variables are measured without error (Pugesek & Tomer, 1995) even though it is known that it is usually impossible to measure variables without error, particularly in the field (Musil et al., 1998). Ignoring measurement errors typically leads to downward bias in parameters because an error in measuring X (explanatory variable) is assigned to the error in predicting Y (response variable), implying that the true effect of X on Y is typically underestimated (i.e. regression dilution/attenuation). Pugesek & Tomer (1995) showed that SEM, by including measuring errors, estimated parameter coefficients more accurately and with less bias compared to MR. Supplementary Code A10 shows an example in which we account for imperfect measurements (through latent variables) of mass regressed on body size structures (tarsus, head and wing length).

SEM statistical packages are under continuous development, but particularly frequentist statistical approaches based on maximum likelihood estimation still have limitations. Random effects in combination with latent variables are currently challenging to model with one of the most widely used R-packages, lavaan (Rosseel, 2012). In the R-package piecewiseSEM (Lefcheck, 2016), it is possible to model random effects when conducting SEM in order to identify direct and indirect pathways, but it is currently impossible to model latent variables with this package.

For categorical predictor variables, a multi-group analysis can be conducted. Multi-group analysis can also be an alternative way to account for random factors with few levels. The question that drives a multi-group analysis is whether two or more groups might differ in terms of the relationships among parameters and the whole model is

run for each level (Grace, 2006). To illustrate the use of categorical variables, we used the age effect in the example of Fig. 2.2b as a category (Supplementary Code A2), which means that the model calculates the relationships (Fig. 2.2d) for each age class separately. In addition, multi-group analysis can also be conducted to test for interactions (with a categorical variable). However, a multi-group analysis together with a binomial response variable is not supported yet in lavaan which raises practical challenges analysing 0/1 survival data using logistic regression in combination with categorical variables, such as area-specific resighting probability which were relevant in our case study. An example of R-code for modelling a binomial response variable but without multiple levels (only one area) is presented in Supplementary Code A11.

Non-linear relationships are common in ecology and there are different ways to address non-linearity. The easiest way is through transformation, as we did in our case study, applying logit-transformation for proportional response variables and squaring mass (Supplementary Code A4). Multi-group analysis can also be used to address a certain type of nonlinear relation (Grace, 2006). Continuous nonlinear relationships are a special challenge for SEM, both for observed but especially for latent variables (Grace, 2006). A useful introduction to this topic is chapter 12 in Kline (2011).

Bayesian approaches to SEM may offer solutions to limitations of frequentist software in dealing with random effects, non-Gaussian data and multiple level categorical predictors, because Bayesian software uses more convenient numerical algorithms. Furthermore, a Bayesian approach allows for constraining estimates using informative priors, so as to include biological knowledge. Bayesian framework have also been used to combine a mark-recapture model with SEM. Cubaynes et al. (2012) show an example of how to model a latent variable ('overall body size') that affects survival estimated within a mark-recapture framework (all in one model). Possible R-packages that can be used for such Bayesian approaches are *rstan* (Stan Development Team, 2020), *jagsUI* (Kellner, 2019) and *nimble* (de Valpine et al., 2017).

To conclude, we show that SEM is a powerful and flexible statistical tool that can lead to models of higher predictive power and with more accurate as well as precise estimates compared to conventional approaches. Therefore, we encourage researchers to consider SEM as a flexible framework to describe the multivariate nature of body condition and thus understand how it affects biological processes, thereby improving

the value of body condition proxies for predicting organismal performance. We emphasize that that SEM can also be a useful tool for other multidimensional ecological concepts as well, such as immunocompetence, oxidative stress and environmental conditions.

Acknowledgement

We thank everybody involved in catching birds, especially Kees Oosterbeek, Symen Deuzeman and Laurens van Kooten. Funding was provided by the Applied and Engineering Sciences domain of the Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO-STW; grant number 14638) as well as by Royal Netherlands Air Force, Birdlife Netherlands, NAM gas exploration and Deltares. We acknowledge the feedback provided by ecologists working at these organisations during half-yearly meetings. The authors declare that they have no competing interests. We also thank Nigel G. Yoccoz and two anonymous reviewers whose comments helped improve the manuscript.

Supplementary material

Supplementary material of Chapter 2 is included as appendix A to this thesis.

CHAPTER 3

Body condition mediates carry-over effects of overwintering environment on reproductive success in a shorebird population

Magali Frauendorf, Andrew M. Allen, Henk-Jan van der Kolk, Sarah Cubaynes, Bruno J. Ens, Simon Verhulst, Eelke Jongejans, Hans de Kroon, Kees Oosterbeek, Karin Troost, Martijn van de Pol

Abstract

Identifying the main drivers of population dynamics is challenging in migratory species, as animals can be affected at different stages of the annual cycle that are geographically separated. Furthermore, the impact of environmental drivers at overwintering sites may not be directly apparent if they carry-over to the reproductive season, and vice versa. Body condition is thought to be the state variable that mediates carry-over effects, yet few studies explicitly consider mechanistic pathways involved, they have been limited to investigating body mass effects, and have rarely been carried out at large spatial scale. Here, we investigate how a key state variable - winter body condition - is influenced by environmental drivers in winter and how it affects subsequent reproductive success in Eurasian oystercatchers (*Haematopus ostralegus*). We expand previous studies by considering a wider range of potential measures of body condition to investigate a potential carry-over effect on a national scale, while also using a recently proposed integrative and flexible statistical framework. We colour banded and measured the condition of 1574 individuals in winter and assessed survival and reproductive success using field and citizen science observations from both wintering and breeding areas over a large spatial scale. We developed a winter body condition index that was linked to environmental drivers and related the body condition index to reproductive success in the subsequent season using structural equation modelling in combination with a multi-state mark-recapture model within a Bayesian modelling framework. Winter body condition predicted the reproductive success, indicating a carry-over effect. Clutches as well as hatchlings from parents with high preceding winter body condition survived longer in the spring, but not because the parents timed their reproduction earlier. The body condition in winter was positively associated with the proportion of grassland around the wintering ground. We conclude that carry-over effects can help us to identify which factors play a role and enables us to use this information in population modelling to clarify the relative importance of threats acting at spatiotemporally separated stages. For the Dutch oystercatcher population specifically, this means that not only environmental drivers in the breeding area explain the decline in the reproductive success but also the environmental condition in winter. Surprisingly, the availability of marginal foraging habitat was the main driver of the

carry-over effect, suggesting that such alternative foraging grounds may be much more important than previously thought. We would therefore recommend to preserve grasslands around large and important high tide roost areas.

Introduction

One of the central goals in population biology, ecology and conservation is to identify the drivers for fluctuations in population abundance (Betini et al., 2013; Brown et al., 2017). However, it can be challenging to reach this goal because many organisms (e.g. birds, fish, marine mammals, African ungulates, butterflies; Calvert et al., 2009) are organized into annual cycles that include different stages (e.g. reproduction, non-breeding) being often temporally and spatially separated (Briedis et al., 2018; Marra et al., 2015). Since these distinct events are linked physiologically and ecologically, preceding events may have profound consequences for the following phases in the annual cycle (Harrison et al., 2011). Such events and processes taking place in one season that result in individuals making the transition between season in different states (condition levels) and consequently affecting individual performance in subsequent seasons are called carry-over effects (Harrison et al., 2011; Norris & Marra, 2007). Through carry-over effects, the impact of environmental conditions in one season may be postponed to the next season, which makes it challenging to identify the drivers that are relevant for the population dynamics.

Even though there may be theoretically a clear biological link between the different stages that animals experience throughout their annual cycle, our understanding of the fundamental ecology of most vertebrate classes is still heavily biased to single-season studies (e.g. breeding season) (Marra et al., 2015). This bias likely exists due to the logistical and analytical challenge in identifying the complex interactions across seasons between individuals and their environment. To improve the understanding of individual and population-level responses to natural and anthropogenic change, a concerted effort to move beyond single-season research is vital (Marra et al., 2015).

Carry-over effects in migratory species are particularly challenging because migrants not only live in different areas in different seasons, but individuals from the same breeding (or overwintering) area may overwinter (or breed) in different areas

(Gunnarsson et al., 2005; Norris et al., 2004). For example, the carry-over effect on reproduction could be mediated by winter condition in different places, which in turn are affected by spatially varying environmental conditions. This complexity emphasizes the need to study carry-over effects on a large spatial scale.

Next to logistical challenges of landscape-scale year-round tracking (Marra et al., 2015) for collecting data to identify carry-over effects, another major challenge is to find statistical framework that enables the analysis of the different events and processes and how they are measured in an efficient and integrative way (Souchay et al., 2018). Specifically, wildlife studies of marked individuals are typically analysed using capture-mark-recapture (CMR) analysis, but CMR can struggle with time-varying individual covariates such as body condition. Furthermore, body condition is a multidimensional concept, and recent studies have suggested that latent variables can be efficient in operationalizing the concept of body condition from multiple measurable body condition traits in the field (Frauendorf et al., 2021). Finally, carry-over effects of conditions in one season to another season must be mediated by a state variable such as body condition, and path analysis provides a logical tool to identify the relative importance of various mechanistic pathways. Fortunately, recently advances have been made where CMR can be combined with structural equation modelling (SEM) to integrate above processes into an integrative analytical Bayesian framework (Cubaynes et al., 2012).

Several studies investigated carry-over effects by linking environmental conditions (e.g. winter climate, sea surface temperature, food availability) in one season directly to the individual performance (reproduction, survival) in the subsequent season (Harrison et al., 2011), without considering the effect on the state of individual in the initial season. Without explicitly considering the mediating mechanistic role of state variables such as individual body condition, we may risk drawing erroneous conclusions. For example, Olivier et al. (2005) found that snow petrels (*Pagodroma nivea*) showed higher reproductive success after winters with greater ice cover. This may appear as a carry-over effect where the environment in the non-breeding season affects the reproduction in the next season. However, the authors suggest that sea ice also promotes overwinter survival of krill, and thereby ensures a larger supply of food during the breeding season, consequently resulting in increased reproductive success.

Environmental conditions in one season may thus be good proxies of environmental conditions in subsequent seasons, but if the causal environmental drivers of organismal performance are from the same season, they are not considered to be carry-over effects. Consequently, it is important to take into account individual state variables or proxies thereof (e.g. condition, arrival/departure date) that mediate effects of environmental conditions on the individual performance in the next season.

Whereas most studies look at body mass as the key individual state variable that mediates carry-over effects across seasons, two individuals could be of similar body mass, and thus appear superficially to be in similar condition, but in practice may still have different abilities to deal with environmental challenges (Harrison et al., 2011). In fact, in the last decade it has become clear that different metrics of body condition are also related to aspects other than body mass and appear to be a more appropriate predictor of fitness (Barry & Wilder, 2013; Nie et al., 2014). In addition, some studies suggested that hormones and the immune system may be involved in carry-over effects (Crossin et al., 2012; Hegemann et al., 2015; McNamara & Houston, 2008a). Therefore, to identify the mechanism of a carry-over effect, it is essential to measure state variables (e.g. nutritional, hormonal, immune state) in one season, ideally link it to environmental drivers in that season, and relate it to individual performance in the next season, which is rarely done.

The Eurasian oystercatcher (*Haematopus ostralegus*) is experiencing a strong population decline in the last decades in many parts of its breeding range (van de Pol et al., 2014). The primary bottleneck for this decline –from a demographic perspective– is reduced reproductive success (Allen et al., 2021; Hulscher & Verhulst, 2003; Roodbergen et al., 2012). The Dutch oystercatcher population is partially migratory, with year-round residents along the coast in the Wadden Sea and Delta estuaries, while inland areas (agriculture and cities) are only occupied during the breeding season by birds from a variety of overwintering areas. As oystercatchers are highly clustered and share the same wintering grounds, but spread throughout the Netherlands for breeding, one could hypothesize that there could also be one common driver leading to reduced condition in winter that carries over to the next season to cause the overall low reproductive success.

In this study, we contribute to the existing knowledge of carry-over effects by

focussing on the mechanism underlying carry-over effects through a body condition metric defined by morphology and physiology combined with a large-scale approach to get a better understanding for the causes of the Dutch oystercatcher population decline. Specifically, we aim to (i) understand the role of body condition in mediating carry-over effects, and (ii) understand which winter environmental effects carry over on the reproductive success and are thus crucial to understand population dynamics of this declining species. These two aims are achieved by three steps: (1) operationalize and quantify body condition of wintering oystercatchers using multiple morphological and physiological variables to (2a) test if winter body condition carries over to the reproductive performance in the subsequent breeding season (directly) (2b) but also indirectly through timing of egg-laying because reproductive success has been shown to be highly affected by breeding phenology and may therefore be a reproductive trait that mediates how condition affects reproductive output (Fig. 3.1a). Finally, (3a) we identify to what extent environmental conditions (food availability and weather) affect winter body condition and (3b) how they affect the reproductive success mediated by the body condition effect (Fig. 3.1a).

Method

Data collection & preparation

Body condition

In total, 1574 oystercatchers were caught with cannon nets or mist nets during 36 catching events around the Dutch Wadden Sea and Delta area in two periods (winters of 2000-2003: 837 birds; winters of 2016-2018: 737 birds; Fig. 3.2; Supplementary Table B1). Birds were banded with colour rings for visual identification.

Blood samples (sex, haematocrit, buffy coat)

Blood samples (approximately 0.35 ml per bird) were taken from the brachial vein. Sex was determined using molecular techniques (DNA) from blood stored in cell lysis buffer at room temperature.

Buffy coat, the fraction of white blood cells, is elevated if the body needs to fight

Figure 3.1: a) Conceptual diagram linking variables to each other in the multi-state mark-recapture structural equation model (MSM-SEM); dotted line) and the path analysis (SEM; dashed line). Directional arrows refer to the direction of the causal relationship. b-e) Zoom in on the different parts of the models illustrating the statistical analysis, where squares (with solid lines), circles, hexagon and squares with dashed lines represent measured, latent, composite variable and the error terms, respectively. Note that the site effect (capture) in (d) is also included in the survival analysis (c) by having a state and time effect.

against infections (Campbell et al., 2008), and tends to be elevated in individuals in adverse conditions (Beechler et al., 2015; Ullman-Culler, 1999). Buffy coat and haematocrit, the proportion of red blood cells with the main function of oxygen transportation, have been shown to predict survival in Eurasian oystercatcher (Verhulst et al., 2004).

Figure 3.2: Study area in the Netherlands showing an overview of the catching locations across the Wadden Sea (a) and the Delta area (b) as well as the area-division (geographical states; tidal basins) used in the multi-state mark-recapture model. (c) indicates an overview map of the locality of the two study areas within the Netherlands. Dots and diamonds indicate catching events in the winter of period 1 (2000-2003) and period 2 (2016-2018), respectively. The size of the symbols indicates the number of caught birds per catching event. Stars indicate the weather station used in the analysis, where the nearest weather station to each catching location is indicated by the same colour (Supplementary Table B2). Orange, blue, grey and green star indicating the weather stations in De Kooy, Hoorn Terschelling, Lauwersoog and Vlissingen, respectively.

Two capillary tubes of approximately 65 μL were taken from each bird and centrifuged 10 minutes at 9503g between 2 to 6 hours (mean \pm se) = 3.6 \pm 0.96 hrs) after

blood extraction. Since this time delay did not significantly affect buffy coat and haematocrit, it was not included as a variable in the analysis. Buffy coat and haematocrit were measured by taking standardized pictures of the blood collection tube in a specific holder constructed for this purpose (Supplementary Fig. B1), and then measuring the length of the portion with red blood cells, white blood cells and plasma in pixels with the program Paint.NET. The haematocrit and buffy coat were calculated by taking the proportion of the length of red blood cells and white blood cells, respectively, to the total length (red blood cells+ white blood cells + plasma). The reason for using pictures and measuring pixels instead of measuring proportions directly in the field was to minimize measuring bias due to more accurate measurements compared to a ruler/calliper. Because repeatability between the two samples per individual was high (on average 0.92; Supplementary Table B3), we calculated the average of both for each haematocrit and buffy coat per individual. The repeatability was calculated by estimating the intra-class correlation coefficients (ICC) (and its 95% confidence interval) and using the variance components from a one-way ANOVA with the R-package ICC (Wolak et al., 2012).

Since haematocrit and buffy coat values ranged from 0 to 1, they were logit transformed before analysis (Warton & Hui, 2011).

Biometry

Biometric parameters, namely length of tarsus to toe (mm), wing length (mm), head length (mm), bill tip height (mm) and body mass (g), were measured following the standard techniques described in Durell et al. (1993). Bill tip height (measured 3 mm from the bill tip using a calliper) was used as a proxy for the type of individuals' feeding specialization (individual characteristics; Fig. 3.1a-b), ranging from worm specialists (indicated by a pointed bill and a low bill tip height) to shellfish specialists (indicated by a blunt bill and high bill tip height) (van de Pol et al., 2009a). Birds were aged based on their plumage, bill and leg characteristics (Cramp & Simmons, 1983) and the age was classified in 1st, 2nd, 3rd calendar year and adults (>3rd calendar year). It is not possible to accurately age adult birds. Handling time (confounding variable; Fig. 3.1a-b) was recorded to correct for time-dependent mass loss as well as possible effects on other

physiological measures (Cirule et al., 2012; Verhulst et al., 2004). Handling time (as a proportion of 24 hours) was defined as the time between capture and measuring.

Across all sampling years, 37% of the birds were not sexed using DNA because no or too little blood was taken. Sampling during winters 2001-2002 and 2002-2003 had less than 5% sexed using DNA, whereas in the remaining years, >80% of the birds were sexed using DNA (Supplementary Table B4). Birds that were not sexed using DNA, were sexed using the classification tree function (Hothorn et al., 2012) from the partykit R-package (Hothorn & Zeileis, 2015). Previous studies have shown relationships between the sex and biometric measures (Durell et al., 1993; Zwarts et al., 1996c). Because van de Pol et al. (2009b) showed that sexual dimorphism varied substantially in time and space, we only included birds caught in winter for the classification tree and also added the sampling year and catching location as additional variables. 75% (n=1061) and 25% (n=281) has been used as training and test dataset, respectively. Most important biometric variables were bill length, bill tip height and bill shape (Supplementary Fig. B2), which resulted in 90% accuracy with a 95% confidence interval of 86% and 94% of correct classification (Supplementary Fig. B3).

Survival

Caught birds were ringed with a unique combination of colour rings (with inscription) and a metal ring. Resightings were predominantly recorded by citizen scientists (Allen et al., 2019a) in ringing programs across The Netherlands in an online portal. Colour-ring wear and loss have negligible effect on the resighting and survival estimates (Allen et al., 2019b). The metal ring data and subsequent recoveries are managed by Vogeltrekstation (the Dutch Centre for Avian Migration and Demography), the administrative centre for bird ringing in the Netherlands. For detailed information on the oystercatcher ringing program in the Netherlands see Allen et al. (2019a, 2019b).

Environmental variables

As environmental variables, we included food availability from the mudflats and grassland proportion as an indication for additional food source (earthworms), conspecific density and weather conditions during winter.

Food availability

Food availability was calculated by multiplying food abundance (Supplementary Fig. B4a) by the exposure time (Supplementary Fig. B4b) of the tidal flats. Food abundance is the abundance of cockles and mussels in gram ash-free dry mass per m^2 . The exposure time is the average exposure time for the winter season (when the captures took place) as a proportion of 24 hours. For food abundance and density data we used a 7 km-radius buffer around the catching location based on information from GPS-tagged oystercatcher movements around several high tide roosts in the Netherlands (Bakker et al., 2021).

Food abundance: Cockles (*Cerastoderma edule*) and mussels (*Mytilus edulis*) are among the principal food sources of oystercatcher in winter (Hulscher, 1996) and were therefore included as food source in the study. Data on cockle and mussel abundance were obtained from survey data performed by Wageningen Marine Research (Troost et al., 2017) on a yearly basis (in spring) on North-South orientated transects (Supplementary Fig. B5). We selected only age classes and sizes of the prey that is possible to consume for oystercatchers (e.g. cockles of age 1 and 2 as well as older than 2 if length was not above 30 mm). We converted the fresh weight into ash-free dry mass (AFDM) using the conversion factor of 0.16 (Zwarts et al., 1996a). Mussels and cockles lose mass during the winter period and we accounted for monthly variation in biomass by calculating biomass for each winter month compared to the spring months (April-June) based on the seasonal biomass variation described in (Zwarts & Wanink, 1993). We calculated the average biomass of cockles within each 7 km-radius buffer around each catching location (resulting in average AFDM of cockles and mussels in gram per m^2 for each buffer) and weighted it with the intertidal area size that becomes exposed (because proportion of land and sea differed per buffer; Supplementary Fig. B5).

Exposure time: Data on exposure time were available from InterTides, which is a program that interpolates tidal water height levels based on observations at 15 tidal gauge stations (Rappoldt et al., 2014). The value 'exposure time' is based on bathymetry (underwater depth of water body floors) combined with the tidal height on a 100mx100m grid (Supplementary Fig. B5). We calculated the average exposure time

for the winter period (November-February), where 1 indicates complete exposure of the tidal area for the whole period and 0 means no exposure at all (Supplementary Fig. B4b). Since InterTides does not give exposure time for the Delta area (Fig. 3.2b) or for a small bay close to North Texel (Fig. 3.2a), we calculated the exposure time for those two areas manually (see Supplementary Text B1 for details).

Grasslands: Although oystercatchers predominantly feed on intertidal flats, especially worm specialists may also feed on inland fields during high tides (Durell et al., 2001a; Goss-Custard & Durell, 1983; Heppleston, 1971; van der Kolk et al., 2019). Therefore, we used data on land use from CBS Statistics Netherlands to calculate the proportion of available foraging areas (grasslands) of the terrestrial area within each 7 km buffer (Fig. 3.4d; Supplementary Fig. B5).

Conspecific density

Since 1975, high-tide roost counts are organized by Sovon Dutch Centre for Field Ornithology to count waterbirds in the Dutch Wadden Sea and the Delta area (Hornman et al., 2012). These counts are done on a monthly basis throughout the winter. We used the counts in November and January since those were most complete for the period of catching events. Within a buffer of 7 km-radius around each catching location, we summed the numbers of counted oystercatchers for the month November and January separately, and weighted them for the counted area, because not the whole buffer area was counted (Supplementary Fig. B5). This resulted in oystercatcher density (number of birds per km²) for each month (November and January). Finally, we averaged the two densities to get a proxy of overall winter density (Supplementary Fig. B4c).

Weather conditions

As weather data we included precipitation and temperature related variables given how it may influence food availability and directly affect the energy required for homeostasis of adult birds (Camphuysen et al., 1996; Goss-Custard, 1984; Kersten & Piersma, 1987). Winter severity has previously been described as an important environmental factor impacting the reproduction and survival of oystercatchers (Schwemmer et al., 2014; van de Pol et al., 2010). The windchill index was also included

to investigate the combined effects of low winter temperatures and high wind speeds given the additional energy requirements (Smith et al., 2012; Wiersma & Piersma, 1994).

All weather data (KNMI, 2020a) were extracted for the nearest weather station from the catching location (mean (sd)=17.4 km (12.1), n=36; Supplementary Table B2) which resulted in four weather stations that were used as source for the weather data (Fig. 3.2). For each catching location, we calculated the weather conditions for a 1-month-period as well as a 2-month-period prior to the catching event since we expect that the period before the catching event rather than an average of the whole winter season may affect the condition of the bird. The weather variables from 1-month and 2-month prior catching showed high correlation (ranging from 0.74 for precipitation anomaly to 0.89 for winter severity; Supplementary Table B5).

The *mean daily temperature* (in °C) ranged from 1.4°C to 6.8°C with a mean (sd) of 3.8°C (1.5) and 2.0°C to 8.5°C with a mean (sd) of 4.5°C (1.7) for the 1-month-period and 2-month-period, respectively, across all catching events (Supplementary Fig. B6a & Fig. B7a). *Precipitation* sum per month ranged from 13.4 mm to 128.3 mm with a mean (sd) of 64.9 mm (30.9) and 32.0 mm to 112.8 mm with a mean (sd) of 71.3 mm (23.2) for the 1-month-period and 2-month-period, respectively, across all catching events (Supplementary Fig. B6b & Fig. B7b).

We calculated *precipitation anomalies* by subtracting the long-term average precipitation per month over the period 1981 to 2010 (KNMI, 2020b) from the actual precipitation per month prior to the catching event. This resulted in values >0 and <0 indicating above and below average precipitation, respectively (Supplementary Fig. B6c & Fig. B7c).

We estimated a *winter severity index* based on the number of 'cold days' (days with a mean temperature < 0°C). In this index, days with mean temperatures below -10°C counted for three points, days between -10°C and -5°C for two points and days between -5°C and 0°C for one point (Ijnsen, 1988). Finally, we tallied the total points for the 2-months and 1-month period prior to the catching event (Supplementary Fig. B6d & Fig. B7d; Camphuysen et al., 1996).

Since high winds can increase the birds energetic needs especially when combined with low temperature (Durell et al., 2001b), we calculated the *windchill index* (W) using

the following equation (Taillon et al., 2006):

$$W = 13.12 + 0.6215A - (11.37 - 0.3965A)V^{0.16}$$

based on the Celsius temperature scale; A is the air temperature in degrees Celsius; and V is the wind speed in kilometres per hour. The index was averaged for the 2-months and 1-month period prior to the catching event resulting in two separate wind-chill variables (Supplementary Fig. B6e & Fig. B7e).

Reproduction

We attempted to locate the breeding ground in the subsequent season for as many individuals as possible that were caught in the winter (from period 2), with valuable help from volunteers.

Breeding success of located individuals was monitored using Reconyx camera traps placed approximately 2m from the nest to minimise disturbance at the nest. Every seven to 10 days, batteries and SD cards were replaced. The number of eggs, hatching date and number of hatched chicks was recorded.

Ideally, lay date would be calculated by back-calculating from the exact hatch date recorded on the pictures, however, due to camera failures causing missing data, nests which had no recorded hatching date had the lay date back-calculated based on egg measurements. Length, weight and width of each egg was measured to the nearest 0.1 mm with a dial calliper or to the nearest 0.1 g with a balance, giving an lay date accuracy of ± 1 -2 days (Jager et al., 2000; Strijkstra, 1986).

After hatching, the chicks were monitored every 2-3 days to ensure if they were still alive. Since they start moving around shortly after hatching, monitoring with camera traps was no longer possible. We followed the hatchlings until the moment of fledgling (around 4-5 weeks) or until there was no sign anymore of the hatchling being alive (e.g. no alarming parents around).

Breeding success was defined as the probability that a clutch survived until the next day (daily clutch survival) which was calculated using the Mayfield method that takes into account the number of observation days correcting for the fact that some clutches are found part-way through the nesting stage and are therefore biased towards successful clutches (Aebischer, 1999). For hatchling survival, we calculated the

maximum number of days the chicks were alive and assume that fledging is reached as soon as the chick can fly (on average between 30-35 days). We only included nests in the analysis where we were certain that it was the first clutch.

Both sexes contribute equally to incubation, clutch defence and hatchling feeding in oystercatchers (Ens et al., 1996). Therefore, we expect that the body condition of either sex could be a state variable mediating carry-over effects and therefore did not differentiate between males and females in the carry-over effect analysis.

Data analysis

We fitted a multi-state mark recapture model combined with a structural equation model (MSM-SEM; Cubaynes et al., 2012) to quantify body condition and relate it to environmental drivers in winter, and path analysis (SEM) to quantify a carry-over effect (Fig. 3.1) in a Bayesian model framework using R-package nimble (de Valpine et al., 2017). To estimate the Bayesian R^2 , we used equations described in Gelman et al. (2019). All statistical analyses were done in R (version 3.5.1) (R Core Team, 2019). In the following sections we describe in detail the different parts of the analyses (MSM, SEM, path analysis).

Next to documenting the mean and 95% credible interval of the posterior distribution for all model results, we also documented the probability of direction (p_d) that can be interpreted as the Bayesian equivalent of the frequentist p-value (Makowski et al., 2019). p_d is the probability that a derived parameter (described by its posterior distribution) is strictly positive or negative, whichever is the most probable. Thus, the p_d -value equals the proportion of the posterior density that has the same sign as the median of the posterior distribution. We define the p_d -values between 0.95 and 0.97 as ‘moderate evidence’, p_d -values between 0.97 and 0.99 as ‘moderately strong evidence’ and values > 0.99 as ‘strong evidence’, as suggested by (Muff et al., 2021).

SEM for condition and environment

Quantification of body condition

We used structural equation modelling (SEM) to quantify body condition (Fig. 3.1a), which we previously showed to be a powerful and flexible tool resulting in higher model

performance when analysing body condition, compared to more conventional statistical techniques (e.g. multiple regression, PCA; Frauendorf et al., 2021).

The variable 'body condition' in this framework was a composite variable, summarizing the multivariate concept of body condition, representing the collective effect of multiple observed variables (Grace & Bollen, 2008). Mass, haematocrit and buffy coat are condition variables expected to affect body condition (Fig. 3.1b). In addition, confounding variables and individual characteristics (sex, age) were included that may affect the condition variables, but that we only want to correct for (Fig. 3.1b). Body mass was corrected for three body size metrics because larger birds are heavier. Thus, we henceforth focus on size-corrected mass as a proxy of fat content. For instance, by considering effects of handling time on body mass, we accounted for time-dependent mass loss. Note that we did not include sex as a confounding variable to correct for different body mass across sexes because the sex and tarsus length were strongly correlated (>0.7). On the other hands, the latent variable body condition can be seen as an independent variable that explains variation in the response variable survival (from the multi-state-model; see next section).

All continuous variables (mass, haematocrit, buffy coat, tarsus length, head length, wing length, bill tip height, catch day, handling time) were z-score standardized (mean = 0, sd = 1) before the analysis. Age and sex were included as categorical variables. Age was divided in three classes: 1-year-old ($n=244$), 2-year-old ($n=153$) and ≥ 3 -year-old ($n=1197$) birds. We could not distinguish between 3-year-old and >3 -year-old birds, because we only had sixteen 3-year-old birds in the dataset. However, in terms of condition, we expect especially the 1- & 2-year old birds being different from adults (>3 year) rather than the 3-year-old birds because no survival differences were found between 3-year old birds and adults (Allen et al., 2021) .

Because previous work has shown that there is a non-linear relationship of handling time on the condition variables (mass, haematocrit and buffy coat) (Verhulst et al., 2004), we added a squared term on handling time.

Since there may also be a non-linear relationship of mass, haematocrit and buffy coat on the individual body condition (e.g. birds with very low or very high mass being in lower condition than birds with average mass), we compared the Watanabe-Akaike information criterion (WAIC) for a model with only linear terms (for mass, haematocrit

and buffy coat) and with a model with an additional squared term for each variable. The WAIC of the model with the linear term only was lower (Supplementary Table B6) and visualization of the relationships confirm that a linear relationship fits better (Supplementary Fig. B8).

Environmental variables

We also used a SEM to conduct variable reduction of the highly correlated weather variables (Supplementary Fig. B9) by using latent variables. Therefore, we combined temperature-related effects (average temperature, wind chill index and winter severity) into one latent variable and precipitation related effects (precipitation sum, precipitation anomaly) into another latent variable (Fig. 3.1d). We investigated linear as well as non-linear effects of all five variables (temperature, precipitation, cockle, and mussel availability as well as grassland proportion), but the model fit with only a linear term was better in all cases (showing a lower WAIC; Supplementary Table B7). Finally, we added a random capture effect (Fig. 3.1d; capture ID in Supplementary Table B1) because individuals caught at the same site and year may not be statistically independent. Because correlation between the food condition variables was low (Supplementary Fig. B9), we did not use latent variables in this case, but investigated their effect on condition directly.

We know from previous studies that individuals with different feeding specialization may response differently to the environment (van der Kolk et al., 2019). Therefore, we included an interaction term between feeding specialization and the environmental variables as a side analysis.

Since we had no prior knowledge on which time period (1 month or 2 months) before the catching event may be crucial in terms of how weather condition influence an individual's body condition, we initially conducted the analysis (the effect of environmental variables on condition; Fig. 3.1d) separately (with the extracted condition variables from the MSM-SEM) by using the weather conditions one month and two months before the catching event. Based on the WAIC of both models, environmental variables collected 1-month prior to catching fitted the data better and hence we only used the 1-month variables in the remainder of the analysis

(Supplementary Table B7).

Multi-state model with SEM (MSM-SEM)

In this section, we describe the multi-state mark recapture (MSM) model and how the SEM (from the previous section) was integrated in the MSM-SEM. Combining structural equation modelling with capture-recapture models allows the integration of imperfect detection with the advantages of SEM to test hypotheses within a complex structural framework (Cubaynes et al., 2012).

We used a seasonal multi-state live dead recovery model with a time-varying individual covariate and a site-specific random time effect (Fig. 3.1c). We used eight geographical areas, hereon states, to estimate survival, resighting probability and seasonal transitions (migration) among areas. We determined the eight geographical states based on expected variation in survival and migration, and partly due to heterogeneity in resighting probabilities. The two principal coastal areas of the Wadden Sea and the Delta were separated due to expected variation in survival resulting from past activities related to human activities like shellfisheries and habitat loss (van de Pol et al., 2014). We divided the inland states between north and south due to the expected variation in transition probabilities, since oystercatchers breeding inland in the southern part of the Netherlands were more likely to migrate to the Delta and further south, while oystercatchers breeding inland in the northern part of the Netherlands were more likely to migrate to the Wadden Sea (Allen et al., 2019a). Dividing inland areas between the north and south enabled us to determine these differing migratory patterns. The (alive) states (geographical location) of the individual were coded according to one of the eight geographical locations (Fig. 3.2): D=Delta, P=Inland south, N=Inland north, B=Balgzand/Texel, V=Texel/Vlieland, T=Terschelling/Ameland, S=Schiermonnikoog and R=Rottum. The ninth state 'X' (Abroad) captured all observations outside the Netherlands (Allen et al., 2019a). The dead recovery was coded as a separate state and did not contain information about where the bird was found.

The sampling period ranged from 2000 to 2019 (20 years). In the early 2000 (2000-2003) as well as in 2016-2018, due to research projects, oystercatchers were caught in

their wintering area intensively for marking and measuring their condition. The time interval was 0.5 years (=6 months) to account for the seasonal structure of our model, thus providing a total of 40 time intervals.

We used a multinomial logit link function to model the transition parameters, ensuring that state transition probabilities sum to 1 (Converse et al., 2012). Some individuals were seen multiple times in a single season, and occasionally in 2 or more different areas. We assigned the geographical state according to the area with the highest number of observations.

In addition, we added an age effect to estimate survival for each age class: juveniles (1-year-old individuals), sub-adults (2 -and 3-year old individuals) and adults (>3-year-old individuals) (Fig. 3.1c). Separating 2 -and 3-year old birds in the analysis was not possible due to sample size limitations, where 40%, 3%, 4% and 53% of the studied population were 1-,2,-3 and >3-year-old birds, respectively (Supplementary Table B8). However, we do not expect that this age-class distinction causes a problem for the biological interpretation because studies have shown that the largest differences in survival are expected between the one-year-old birds and adults (Allen et al., 2021; Goss-Custard et al., 1982; Schwemmer et al., 2014).

Finally, we aimed to quantify whether the body condition index was a good proxy of individual fitness. Therefore, we combined both models and used the body condition from the structural equation model (SEM) as an individual covariate in the mark-recapture model (Fig. 3.1c). This approach allowed us to assess the influence of 'body condition' of individual i in winter t , on survival to $t + 1$, rather than treating condition as a static trait being constant across years, i.e. we treated body condition as a time-varying individual covariate that was only related to survival in the first time step after capture. In addition, 'Catch day' was included as a second time-variant individual covariate in the model because birds caught in the beginning of the winter had a higher chance to die than birds caught at the end of the winter (i.e. these birds had already survived most of winter). Similar to body condition, the individual covariate of catch day was only related to survival in the first time step after capture.

To speed up computation and help the model to converge, we used prior information obtained using the same population/data (Allen et al., 2019a, 2021) on the state and age specific survival and resighting probability obtained from a multi-state

model with RMark (Laake, 2013). The reason that we did not build the whole model in RMark was that we cannot integrate structural equation models nor integrate time-varying individual covariates in this modelling framework. For the available prior information from the RMark model, resighting data from 14 043 marked individuals with in total at least 46 806 resightings and 675 dead recoveries over a time-period of 20 years (2000-2020) was used. We included the priors with a beta distribution, using the mean and the standard deviation of the estimates extracted from the RMark model (Supplementary Fig. B10). If estimates from RMark model had high standard errors (and thus were unreliable; e.g. juvenile resighting probability of inland north and south; Supplementary Fig. B10), we used an uninformative prior with a beta distribution (i.e. $\text{dbeta}(1,1)$).

For all remaining regression parameters (from the SEM part of the model; green part in Fig. 3.1b), we specified non-informative priors with normal distribution and large variances, $N(0,10)$ (see the link to data archive under 'Research Data Management' for R-code and a complete specification of the model and priors used).

The full dataset (2000 – 2020) only provided information on the priors and helped to estimate the survival part of the MSM-SEM model (Fig. 3.1c). To estimate the survival part of the MSM-SEM (yellow part in Fig. 3.1b-c), we decided, for reasons of computational power, to use only the encounter history for 4 time intervals after the last winter catch for each period (Fig. 3.2) for the birds where condition data were available ($n=1574$). The choice of taking 4 time intervals was mainly based on the fact that after the last winter catch (2017-2018) the encounter history for only additional 4 time intervals was available. To have consistent time intervals across the two periods, we also used 4 time intervals after the last catch of the first period (2002-2003). This resulted in a total of 18 time intervals for the MSM-SEM (10 time intervals for period 1 and 8 time intervals for period 2). This is reasonable to do because we used the prior information from the RMark model on a large dataset (>14000 individuals). By removing the years between the catching events of the two periods (Fig. 3.2; 2005-2015), we may miss 15% of the individuals being resighted (Supplementary Table B9).

In addition, we added the SEM on environmental variables (Fig. 3.1d) to the MSM-SEM, as described in the previous section.

We ran the analysis with the R-package nimble (de Valpine et al., 2017).

Convergence was assessed using the Gelman-Rubin statistic (Gelman, 1996) which compares the within to the between variability of chains started at different dispersed initial values. In addition, the convergence was assessed by visually inspecting the mixing of the chains and the posterior distributions of all parameters. We ran two MCMC chains of 10000 iterations with a burn-in of 1000 and a thinning of 10, which resulted in acceptable convergence (Appendices I-III).

SEM for carry-over effect

To determine if a carry-over effect occurs, we conducted path analysis with the R-package brms (Bürkner, 2017, 2018) to investigate the effect of the direct as well as indirect pathway via lay date (Fig. 3.1e). Since the reproductive success has been shown to be highly affected by breeding phenology (e.g. lay date; Low et al., 2015; Reséndiz-Infante et al., 2020), we may expect that winter environmental variables or condition are also mediated by the timing of egg laying (Jean-Gagnon et al., 2018; Montreuil-Spencer et al., 2019). Since we only had a small subset of birds (max. n=32) for which we had information on their condition in winter and on reproductive success in the subsequent breeding season, we ran the path analysis in a separate model rather than in the same model as the MSM-SEM (Fig. 3.1a).

We ran two separate path analyses, one with daily clutch survival (n=32), and one with daily hatchling survival (n=25) as response variable. For the path analysis with 'daily clutch survival probability' as a response variable (effect of condition on daily clutch survival and effect of lay date on daily clutch survival; Fig. 3.1e), a beta distribution was used. When lay date was the response variable, we used a Gaussian distribution. For the path analysis on hatchling survival (days) we used a Poisson distribution. We standardized lay date separately for mainland and island breeding areas, because inland breeding birds started their clutch on average 10 days earlier (Supplementary Fig. B11). Birds breeding in cropland showed significantly lower hatchling survival (Supplementary Fig. B12b), whereas body condition did not differ significantly across habitat types (Supplementary Fig. B12a). This may influence the relationship of body condition on hatchling survival (Supplementary Fig. B12c) and we therefore included a variable 'crop' (as 0/1 for no/yes) to the path analysis on hatchling

survival. We did not include any habitat variable in the clutch success path analysis because there was no substantial effect of habitat type (Supplementary Fig. B13).

We used two MCMC chains of 15 000 iterations, a burnin of 4000 iterations and a thinning of 1 that resulted in acceptable mixing and convergence (Supplementary Fig. B14-B15 & Table B10-B11).

Results

Operationalizing and quantifying winter body condition

Body mass was positively correlated with three metrics of body size (tarsus length, head length, wing length; Fig. 3.3a). Therefore, we henceforth focus on size-corrected mass (i.e. the residuals of body mass regressed on these three size measures) as a proxy of fat content. Size-corrected mass, haematocrit and buffy coat were corrected for the effect of multiple potential confounding variables (Fig. 3.3a-c). Individuals that had to wait longer before being handled (after the catch) had a lower size-corrected mass and buffy coat, but higher haematocrit. In addition, birds caught later in the winter season show lower size-corrected mass and buffy coat, but higher haematocrit. Older birds were heavier but had lower haematocrit and buffy coat, while males had a slightly higher haematocrit and buffy coat than females. Shellfish specialists (i.e. bird with a high bill tip height), had a higher size-corrected mass, buffy coat and a lower haematocrit than worm specialists.

Model results show that size-corrected mass was negatively associated with winter body condition ($\gamma_1 = -1.55[-2.61; -0.63]$), whereas haematocrit and buffy coat were positively associated with condition ($\gamma_2 = 0.61[0.09; 1.15]$, $\gamma_3 = 0.61[0.00; 1.33]$, respectively; Fig. 3.3d-f). Relationships were consistent (in terms of direction) across the two periods (2000-2003; 2016-2018; Supplementary Fig. B16).

By definition of the statistical model used to operationalize body condition, birds with higher body condition have a higher survival probability. Notwithstanding, the effect of body condition was strong ($\beta_1 = 0.74[0.47; 1.01]$), with the predicted survival increasing from 0.2 to virtually 1.0 when comparing birds with the lowest and highest body condition in our study (Fig. 3.3g). Furthermore, body condition explained 25% of

the variation in survival across states, years and age classes.

Figure 3.3: The effect of confounding variables (e.g. age, sex, handling time) on the condition variables (a) size-corrected body mass, (b) haematocrit and (c) buffy coat. Dots and lines or shaded areas indicating the median and 95% credible interval, respectively. The dotted grey line showing the 0-line for the parameter estimates, meaning that variables not crossing the dotted grey line showing significant effect on the condition variable. Note that for the categorical variables (age and sex), it is the difference between the classes that is of interest rather than the overlap with the dotted line. d-f showing the effect of the size-corrected mass, haematocrit and buffy coat on body condition, respectively. Note that the predictor variables (condition measures) in d-f have been z-score standardized (mean=0, sd=1) before the analysis and the values shown here are standardized as well as corrected for the confounding variables. g) shows the relationship between condition and the predicted survival probability. Note that the fitted line is the survival probability for an average state and year. The dots represent the predicted survival probability from the multi state model which is the reason that the dots from a state/year/age combination are shaped in logistic line. In addition, g is a contrast plots meaning that the reference group of the survival probability for the state/age combination is 0 and the other levels are plotted in contrast to the 0. This is why the credible interval is 0 at condition 0. The intercepts for composite variable condition is 0 resulting in no credible interval at (0,0) in d-f. For the effect of body condition on survival (g) per age class see Supplementary Fig. B17.

Figure 3.4: Results from the two separate clutch survival (orange, $n=32$) and hatchling survival path analyses (blue, $n=25$) with the posterior mean, 95% credible interval in brackets and probability of direction (p_d) along the path ways. a) – c) visualize the path ways with the binned raw data points (averaged per levels of the independent variable), the fitted line (solid for an at least moderately strong effect and dashed for no evidence of an effect) and the shaded area for the 95% credible interval. Note that the hatchling survival data set only includes the nests that successful hatched from the clutch survival data set. Note that body condition is the condition of the parent in the preceding winter.

Carry-over effects of winter body condition on reproductive success

There was moderately strong evidence of an effect of both body condition and lay date on the reproductive success, as path analysis revealed a positive association between individual winter body condition and lay date on the clutch as well as hatchling survival (Fig. 3.4a,c). However, the positive effect of body condition on reproductive performance did not appear strongly mediated by earlier laying, as (i) there was no evidence for an effect of winter body condition on lay date (Fig. 3.4b; $p_d<0.94$), and (ii)

the direct pathway of winter body condition on clutch and hatchling survival was much stronger (0.34 and 0.13, respectively) than the indirect pathway via laying date (-0.04 for clutch as well as hatchling survival; Fig. 3.4). In addition, birds breeding on crop fields showed lower hatchling survival and later lay date (Supplementary Table B11).

Environmental drivers of body condition in winter

We found moderately strong evidence for an effect of grassland proportion on body condition in winter (Fig. 3.5f; $0.24[0.02;0.45]$; $p_d=0.98$). In addition, we found no evidence for an effect of conspecific density, temperature, precipitation, cockle or mussel availability on the winter body condition as the probability of direction (p_d) is smaller than 0.95 (Fig. 3.5a-e).

We found evidence that individuals with different feeding specializations show different body condition (Supplementary Fig. B18). Worm specialists showed a lower body condition ($-0.35[-0.53;-0.18]$) compared to shellfish specialists ($0.13[-0.01;0.28]$).

In addition, the effect of environmental variables on the condition depended on feeding specialization (Supplementary Fig. B19). For instance, the model shows strong evidence for worm specialists being more positively affected by higher temperature ($0.27[0.02;0.53]$) in winter than shellfish specialists ($-0.04[-0.33;0.26]$). Shellfish specialists benefited more from higher cockle availability ($0.09[-0.16;0.36]$) than worm specialists ($-0.13[-0.36;0.11]$).

For a more biological interpretation, we calculated the direct effect of the four environmental variables, with the strongest statistical evidence (p_d), experienced in winter on hatchling survival. We found that a 1 °C increase of winter temperature increased the hatchling survival (average 18.2 days) by 1 day, which corresponds to a 10% increase in hatchling survival (Fig. 3.6, Supplementary Table B15). Similarly, an increase of 0.87% in conspecific density (=1 individual/km²), 13% (=0.01) increase in grassland proportion around the wintering ground and 18% increase of cockle availability (=1 g AFDM/m²) lead to an increase of 10% in overall hatchling survival (Fig. 3.6, Supplementary Table B12).

Figure 3.5: The effect of environmental variables (weather (a-b), density (c) and food condition (d-f)) on the individual winter body condition. Dots indicating the raw data points per sample year and tidal basin (state). Lines indicating the fitted line and shaded areas showing the 95% credible interval. Values in the left upper corner show the posterior mean with the 95% credible interval in brackets as well as the probability of direction p_d . Solid and dashed line indicate evidence or no evidence of an effect of the environmental variable on body condition (based on p_d), respectively.

Figure 3.6: Overview of the main results of the study. Signs (-/+) indicate the direction of the relationship. The arrows in the right box indicate an increase in the variable. For instance, a 13% increase in grassland proportion results in 10% increase in hatchling survival, which is equal to one extra day of the survival of the hatchling. Note that we only show here the four environmental variables that had the strongest statistical evidence (p_d) for an effect on body condition.

Discussion

To understand the population dynamic and specifically the drivers for the decline of the Dutch oystercatcher population, this research was divided in two main aims. (1) Understanding the role of body condition in mediating carry-over effects and (2) understanding which winter environmental effects carry over on the reproductive success. We achieved these aims via three steps using a nationwide dataset collected over a long-time span. First, we used a novel analytical method that integrates capture-mark recapture and structural equation models (Cubaynes et al., 2012) to quantify body condition of wintering oystercatchers using three morphological and physiological variables that were good predictors of survival. Secondly, we showed that winter body condition directly carried over to the reproductive performance in the subsequent breeding season, and not via birds laying earlier. Third, we showed that grassland around wintering areas significantly increased the winter body condition, but also winter conspecific density, temperature and cockle availability appeared to have a positive biological effect on body condition, but these effects could only be estimated with low precision (low p_d). In the following sections, we start by placing the overall

findings of our study in a broader ecological context by discussing the importance of carry-over effect studies for the understanding of population dynamics. Next, we discuss the results for each of the three steps in detail. Finally, we end this discussion with some recommendations for future studies and management implications.

The findings of this study in a broad ecological perspective

We used body condition as an individual trait that may mediate the carry-over effect. According to Harrison et al. (2011), it is of high relevance to investigate ‘true’ carry-over effects with individual traits (e.g. condition, arrival date) to get better insight in the causal mechanism rather than investigating relations between environmental conditions in one season and the individual performance in the next season. There are already various studies that investigate ‘true’ carry-over effects across taxa (Bearhop et al., 2005; Gunnarsson et al., 2006; Sorensen et al., 2009). With our study, we contribute to this list of carry-over effect studies. In addition, we expand to existing studies by using a novel integrative statistical framework, the way how we quantified body condition and the national scale of this study.

However, we want to emphasize the importance to consider a mediating individual trait. We find a carry-over effect of the grassland proportion in winter to the reproductive success, mediated by body condition. The other environmental variables (e.g. food availability, weather) do not show clear evidence for an effect. This helps us to better understand which variables really drive the population dynamics and the mechanism behind it. For example, pup production in Australian fur seals (*Arctocephalus pusillus doriferus*) was negatively correlated with winter sea-surface temperature (Gibbens & Arnould, 2009). However, it is not possible to be certain about the mechanism driving the observed differences between individuals because they did not link it to a quantified individual trait like timing of breeding or condition. For instance in our study system, warmer winters may result in low food availability in spring for coastal breeding oystercatchers because (1) large reproductive events of bivalves are more likely to follow cold spells in winter (Beukema et al., 2009) and (2) higher sea temperature in winter results in higher metabolic rate resulting in increased weight loss (Zwarts, 1991). Without an individual trait, we may have found a

relationship between winter temperature and reproductive success (of the coastal breeders). However, this would not be a real carry-over effect since the effect of food availability is basically operating intra-seasonally and not inter-seasonally. In addition, this process may not necessarily cause individual variation in reproductive success.

With evidence of a carry-over effect in this study, we can exclude that the performance during breeding season is solely due to ‘fixed’ individual variation (e.g. a better individual is always performing better independent of what it experiences in a previous season, and a bad individual is always performing poorly). We can exclude now, for instance, that the individual differences in reproductive performance are only based on the overall foraging efficiency of an individual (being similarly good or bad in winter and spring).

Despite the importance of investigating carry-over effects to understand population dynamics, these kinds of studies also pose some challenges. Tracking individuals throughout their annual life cycle and collecting a valuable amount of data year-round (or at least during two seasons) so that analyses are powerful enough to encounter significant effects, is one major challenge (Harrison et al., 2011). In our study, finding individuals back during the breeding season was difficult despite substantial ring reading effort of citizen scientist. Some advanced technologies of GPS-tracking would have probably increased the sample size (for the carry-over effect analysis; Fig. 3.1), however, this also means larger expenses. Despite these logistical challenges of tracking individuals across seasons, we found clear associations (carry-over effect), even though the sample size was limited.

Another critical challenge is to find a framework that analyses the different events and processes jointly (Souchay et al., 2018). In this study, we followed the novel approach by integrating path analysis within a capture-recapture framework (Cubaynes et al., 2012) and combine this with the use of composite latent variables to summarize the multidimensional nature of the concept body condition (Frauendorf et al., 2021), resulting in a powerful and flexible framework that can be used in future studies. We combine here different statistical approaches. We use latent variables, a not directly measured variable, to quantify body condition and incorporate this body condition index directly as time-variant individual covariate in a multi-state mark recapture model that accounts for imperfect detection. Conventional programs for mark-recapture

models like MARK (White & Burnham, 1999) would not allow such an incorporation. By quantifying the body condition based on not only body mass, but also accounting for physiological measures, we expect to have a more appropriate predictor explaining individual fitness, especially for this specific oystercatcher population (Frauendorf et al., 2021; Harrison et al., 2011).

However, still there can occur computational limitations, especially with long time series (like in our study 40 time steps, 9 states and 3 age classes), that result in large transition matrices. Nevertheless, with the steadily improving technologies and development of packages, this flexible framework gives a lot of opportunities.

In our study, we were limited by the number of birds that were found back in its breeding territory. That also meant that we created a condition index by relating the different condition variables that we measured (body mass, haematocrit, buffy coat) to explain most of the variation in survival. Ideally, we would be more interested in a body condition that explains individual variation in reproduction, since we are investing carry-over effects, for all individuals that were captured in winter (Fig. 3.1a). Using reproduction as response variable would also allow to run the path analysis and the MSM-SEM in one model rather than in two (with a subset of the data), as we have done (Fig. 3.1). Still we are confident about our approach, because it appears that the condition explaining variation in survival also captures the condition explaining variation in reproduction. Since otherwise, we would have not found a carry-over effect. However, in other study systems, the optimal condition estimate may be less similar depending on whether it is fitted to variation in survival or reproduction. Structural equation modelling therefore also allows to study context-dependent condition that may vary during the life cycle and/or with the fitness trait. Albatrosses for instance are known to prioritize reproduction in one year, but survival in another year (Froy et al., 2013). This would probably result in different condition indices in different years.

To summarize, the biological challenge in our analysis was actually in connecting winter body condition to survival. In fact, the main challenge was, that we found biological effects of winter environmental conditions on the winter body condition, but that the precision of these effects was low (and overlapped with zero). The general insight from this study may therefore be that although there are challenges of following

individual across seasons and integrating the data in one statistical framework, we were able to estimate these effects reasonably well with few individuals; possibly because we included individual condition as a state variable and thereby estimated the relationship at within-individual level. Thus, we filtered out among individual variation that may add noise to environmental associations by comparing population averages among years with different body and environmental conditions. By contrast, estimating how environmental conditions affect body condition is logistically less challenging, but probably needs a lot of data over many years and areas to estimate them reliably. We did not realize this challenge a priori and it may be useful for researchers to be aware of this potential challenge, even if this may not hold generally across all study systems.

Quantification of body condition

In this section we discuss the results from the quantification of the individual body condition. We found a negative relationship of body mass (corrected for size) on the individual condition and a positive relationship of haematocrit and buffy coat on condition.

The negative relationship between size-corrected mass and condition as well as the positive relationship between buffy coat and condition are contrasting results compared to Verhulst et al. (2004). They found that body condition (and return rates of wintering oystercatchers) was positively related to size-corrected mass and negatively related to buffy coat with condition, respectively. However, we should keep in mind that for three reasons the results are not completely comparable. Firstly, we use here more years (four winters) compared to Verhulst et al. (2004), that used only one winter. In addition, we expanded the number of catching areas to a wider range across the Wadden Sea and the Delta area. A second difference is that Verhulst et al. (2004) is that, even though they estimated return rates (and included a site-effect as a factor to account for different resighting probabilities across areas), they did not account for transition probability between tidal basin and imperfect detection. In the multi-state model of our study movement probability between states and imperfect detection is taken into account to estimate survival probability. Lastly, they used a PCA to quantify body condition (of the condition variables body mass, haematocrit and buffy

coat), which means that they identified the axes of body condition based on the correlation patterns among those condition variables (Abdi & Williams, 2010), whereas we defined the body condition based on the weight that mass contributes to explaining the variation in survival. As both the methods and data used in our study differs considerably from those used by Verhulst et al. (2004), this may explain some of the apparently contrasting results on how different condition measures were related with body condition. Overall, we think that our approach advances on the approach by Verhulst et al. (2004) in various important ways, such that we consider our results to be more reliable.

Haematocrit, the proportion of red blood cells with the main function of oxygen transportation, has been shown to be positively related to survival in Eurasian oystercatcher (Verhulst et al., 2004) and crimson fishes (*Neochmia phaeton*) (Milenkaya et al., 2015). Also Piersma et al. (1996) found that high haematocrit levels were associated to better health in bar-tailed godwits. Buffy coat, the fraction of white blood cells, is often expected to be elevated if the body fight against infections (Beechler et al., 2015; Campbell et al., 2008; Ullman-Culler, 1999). However, low levels of white blood cells may also be indicative of immunosuppression, with an associated increase in susceptibility to infections, whereas, in contrast, high levels may indicate a well-working immune system (Hanssen et al., 2005).

We may expect a parabolic relationship between the condition variables (size-corrected mass, haematocrit and buffy coat) and condition. However, a model with a non-linear effect of the condition variables (squared variable) did not fit better than the model with only a linear effect of the condition variable (Supplementary Table B6). If a parabolic relationship between x and y exists, but only the right or left part of the range in x is sampled, we can only detect a linear instead of non-linear relationship between x and y . Following this idea, our results concerning the variable body mass may indicate that we did not sample a lot of individuals being close to starvation (low body mass and low survival) and therefore only detected a negative linear relationship between mass and condition.

A possible explanation for the negative relationship between mass and condition may be that birds that are very heavy, are more easily caught by predators since they are less agile due to higher mass (Zwarts et al., 1996b). Peregrine falcons (*Falco*

peregrinus) are potential predators of oystercatchers in their wintering ground and the number of wintering peregrine falcons increased in the Netherlands in the last decades (Supplementary Fig. B20). A second possible explanation is that birds in higher condition are also those being more dominant and having constant access to food sources such that they do not need to store fat reserves for bad times as low-condition individuals should do to have a higher chance of survival in times of food shortage (Cuthill et al., 2000; Ekman & Liliendahl, 1993). However, it is important to keep in mind that this hypothesis may depend on the relative importance of the effects of social dominance on food supply and predation risk (Verhulst & Hogstad, 1996).

Carry-over effect

We found that higher body condition in winter carries over to higher reproductive success in the subsequent season. The positive effect of winter body condition on the reproductive success is consistent with the idea that individuals that enter the breeding season in better condition can better protect the clutch against predators (chasing them away). In addition, such individuals may be able to have higher nest attendance (because of less need to forage if birds in lower condition) so that the chance of clutch predation is lower. In addition, birds in good condition, may also have more energy to find enough food for their chicks. If they spend more time on finding food and transport it to the hatchlings, this will keep the chicks satisfied and they remain safe in hiding.

Furthermore, we did not find a relationship between condition and lay date. A possible explanation may be that the condition variables (body mass, haematocrit and buffy coat) we use to define body condition show relatively strong within-individual variation between different winter seasons. Data from birds being caught twice in different winters reveal that within-individual variation is about 70% for body mass and buffy coat, and 30% for haematocrit (Supplementary Table B13). Therefore, body condition is a more dynamic trait, whereas lay date is known to be highly repeatable across years within individuals and relatively constant throughout the lifetime of an individual (van De Pol & Pettifor, 2006).

Winter environmental effects

We found that some environmental variables had weak to strong effects on the winter body condition and we will next discuss those effects in more detail. We found the available grassland around a catching site had a relative strong positive effect on winter body condition. Several studies showed already that oystercatchers also forage on grasslands in winter but it is usually seen as indication that individuals have problems finding enough food during low tide on the mud flats (Caldow et al., 1999; Durell et al., 2001a; Heppleston, 1971). Especially worm specialists make use of it as an additional food source during high tide (when intertidal flats are not exposed for foraging) but also during low tide as an potentially alternative food source (van der Kolk et al., 2019). Our results strongly suggest that grasslands are more important for wintering oystercatcher than appreciated up to now. This may be especially the case under certain conditions (e.g. full moon, probably in combination with rainy weather; van der Kolk et al., 2019).

Higher oystercatcher density resulted in higher individual condition and survival. Probably, oystercatchers aggregate in good feeding areas, so that the positive density effect may be better interpreted as a high site quality effect (Ens & Cayford, 1996; Swennen, 1984). In addition, individuals aggregated in larger flocks have a lower chance of being caught by a predator, consequently resulting in higher survival, than an individual feeding in a smaller flock (Cresswell, 1994). Also increased vigilance associated to a larger flock size can increase the survival of an individual either through faster response to predator appearance or through more available time that can be spent on foraging or resting (Cresswell, 1994).

Temperature had a positive effect on the winter body condition. This is in line with outcomes from previous studies that show that milder winter resulted in higher survival (Durell et al., 2001b; van de Pol et al., 2010). Unfortunately, the studied period did not include years with extreme cold weather conditions. For instance, the Netherlands had a relatively cold winter in 2009/2010 with a mean daily temperature of 1°C (Supplementary Fig. B21) but also in 2011/2012 there were several mean daily temperatures below 0°C going down to minus 12°C were, consequently, several shorebirds have been found dead along the coast (Schwemmer et al., 2014).

Higher cockle availability also showed to some extent an increase in body condition,

however, this effect is not as strong as from the other three environmental variables (grassland, density, temperature). This may suggest that the condition, how we defined it, is not strongly affected by cockle availability as food source.

Interestingly, we also see differences in the response to environmental drivers between feeding specialists. It is already known that different feeding specialists (worm vs. shellfish specialists) differ in their foraging time and apparent survival and that feeding specialists differ in how environmental conditions alter their foraging time. This study adds to the previous study by van der Kolk et al. (2019) by confirming that there is also a mechanism that mediates body condition. Worm specialists are more sensitive to temperature than shellfish specialists because during cold weather condition, they cannot utilize grasslands as invertebrates are unreachable in the frozen soil. In addition, soft-bodied prey like ragworms (*Nereididae*), which are an important food source in intertidal flats for worm specialists (van de Pol et al., 2009), are more difficult to obtain under colder conditions than shellfish as they become less active.

The result that individuals respond differently to the environment is also important for carry-over effect studies in general. Carry-over effects on individual level do not necessarily need to have impact on the population level. From our result, we may suggest a stronger carry-over effect on individual level, given the effect of the environment differs for different feeding specialization. However, on population level, this effect (of environment on condition) may be less clear because the individuals benefiting from one environmental variable is counterbalanced at the population level by other individuals experiencing disadvantages from the same environmental variable.

The choice of the environmental factors we included in the analysis is based on previous research, but we cannot exclude the existence of important unmeasured environmental variables that may affect the condition and survival. Overall, the precision of the effects of the six considered environmental variables was low, with only the 95% confidence intervals of the estimated effect of grassland proportion on body condition not overlapping with zero (Fig. 3.5). Nevertheless, when calculating the effect of the four environmental variables that present the strongest effect through body condition to the reproduction, we show that although our precision is low, there is a considerable biological effect (Fig. 3.6). Even though the results may be still imprecise at the moment, they show at least some biological significance in the overall effect on

hatchling survival. Including a larger number of years and areas may improve the precision of environmental effect sizes in future studies.

Future outlook and implications for the Dutch oystercatcher population

To summarize, this study helped us to get better insight in the mechanism driving the population decline. We contributed to existing literature by showing an example of a carry-over effect study that uses an advanced analytical approach, uses a condition index (including the physiological state of an individual) as mediating individual trait on a large national scale. This study also emphasizes the importance for large spatiotemporal carry-over effect studies, especially when concerning migratory species.

In the introduction, we mentioned the hypothesis that there may be one common environmental driver in the wintering ground that all individuals experience during winter and may explain the low reproductive success across the Netherlands since the 1990s (Roodbergen et al., 2012). The only variable that received strong statistical support and that could be potentially explaining this hypothesis would be the grassland proportion. According to CBS et al. (2021), the size of permanent grasslands decreased by almost 40% across the Netherlands since 1980s, whereas arable land increased by 6% (across crop types). We can therefore recommend preserving grasslands, especially permanent grasslands (rather than changing them to arable land or even buildings) close to highly used high tide roost areas to ensure that the birds have the possibility to forage on grasslands close to their roost areas. The soil quality in permanent grasslands is higher because it is less disturbed than in temporary grasslands or arable land and, consequently resulting in higher earthworm abundance (Onrust et al., 2019). Earthworms are an important food source for oystercatchers foraging on grasslands (Zwarts et al., 1996b).

We also note that we found indications that temperature, cockle abundance and competitor density could also have biologically carry over effects, but we cannot be very certain about these yet (very low precision and confidence intervals overlapping with zero). Winter temperature showed a positive effect on the condition, but winters became milder in the last decades, and thus cannot explain low(ered) reproductive

success in recent decades. The food availability of shellfish could potentially explain the low reproductive success. Especially the mussel stocks (available for oystercatchers) decreased since the 1980s (van der Meer et al., 2019; Waser et al., 2016). At that time, the Dutch oystercatcher population was still growing. In contrary, there is no clear evidence of a consistent change in the highly variable cockle stocks in the Wadden Sea in the period 1980-2020 (Beukema & Dekker, 2006; Troost et al., 2021). The density effect (Fig. 3.5 & 3.6) is potentially a result of intrinsic as well as extrinsic effects and difficult to disentangle which variable is responsible for instance for a habitat quality effect (other than shellfish availability).

Ultimately, the findings of our study (e.g. effect sizes of the different pathways) can be included in population models to compare the relative effect of the winter on the reproductive success compared to environmental drivers in the breeding ground, to better understand the relative importance of winter and summer drivers on the demography of the Dutch oystercatcher population.

Acknowledgement

We thank all the volunteers, students and researchers that helped collecting data by ring resightings, winter catches and monitoring the reproductive success. We also want to thank Henk van der Jeugd (Dutch Centre for Avian Migration and Demography) for making the dead recovery data available for this research. Funding was provided by the Applied and Engineering Sciences domain of the Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO-STW; grant number 14638) as well as by Royal Netherlands Air Force, Birdlife Netherlands, NAM gas exploration and Deltares. Handling, taking blood samples and ringing of the oystercatchers was done under license of the Dutch Flora and Fauna Law (FF/75A/2013/038) and the Natuurbeschermingswet (824351 and ZK17000170/17024425) and approved by the Dutch Ethical Committee (Sovon AVD25002015200-001). We acknowledge the feedback provided by ecologists working at these organisations during half-yearly meetings.

Supplemental material

Supplementary material (additional figures, tables and text) of chapter 3 is included as appendix B to this thesis.

Since Appendix I-III are long (i.e. number of pages) and in different formats (.pdf, .csv), they can be found under the data archive link for chapter 3 under 'Research Data Management'.

Appendix I: Density and trace plots of the MSM-SEM (.pdf)

Appendix II: Potential scale reduction factor (PSRF, R-hat) of the MSM-SEM (.csv)

Appendix III: Parameter estimates of the variables from the MSM-SEM (.pdf)

CHAPTER 4

Love thy neighbour? – Spatial variation in density dependence of nest survival in relation to predator community

Magali Frauendorf, Andrew M. Allen, Eelke Jongejans, Bruno J. Ens, Wolf Teunissen, Christian Kampichler, Chris A. M. van Turnhout, Liam D. Bailey, Hans de Kroon, Jenny Cremer, Erik Kleyheeg, Jeroen Nienhuis, Martijn van de Pol

Abstract

In many species, density-dependent effects on reproduction are an important driver of population dynamics. However, it is rarely considered that the direction of density-dependence is expected to vary over space and time depending on anti-predator behaviour and predator community. Aggregation may allow for effective group mobbing against avian nest predators whilst aggregation may also attract mammalian predators, causing negative density dependence. We aim to quantify spatial variation in the effect of conspecific breeding density on nest survival in a mobbing bird species (Eurasian oystercatcher; *Haematopus ostralegus*) and identify whether this variation in density dependence can be explained by the predator community. We integrated reproductive data with breeding territory maps of Eurasian oystercatchers and occupancy maps of avian and mammalian predator species across the Netherlands for a 10-year period. Spatial variation in the composition of the predator community explained the effects of neighbour density, showing decreasing nest survival when both conspecific density and mammalian dominance increased. Also heterospecific density (from breeding godwits and lapwing) have an additional effect on the oystercatcher nest survival. Strikingly, this pattern did not extend to mammal-free island populations. Our study provides evidence that both the strength and sign of density dependence can vary spatially within species, implying that it is dangerous to generalize results from a single local population to larger-scale management implications and modelling exercises. The study also suggests that conservation actions that aim to attract breeding birds should be prioritized in areas with fewer mammalian predators, but this idea requires further testing on island populations.

Introduction

Density dependence is a key factor for understanding and managing the dynamics of species (Ringelman et al., 2012). Density dependence can take positive or negative directions. At high population densities close to the carrying capacity, population density and growth are generally negatively related due to increased competition for resources (Dunn et al., 2015), predator attraction (Gunnarsson & Elmberg, 2008) or parasite transmission (Deredec & Courchamp, 2006), which prevents populations from growing further (Mayer et al., 2019). On the other hand, at low population size, density dependence can be positive due to problems in, for example, finding mates or deterring predators (Kramer et al., 2011). If declining populations reach low densities, positive density dependence could lead to an acceleration of decline, ultimately causing an extinction vortex (Luque et al., 2016), which is also known as an Allee effect (Allee, 1927). This may occur even if the original factor that caused the initial population decline is no longer present.

Most empirical studies of density dependence focus on a single local population from which the results may be generalized over a larger spatial scale (Ackerman et al., 2004; Nummi & Saari, 2003; Prop & Quinn, 2003; Stephens & Sutherland, 1999). However, the mechanisms that shape density dependence strongly depend on the ecological circumstances (e.g. presence and behaviour of particular predators; Hogstad, 1995), and are thus expected to vary spatiotemporally (Knipl & Rost, 2016; Tobin et al., 2007; Walter et al., 2017), which may make broad generalisation unreliable.

Predator-driven density dependence (Cresswell & Quinn, 2011; Olson et al., 2015) has been increasingly identified as important to the dynamics of wild animal populations (Kramer et al., 2009). This holds particularly for bird species, where predation is one of the main causes of reproductive failure (Møller et al., 2018; Palmer et al., 2019). Whether aggregation during the reproductive season (i.e. breeding at high density) incurs a benefit or a cost in birds, and thus results in a positive or negative density effect on nest survival, may depend on how predators and prey interact (Forsman et al., 1998; Ringelman, 2014) and on the presence and behaviour (e.g. cognitive and perceptual ability) of nest predators (Auger-Methe et al., 2016; Blanco & Bertellotti, 2002; Rangen et al., 2001).

Anti-predator behaviour by the parents, like predator mobbing (Krams et al., 2009), can reduce nest predation rates if birds nest close to each other and help in protecting neighbouring nests (Larsen & Grundetjern, 1997; Quinn & Ueta, 2008). However, if the anti-predator behaviour of the prey species is ineffective, for example if densities become too low for group defence to be effective (Sönnichsen et al., 2013), spacing out to avoid predators may be a more efficient predator avoidance strategy (Picman, 1988). If predators can learn to exploit areas with higher nest densities (Larivière & Messier, 1998; Ringelman, 2014; Yahner & Mahan, 1996) or by exhibiting “area-restricted searching” behaviour once they find a nest (Bernard, 2004), this will increase the predation risk of nests at high densities. Area-restricted searching is well known for a variety of mammalian predators, which mainly use olfactory cues and are nocturnal (Hogstad, 1995; Nummela et al., 2013; Rangen et al., 2000). Avian nest survival may thus be negatively density-dependent in the presence of predator species that exploit areas with high nest densities and where deterrence is ineffective, while positively density-dependent if other predators occur that can be cooperatively deterred by prey.

Inter-population variation in density dependence is likely to be highly relevant, but only a limited number of these studies relate it to predation (Banda & Blanco, 2009; Lebeuf & Giroux, 2014; Oro et al., 2006). Existing studies have focussed on the role of a single predator species concerning predator-driven density dependency. Notably, studies focussing on a wider range of species that make up the predator community are lacking, even though its importance has been emphasized in the literature (Rangen et al., 2001).

The Eurasian oystercatcher (*Haematopus ostralegus*) is a particularly relevant species to investigate spatial variation in density-dependent nest survival. There is concern that the ongoing population decline over much of the Netherlands (Roodbergen & Teunissen, 2019) of this near-threatened bird species (BirdLife International, 2021) could accelerate due to positive density-dependent nest survival. The reason for this is that experimental and observational evidence from one population dominated by avian predators showed that nests with no neighbours within 50 m rarely survived, whilst nest predation was virtually absent in the presence of nearby neighbours in this mobbing species (Bailey et al., 2017). The key challenge is now to understand if such exceptionally strong positive dependence also occurs across

populations experiencing a diversity of predator communities over a large spatial scale.

To better understand the importance of density dependent effects on a landscape scale, we investigated (i) the spatial variation in density-dependent nest survival of oystercatchers in the Netherlands and (ii) whether this variation was correlated with the composition of local predator community. We hypothesize that there is substantial spatial variation in the sign and strength of the density effect on nest survival across populations. We predict that there is a positive effect of conspecific neighbour density on nest survival in areas dominated by avian predators due to the mechanism of predator deterrence and effective mobbing behaviour (Fig. 4.1a; as in Bailey et al., 2017). On the other hand, we expect that density has a negative effect on nest survival in areas dominated by mammalian predators, where the mechanism of predator avoidance may play an important role (Fig. 4.1b). Possibly, when both predator groups are present, density dependence may not be apparent as positive and negative effects cancel one another out (Fig. 4.1c; for more complex predictions see Discussion).

Figure 4.1: Illustration of possible relationships between nest survival and breeding pair density with different predator communities (avian dominated: dashed line, mammalian dominated: dotted line or mixed: solid line; see also profile drawings) for a situation in which (a) only predator deterrence, (b) only predator avoidance and (c) a combination of both mechanisms shape density dependence of nest survival. Note that for the purpose of our study, the density-dependent relationships depicted are under the general assumptions that deterrence is more effective against avian predators than mammalian predators, and that predators, especially mammals, have learned or use search behaviours to exploit areas with high nest densities (i.e. predation is not incidental). Density-dependent relationships are however more complex and deviations from the above will result in different relationships, as covered in the discussion section.

Finally, other species nesting nearby may also provide antipredator benefits (Semeniuk & Dill, 2006), or may also attract nest predators. We therefore considered the contribution of other bird species that breed in similar habitats as oystercatchers, that are also known for their mobbing behaviour against predators, and that suffer from similar nest predators (Møller et al., 2018).

To our knowledge this is the first study investigating density-dependent nest survival across multiple populations, also incorporating a wide range of predator species (predator composition) rather than focussing on one specific predator species. Therefore, our study aims to provide a better understanding of the factors that drive spatiotemporal variation in density dependence, which can be important for species conservation and management.

Methods

Study system

The Eurasian oystercatcher is a long-lived bird that, historically, bred on saltmarshes and dunes along the coastline of Europe, where it feeds on intertidal mudflats. Since the 1950s, it colonized inland breeding areas up to a few hundred kilometres from the coast, and it now predominantly breeds on agricultural land in many parts of Europe (Goss-Custard, 1996). Oystercatcher breeding pairs are highly territorial and show extreme site-fidelity to their breeding area (Goss-Custard, 1996). Oystercatchers are well known for their intensive group mobbing behaviour (Gochfeld, 1984), with typically multiple breeding pairs jointly chasing avian predators throughout the incubation and chick-rearing phase.

During the breeding season (April until July) oystercatchers lay eggs in a shallow nest scrape on the ground (clutch size 1-4, typically 3), which they incubate for 27 days. Vegetation around nests and cryptic egg colours and markings provide the major source of nest concealment, as they use little nesting material. Following nest loss, one or more replacement clutches may be laid.

We focussed our study on 10 years (2009 - 2018) during which nationwide data was available on (i) oystercatcher nest survival, (ii) breeding density of oystercatchers and three co-occurring heterospecifics, and (iii) predator community (10 years for

mammalian predators and 3 years for avian predators). At breeding sites on saltmarshes on the Dutch Wadden Sea islands, mainly avian predators like gull species (*Laridae*) and western marsh harriers (*Circus aeruginosus*) are present (Verboven et al., 2001; Supplementary Fig. C1). In inland breeding areas, in addition to avian predators like gulls and crows (*Corvidae*), oystercatchers also have to deal with mammalian predators like the red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*), stoat (*Mustela ermine*), beech marten (*Martes foina*) and European polecat (*Mustela putorius*) (Teunissen et al., 2008; Supplementary Fig. C1), which do not occur on island sites, except for stoat being present on the island of Texel (Supplementary Fig. C1).

Reproductive, conspecific and heterospecific breeding density data

Data on oystercatcher nest survival was available across the Netherlands, including GPS coordinates of exact nest locations. Nests were revisited several times and the fate of the nest was noted. The nest survival is defined as the probability that a nest will survive until the next day (daily nest survival), which thus accounts for differences in exposure time. This accounts for the fact that nests are found part-way through the nesting stage and are therefore biased towards successful nests (Mayfield method; Aebischer, 1999).

We used breeding density of oystercatchers (conspecific) and of three sympatric species (heterospecific) as a proxy for mobbing density. Data from the Dutch Breeding Bird Monitoring program (BMP) were used to obtain a measure of meadow bird (Eurasian oystercatcher, common redshank (*Tringa totanus*), northern lapwing (*Vanellus vanellus*) and black-tailed godwit (*Limosa limosa*)) breeding density around all oystercatcher nest locations. BMP is based on intensive territory mapping in fixed study plots carried out by well-trained volunteers that follow a standardized protocol (van Turnhout, 2010). In short: territory mapping is based on a large, and annually constant, number of field visits (5-10 between March and July depending on species) in which all birds with territorial behaviour (e.g. song, pair bond, display, alarm, nests) are recorded on maps. Species-specific interpretation criteria are used to determine the number and exact locations of “territories” per species at the end of the season (since 2011 using an automated procedure; van Dijk et al., 2013). The number of “territories” is considered a reliable proxy of true abundance and we expect approximate linear relationships between the surveyed samples and the total density of each species (van

Turnhout et al., 2010).

The scale at which density is measured can impact the outcome of analyses (Bailey et al., 2017). On the islands of Ameland (Island 1) and Schiermonnikoog (Island 2), the nesting density within a radius of 50 m and 100 m around a focal nest explained the most variation in predation rates (Bailey et al., 2017; Martig, 2017). We assume that the effective mobbing distance is similar in other populations, but since breeding densities are lower in inland areas, we used a 100 m radius to determine breeding density, as this resulted in most variation of breeding density in our data. Therefore, we overlaid a circle with a radius of 100 m (3.14 ha) around each nest location on the BMP territory maps and calculated the number of breeding territories within this area (including the focal breeding pair). We only included focal nests in the analysis for which at least 85% of the 100 m radius circle was included within a BMP census area (Supplementary Fig. C2). The breeding densities for the local populations (ranging from 0.64-1.6 pairs/ha) and the country-wide dataset (ranging from 0.32-1.28 pairs per ha) showed similar range (Supplementary Table C1).

Overlaying the nest survival data with the territory maps resulted in 661 observations consisting of two types of datasets: a) a “country-wide dataset”, based on country-wide nest data collected by trained volunteers (yellow dots in Fig. 4.2) and b) “local population datasets”, based on highly detailed nest data from local populations collected by professional researchers (blue, green and purple dots in Fig. 4.2). Spatially separate studies on the same island (on ‘Island 1’ and ‘Island 3’; Fig. 4.2) were treated as separate populations, since habitat and nest survival of the local populations differ within the islands. Note that the method of density estimation did not differ between the two dataset types (both based on the BMP) and nest survival was sampled in the same way in both datasets.

Predator community

We constructed indices of predator community by constructing nation-wide species distribution models for each potential predator species (based on presence-absence data). We recorded predation events with cameras placed at oystercatcher nests to (a) identify which predator species should be taken into account and (b) to quantify its relative importance as a nest predator. Subsequently, we calculated a predator

community index for each nest location.

Figure 4.2: a) Map of the Netherlands with the distribution of nest locations and their data source. Country-wide dataset (yellow dots) including spatially well-distributed nest locations collected by trained volunteers; two local populations are located on the island 1 (green dots) and 3 (blue dots); one local population on the island 2 (purple dots). b) showing the number of nests included in the analysis per year and dataset source.

We used species distribution modelling to estimate the probability of presence for each potential predator species. Mammal presence-absence data for a 10-year period (2009-2018) from the Dutch National Database on Flora and Fauna (www.ndff.nl) were used. Nationwide avian presence-absence data and distribution maps were available from the Sovon Bird Atlas project (Sovon Vogelonderzoek Nederland, 2018) for a 3-year period only (2013-2015), but localized annual survey counts reveal little inter-annual variation for the whole study period (2009-2018; Supplementary Fig. C3). Note that the multiple years of data were pooled to one single static distribution model per species. Observed predator presence data were combined with open-access landscape data to estimate the probability of presence (ranging from 0 to 1) for each predator species for

each 1x1 km grid cell nationwide (Supplementary Fig. C1) with the R-package SDMaps (Kampichler et al., 2020). For more detail on the methodology, see Supplementary Text C1. These predator maps can be used to give an indication of the probability of presence for each predator species.

To choose which predators' species distribution models should be taken into account for the predator community index and to quantify their relative importance as a nest predator, we identified predation events based on camera trap monitoring (Supplementary Fig. C4). Camera traps were placed near 177 nests (1.5-2 m from the nest at 50-70 cm height) in different habitats (on random allocation within each study area) throughout the Netherlands (36 cameras were placed on island saltmarshes, 94 cameras on island farmland and 47 cameras on mainland farmland) (Supplementary Fig. C4), during which 95 predation events were detected. Mammalian predators made up 20.2% of predators detected on camera traps. These included red fox (9.5%), European hedgehog (*Erinaceus europaeus*) (3.2%), brown rat (*Rattus norvegicus*) (3.2%), beech marten (2.1 %), stoat (1.1%) and other unidentifiable mammal species (1.1%). Area-restricted searching is well known for red foxes (Larivière & Messier, 1998), beech martens (Kitikidou et al., 2014; Rödel & Stubbe, 2006), stoats (King & Powell, 2006), European polecats (Lode, 2000) and striped skunks (*Mephitis mephi*) (Nams, 1997). Avian predators made up 68.6% of all detected predators and included carrion crow (*Corvus corone*) (23.2%), western marsh harrier (21.1%), common gull (*Larus canus*) (6.3%), unknown gull species (5.3%), herring gull (*Larus argentatus*) (4.2%), unknown predatory bird species (4.2%), oystercatcher (2.1%), lesser black-backed gull (*Larus fuscus*) (1.1%) and common buzzard (*Buteo buteo*) (1.1%). The remaining 11.2% were unidentifiable predators (Supplementary Fig. C4). Note that camera traps were placed at a subset of locations (mostly islands) to identify the predator species, rather than randomly placed throughout all populations to estimate the predator density.

Monitoring schemes of mammalian and avian predators differed (Supplementary Text C1 & Table C2) and because we aimed to make the probability of presence comparable between both predator types (avian and mammal), we normalized the data (per predator type) using the formula $\frac{x-x_{min}}{x_{max}-x_{min}}$. Gull species are colony birds and have large foraging areas compared to the other predator species, and we accounted for

their larger space use by taking the mean probability of presence of a 3 km-radius buffer around the nest location (Rock et al., 2016), whereas we used a 1 km-radius for all other predator species. We excluded two predator species that together accounted for 6.4% of all camera-recorded nest predation events: Brown rat was excluded as there were too little field data to produce reliable species distribution maps for this species, while hedgehog was excluded because this mammal is not expected to exhibit area-restricted searching behaviour at the spatial scale at which oystercatchers breed (Schmidt & Whelan, 1999).

We calculated a “mammalian dominance index” by dividing the sum of the probability of presence of all mammalian predators by the sum of the probability of presence of all mammalian plus avian predator species. This resulted in a value of 1 for only mammalian predators present and of 0 for only avian predators present. Finally, some predators may be more important than other predators (in terms of oystercatcher nest predation) and thus their presence could be weighted based on predation threats. Weighting was based on frequency of predation events from the camera trap monitoring (Supplementary Fig. C4 & Table C3). This resulted in two potential “mammalian dominance index” proxies, a “weighted” and an “unweighted” one (Supplementary Table C4).

Data analysis

Local population analysis

To test for statistical differences in density-dependent nest survival between the local populations (island study sites), we used a generalized linear mixed model (GLMM) with binomial distribution and logit-link function for nest survival (N). We included the main effects and interaction between the linear covariate density (D) and the factor local population (P) as explanatory variables. To account for confounding effects of predictors other than density that could influence nest survival, we included distance to the coast (C) (reflecting distance to benthic or terrestrial food source) as a continuous fixed effect. We also included random intercepts u and v to account for the variation in nest survival among years (i) and habitat types (j). Habitat type was based on data from CBS Statistics Netherlands, which was combined into one variable consisting of seven

classes, with the most common classes being grassland, arable land and nature areas (Supplementary Table C5). The regression model is shown in equation 4.1 with ϵ indicating the residuals, β_0 the intercept and β_{1-4} the regression coefficients of the model.

$$\text{Logit}(N_{ij}) \sim \beta_0 + \beta_1 D_{ij} + \beta_2 P_j + \beta_3 D_{ij} P_j + \beta_4 C_j + u_i + v_j + \epsilon_{ij} \quad \text{Equation 4.1}$$

Predator community analysis

To identify if either the “weighted” or “unweighted” mammalian dominance index better explains the variation in density-dependent nest survival of oystercatchers, we used an information theoretic model selection approach using Akaike information criterion (AIC) (Burnham & Anderson, 1998). The index with the lowest AIC (the “unweighted” mammalian index; Supplementary Table C4) was selected and is from here on referred as “mammalian dominance index” (Fig. 4.3). To determine whether spatial variation in density-dependent nest survival can be explained by the predator community, we adjusted equation 4.1 by replacing the local population (P) term by the linear covariate mammalian dominance index (M) (equation 4.2).

$$\text{Logit}(N_{ij}) \sim \beta_0 + \beta_1 D_{ij} + \beta_2 M_j + \beta_3 D_{ij} M_j + \beta_4 C_j + u_i + v_j + \epsilon_{ij} \quad \text{Equation 4.2}$$

We first fitted the model (equation 4.2) on the country-wide citizen science dataset that was collected across the Netherlands and over many years. Since the dataset does not include many nests from islands with low mammalian dominance, we subsequently investigated whether the five island populations (on Islands 1-3; Fig. 4.2) fit the model results of the country-wide dataset. Bailey et al. (2017) conducted a similar research for the local population of Island 2, but in a different year than shown in Fig. 4.2. Therefore, we transformed the density metric used in Bailey et al. (2017) (Supplementary Text C2 & Table C6) and added it in the visualization of the main results (Fig. 4.4). We analysed the country-wide and island datasets separately using this two-step approach as they have large differences in the spatiotemporal sampling and barely overlapping predator communities (see Discussion). We assume nests to be spatially

independent from each other in the statistical analysis because we did not find support for spatial autocorrelation in the data (Supplementary Fig. C5).

a)

Figure 4.3: a) Overview of the spatial distribution of the mammalian dominance index used in the analysis and b) the distribution of the number of cells across the mammalian dominance index. 0 indicates that no avian predators are present, whereas at 1 only mammalian predators are present. Note that the small peak at 0 mammalian dominance index (in b) (meaning only avian predators are present) comes from the five mammalian predator free Wadden Sea islands. Coordinates are in the Dutch RD coordinate system, where one unit is 1 km.

To quantify if other meadow bird species play a role in the density-dependent nest survival (both contributing to group mobbing and predator avoidance), we used the

same model that was selected as the best fitting model for the “country-wide dataset analysis” and replaced the oystercatcher density by densities of different meadow bird compositions (oystercatcher+lapwing, oystercatcher+godwit, oystercatcher+redshank, oystercatcher+godwit+lapwing, or all four species combined). Statistical analyses were done in R (version 4.1.2) with R-package lme4.

Results

In the country-wide dataset, oystercatcher breeding density showed different effects on nest survival depending on mammalian dominance (Fig. 4.4; $\beta=-7.17$, $sd=3.07$, $p=0.02$, $n=300$; Supplementary Table C7). This indicates that, in accordance with our hypothesis (Fig. 4.1b), there is a negative effect of density on the nest survival at relatively high mammalian dominance, while the density effect is positive at relatively low mammalian dominance (Fig. 4.4).

Density-dependent nest survival also varied considerably among the more avian-predator dominated local island populations, with both the strength and the direction of the relationship varying (Fig. 4.4; Supplementary Fig. C6). Two island populations corresponded well with the predictions of the significant interaction between the mammalian dominance index and the breeding density in the country-wide dataset (Island 3 population 2; Island 2 population 2; Fig. 4.4). They match our initial prediction that density-dependent effects will be positive when there is lower mammalian dominance. Note that the habitat of Island 3 population 2 is comparable to the habitat of the country-wide dataset (being mainly agricultural areas). Three of the mammalian predator-free island populations (Island 1 and 2) did not match the expectation and did not fit the model prediction of the country-wide dataset (Fig. 4.4). Specifically, based on the avian dominated predator community on these three island populations, we would have predicted strong positive density dependence, based on the deterrence hypothesis (Fig. 4.1a), but we actually found negative density dependence for the Island 1 population 1&2 and Island 2 population 1 (Supplementary Fig. C6 & Table C7).

Including the heterospecific density of other meadow birds (black-tailed godwit, northern lapwing, and common redshank) on the oystercatcher nest survival supports the results that are found when focussing only on breeding oystercatchers ($\beta=-1.6$,

sd=0,51, p=0.002, n=300; Supplementary Table C8). Breeding density of heterospecifics shows an interaction effect with mammalian probability of presence, where nest survival of oystercatchers is lower if density of breeding meadow birds and mammalian probability of presence are both high (Supplementary Fig. C7). Especially by adding the density of godwits alone, or together with breeding lapwings, next to the oystercatcher density, improved the model fit significantly with a Δ AIC of 9 (Supplementary Table C8). Also breeding lapwings (as single heterospecific species) in the surrounding of an oystercatcher nest increased the model fit by Δ AIC of 6. Breeding common redshanks, next to breeding oystercatcher density, showed least improvement of the model with Δ AIC of 3 (Supplementary Table C8).

Discussion

We investigated how density-dependent nest survival of a mobbing bird species varies spatially and tested whether the predator community can explain the observed country-wide spatial variation in sign and strength of density dependence. Our results show—in line with our prediction—that there is no consistent positive effect of density on nest survival across populations. The relative dominance of mammalian predators explains the spatial variation in both the direction and strength of density-dependent nest survival in the country-wide dataset. Nest survival in mammalian dominated predator communities was negatively density-dependent, in line with the predator avoidance hypothesis (Fig. 4.1b), while more avian-rich predator communities exhibited positive density dependence in line with the predator deterrence hypothesis (Fig. 4.1a). However, data from local island populations without mammalian predators (relevant for this study species and aim), being mainly in saltmarsh habitat, did not fit this relationship, suggesting that the predator avoidance and deterrence hypothesis cannot explain patterns of density dependence in (most) island populations.

The general implications of our study are best illustrated by what it can teach us about population decline in our study species. The Dutch oystercatcher population (which comprises 30% of the species' European breeding population) has undergone a strong continuous decline over the past three decades (Roodbergen & Teunissen, 2019), and declining reproductive output has been implicated as a contributing

Figure 4.4: a) Model estimates of the effect of conspecific breeding density on oystercatcher nest survival (\pm SE as error bar) as a function of mammalian dominance index. Note that the mammalian dominance index (a) is the ratio of the probability of presence of mammalian and avian predators (Supplementary Fig. C8). Dashed horizontal line represents the point at which no density-dependent nest survival occurs. The solid line indicates the model fit of the interaction between the mammalian dominance index and breeding density based on the country-wide dataset only. Horizontal error bars indicate the range (standard error) of the mammalian dominance index in each population. The grey triangle (close to/above the dark green triangle) is extracted from Bailey et al. (2017) and transformed to the density metric used in this study (Supplementary Text C2 & Table C6). Island 2 population 2 represents exactly the same area as population 1, but in a different year. b) illustrates that the parameter estimates plotted in panel (a) are the slope from the relationships between daily nest survival and breeding density from the binomial model, showing here the example the different relationships at low (yellow) and high (red) mammalian dominance. To show the effect on the nest survival for the whole breeding period (27 days of incubation), we show the nest survival on the logarithmic secondary y-axis. For the visualization the slopes of each population (point in a) and its 95% confidence interval see Supplementary Fig. C6. Note that statistical analysis for the country-wide dataset (yellow, orange and red dot) was done using the continuous mammalian dominance index; the index was split in three categories only for visualization purpose here.

demographic cause (Allen et al., 2021). The concern of a nation-wide Allee effect in the Dutch oystercatcher population was not supported by our study, since we could not find any consistent positive density-dependent nest survival in our country-wide analysis. This suggests that Allee effects do not seem to be omnipresent. Thus the ongoing nationwide decline must be caused by other reasons than Allee effects and either the original drivers of decline may still be active, or new ones have appeared (Allen et al., 2021). Other potential causes may be agriculture intensification (nest destruction due to increased frequencies of agricultural activities e.g. mowing), low food availability (because of use of artificial fertilizers and pesticides; Duriez et al., 2005; Hulscher & Verhulst, 2003), human disturbance and climate change (van de Pol et al., 2014).

Our study showed that the predator community modulates the effect of density-dependent nest survival in the country-wide dataset, to such an extent that it varies between negative and positive density dependence. Thus, our study suggests that, in addition to group mobbing behaviour shaping the density dependence in this species (Bailey et al., 2017), the mechanism of predator avoidance and presence of mammalian predators likely also plays an important role (Fig. 4.1c). Visualizing the probability of presence for mammalian as well as avian predators separately (Supplementary Fig. C8) shows that the predator avoidance mechanism seems to play a larger role than the predator deterrence mechanism in explaining the pattern found when investigating the effect of the mammalian dominance index (Fig. 4.4). The predator deterrence mechanism (Fig. 4.1a) can explain our results at below-average mammalian dominance. This adds to the study from Oro et al. (2006) who investigated the predator-prey system of two gull species (predator species *Larus michahellis* and prey species *Larus audouinii*) and showed that small groups of the prey species were unable to defend their nests against a large number of the predators. In their study, fecundity was reduced at low prey density compared to high prey density. From our results we interpret that a predator avoidance mechanism acts in sites with high mammalian dominance (Fig. 4.1b), which adds to similar results by Banda & Blanco (2009). These authors found negative density-dependent nest survival due to mammalian predator attraction (foxes and rats) in red-billed choughs (*Pyrrhocorax pyrrhocorax*), resulting in lower breeding survival at high nest density. As far as we know, our study is the first investigating the

effect of a broad range of predator species (predator composition) by combining the two possible mechanisms of predator deterrence and avoidance in one study. Though such a comprehensive approach is more challenging, it may be the only relevant approach for the many species that face a broad predator community and complex predator-prey interactions.

In fact, our results tentatively suggest that it is inefficient for breeding oystercatchers to occur at high densities in agricultural breeding areas where mammalian dominance is relatively high. We also found an additional benefit from heterospecifics in terms of anti-predator behaviour. Heterospecific anti-predator benefits have been found in various species groups like reptiles (Vitousek et al., 2007), fish (Semeniuk & Dill, 2006), mammals (Lea et al., 2008) and birds (Magrath et al., 2015). Heterospecific benefits have even been suggested for other meadow birds (Møller et al., 2018), such that for each species (northern lapwing, common redshank, black-tailed godwit, dunlin and ruff), survival was higher when the density of heterospecifics was higher. When investigating the meadow bird density rather than only oystercatcher breeding density, we found the same relationships, namely a positive effect of breeding density on the nest survival at avian dominated areas and a negative effect of breeding density on nest survival at areas dominated by mammals. This indicates that in areas where it is advantageous to breed at high density (e.g. higher avian probability of presence, where mobbing is effective) it is beneficial to also have other meadow birds breeding in the surrounding. However, in areas of high mammalian predator presence, it is also disadvantageous for the oystercatcher nest survival, if other meadow birds breed close by. Our results may therefore indicate that conservation actions that aim to attract breeding meadow birds should be prioritised in regions with a relatively low ratio of mammalian compared to avian predators.

However, we note that a “low mammalian dominance” (and thus relatively high avian dominance) in our country-wide dataset has a median of 0.53, which indicates a relatively mixed probability of presence of avian and mammalian predators. Therefore, to confidently translate our results into conservation implications for island breeding oystercatchers (on saltmarshes), we would ideally analyse density and nest survival data from more years and sites, particularly in areas with low mammalian dominance. In addition, more support from other studies that focus on the effect of predator

composition on density-dependent nest survival is needed to confirm whether such a conservation prioritization strategy is suitable.

Strikingly, our results were inconsistent across the Netherlands. Lebeuf & Giroux (2014) also found mixed results in terms of density-dependent nest survival in Canada geese (*Branta canadensis maxima*), that they hypothesized was caused by having different mammalian predator species present at different study sites. We expected all the island populations with extremely low mammalian dominance to exhibit positive density-dependent nest survival based on the experimental evidence by Bailey et al. (2017). A possible reason why these local island populations do not fit the relationship of the nation-wide dataset may be extreme predation levels in the limited years of study. Ringelman et al. (2012) hypothesized that at extreme predation levels (high or low), it can be difficult to detect density-dependence.

The negative density-dependent nest survival found in some island populations (with mainly avian predators) could also be explained by a stronger effect of avian predator attraction compared to the effective mobbing strategy of the prey species. Arguably the schematic predictions in Fig. 4.1 are a simplification of the hypotheses and does not show all possible nuances of the mechanisms involved. For instance, it may be possible that some avian predators are also effective in finding high nest densities and when they would not be deterred, the strength of the negative relationship may be comparable to that of mammalian predators. Nevertheless, we assume, based on literature mentioned in the introduction, that avian predators (relevant for this study) are less efficient in finding high nest densities and at the same time are easier deterred by oystercatchers than mammalian predators (relevant for this study), as stated in the hypotheses.

Several key methodological decisions (e.g. including the choice of heterospecifics, predators and effective mobbing distance) were partly based on previous field studies done on a small spatial scale with relatively high breeding densities. We suggest that conducting experimental studies may help to make more informed methodological choices. A field experimental study that investigates the additional mobbing effect of heterospecifics on nest survival would help in deciding whether to include or exclude other meadow bird species in the analysis (Møller et al., 2018). Furthermore, we know that oystercatchers protect neighbours nesting up to 50-100m in an island population

with high densities (Bailey et al., 2017). Experimental studies would be helpful in understanding how the protective effect of mobbing varies at different breeding densities (mobbing behaviour could be density dependent), not only with artificial but also with natural nests (Major & Kendal, 1996).

Changes in the Dutch landscape have led to increasing numbers of predators over the last 40 years (Roodbergen & Teunissen, 2019) and it is known that predation levels can fluctuate among years (Teunissen et al., 2008), probably due to varying predator abundance, alternative prey species (Nolet et al., 2013) or mesopredator release (Ritchie & Johnson, 2009). For our relatively short study period (of 10 years), we do not have any evidence of extreme changes in population numbers of the avian predator species (Supplementary Fig. C3). For studies conducted on a larger temporal scale or with more fluctuations in the number of predators, it would be wise to consider predator maps that vary on temporal scale.

To conclude, the results show that there is no consistent positive effect of density on nest survival across populations. This emphasizes the risk of generalizing results from a single local population for management decisions and population modelling. Therefore, we encourage researchers across different study systems to set up studies at large spatial scale, if possible. In addition, we would like to emphasize with this study that taking into account possible density-dependent effects in relation to the whole predator community, rather than to one specific predator species, can be important in identifying causes of population regulation and decline and making appropriate conservation decisions.

Acknowledgements

We thank all the volunteers and researchers for collecting reproduction and territory mapping data of oystercatchers in the Netherlands. We thank LandschappenNL and Aad van Paassen for providing access to a large part of the reproduction data. Funding was provided by the Applied and Engineering Sciences domain of the Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO-STW; grant number 14638) as well as by Royal Netherlands Air Force, Birdlife Netherlands, NAM gas exploration and Deltares. We acknowledge the feedback provided by ecologists working at these organisations

during half-yearly meetings.

Supplementary material

Supplementary material of Chapter 4 is included as appendix C to this thesis.

CHAPTER 5

The synergistic effects of environmental drivers of declining reproduction of a threatened meadow bird across the Netherlands

Magali Frauendorf, Bruno J. Ens, Andrew M. Allen, Eelke Jongejans, Hans de Kroon, Wolf Teunissen, Christian Kampichler, Erik Kleyheeg, Jeroen Nienhuis, Kees Oosterbeek, Martijn van de Sluijs, Martin de Jong, Jan de Jong, Martijn van de Pol

Abstract

Meadow birds have declined strongly across Europe in the last few decades due to anthropogenic drivers, such as agricultural intensification, predation and climate change. Some studies investigated already potential effects of single threats, whereas the impacting drivers and their strength may depend on the exact study system. However, it is likely that different threats interact and understanding potential synergistic effects can improve our understanding of the ongoing population decline and help identify appropriate management actions. We combined reproduction data on clutch and hatchling survival of Eurasian oystercatchers (*Haematopus ostralegus*) with environmental data (distribution maps from predator species, weather, food abundance and land use intensity) on a national scale spanning a period of two decades (2000-2021). We identified the relative impact of these environmental factors on the reproductive success and investigated their potential interacting effects. Average clutch survival was 44%, average chick survival 10%, and overall average reproductive success was 0.1 fledglings/pair, which is well below what is needed for a stable population. Reproductive success was highest in areas and years (i) with fewer predator abundances (buzzard, fox, beech marten for clutch survival, and crow and stoat for hatchling survival), (ii) with higher (for clutch survival) and optimal rainfall (for hatchling survival) and (iii) with lower earthworm abundance (for hatchling survival). We also show that in less favourable habitat (with higher land use intensity), clutches were more vulnerable to predation by buzzards, indicated by an interactive effect. In addition, predation risk by stoats was higher when earthworm abundance was high, suggesting that a reduction in an alternative food source (rabbits) may increase predation risk on oystercatcher nests. This study shows that it is important to investigate the clutch and chick stages separately, because environmental drivers impact those stages in a different way. We emphasize the importance to focus on improving the survival of hatchlings, rather than the clutch survival, to increase the overall reproductive success. In addition, we suggest to also consider the effect of population dynamics of alternative prey species of the predators. Based on our conclusions, we provide three management recommendations: (i) predator-exclusion with fences, (ii) mice pyramids to provide alternative food source for predatory species and (iii) reducing the homogenous landscape by lower land use intensity.

Introduction

Understanding how anthropogenic impacts affect population dynamics is crucial to be able to explain why species are threatened, and also to be able to turn the tide (Cardillo et al., 2005). Population dynamics (e.g. changes in abundance over time) are a function of three fundamental demographic parameters: reproduction, survival and dispersal (Rothschild et al., 1997; Townsend et al., 2008). As management actions, to conserve a species, have to influence one or more of these three parameters, estimation of these parameters and how they are linked to environmental variables are of high importance (Nichols et al., 2004). However, conservation actions that only target single-threat drivers have the risk of being inadequate due to potential cascading effects caused by unmanaged synergies (Brook et al., 2008). Synergistic processes are defined as various perturbations that interact positively to increase the extinction risk of a species (Brook et al., 2008). For example, habitat loss might increase the vulnerability of some species to global warming by further stressing their physiological tolerance and making range shifts impossible (Brook et al., 2008). Especially specialized species are at greater risk to experience negative synergistic effects threatening its extinction (Davies et al., 2004).

Birds associated with grasslands and agricultural habitats are one of the most threatened groups of bird species across Europe (BirdLife International, 2021). Low breeding success seems to contribute most to the decline in meadow bird species (Roodbergen et al., 2012). The main reported causes for the decline in breeding success of meadow birds are intensification of the agricultural activities, climate change and high predation rates (van de Pol et al., 2014). Intensively used agricultural areas are often associated with early mowing regimes that may destroy clutches or chicks with machines or with trampling by livestock (Beintema & Muskens, 1987; Franks et al., 2018; Kentie et al., 2013; Schekkerman & Beintema, 2007). Agricultural intensification may also lead to lower groundwater levels and raising water levels may improve soil conditions, consequently resulting in higher food availability (e.g. arthropods, Lumbricidae) (Felici et al., 2019; Martay & Pearce-Higgins, 2020; Onrust et al., 2019; Schekkerman & Beintema, 2007; Seibold et al., 2019). Climate change may lead to more frequent droughts in some inland areas (Philip et al., 2020), which may also cause lower groundwater levels and therefore lower food availability (Onrust et al., 2019; Sarychev

& Mischenko, 2014). Many predator populations are increasing and predation is one of the most reported threats to egg and chick survival (Plard et al., 2019; Seymour et al., 2003; Zielonka et al., 2019).

However, it is likely that several threats interact with each other (Evans, 2004). Agricultural intensification leads to more homogenous landscapes (Benton et al., 2003; Foley et al., 2005) in which clutches may be easier to locate and chicks are unable to hide from predators (Roos et al., 2018; Schekkerman et al., 2009). Kentie et al. (2015) suggest that nests of black-tailed godwits (*Limosa limosa*) become more vulnerable to predation when land use intensity increases. In addition, it seems that agri-environmental schemes (the funding of farmers and land managers to farm in a way that supports biodiversity, enhances the landscape, and improves the quality of water, air and soil) are not working when ground water level is low and predation rates are high (Roodbergen & Teunissen, 2014). When food shortage leads to longer parental foraging trips, parents may spend less time guarding the nest, increasing the risk of clutch predation (Evans, 2004). Poor condition of the parents due to low food availability may also reduce the level of clutch and chick defence against predators (Evans, 2004). Furthermore, climate change has shifted agricultural activities to occur earlier in the season, resulting in a higher proportion of black-tailed godwit clutches and chicks being exposed to such activities (Kleijn et al., 2010). Higher spring temperatures enhance grass growth, which means that farmers can start mowing earlier and more frequently which decreases clutch survival (Kentie et al., 2018). Agricultural advancement also reduces the amount of foraging habitat available when chicks hatch and lowers the quality (taller and denser) of vegetation in the remaining foraging area.

Besides the fact that potential interactive effects have been suggested but rarely quantified, several studies highlight the importance of large spatial scale investigations (Felici et al., 2019; Franks et al., 2018; Roodbergen et al., 2012). For instance, Czarniecka-Wiera et al. (2020) suggest that effective grassland management should be planned on a larger spatial context, because focussing on the management of a single site did not turn out to be successful. In addition, population decline may be caused by different abiotic and biotic factors, varying spatially and temporally and acting synergistically in a context-dependent way (Blaustein & Kiesecker, 2002). This may

result in different populations of the same species reacting in different ways to the same environmental drivers (Frauendorf et al., 2022). Thus, generalization about reasons for population decline should take into account the context-dependent dynamics of ecological systems, hence being based on a large spatial scale rather than on a single or few populations (Blaustein & Kiesecker, 2002). Notwithstanding, large scale investigations of the importance of environmental drivers are rare due to the challenges in collecting demographic data on such scale.

In addition, still little is known about the drivers of the variation in chick survival because chicks are often much more difficult to monitor (Franks et al., 2018). Plard et al. (2019) also emphasizes the relevance of studying both the clutch and hatchling survival separately since different threats may vary across the stages. For example, the implemented protection of lapwing nests had a positive effect on the nest success, but did not improve the chick survival, so that the population growth remained insufficient (Plard et al., 2019).

The Eurasian oystercatcher (*Haematopus ostralegus*) is historically a shorebird breeding on saltmarshes and in dunes. However, nowadays they breed predominantly (as a meadow bird) in agricultural areas, though urban areas are become increasingly important (Ens & Underhill, 2014) and part of the population still breeds in coastal areas (Ens et al., 2011; Goss-Custard et al., 1996). Among the group of meadow bird species, it is showing the steepest declines in the Netherlands, with a 70% decline of the breeding population since 1990 (Netwerk Ecologische Monitoring, Sovon, provincies & CBS, 2021).

In different breeding habitats, birds are exposed to different threats. For instance, on coastal breeding ground, nesting birds experience clutch flooding due to an increase in sea level rise or more frequent storm events (Bailey et al., 2019). In urban areas they mainly breed on roofs, which may reduce predation risk from mammals (Ens & Underhill, 2014). Whereas there has been a lot of research on threats of the coastal breeding population (van de Pol et al., 2010, 2014), it remains unclear which factors are driving the temporal and spatial variation in reproductive success in inland agricultural breeding areas, the habitat where 75% of the Dutch population breeds (Ens et al., 2011).

We address these different knowledge gaps simultaneously by studying the relative

impact of different potential environmental drivers on the reproductive success of the Eurasian oystercatcher on a large scale (the Netherlands) spanning a period of two decades (2000–2021). We investigate which environmental drivers (predator and food abundance, weather and land use intensity) explain spatiotemporal variation in (1) clutch survival, (2) hatchling survival and (3) fledgling production, while specifically focussing on the interactive effects of those variables.

Method

Data collection

Data on reproduction

Data on reproduction were collected according to standardized monitoring schemes by professionals and citizen scientists throughout the Netherlands during the period 2000–2021 (Supplementary Fig. D1). Coordinates were recorded from each nest location, which were revisited several times to record the fate of the eggs and chicks. The clutch size was recorded, as well as the clutch number (first clutch or replacement clutch). From these data we could calculate (1) daily clutch survival probability, (2) chick survival probability, and (3) reproductive output of a nest. Clutch survival was calculated from daily survival rate estimates (Aebischer, 1999; Mayfield, 1975) to account for differences in exposure time among nests. By taking the average daily clutch survival to the power of 29 (egg laying period + incubation period; Hötter, 2010), we calculated clutch survival for the whole egg-phase period. We assume that the birds lay one egg per day with an average clutch size of 3 and have an incubation period of 27 days, whereby they start directly with incubation after having laid the last egg. Chick survival was estimated as the proportion of hatchlings that reached fledging age. The reproductive output was defined as the number of fledglings produced per breeding pair per year.

Timing of first egg-laying ('lay date') is known to be an important determinant of the reproductive success in oystercatchers (Allen et al., 2021; Ens et al., 1996). Lay date was determined mainly by three different methods: (1) Egg measurements (length, weight and width) measured to the nearest 0.1 mm with a dial calliper or to the nearest

0.1 g with a balance, giving an accuracy of ± 1 -2 days (Jager et al., 2000; Strijkstra, 1986). (2) Back-calculation by using the hatch date or the age of the chicks, when the nest was visited while hatching, recorded on camera traps or when the chicks are caught for ringing. (3) Using the combination of data on nest visits and the breeding period. If the exposure time of the nest (date that nest is last active minus the find date) is close to the 29 days of breeding period, the lay date can be calculated with high accuracy. We only included lay date data with a bias up to 3 days in the analysis. For 13% of the nests, the lay date was determined with method 1, for 45% of the nests it was determined with method 2 and the lay date of the remaining 42% of the nests was determined with method 3.

Data on environmental variables

Environmental variables included in the analysis comprise habitat, weather, food abundance, predator probabilities of presence, land use intensity (and clutch protection measures) and the distance to the intertidal flats (coast). The variables vary mainly on spatial scale, whereas only the weather variables and nest protection vary on spatial and temporal scale (Table 5.1). We assume that high land use intensity combines different aspects like early mowing dates and low ground water levels and therefore only included the variable 'land use intensity' (Kentie et al., 2018).

Habitat

Habitat was classified based on three different sources of open access data sets: (1) data on habitat type from CBS Statistics Netherlands (CBS, 2021), (2) data from Netherlands Enterprise Agency on the land use on agricultural fields (e.g. arable land with crop type, temporary grassland) (Rijksoverheid, 2021), and (3) data on saltmarsh areas from the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management (Rijkswaterstaat, 2021). CBS data were available for 2000, 2003, 2006, 2008, 2010, 2012, 2015 and helped us to distinguish between agricultural, urban areas and natural areas (nature reserves). For the land use type on agriculture fields, data were available yearly from 2009-2018 and 2021. With the land use data, we made a sub-category of the agricultural land and subdivided it in (a) temporary grasslands, (b) permanent

grasslands, (c) arable land and (d) natural grassland. The Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management documented the coastal habitat types (saltmarsh, dunes) every six years from 2000-2018. We used for each of the three sources the last known habitat type (prior to the monitoring year). The combination of these three sources allowed distinction between seven habitat types relevant for breeding oystercatchers: natural coastal and non-coastal breeding habitats, being (1) saltmarshes or (2) dry natural areas (e.g. dunes) at the coast and (3) non-coastal natural grasslands (inland), whilst agricultural breeding habitats, distinguished between (4) arable land, (5) temporary- and (6) permanent grasslands, and finally (7) urban breeding habitat. Temporary grassland are areas that were only cultivated for less than 4-5 years in a row and then ploughed and seeded with grass or an arable crop. Permanent grasslands are fields which are always grasslands (no arable land) and are only allowed to be sowed less frequently than once in five years. Permanent and temporary grasslands have no management restrictions (e.g. late mowing, fertilization). Natural grasslands are extensively used grasslands with relative late mowing dates and restrictions in the amount of used fertilizers. Farmers get subsidies for those restrictions. For an overview of the distribution of habitat per year and reproductive parameter see Supplementary Fig. D2.

Weather

Data on precipitation shortage/surplus were available from the Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (KNMI, 2020a). Daily precipitation (mm) and potential evapotranspiration (mm) was extracted from the nearest (of the in total 30) weather stations (mean (sd)=14.2 km (6.7)). Subtracting the estimated evaporation from the precipitation results in a value x indicating precipitation shortage for $x < 0$ and precipitation surplus for $x > 0$. We calculated the precipitation shortage/surplus (mm/month) for each habitat and breeding stage based on average lay date information because clutch stage and hatchling stage take place during different months in the breeding season and lay date differs between habitat types (Supplementary Fig. D3). For instance, birds breeding along the coast and depending on coastal food supplies breed considerably later than inland breeding birds (Supplementary Fig. D4). This resulted in different time periods depending on habitat

type and stage: (1) clutch stage in coastal habitat: 18th May-17th June, (2) clutch stage in agricultural and urban habitat: 29th April-29th May, (3) chick stage in coastal habitat 17th June-17th July, (4) chick stage in agricultural and urban habitat: 29th May-28th June (Supplementary Fig. D3). For each individual nest, we calculated the precipitation shortage for the relevant time period (depending on habitat type and stage) for the year of monitoring. Precipitation can vary spatially as well as temporally. Within-year (temporally) variation was higher in the data set of hatchling survival (78%) than in the dataset for the clutch survival (48%) (Supplementary Fig. D5).

Food abundance

We used data on earthworm abundance in the Netherlands published in Rutgers et al. (2016) with a resolution of 100x100 m. Since oystercatchers use the area around their clutch to forage, we calculated the mean abundance of earthworms (numbers/m²) for a radius of 170 m around the nest location. This radius is based on data from 18 inland breeding oystercatcher that were tagged with a GPS (with an accelerometer) that provided information on the behaviour of the birds (Supplementary Text D1).

Probability of predator presence

We used species distribution modelling to estimate the probability of presence for each potential predator species (Teunissen et al., 2020). Mammal predator probability of presence were estimated using presence-absence data for a 10-year period (2009-2018) from the Dutch National Database on Flora and Fauna (www.ndff.nl). Avian predator probability of presence were estimated using nationwide avian presence-absence data from the Sovon Bird Atlas project (Sovon Vogelonderzoek Nederland, 2018) for a 3-year period only (2013-2015), but localized annual survey counts reveal little inter-annual variation for the whole study period (2000-2021; Supplementary Fig. D6-D7) for the predator species used in this study. Note that the multiple years of data were pooled to one single static distribution model per species. Within the R-package SDMaps (Kampichler et al., 2020) distribution maps were conducted with Random forest models (Boulesteix et al., 2012) to link the presence data (of the species) to environmental (landscape) variables. This resulted in a probability of presence (ranging

from 0 to 1) for each predator species for each 1x1 km grid cell nationwide. For a detailed description of the method see Frauendorf et al. (2022). These predator maps can be used to give an indication of the probability of presence for each predator species.

At breeding sites on saltmarshes on the Dutch Wadden Sea islands, mainly avian predators like gull species (Laridae) and western marsh harriers (*Circus aeruginosus*) are present (Verboven et al. 2001) next to European hedgehogs (*Erinaceus europaeus*) as potential mammalian egg predators (Teunissen et al., 2008). In inland breeding areas, in addition to avian predators like gulls, crows (Corvidae) and common buzzards (*Buteo buteo*), oystercatchers also have to deal with mammalian predators like the red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*), stoat (*Mustela ermine*), beech marten (*Martes foina*) and European polecat (*Mustela putorius*) (Mason et al., 2018; Teunissen et al., 2008), which do not occur on island sites, except for stoat being present on the island of Texel (Table 5.1). Furthermore, potential additional chick predators may be grey heron (*Ardea cinerea*) and white stork (*Ciconia ciconia*) (Teunissen et al. 2008).

Gull species are colony birds and have large foraging areas compared to the other predator species, and we accounted for their larger space use by taking the mean probability of presence of a 3 km-radius buffer around the nest location (Rock et al., 2016), whereas we used a 1 km-radius for all other predator species. Brown rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) are a potential predator for meadow bird clutches and chicks, however, recorded cases are small (up to 3%; Frauendorf et al., 2022; Teunissen et al., 2008). We had to exclude the brown rat from the analysis, because there were too little field data to produce reliable species distribution maps. Also domestic cats (*Felis catus*), and especially free-roaming cats, can cause substantial mortality in wildlife (Loss et al., 2013). However, data on registered pet cats, to get an idea of the density, are not accessible because of the privacy law. In addition, a large proportion, and those causing the highest proportion of mortality, are un-owned cats, that are not registered. So far, data are not available to create distribution maps for domestic cats.

Land use intensity & nest protection measures

Based on satellite images, the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) was calculated giving an indication of the green biomass (value between 0 and 1). With the

NDVI values, we estimated the mean vegetation growth curve for all land use types (e.g. temporary grassland, permanent grassland, arable field) and determined the more intensive (above average grow curve) or extensive (below average grow curve) agricultural areas, resulting in a continuous land use intensity index.

In agricultural breeding habitats, volunteers protect clutches by placing for instance poles to inform farmers about nest locations and protect the nests from being destroyed by machines. We distinguished if nest protection took place (1) or not (0), in agricultural habitat (Supplementary Table D1).

Distance to the coast

Distance to the mudflats is a crucial indicator for the distribution of breeding oystercatchers (Kampichler et al., 2013). For wintering oystercatchers, grasslands are traditionally considered as less profitable and a refuge feeding habitat for weaker individuals (Durell et al., 2001a). Consequently, there may also be an effect on breeding oystercatchers. Birds that breed close to the coast have the possibility to forage at the coast or on grasslands, and may therefore adapt more easily to changing conditions, for example, if drought causes food shortages on grasslands, then birds nesting close to the coast can still feed on the mudflats.

Statistical analysis

We first ran generalized linear mixed models with three different response variables (1) daily clutch survival (n=17800 nests), (2) hatchling survival (n=1933 nests) and (3) the number of fledglings (n=5227) with the R-package lme4 (Bates et al., 2015). We used the cbind function for the response variables (daily clutch survival and hatchling survival) and a binomial distribution with a logit-link function. For the model with the 'number of fledglings' as response variable, we used a Poisson distribution and logarithm link-function, after having tested for zero-inflation in the data with the DHARMA R-package (Hartig, 2021). The aim of these analysis was to visualize the spatial (habitat-related) and temporal (annual) variation for the overall reproductive output and per stage (clutches and hatchlings separately).

Next, we ran the two models on clutch survival (n=17447 nests) and hatching

survival ($n=1890$ nests) by adding the fixed effects. Habitat and year were still included as crossed random effects in both models to account for higher dependence between nests within a year and habitat type. Note that the sample sizes for the clutch and hatchling survival model are lower when the fixed effects are included, because some data were not available in the fixed effects and those rows were therefore removed from the analysis.

Lay date (selected for nests with only first clutch) was included as a fixed factor in the model because we expected it to explain variation in nest and chick survival and we wanted to account for its potential effect. We standardized lay date per year and habitat by subtracting the mean lay date per habitat and year from the individual lay date and dividing it by the overall standard deviation (across habitat and year). Standardizing lay date makes it comparable across different habitats. In addition, since we found an advancement of lay date in agricultural habitat over time (Supplementary Fig. D8), we also standardized the lay date by year.

In the long-term study populations (conducted on the coastal breeding grounds by researchers) nests were generally more intensively monitored. Consequently, nests were potentially found before the parents had started incubating. Nest loss during egg laying is higher than after the incubation has started (Ens, 1991; Verboven et al., 2001). In total, 4% of all nests were found before clutch completion. Excluding those nests resulted in similar relationships and model results compared to including those nests (Supplementary Table D2). Hence we decided to include those nests in the final analysis.

To avoid overparameterization of the model, we identified in a first step which predators were of importance (showing a significant effect) in explaining variation in nest and chick survival by running a model selection (with the dredge function and model averaging with the R-package MuMin; Bartoń, 2020).

Potential explanatory variables showing a high Pearson correlation between each other ($p>0.7$) were not included in the analysis process. In the clutch survival data set, herring gull was strongly correlated with the lesser black-backed gull ($p=0.96$; Supplementary Fig. D9) and the marsh harrier ($p=0.77$; Supplementary Fig. D9). Correlation between the lesser black-backed gull and marsh harrier was 0.79 (Supplementary Fig. D9). Therefore, we ran the predator selection model procedure

separately with either the herring gull, the marsh harrier or the lesser black-backed gull. All three models resulted in the same significant predators. In the hatchling data set, we found strong correlations between herring gull, lesser black-backed gull, buzzard and marsh harrier, ranging from 0.75 to 0.96 (in absolute values; Supplementary Fig. D10). We therefore ran again four predator selection models with all four predator species at a time. All four models showed again the same significant predator species that were included in the final model.

Next, we ran the full clutch survival model with the pre-selected predator species (common buzzard, marsh harrier, beech marten, red fox) from the model selection approach, lay date, land use intensity, food abundance, precipitation shortage, nest protection and distance to the coast (Table 5.1). In the hatchling survival model, we included the pre-selected predator species (carrion crow, white stork, stoat) from the model selection approach, lay date, land use intensity, food abundance, precipitation shortage and distance to the coast (Table 5.1). In both models we added an interaction effect between land use intensity and each predator species as well as between earthworm abundance and each predator species. Because we expected potential non-linear effects for lay date and precipitation, we compared the different combinations of the models with a squared term of lay date and precipitation and without a squared term. The best fitting model was selected that showed the lowest Akaike Information Criterion (AIC; Burnham & Anderson, 1998; Supplementary Table D3).

All explanatory variables were standardized (mean=0, sd=1) before analysis to enable the investigation of the standardized effect size (as an indication for the relative impact) of the variables on clutch and hatchling survival.

Not all explanatory variables are relevant for each habitat type. For instance, foxes are not expected to be main predators for urban roof breeding oystercatchers; land use intensity is only relevant in agricultural habitat and also earthworm abundance is expected to be hardly important for oystercatchers in coastal breeding habitat (e.g. saltmarshes) given that they can forage on intertidal flats. We used dummy variables for those specific cases, giving a 0 if the variable was of importance in that specific habitat/situation and a 1 if it was not. The dummy variable was then included as an interaction effect in the model with the variable of interest. Therefore, we were able to include all data and to compare the relative impact of all the different environmental

drivers even though they are acting in different habitat types.

All statistical analyses were done in R (version 4.1.2; R Core Team, 2019).

Table 5.1: Overview of the variables included in the two models (clutch and hatchling survival model) showing the habitat type where they are expected to play an important role, on which scale (spatial/temporal) and the period that the variable covers. Coastal breeding habitat indicates saltmarshes and dry natural areas; agricultural habitats indicate grasslands and arable land. Bold 'X' indicates the variables that were included in the full model (after the predator selection process).

Variable	Details on variable	Clutch survival	Hatchling survival	Habitat type	Scale	Period of data
Avian predators	Common buzzard	X	X	All habitats	Spatial	Average of the period 2013-2015
	Western marsh harrier	X	X			
	Carrion crow	X	X			
	Herring gull	X	X			
	Lesser black-backed gull	X	X			
	White stork		X			
	Grey heron		X			
Mammalian predators	Stoat ¹	X	X	Agricultural habitat and coastal breeding habitat	Spatial	Average of the period 2009-2018
	European hedgehog	X				
	Red fox ²	X	X			
	European polecat ²	X	X			
	Beech marten ²	X	X	All habitats		
Weather		X	X	All habitats	Spatial & temporal	Yearly (2000-2021)
Earthworm abundance		X	X	Urban and agricultural habitat	Spatial	Average of the period 1997-2011

Table 5.1: Continued.

Variable	Details on variable	Clutch survival	Hatchling survival	Habitat type	Scale	Period of data
Land use intensity		X	X	Agricultural habitat	Spatial	2013
Clutch protection		X		Agricultural habitat	Spatial & temporal	Yearly (2000-2021)
Distance to the coast ²		X	X	All habitats	Spatial	Yearly (2000-2021)

¹ Only occurring on the island of Texel and the mainland (Frauendorf et al., 2022).

² Only occurring/relevant on/for the mainland.

Results

Year -and habitat-related variation in reproductive performance

Oystercatcher pairs produced an average 0.11 fledglings per year for the whole study period (2000 – 2021) which is well below the number of fledglings needed for a stable population (blue line in Fig. 5.1e,f). Average daily clutch survival was 97% giving a clutch survival of 44%. On average, only 10% of chicks survived from hatching to fledging (Fig. 5.1). Variation in clutch survival was of similar magnitude across habitats and among years (Fig. 5.1a,b). However, variation in hatchling survival (Fig. 5.1d) and fledgling production (Fig. 5.1f) was higher across years compared to the spatial variation across habitats (Fig. 5.1c,e). Overall, the temporal and spatial variation in fledgling production and in hatchling survival appears to be very similar (Fig. 5.1c vs. 5.1e & 5.1d vs. 5.1f).

Clutches located in temporary grasslands had the highest survival (Fig. 5.1a), whereas hatchlings survived best in urban areas (Fig. 5.1c). Clutch survival was lowest in coastal and inland natural breeding habitats (saltmarshes, dry natural areas and natural grasslands; Fig. 5.1a), whereas hatchling survival was relatively higher (but still low in absolute terms) in these same areas compared to other breeding habitats (e.g. agricultural areas; Fig. 5.1c). In contrast, nests in agricultural habitats had high clutch survival and relatively low hatchling survival (Fig. 5.1a,c). Also the interannual variation in clutch and hatchling survival did not exhibit similar patterns (Fig. 5.1b,d), suggesting

Figure 5.1: Spatial (a,c,e) and temporal (b,d,f) variation of reproduction of Eurasian oystercatchers in the Netherlands. (a,b) show the clutch survival, (c,d) visualize the hatchling survival and (e,f) show the reproductive output (number of fledglings per pair per year). Dots with error bars show the mean and standard error per habitat type (a,c,e) or year (b,d,f). The horizontal dashed grey line visualizes the mean for the whole study period. Colours in the habitat type visualize the four categories: yellow – coastal breeding habitat, green – grasslands, brown – arable land, grey – urban habitat. The models were run with a binomial or Poisson distribution. To correctly visualize the standard errors of the model output, we show the y-axes on a logarithmic scale. Note that the reproductive output panels (e,f) are not the product of panel a-d. The models are run on a different subset of the data (see method section for more detail). Clutch survival covers the survival probability of the clutch over the whole breeding period of 29 days (egg laying + incubation). Horizontal blue solid lines (e,f) show the threshold of fledgling production for a stable population from Allen et al. (2021).

that different threats play a role in each stage. Fledgling production was highest in urban breeding habitat (Fig. 5.1e), slightly above average in arable land and temporary grasslands, but below average in saltmarsh breeding habitat.

Predictors of clutch survival

Clutches had a higher survival when there were fewer buzzards, foxes and beech martens. The effect of beech martens was particularly strong, as suggested by the standardized coefficients (Fig. 5.2a,c-e). In addition, clutches survived better with a higher precipitation surplus (precipitation relative to evapotranspiration) (Fig. 5.2a-b). Moreover, the effect of buzzard on clutch survival mainly existed in areas where land use intensity was high, as shown by the significant statistical interaction between buzzard probability of presence and land use intensity (Fig. 5.2f).

Lay date was included in the model, but we did not visualize the relative impact of lay date on clutch survival in Fig. 5.2a, because we aim to focus here on the environmental drivers rather than on the effect of individual quality. Nevertheless, it is important to account for the effect of lay date on clutch survival which indicate that clutch survival was higher if birds lay earlier in the season ($\beta=-0.5$, $se= 0.04$; Supplementary Fig. D11).

Predictors of hatchling survival

Chicks had lower survival when the presence of probability of stoat and crows was higher (Fig. 5.3a,c,e). Contrary to expectation, higher earthworm abundances resulted in lower chick survival (Fig. 5.3d). In addition, chick survival was highest at average levels of precipitation (relative to evapotranspiration), as chick survival increased until a precipitation shortage of ~ 30 mm/month was reached, but a further increase in precipitation towards a precipitation surplus decreased the chick survival (indicated by positive values in Fig. 5.3b). The negative effect of stoat presence on chick survival, was especially present when earthworm abundance was high (Fig. 5.3f). Hatchlings had a higher survival if parents started laying earlier ($\beta=-0.39$, $se= 0.1$; Supplementary Fig. D12), and this effect was included in the same model.

Figure 5.2: Clutch survival model results with (a) giving an overview of the relative impact of the variables included in the model, ordered from strongest negative effect to strongest positive effect. Dots and bars indicate the standardized coefficients with its 95% confidence interval. Variables overlapping with 0 are not significant. Significant variables ($p < 0.05$) are, in addition, indicated by the asterisk above standardized coefficient and the bold variable name. Subscript 'S' and 'ST' indicate that the variable varies on spatial scale and spatial-temporal scale, respectively. Remaining panels (b – f) visualize the fitted line with its 95% confidence interval (shaded area) of the significant variables. The dots represent the effect of binned raw data points (where the size of the dots is proportional to its sample size). Low and high in the legend of the interaction effects (f) represent -2 and +2 standard deviation from the mean, respectively. Although we statistically analysed environmental impacts on daily clutch survival, we plot what this means for the clutch survival covering the whole breeding period of 29 days (egg laying + incubation), as this is more intuitive to interpret (and this is why the y-axes are visualized on a logarithmic scale). Note that in panel (b) a value of 0 indicates precipitation being equal to evapotranspiration, a value < 0 indicates precipitation shortage and a value > 0 indicates precipitation surplus.

Figure 5.3: Chick survival model results with (a) giving an overview of the relative impact of the variables included in the model, ordered from strongest negative effect to strongest positive effect. Black dots and bars indicate the standardized coefficients with its 95% confidence interval of the linear variable term, whereas the grey dot and bar indicates the effect of the non-linear term of precipitation. Variables overlapping with 0 are not significant. Significant variables ($p < 0.05$) are, in addition, indicated by the asterisk above standardized coefficient and the bold variable name. Subscript 'S' and 'ST' indicate that the variable varies on spatial scale and spatial-temporal scale, respectively. Remaining panels (b - f) visualize the fitted line with its 95% confidence interval (shaded area) of the significant variables only. Dots represent the effect of the binned raw data points (where the size of the dots is proportional to its sample size). Low and high in the legend of (f) represent -2 and +2 standard deviation from the mean, respectively. Note that in panel (b) a value of 0 indicates precipitation being equal to evapotranspiration, a value < 0 indicates precipitation shortage and a value > 0 indicates precipitation surplus.

Discussion

With this study we aimed to investigate which environmental drivers (predator and food abundance, weather and land use intensity) explain the spatiotemporal variation in (1) clutch survival, (2) hatchling survival and (3) reproductive output, while specifically focussing on the interactive effects of environmental variables.

Average clutch survival is 44%, average chick survival 10%, and overall average reproductive output was 0.1 fledglings per pair per year. Clutch survival was highest in agricultural areas (especially temporary grasslands) and lowest in natural inland and coastal areas. In contrast, hatchlings showed above average survival in urban areas, average survival in coastal breeding habitats and lowest survival in agricultural areas (grasslands and arable fields).

Beech marten, buzzard and fox probability of presence negatively affected clutch survival, whereas higher precipitation (relative to evapotranspiration) increased clutch survival. The negative effect of buzzard presence was stronger at high land use intensity, compared to low land use intensity.

Hatchlings had higher survival when the probability of stoat and crow presence was lower and with lower earthworm abundance. In years of drought (below average precipitation relative to evapotranspiration), hatchling survival was lower. However, also high precipitation surplus reduced the hatchling survival. The negative effect of stoat presence on hatchling survival was specifically present when earthworm abundance was high, which was indicated by an interaction effect between earthworm abundance and stoat presence.

In this section, we start with a discussion what the reproductive output means for the oystercatcher population in the Netherlands. Then, we discuss the effect of the different environmental variables and the synergistic effects. We finalize this discussion with some recommendations for management implications to increase the reproductive output of oystercatchers in the Netherlands.

Reproductive output compared to what is needed for viable populations

The overall reproductive success (0.11 fledglings) appears to be much too low to sustain a stable Dutch oystercatcher population. Van de Pol et al. (2010) reported a threshold

of 0.35 fledglings per pair per year for a well-studied coastal population, and more recent population dynamical calculations even show a higher threshold of 0.40 (Allen et al., 2021). Only urban breeding birds seem to reach the most recent calculated threshold (Fig. 5.1e) and only in the year 2020 did the nationwide reproductive output come close to the threshold for a stable population (Fig. 5.1f).

The average clutch survival that we found in this study (44%) is close to what has been reported in literature for a shorter time period (47% for 1996-2006; Roodbergen et al., 2012). The reported clutch survival before 1980 has been documented to be only 36% (Roodbergen et al., 2012). Similarly, clutch survival reported from the UK before 1980 was below 40% (Briggs, 1984). Other studies reported large variation in clutch survival. According to Goss-Custard et al. (1996), the clutch survival varied between 35% and 95% between 1930 and 1980. Nevertheless, the comparison with clutch survival estimates from the literature does not seem to suggest that the nationwide low reproductive output in the Netherlands is caused by poor egg survival.

By contrast, we found a very low hatchling survival (10%) compared to literature data. Hatchling survival was 49% before 1980 across Europe (Roodbergen et al., 2012) and 18% in coastal areas in the Netherlands 1984-2010 (Roodbergen & Teunissen, 2019). This comparison strongly suggests that the chick stage may be the demographic bottleneck in the Netherlands over past two decades.

Predictors of clutch and hatchling survival: single variable effects

Habitat and year effect

The results of this study emphasize that habitats impact the clutch and hatchling survival differently, because the two stages do not show similar patterns (Fig. 5.1). Similarly, also the patterns of the temporal variation in clutch and hatchling survival differ. Therefore, to successfully increase the reproductive success, management implications should be applied to specific stages. We would have expected higher clutch survival in urban areas; however, the overall high reproductive success in urban areas seems to be a result of the high hatchling survival compared to the other habitats. In urban areas, oystercatchers mainly nest on flat roofs (Ens & Underhill, 2014). Even though mammalian predator species may cause fewer clutch losses for roof breeding

oystercatchers compared to oystercatchers breeding in agricultural areas, avian predators can still pose a risk and seem to play an important role for roof breeding oystercatchers. Teunissen et al. (2008) found a higher chance of clutch predation by mammalian predators than by avian predators in agricultural breeding habitats for northern lapwings (*Vanellus vanellus*) and black-tailed godwits (*Limosa limosa*). However, this may not be the case in urban areas.

Intensely used agricultural areas (grasslands used for regular mowing or for livestock and arable land) show relatively high clutch survival compared to natural and urban breeding grounds. Oystercatcher generally start nesting in open and low vegetation where they have a good overview for approaching predators (Ens & Underhill, 2014). This may result in higher clutch survival on agricultural fields. Grasslands with regular management (no delayed mowing) or those used by livestock in general have lower vegetation height than for instance 'natural grasslands' (with delayed mowing), where at least mammalian predators can approach without being seen on time.

Agricultural habitats may function as an ecological trap. Possibly, oystercatchers prefer starting breeding in those open areas, which results in higher clutch survival. However, once the eggs hatch, the survival of the chicks is below average (Fig. 5.1c). This may be caused by overall higher vegetation (e.g. maize fields) at the period of chick growth, in which oystercatcher parents have a poor overview of the surrounding area and therefore do worse in anticipating to approaching predators.

Predator probability of presence

Carrion crow, which is often accused for being a key egg predator did not turn out important in our analysis, which echoes studies on lapwing and godwit nests (Teunissen et al., 2008). Instead, carrion crow and stoat were the most important predator species influencing the hatchling survival. Mustelids like stoats have been reported as an important chick predator in especially agricultural habitat in godwits as well (Schekkerman et al., 2009; Teunissen et al., 2008).

It is likely that annual variation in predator abundance may explain some of the additional temporal variation we observe in Fig. 5.1, but only 'static' distribution models (pooled over all years; 2009-2018) could be used in our study due to data

limitations. For future research, it would be advisable to develop a well-designed monitoring scheme to collect useful data on mammal presence on a large spatial and temporal scale that can be used in distribution models.

Food abundance

Against expectations, higher earthworm abundance led to lower hatchling survival. We expected that higher earthworm abundance as important food source for inland breeding oystercatchers would increase hatchling survival. It is possible that areas of higher food abundance attract more oystercatchers so that they nest at higher density and need to share the available food among more individuals. Earthworm abundance did not vary strongly across habitats (e.g. being lower in urban habitat; Supplementary Fig. D13) so that it does not explain the negative relationship of earthworm abundance with hatchling survival. However, there may also be an effect of competition for food (earthworms) with other species. Especially in urban areas, where we found a high hatchling survival, robins (*Erithacus rubecula*) and blackbirds (*Turdus merula*), that also rely on earthworms, are more common than in agricultural areas (Martay & Pearce-Higgins, 2020). Since oystercatchers need to share available earthworm abundance with songbird species, less food is available per individual, resulting in lower hatchling survival. At the same time, that would mean that there is another important (still unknown) driver in urban areas that may explain the high hatchling survival.

In addition, it is known that earthworm abundance changes throughout the season with a peak in abundance in March/April and lower abundance in May/June (Briggs, 1984), when the chicks grow up. From observational studies, we also know that chicks are often fed by the parents with leatherjackets (larvae of crane flies) (Edwards & Lofty, 1978; Heppleston, 1971; Tracey, 1980). In late spring, leatherjackets are much more abundant and have a higher body mass than in early spring (during the egg stage). Unfortunately, we do not have information on the distribution of leatherjackets across the Netherlands, but potentially, leatherjacket and earthworm abundance are negatively correlated.

We did not find a significant effect of earthworm abundance on clutch survival, but this may be a result of the beech marten that is included in the same model. Beech marten probability of presence and earthworm abundance showed an intercorrelation

of -0.54 (Supplementary Fig. D9), which not exceeded the threshold of 0.7, so that we included both variables in the model. However, by excluding the beech marten from the model, earthworm abundance shows a significant positive effect on clutch survival, which is supported by plotting the raw data of earthworm abundance and clutch survival (Supplementary Fig. D14). Therefore, it seems that higher earthworm abundance results in higher clutch survival, but this effect disappears because of the strong effect of beech marten on clutch survival.

Our total earthworm abundance metric is only as a proxy for the food availability. The earthworm map is based on 20×20×20cm soil samples (Rutgers et al., 2016). The vertical distribution of earthworms in the soil determines how many earthworm can finally be reached by the oystercatchers (Onrust et al., 2019). The oystercatcher, as a tactile hunting meadow bird, is expected to capture earthworms in the upper 10 cm of the soil layer (within the reach of their bill) (Onrust et al., 2019). As the soil samples included the depth range relevant for oystercatchers, the used earthworm map likely is a reasonable proxy of the earthworms that are available for oystercatchers. However, the used earthworm map is static ignoring potential yearly variation, whereas earthworm abundance may also depend on for instance previous winter coldness (Timmerman et al., 2006). A map that considers abundance across years could potentially be a better predictor of oystercatcher clutch or hatchling survival.

Weather conditions

Drought (precipitation relative to evapotranspiration) had an effect on clutch as well as hatchling survival. Clutch survival steadily increased with increasing precipitation surplus. Possibly, with wetter conditions, access to earthworms is easier because they are less deep in the soil and are more accessible to the oystercatcher's bill (Onrust et al., 2019). Parents that have easier access to food may leave the nest less unattended, which, in turn, may reduce predation risk. By contrast, hatchling survival showed a peak at average precipitation (Fig. 5.3b). Possibly, chicks suffer from high levels of precipitation in terms of thermoregulation. For instance, northern bobwhite (*Colinus virginianus*) chicks are vulnerable to rainfall and temperature because they leave the nest shortly after hatching, without fully developed feather and plumage characteristics, which limits the thermoregulation and at the same time make them

more reliant on the parental care (Terhune II et al., 2019).

We also would expect that weather conditions (e.g. drought) interact with earthworm abundance. In years with lower precipitation, earthworm dig deeper into the soil, so that they are more difficult to be reached by the oystercatcher bill. Unfortunately, since the earthworm distribution map does not include any annual variation (one earthworm distribution map per year), we could not investigate this possible interactive effect.

Predictors of clutch and hatchling survival: synergistic effects

Common buzzard is known as a typical chick predator (Schekkerman et al., 2009; Teunissen et al., 2008). However, we found that probability of presence of buzzard strongly negatively affected the clutch survival, rather than the hatchling survival. Notably, buzzards primarily negatively affected clutch survival when land use intensity was high. Potentially this synergistic effect is caused by the fact that at higher land use intensity, alternative food source (e.g. mice) are easier accessible to buzzards during mowing or ploughing. This may attract buzzards, which in turn predate on oystercatcher clutches.

Higher probability of presence of stoat resulted in lower hatchling survival. This was especially the case at higher earthworm abundance. This, is at first glance an unexpected relationship, but could be explained by looking at the principal and alternative food source of stoats. Stoats mainly feed on rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) (McDonald et al., 2000) and rabbits predominantly occur on sandy soil with low ground water level, so that they can burrow their holes (Lombardi et al., 2003; Provoost et al., 2011). In sandier soil, earthworm abundance is also lower. Consequently, in areas where rabbits are less present stoats are known to switch to an important alternative food source: chicks (Smith et al., 2010). In those areas, the earthworm abundance is higher, but the predation chance on chicks is also higher (because rabbits are less present).

A more homogenous landscape as a result of agriculture intensification is also a reason for declining hare and rabbit populations in the last decade (Carroll, 2007; Pavliska et al., 2018). Both species (hares, rabbits) are also important and typical prey

species for predators of oystercatcher clutches and hatchlings (e.g. red fox, stoat). Consequently, the predators may switch to the alternative prey and therefore increase predation risk on oystercatcher nests. Typically, factors influencing predation risk are viewed only from the perspective of predators or prey populations. Only few studies examined the predation risk in a food-web context, by including alternative food sources (McGregor et al., 2020; Nordberg & Schwarzkopf, 2019).

The interaction effects that we found between buzzard and land use intensity on clutch survival as well as between earthworm abundance and stoat on hatchling survival suggest that we may need to sustain a well-balanced predator-prey food-web to reduce the strong impact of predation on oystercatcher reproduction. In addition, we strongly emphasize to consider in future studies the effect of population dynamics of alternative prey species.

Still few studies have explicitly quantified the nature of interactive effects between multiple environmental stressors, especially on large spatial scale (Darling & Cote, 2008). This study highlights the importance to investigate interactions between multiple environmental drivers because they can actually occur, as we have shown, and can provide us with a more detailed understanding on how exactly different environmental drivers affect a demographic trait. At the same time, these interactive effects generated new hypotheses that should be tested. For instance, including abundances of alternative food sources (e.g. mice, rabbits, hare) in the model to investigate if the interactions we found can be explained by these additional variables. In addition, our study also emphasizes the relevance of investigating the two stages of clutch and hatchling survival separately, because there are influenced in a different way by different environmental drivers. Also, the synergistic effects differ between the stages.

Management implications

Nest protection measures are often applied in meadow bird conservation to prevent destruction of clutches by agricultural activities (Franks et al., 2018). However, our study implies that nationwide clutch survival is not low at all compared to historical data and suggests that the main problematic stage is the hatchling survival, leading to low overall reproductive output in Dutch oystercatchers. A back-of-the-envelope

calculations illustrates how further management aimed at increasing clutch survival is likely to be both insufficient and inefficient. For example, if we assume a median clutch size of three eggs and optimistically ignore partial predation of clutches and broods for reasons of simplicity, then even if management was able to increase clutch survival from the observed 44% to a perfect 100%, this still leads to insufficient fledgling production ($0.3 \text{ fledglings} = 3 \text{ eggs} * 100\% \text{ clutch survival} * 10\% \text{ hatchling survival}$). By contrast, to achieve a required fledgling production for a stable population of 0.4 we would 'only' need to increase hatchling survival from 10% to 30% (though in practice the survival needs to be even higher due to partial clutch and brood predation). Management implications focussing on the increase in chick survival may therefore be more effective in increasing the overall reproductive success.

Chick survival can be improved in various ways, though some actions are highly habitat specific. For example, in urban areas providing water and shelter on the flat roofs could help chicks surviving extreme weather conditions like drought or heavy rain falls. Predation is important in many habitats, although the predator community compositions will vary among habitats. Managing predator abundance is a scientifically, ethically and practically complex matter that requires careful consideration of all available options (Bolton et al., 2007). First, predator control as a tool of abundance reduction could be a potential implication. However, capturing and trapping stoats is not allowed since they are a protected species in the Netherlands and population numbers seem to decline (Broekhuizen et al., 2016; Schekkerman et al., 2009). In crows, several studies concluded that culling is ineffective in reducing the numbers (Jiguet, 2020; Preininger et al., 2019) because of their specific group dynamics. Immature crows gather in large groups at sites where food is abundant and move regularly between groups, function as metapopulations at broad spatial scales (Marchand et al., 2018). Culling at local scale is therefore not effective in reducing numbers at large spatial scale so that hunting needs to be organized on a large scale to be effective, which, in turn is logistically and ethically challenging.

An alternative non-lethal measure to reduce mammalian predator abundance is the exclusion of predators through fences around areas of breeding birds. Predator-exclusion fencing deters large mammalian predators in two ways: either by presenting a physical barrier and/or by modifying behaviour through the use of an unpleasant

electric shock (Poole & McKillop, 2002). Studies have shown that this can be an effective management tool to improve the breeding success in waders by reducing predation by large mammals (e.g. foxes) (Malpas et al., 2013). Lapwing chick survival increased from almost 0 to 24% in Switzerland and number of fledglings per pair increased from 0.23 to 0.79 in England after the construction of fences around fields (Malpas et al., 2013; Rickenbach et al., 2011).

However, the type of fencing often described in this context does not exclude small mustelids like stoats (Malpas et al., 2013) and it is not clear yet how fencing should be designed to be effective in excluding stoats. In addition, avian predators are not excluded by fencing, so that it would not reduce the risk of hatchling predation by crows. Crows may even be able to learn to recognize fenced areas to locate chicks (Murphy et al., 2003). Overall, predator exclusion-fencing can be logistically challenging to build and a costly and time-intensive to maintain the fences at large scale (Plard et al., 2019; Smith et al., 2011).

A probably cheaper and less logistically challenging tool on a large scale that may also work on short-term, may be the construction of 'mice pyramids' (Fig. 5.4). They originate from the agricultural practices to dry the hay (Fig. 5.4a). Since they attract mice (in terms of shelter and/or food) they were also historically used to keep mice away from agricultural fields where mice can cause substantial destruction of crops and grasslands (e.g. feeding on grass roots or crop seeds). With some adjustments in the construction (e.g. tube for providing grain for the mice), these pyramids are used in the Netherlands in recent years as a tool to protect mice-hunting diurnal and nocturnal raptors (Fig. 5.4b). Raptors like common kestrel (*Falco tinnunculus*), common buzzards and various owl species profit from the increase in mice abundance (Vogelbescherming Nederland, 2017). Other organisations also suggest these pyramids to protect mustelids (stoat, weasel, polecat) (Bouwens, 2017; Veldman et al., 2021). Stoats for instance also feed on mice, especially in areas with lower rabbit abundances (Smith et al., 2010). These pyramids are easy to build and maintained. Detailed instructions can be found under (Landschapsbeheer Nederland, 2009).

As far as we know, this tool has not been implemented as a management implication for the protection of meadow birds yet. Given the characteristics of these pyramids and the interpretation of our study results suggest that the high predation

risk may be (partly) caused by a reduction of alternative food source for the predatory species, these constructions may be an interesting management tool. Since these pyramids have not been used for meadow bird protection yet, investigations about its effectiveness in an increase of the reproductive success is still necessary.

Figure 5.4: Illustration of a (a) more original haystack for drying hay and the adjusted (b) 'mice pyramid' to attract mice as food provisioning for raptors and mustelids. Drawings come from *Landschapsbeheer Nederland* (2009).

Finally, promoting more extensive land use to reduce homogeneity in the Dutch landscape (Foley et al., 2005) may be a management implication to reduce predator abundances. The effectiveness may be less visible on a short term, but on a long-term predator-prey interactions would become more naturally balanced. Oystercatcher nests would be less easy to locate and chicks would have more possibilities to hide in higher vegetation (Plard et al., 2019; Roos et al., 2018). In addition, lower land use intensity may promote an increase in alternative food source for predators like rabbits and hares (Carroll, 2007; Pavliska et al., 2018). An additional positive side effect of a more extensive land use is the improvement of the soil quality. Less disturbance of the soil by machines (e.g. manure injection) and high ground water levels can increase the abundances of arthropods and earthworms as food source for breeding meadow birds (Onrust et al., 2019).

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank all volunteers, students and researchers, as listed in Supplementary Text D2, which helped with collecting the reproduction data. We thank Landschappen NL (Aad van Paassen) for providing their data for this research. In

addition, we want to thank all farmers, Staatsbosbeheer, Natuurmonumenten and Koninklijke Maatschap Wilhelminapolder for permitting the access to their properties for the monitoring of the nests. Funding was provided by the Applied and Engineering Sciences domain of the Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO-STW; grant number 14638) as well as by Royal Netherlands Air Force, Birdlife Netherlands, NAM gas exploration and Deltares. We acknowledge the feedback provided by ecologists working at these organisations during half-yearly meetings.

Supplementary material

Supplementary material of Chapter 5 is included as appendix D to this thesis.

CHAPTER 6

Synthesis

Unravelling what is driving a population to decline in abundance is challenging. Population dynamics are complex processes that are determined by (potentially interacting) intrinsic and extrinsic factors, affecting different demographic parameters (survival, reproduction, migration). In many species demographic processes occur at geographically separated stages of the annual life cycle. In addition, understanding how a local population responds to specific threats does not necessarily mean that we can generalize these results to a broader population level scale (e.g. metapopulation). In the general introduction (**chapter 1**), I identified two main approaches that can help in understanding population decline in general and that of Dutch oystercatchers specifically: (1) use a full annual life cycle perspective (**chapter 2 & 3**), (2) identify intrinsic and extrinsic factors and their potentially interacting effect (**chapter 4 & 5**). I also highlight that a large-scale perspective is required to fill these knowledge gaps and that citizen science is a crucial tool for performing large-scale studies.

With this thesis, I contribute to a better insight in understanding what causes the decline of the Dutch oystercatcher population, with a focus on the reproduction of inland breeding birds. We collected several body condition variables from individuals caught and marked across the Netherlands on their wintering grounds, and quantified individual body condition with structural equation modelling (**chapter 2**). Next, we monitored the reproductive success of the marked individuals, applied the method described in **chapter 2** and integrated it with a multi-state survival model (in a Bayesian framework). This enabled us to identify potential carry-over effects from the individual winter body condition on the reproductive performance in the subsequent season (**chapter 3**). We also quantified to what extent intrinsic (competition) and extrinsic (food, weather) variables affect the winter body condition. In the next two chapters we focussed completely on the breeding area and identified the interactive effects of intrinsic (breeding density) and extrinsic (predator composition) variables on clutch survival (**chapter 4**). Finally, we investigated how a large range of environmental variables (land use intensity, food abundance and weather conditions) interact and affect the clutch as well as hatchling survival in the Dutch population (**chapter 5**). In this final chapter, I synthesise the newly gained knowledge in a broad ecological perspective and place it in a context of the oystercatcher population decline. In addition, I provide some recommendations for future studies, monitoring programs and discuss

management implications.

Synthesis from a broad ecological perspective

The different chapters in this thesis all emphasize that a large-scale ecological approach is important to understand population dynamics because (i) different mechanism may act at different places and (ii) that if the same mechanism acts at many places, one might still need to sample substantial spatiotemporal variation to detect and quantify relationships reliably. Specifically, in **chapter 4**, we show that processes that take place at a local scale or in a single population, do not necessarily occur in the same way on a broader scale. Whereas we would have expected a positive density-dependent nest (clutch) survival on a large scale, because we found such a relationship in one island population, we learned that generalizing the results from this single population to a larger scale can lead to erroneous conclusions. Actually, until now, only a limited number of studies on density-dependence compared density-dependent effects between populations, let alone over different and large spatial scales (Banda & Blanco, 2009; Lebeuf & Giroux, 2014; Oro et al., 2006). In **chapter 3**, we hypothesize that increasing the spatiotemporal scale of the measured environmental variables may help to estimate the relationship between the winter environment and body condition more precisely. Especially for long-lived migratory species, it may be important to realize that long-term and large scale monitoring of the environment is a relevant basis to model population dynamics accurately. Also in the literature on meadow birds, several studies already highlighted the importance of broad-scale investigations (Felici et al., 2019; Franks et al., 2018; Roodbergen et al., 2012).

If the mechanistic link of a potential carry-over effect is not taken into account, one may draw erroneous conclusions (e.g. attributing the wrong environmental drivers). For example, Olivier et al. (2005) found that snow petrels (*Pagodroma nivea*) show higher reproductive success after winters with greater ice cover. This may appear as a carry-over effect, where the environment in the non-breeding season affects the reproduction in the next season. However, the authors suggest that sea ice also promotes overwinter survival of krill, and thereby ensures a larger supply of food during the breeding season, consequently resulting in increased reproductive success. Thus, the reproductive success is, in this case, not affected by the environmental condition

through the mediation of an individual trait in the previous season, as it superficially appears. Instead, the environmental condition in one season affects the environment in the next season, resulting in increased demographic performance. It is important to realize that those different interpretations may lead to different conclusions and management recommendations. Therefore, it is crucial to investigate an individual trait (e.g. timing of egg-laying, condition) that mediates the interaction between seasons. With this, it is possible to get a better insight in the mechanism driving the population dynamics and disentangling the effects of intrinsic (e.g. individual quality) and extrinsic (e.g. environmental) drivers (Harrison et al., 2011; Norris & Marra, 2007).

In addition, using a mechanistic approach (at the individual level) may help in detecting carry-over effects. We were able to detect carry-over effects despite relatively small sample sizes. Possibly, by including individual condition as a state variable, we do an analysis at within-individual level. Thereby we filter out among individual variation that may add noise to environmental associations that compare population averages among years with different body and environmental conditions. Furthermore, we used a condition index incorporating morphological as well as physiological variables, which may represent the individual state in a more appropriate way because it may lead to a more precise measure of fitness. Whereas most studies look at body mass as the key individual state variable that mediates carry-over effects across seasons, two individuals could be of similar body mass and thus appear superficially to be in similar condition, but in practice may still have different abilities to deal with environmental challenges (Harrison et al., 2011; Wilder et al., 2016). In fact, in the last decade, it has become clear that different metrics of body condition are also related to aspects other than body mass and appear to be more appropriate predictors of fitness (Barry & Wilder, 2013). For example, an animal can have high lipid content but have low reproductive success if it is deficient in other nutrients (e.g. protein, vitamins, minerals) that it needs to reproduce (Nie et al., 2014). Notably, some studies suggested that hormones and the immune system may be involved in carry-over effects (Crossin et al., 2012; Hegemann et al., 2015).

It may especially be advantageous, if we operationalize a condition index based on how well it explains variation in a fitness trait of interest, rather than simply relying on correlation structures among potential condition variables, as we show in **chapter 2**.

Relying on a correlation structure may be a disadvantage for two main reasons. First, the condition variables may represent very different (uncorrelated) axes of the individual condition and, secondly, they may not necessarily show the relationship with the fitness trait that we would expect and assume based on previous knowledge. As we show in **chapters 2 & 3**, we found an unexpected negative relationship between the size-corrected body mass and condition (explaining variation in survival). Therefore, I would advise for future carry-over studies to make sure that the individual state (e.g., nutritional, hormonal, immune) is considered as a mechanistic link to ensure that appropriate conclusions are drawn and to enhance the chance to detect carry-over effects. In addition, I recommend considering several potential condition variables, rather than solely body mass.

We found that individuals are affected by the environmental condition in winter (grassland proportion, **chapter 3**). Hence, we can conclude that the reproductive success is not only shaped by individual quality (which we expect to be constant throughout the individuals' lifetime). However, to appropriately understand the relative contribution of the individual quality and the (more dynamic trait) individual condition (affected by habitat quality for instance), we would need to conduct experiments or studies with longitudinal data (Harrison et al., 2011; Norris & Marra, 2007). For instance, Daunt et al. (2014) could distinguish between an individuals' lifetime quality effect and environmental effects on the foraging time spent during the non-breeding period on the subsequent breeding performance in European shags (*Phalacrocorax aristotelis*). Interestingly, we found that the response of individual's body condition to the environmental variables depended on the feeding specialization (which is probably a proxy for individual quality; van der Kolk et al., 2019) (**chapter 3**). For instance, birds with a blunt bill (shellfish specialists) were more positively affected by higher cockle availability compared to worm specialists or intermediate feeders. This can give additional insights in the effect on a population level since we have information that the proportion of feeding specialists changed over time (Supplementary Fig. E1). The proportion of worm and shellfish specialists has decreased by 8% and 6%, respectively, from the early 2000s (Supplementary Table E1). In contrast, the proportion of individuals with an intermediate bill shape increased by 14% (Supplementary Table E1). We may therefore suggest that the overall population has

become less susceptible to fluctuations in cockle abundance in the past 20 years.

This thesis also emphasizes the need to investigate interactions between drivers within the season of interest. For instance, in **chapter 4**, we show that the predator composition determines the effect of breeding meadow bird density on clutch survival. Whereas existing studies have investigated the role of a single predator species concerning predator-driven density dependency, studies focussing on a wider range of species that make up the predator community are still rare, even though its importance has been emphasized in the literature (Rangen et al., 2001). Interactions may occur not only within one type of threat (e.g. predators), but also among different types of threats (e.g. land use and climate) (Evans, 2004; Kentie et al., 2015; Kleijn et al., 2010; Roodbergen & Teunissen, 2014). And especially research on large spatial scale is missing (Darling & Cote, 2008).

In addition to some existing studies on synergistic effects on meadow bird populations across Europe (Kentie et al., 2015, 2015; Kleijn et al., 2010; Roodbergen & Teunissen, 2014), with **chapter 5**, we contribute and add to existing literature by finding interactive effects between land use, food abundance and predator presence at a broad national scale. With our outcomes, we show that investigating synergistic effects can provide us with a more detailed understanding on how exactly different environmental drivers affect a demographic trait. At the same time, these interactive effects generated new hypotheses that should be tested. For instance, including abundances of alternative food sources (e.g. mice, rabbits, hare) in the model to investigate if the interactions we found can be explained by these additional effects. Actually, only few studies examined the predation risk in a food-web context, by including alternative food sources (McGregor et al., 2020; Nordberg & Schwarzkopf, 2019).

Finally, we provide examples of statistical frameworks (**chapter 2 & 3**) that can be useful tools in different types of ecological studies (e.g. behaviour, physiology). For instance, we show in **chapter 2** how the multivariate nature of body condition can be quantified. In **chapter 3** we analyse jointly the different processes and events to identify a carry-over effect by combining environmental variables, individual body condition, and the reproductive performance within a mark-recapture framework. These frameworks of structural equation modelling and Bayesian approach are powerful and flexible analytical tools that can provide several advantages (e.g. improved model

performance) compared to more conventional analyses. Therefore, we encourage researchers to consider those novel statistical techniques.

The Dutch oystercatcher population

Since the 1990s, the Dutch oystercatcher population (which comprises 30% of the species' European breeding population) showed a steady and continuous decline (Roodbergen & Teunissen, 2019; van de Pol et al., 2014). It appears that especially reproduction, rather than survival, is the bottleneck for this decline (Plard et al., 2019; Roodbergen et al., 2012). Therefore, we had two main aims: (1) How does the environment in winter affect the reproductive performance in the subsequent season (through a carry-over effect) and (2) how does the environment during the breeding season affect the reproductive performance (Fig. 1.1). In this section, I will discuss the main results from this thesis concerning these two main questions in the context of the Dutch oystercatcher population.

Condition and survival in winter (carry-over effect)

Concerning the situation in winter, the only variable that received strong statistical support and that could be potentially explaining the continuous decline in reproduction (clutch and hatchling survival) across the Netherlands is the available grassland proportion in the wintering areas (on the islands and along the coast on the mainland). According to CBS et al. (2021), the size of permanent grasslands decreased by almost 40% across the whole Netherlands since the 1980s, whereas arable land increased by 6% (across crop types). Earthworms in grasslands provide an alternative food source next to shellfish on intertidal flats (Caldow et al., 1999; Durell et al., 2001a; Heppleston, 1971). Even though there is probably no direct lethal effect of low proportion of grasslands close to high-tide roosts, we find a clear effect on the condition of the individuals that carried over to the reproductive season. We already know that specific individuals (with pointed bills) use grasslands as additional food source next to the mudflats (van der Kolk et al., 2019). Our results indicate that the effect of grasslands close to wintering grounds is more important than previously expected (**chapter 3**).

The other environmental variables that we included in the model (temperature,

cockle and mussel abundance, and competitor density) could also have biologically strong carry-over effects. However, we cannot be certain about these yet because the model showed low precision of the effect of these variables on the body condition. The food availability of shellfish could potentially explain the low reproductive success. Especially the mussel stocks (available for oystercatchers) decreased since the 1980s (van der Meer et al., 2019; Waser et al., 2016). At that time, the Dutch oystercatcher population was still growing. In contrary, there is no clear evidence of a consistent change in the highly variable cockle stocks in the Wadden Sea in the period 1980-2020 (Beukema & Dekker, 2006; Troost et al., 2021). However, the confidence interval around these variables was high (overlapping with zero) so that we cannot draw clear conclusions about the effect of shellfish food availability on the body condition at this point. The winter temperature showed a positive effect on the condition, but winters became milder in the last decades, so we would expect that this variable developed in a beneficial direction for the oystercatcher reproduction. Hence, temperature does probably not explain low reproductive success in recent decades. The limited data on spatiotemporal variation in environmental variables make it challenging to detect, potentially present, effects of the environment on individual condition.

In **chapter 3**, we did not estimate a potential carry-over effect from summer season to the winter season (see also Fig. 1.1). This effect is less frequently investigated than carry-over effects from non-breeding to breeding season and would ensure that the ‘full’ annual cycle rather than the ‘half annual cycle’ is investigated, which is still rarely done (Harrison et al., 2011; Marra et al., 2015). Ignoring such a relationship may lead to a misclassification of the mechanism underlying the individual variation. Theoretically, the food availability during breeding season or extreme weather conditions could also increase mortality during return to the wintering areas or even at the wintering area itself (Harrison et al. 2011). However, for two reasons investigating this relationship had lower priority in our study population. Firstly, we would expect that this effect is especially strong in long distant migrants rather than in this studied short distance migrant population. Secondly, we would not expect a long-lived species to prioritize the breeding season over its own subsequent survival in winter (Kersten, 1997).

Breeding season

We investigated the effect of the environmental drivers on the reproductive success separately for the clutch and hatchling survival because we expected that different threats may vary across the stages (Plard et al., 2019). We will start in this section by discussing first potential drivers on the clutch survival, and then on the hatchling survival.

Given that Bailey et al. (2017) found a positive density dependency in clutch survival in the local oystercatcher population on the island of Schiermonnikoog, there was valid concern that an Allee effect may cause the nationwide reproductive decline. Bailey et al. (2017) found that at higher breeding density, oystercatcher nests suffer less predation risk, presumably due to the higher mobbing intensity by neighbours. Since the oystercatcher population keeps declining and breeding densities become smaller, we could expect a collapse of the population due to this positive density dependent nest survival (extinction vortex). In addition, in inland breeding areas, we observed much lower breeding densities than on the island of Schiermonnikoog, where the original study has been conducted. Therefore, we were wondering how nests could survive in those low inland breeding densities. In **chapter 4**, we show that the concern of a nationwide Allee effect in the Dutch oystercatcher population was not justified. We could not find any consistent positive density-dependent nest survival in our countrywide analysis but found different effects of density-dependent nest survival under different predator compositions. Therefore, it seems that Allee effects are not omnipresent in the Dutch oystercatcher population. Thus, the ongoing nationwide decline must be caused by other factors than Allee effects.

Clutch survival was highest in agricultural areas (especially temporary grasslands) and lowest in natural inland and coastal areas (**chapter 5**). Beech marten, buzzard and fox probability of presence negatively affected clutch survival, whereas higher precipitation (relative to evapotranspiration) increased clutch survival. The negative effect of buzzard presence was stronger at high land use intensity, compare to low land use intensity. Possibly, this interactive effect is caused by the fact that at higher land use intensity, alternative food source (e.g. mice) are easier accessible to buzzards like for instance during mowing or ploughing. This may attract buzzards, which in turn predate on oystercatcher clutches.

However, our study implies that nationwide clutch survival (average of 44%) is not low compared to historical data and suggests that the main problematic stage is the hatchling survival, leading to low overall reproductive output in Dutch oystercatchers (**chapter 5**). A back-of-the-envelope calculations illustrates how further management that aims to increase clutch survival is likely to be both insufficient and inefficient. For example, if we assume a median clutch size of three eggs and optimistically ignore partial predation of clutches and broods for reasons of simplicity, then even if management was able to increase clutch survival from the observed 44% to a perfect 100%, this still leads to insufficient fledgling production ($0.3 \text{ fledglings} = 3 \text{ eggs} * 100\% \text{ clutch survival} * 10\% \text{ hatchling survival}$). By contrast, to achieve a required fledgling production for a stable population of 0.4 we would 'only' need to increase hatchling survival from 10% to 30% (though in practice the survival needs to be even higher due to partial clutch and brood predation). Management implications focussing on the increase in chick survival may therefore be more effective in increasing the overall reproductive success.

Hatchlings had higher survival when the probability of stoat and crow presence was lower. In years of drought (below average precipitation relative to evapotranspiration), hatchling survival was lower. However, also high precipitation surplus reduced the hatchling survival. The negative effect of stoat presence on hatchling survival was specifically present when earthworm abundance was high, which was indicated by an interaction effect between earthworm abundance and stoat presence. This, is at first glance an unexpected relationship, but could be explained by looking at the principal and alternative food source of stoats. Stoats mainly feed on rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) (McDonald et al., 2000) and rabbits predominantly occur on sandy soil with low ground water level, so that they can burrow their holes (Lombardi et al., 2003; Provoost et al., 2011). In sandier soil, earthworm abundance is also lower. Consequently, in areas where rabbits are less present stoats are known to switch to an important alternative food source: chicks (Smith et al., 2010). In those areas, the earthworm abundance is higher, but the predation chance on chicks is also higher (because rabbits are less present).

Hatchling showed above average survival in urban areas, average survival in coastal breeding habitats and lowest survival in agricultural areas (grasslands and arable fields).

Actually, only urban breeding oystercatchers were able to reach the necessary threshold of 0.4 fledglings per pair to ensure a stable population (Allen et al., 2021). This comes mainly from the high hatchling survival in this habitat type (**chapter 5**).

It is impressive how well oystercatchers have adapted to breeding on the roofs. Compared to other meadow birds (e.g. lapwings, godwits) the oystercatcher population probably has an advantage in flattening the steep population decline because of the advantage of breeding in urban areas which appears to be really successful compared to other breeding habitats. However, the proportion of urban breeding oystercatchers is still comparably low (to other habitat types). An estimation from 10 years ago revealed that about 4% were breeding in cities (Ens et al., 2011). This percentage has probably increased in the last 10 years. However, the most important breeding habitat type is still agricultural areas that make up 75% of the population breeding habitat (Ens et al., 2011).

However, there is still little known about the exact mechanism of habitat selection and dispersal. In some local populations, we see an increase of breeding birds in urban areas, whereas the surrounding agricultural area show a decline in breeding numbers (Dijkstra & Dillerop, 2016). Since the individuals are colour-ringed, we know that at least some of the birds from agricultural breeding ground moved to the urban area. However, it is unclear how common this process is on a large scale. And how do juvenile birds choose their breeding habitat? Do juveniles, born on a roof, become a roof breeder? We observed a GPS-tagged oystercatcher that was in its 3rd calendar year flying around a large area over the province of North-Holland during the breeding season several times, without starting breeding at all. Was it searching for a good breeding habitat? Bailey et al. (2019) show that territory settlement is more likely in areas of high fledgling output. That would mean that understanding the variation of the reproductive success across the Netherlands is also key component to predict habitat selection and redistribution of oystercatchers across habitats in the Netherlands.

In addition, concerning the urban breeding oystercatchers, there is a successful citizen science program (www.scholeksterophetdak.nl) that was launched recently (in 2018) to raise awareness in citizens of urban regions about the roof breeding oystercatchers to increase the understanding on the risks and chances for the urban birds. In addition, the aim is to get better insight in which measures effectively help the

hatchlings to survive on the roof (e.g. placing a mesh wire in front of the roof gutter).

A probably limiting factor to identify the effect of environmental drivers on the reproductive success more precisely, that I came across during my thesis, was the limited temporal variation in the data. For instance, the distribution maps for many mammalian species are 'static' over time. Changes in the Dutch landscape have led to increasing numbers of predators over the last 40 years (Roodbergen & Teunissen, 2019) and it is known that predation levels can fluctuate among years (Teunissen et al., 2008), probably due to varying predator abundance and alternative prey species (Nolet et al., 2013). For instance, a peak year of voles can result in lower predation rates of meadow birds because an alternative food source is present. The high number of voles as a prey, however, may lead to an increase of the predators in the subsequent year and when vole numbers drop (in the subsequent year), predator pressure on meadow bird clutches and hatchlings will be higher. For our relatively short study period (of 10 years in **chapter 4** and 20 years in **chapter 5**), we do not have evidence of extreme changes in population numbers of the avian predator species on the national scale. However, these kinds of additional predator-prey interactions often occur on a local scale. Therefore, distribution maps varying not only spatially but also annually, would probably help in detecting the effects of environmental drivers. Creating well-performing spatiotemporal distribution models requires the necessary input data that are not available so far for mammalian predators. Therefore, I highly recommend that more effort is put in establishing a long-lasting citizen science program for the monitoring of mammal species across the Netherlands.

A threat that we did not include as a potential driver in this thesis is hunting. Over most of its distribution the oystercatchers are legally protected or not hunted since the mid-1980s. Nonetheless, hunting seems to be still a major source of mortality for oystercatchers overwintering in France. Regularly, colour-banded birds are reported shot, but little is known of how large the impact of hunting is on the population level (van de Pol et al., 2014). Related to this point, we need to emphasize that we 'only' focus on the Dutch population. However, the decline of meadow birds in general happens on a European level. So, what about the oystercatchers in the German and Danish Wadden Sea? It is expected that they experience similar threats as the Dutch population (Roodbergen et al., 2012). But what about Norwegian breeding birds that

overwinter here? What are the threats for coastal breeding oystercatchers in Scandinavia? Increasing the scale of the research beyond national borders is rarely done because it is often related to logistical challenges in terms of data gathering; but it would be really beneficial in getting an even better understanding on the European population dynamics (Roodbergen et al., 2012).

In addition, there are occasional observations of breeding birds reported as road kills. However, it is not clear yet, how large the impact of road kills is on the annual survival in the Dutch population. It is possible that the relatively low adult survival from inland birds is a result of road kills (Allen et al., 2019).

Ultimately, to get a more complete understanding of the Dutch oystercatcher population dynamics, the results of the different chapter of this thesis (e.g. effect sizes of the different pathways, variation of reproductive output across habitats) will be combined with the effects of other human pressures (sea level rise, disturbance; Fig. 1.1) and finally incorporated in population models to estimate their cumulative effects on local and metapopulation dynamics (Fig. 1.1). This is the main goal of the project CHIRP (Cumulative Human Impact on biRd Populations), where this thesis is part of.

Recommendations for management implications

Based on the newly gained knowledge, I will give some management recommendations that can potentially help to reduce or even stop the Dutch oystercatcher population decline.

The reproductive success (clutch as well as hatchling survival) is too low to keep the Dutch oystercatcher population stable at the moment (Allen et al., 2021). In terms of reproduction, it is important first to realize that there are different risks for the clutches and the hatchlings and that management actions can be applied more efficient when we are aware of these differences. Compared to historical reproduction data, we see the strongest decline in the hatchling survival. In addition, a simple calculation illustrated that it is more efficient to try to increase the hatchling survival, rather than the clutch survival, to help the reproductive output to reach the threshold of a stable population. Hence, we suggest that management implications should focus on increasing the hatchling survival of the oystercatchers. In addition, given that three quarters of the Dutch population breeds in agricultural area, it is important to focus on

this habitat type.

The most important drivers of the oystercatcher reproductive performance throughout this thesis are the predator species. The management of predator abundance is a scientifically, ethically and practically complex matter that requires careful consideration of all available options (Bolton et al., 2007). Nevertheless, I will give some insights on different options that I think are most efficient at this time point. I ordered these recommendations on how I would prioritize the actions and want to emphasize that these recommendations are partly based on the results from this thesis but also based on my expert judgment that I gained during the last years.

1. Reduce land use intensity landscape

Decreasing land use intensity can be useful for two different reasons. First, promoting more extensive land use can reduce homogeneity in the Dutch landscape (Foley et al., 2005). Generalist predators are less susceptible or may even profit from a changing landscape becoming more monotonous (Moritz & Agudo, 2013). Therefore, predators may increase in abundance, leading to higher predation risks for meadow birds in general. The predator-prey interactions are therefore unbalanced in this human dominated landscape, resulting in predators being a main cause for the reproductive failure of meadow birds. Second, a more homogenous landscape as a result of agriculture intensification is also a reason for declining hare and rabbit populations in the last decade (Carroll, 2007; Pavliska et al., 2018). Both species (hares, rabbits) are also important and typical prey species for predators of oystercatcher clutches and hatchlings (e.g. red fox, stoat). Consequently, the predators may switch to the alternative prey and therefore increase predation risk on oystercatcher nests.

2. Increase the abundance of alternative prey species

Another way to a more balanced predator-prey food-web to reduce the strong impact of predation on oystercatcher reproduction may be the construction of ‘mice pyramids’ (Fig. 5.4). Probably this is a cheap tool that can easily be implemented on a large scale. ‘Mice pyramids’ originate from the agricultural practices to dry the hay (Fig. 5.4a). These pyramids are used in the Netherlands in recent years as a tool to protect mice-hunting diurnal and nocturnal raptors (Fig. 5.4b) because they attract mice (by

providing shelter and food). Raptors like common kestrel (*Falco tinnunculus*), common buzzards and various owl species profit from the increase in mice abundance (Vogelbescherming Nederland, 2017). Other organisations also suggest these pyramids to protect mustelids (stoat, weasel, polecat) (Bouwens, 2017; Veldman et al., 2021). Stoats for instance also feed on mice, especially in areas with lower rabbit abundances (Smith et al., 2010). These pyramids are easy to build and maintained. Detailed instructions can be found under (Landschapsbeheer Nederland, 2009).

As far as we know, this tool has not been implemented as a management implication for the protection of meadow birds yet. Given the characteristics of these pyramids and the interpretation of our study results suggest that the high predation risk may be (partly) caused by a reduction of alternative food source for the predatory species (**chapter 5**), these constructions may be an interesting management tool. Since these pyramids have not been used for meadow bird protection yet, investigations about its effectiveness in an increase of the reproductive success is still necessary.

3. Provide water and shelter on roofs

At the moment, urban habitats are the only habitat type that show a reproductive output that is high enough to sustain a stable population (**chapter 5**). Nevertheless, there are threats for roof breeding oystercatchers as well, where we, as humans, could help. Roof breeding oystercatchers are especially exposed to weather conditions like drought or rain. Extra shelter on the roof can help to hide from extreme sun or heavy rain. In addition, it could help to hide from flying predators. During an extreme dry season, it can also help to provide a water bowl to prevent dehydration.

4. Preserve grasslands close to the coast

The grassland proportion around the roost site showed a relatively strong effect on the winter body condition. Even though this effect does not appear to be lethal, it reduced the condition of the bird, which results in a lower reproductive performance in the subsequent season (**chapter 3**). We therefore recommend preserving grasslands, especially permanent grasslands (rather than changing them to arable land or even buildings) close to highly used high-tide roost areas to ensure that the birds have the possibility to forage on grasslands close to their roost areas. The soil quality in

permanent grasslands is higher because it is less disturbed than in temporary grasslands or arable land and, consequently resulting in higher earthworm abundance (Onrust et al., 2019).

5. Consider the predator community before deciding where to construct new attractive meadow bird reserves

This management implication focusses on the clutch survival rather than the hatchling survival. However, I would like to mention it here because I think that it is relatively easy to consider when constructing new meadow bird areas inland to attract breeding oystercatchers. If there are choices where exactly (location) such areas or reserves are built, I would recommend to take the predator community into account and prioritize regions with predominantly avian predators. If these areas aim to attract high number of breeding meadow birds, avian predators are effectively mobbed away. However, mammalian predators are attracted by high breeding numbers and experts in searching the whole area or field for nests. At the same time, they are less effectively chased away by meadow birds, which increases the chance of predation at high breeding density.

6. Predator control and exclusion

Predator control as a tool of abundance reduction could be a potential implication. However, capturing and trapping stoats is not allowed since they are a protected species in the Netherlands and population numbers seem to decline (Broekhuizen et al., 2016; Schekkerman et al., 2009). In crows, several studies concluded that culling is ineffective in reducing the numbers (Jiguet, 2020; Preiningner et al., 2019) because of their specific group dynamics. Immature crows gather in large groups at sites where food is abundant and move regularly between groups, function as metapopulations at broad spatial scales (Marchand et al., 2018). Culling at local scale is therefore not effective in reducing numbers at large spatial scale so that hunting needs to be organized on a large scale to be effective, which, in turn is logistically and ethically challenging.

An alternative non-lethal measure to reduce mammalian predator abundance is the exclusion of predators through fences around areas of breeding birds. Predator-exclusion fencing deters large mammalian predators in two ways: either by presenting

a physical barrier and/or by modifying behaviour through the use of an unpleasant electric shock (Poole & McKillop, 2002). Studies have shown that this can be an effective management tool to improve the breeding success in waders by reducing predation by large mammals (e.g. foxes) (Malpas et al., 2013). Lapwing chick survival increased from almost 0 to 24% in Switzerland and number of fledglings per pair increased from 0.23 to 0.79 in England after the construction of fences around fields (Malpas et al., 2013; Rickenbach et al., 2011).

However, the type of fencing often described in this context does not exclude small mustelids like stoats (Malpas et al., 2013) and it is not clear yet how fencing should be designed to be effective in excluding stoats. In addition, avian predators are not excluded by fencing, so that it would not reduce the risk of hatchling predation by crows. Crows may even be able to learn to recognize fenced areas to locate chicks (Murphy et al., 2003). Overall, predator exclusion-fencing can be logistically challenging to build and a costly and time-intensive to maintain the fences at large scale (Plard et al., 2019; Smith et al., 2011).

APPENDIX A

Supplementary material chapter 2

Conceptualizing and quantifying body condition using structural
equation modelling: A user guide

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table A1: Catching events and their characteristics.

Date	Location	Long- itude	Lat- itude	Winter	Number of birds		
					Juveniles	Sub- Adults	Adults
2-12-2016	Vlieland, Vliehors	4.95	53.24	2016- 2017	0	5	1
3-12-2016	Vlieland, Vliehors	4.95	53.24	2016- 2017	4	0	1
4-12-2016	Vlieland, Vliehors	4.95	53.24	2016- 2017	2	0	0
5-12-2016	Vlieland, Vliehors	4.95	53.24	2016- 2017	0	0	1
18-12- 2016	Vlieland, Vliehors	4.97	53.25	2016- 2017	1	2	3
18-12- 2016	Vlieland, Vliehors	4.97	53.25	2016- 2017	6	2	5
18-12- 2016	Vlieland, Vliehors	4.97	53.25	2016- 2017	1	0	0
19-12- 2016	Vlieland, Vliehors	4.97	53.25	2016- 2017	1	0	0
16-1-2017	Vlieland, Vliehors	4.95	53.24	2016- 2017	0	1	1
17-1-2017	Vlieland, Vliehors	4.95	53.24	2016- 2017	0	30	45
18-1-2017	Vlieland, Vliehors	4.95	53.24	2016- 2017	0	5	5
25-1-2017	Schier- monnikoog 2e slenk	6.23	53.48	2016- 2017	0	14	34
20-2-2017	Balgzand Normerven	4.94	52.91	2016- 2017	0	30	37
24-2-2017	Eemshaven	6.78	53.46	2016- 2017	0	4	14
28-2-2017	Molenkolk, Texel	4.80	53.02	2016- 2017	0	8	49
15-12- 2017	Vlieland, Vliehors	4.96	53.25	2017- 2018	1	11	24

Supplementary Table A1: Continued

Date	Location	Longitude	Latitude	Winter	Number of birds		
					Juveniles	Sub-Adults	Adults
18-12-2017	Vlieland, Vliehors	4.96	53.25	2017-2018	12	12	16
19-12-2017	Vlieland, Vliehors	4.96	53.25	2017-2018	0	5	11
19-12-2017	Vlieland, Vliehors	4.92	53.23	2017-2018	0	8	32
6-2-2018	Oosterend, Terschelling	5.39	53.40	2017-2018	0	0	3
26-1-2018	Balgzand, 't Kuitje	4.79	52.93	2017-2018	0	6	69
19-1-2018	Prunje-polder, Oosterschelde	3.85	51.69	2017-2018	0	21	108
21-1-2018	Ameland, Vogelpolle	5.67	53.42	2017-2018	0	25	77
16-2-2018	Striep, Terschelling	5.30	53.38	2017-2018	0	1	17
17-2-2018	Sehael, Terschelling	5.32	53.38	2017-2018	0	5	45
30-1-2018	Schor Wilhelminapolder, Oosterschelde	3.90	51.54	2017-2018	0	16	106
19-2-2018	Schiermonnikoog, 2e Slenk	6.23	53.48	2017-2018	0	36	48
20-2-2018	Schiermonnikoog, 2e Slenk	6.23	53.48	2017-2018	0	12	22

Appendix A

Supplementary Table A2: List of variables and their characteristics included in the analyses (for adults only).

Variable name	Unit	Type	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Nr. Obs. **	Transformation ***
Body weight	gr	Continuous	564	50	439	774	772	-
Tarsus length	mm	Continuous	97	3	87	108	774	-
Head/bill length	mm	Continuous	120	6	105	142	773	-
Wing length	mm	Continuous	265	6	245	286	767	-
Cholesterol	mmol /L	Continuous	13.2	2.6	6.9	26.2	408	-
Bill chroma	-	Continuous	85	2	83	93	589	-
Bill luminance	-	Continuous	69	3	61	79	589	-
Bill hue	-	Continuous	63	5	47	79	600	-
Haematocrit	-	Proportion	0.45	0.03	0.38	0.54	549	Logit
Buffy coat	-	Proportion	0.006	0.002	0.001	0.018	551	Logit
Uric acid	mmol /L	Continuous	1.18	0.73	0.23	3.99	386	-
Corticosterone (standardized*)	pg/mg	Continuous	0.0	1.0	-2.6	6.0	607	-
Handling time	-	Proportion	0.14	0.06	0.02	0.30	774	-
Bill tip height	mm	Continuous	4.2	0.9	1.5	6.4	768	-

Supplementary Table A2: Continued.

Variable name	Unit	Type	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Nr. Obs. **	Transformation ***
Sex	-	Factor	Used as continuous variable in the model. Females (F, n=311) coded as 1 (reference group), males (M, n=463) coded as 2.				744	-
Density	Number/km ²	Continuous	114	68	14	255	774	-
Survival	-	Proportion	0.87	0.06	0.74	0.92	774	Logit

* Standardized among years. For more information see Supplementary Fig. A24.

** Note that not all variables were collected during each capture and therefore sample sizes varied among analyses.

*** Transformation before analysis.

Supplementary Table A3: Pearson's correlation between the three colour parameters per age class.

Correlation between	Adults	Sub-Adults
Hue & Luminance	0.97	-0.11
Chroma & Hue	-0.83	-0.41
Luminance & Chroma	-0.70	0.94

Supplementary Table A4: Loadings from PC1 and PC2 of the energy-store-PCA. PCA analyses were conducted with the R-package FactoMineR (Le et al., 2008).

	PC1	PC2
Residuals	0.98	0.18
Ratio	0.98	-0.18

Appendix A

Supplementary Table A5: Loadings from the PC1, PC2 and PC3 of the adult bill colour. PCA analyses were conducted with the R-package FactoMineR (Le et al., 2008).

	PC1	PC2	PC3
Hue	0.99	0.10	0.08
Luminance	0.95	0.31	-0.06
Chroma	-0.90	0.44	0.02

Supplementary Table A6: Loadings from the PC1, PC2 and PC3 of the sub-adult bill colour. PCA analyses were conducted with the R-package FactoMineR (Le et al., 2008).

	PC1	PC2	PC3
Hue	-0.49	0.87	0.02
Luminance	0.92	0.39	-0.05
Chroma	1.00	0.07	0.06

Supplementary Table A7: Model fit indices of all models. Statistical significance of the chi-square statistic (using $\alpha = 0.05$) indicates that the fit of the model has to be rejected. With increasing sample sizes, chance of detecting a smaller difference between the hypothesized value and the true value is greater and therefore may lead to rejection of the model (Grace & Keeley, 2006; Jak & Jorgensen, 2017; Shipley, 2016). Since we have relatively high sample sizes (>300), we also document alternative fit indices: the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA; Kline, 2011), standardized root mean square residual (SRMR; Hu & Bentler, 1999) and the comparative fit index (CFI; Bentler, 1990).

	Chi-square	p-value	DF	CFI	SRMR	RMSEA	Lower RMSEA	Upper RMSEA
Energy store model (Fig. 2.2a, Supplementary Code A1)	0	NA	0	1	0	0	0	0
Bill colour model (Fig. 2.2b, Supplementary Code A2)	1141.24	<0.001	2	0.68	0.06	1.22	1.16	1.28
Composite model (Fig. 2.4, Supplementary Code A3)	77.83	<0.001	9	0.78	0.05	0.13	0.10	0.15
Composite model with squared mass (Fig. 2.4, Supplementary Code A4)	77.19	<0.001	12	0.65	0.07	0.11	0.09	0.13
Latent+ composite model (Fig. 2.5, Supplementary Code A5)	363.72	<0.001	68	0.92	0.08	0.10	0.09	0.11

Supplementary Table A7: Continued.

	Chi-square	p-value	DF	CFI	SRMR	RMSEA	Lower RMSEA	Upper RMSEA
Latent+composite model with direct and indirect effect of body size (Supplementary Fig. A13a & Code A6)	276.97	<0.001	51	0.94	0.08	0.10	0.09	0.11
Latent+composite model with only indirect effect of body size (Supplementary Fig. A13b & Code A7)	277.63	<0.001	52	0.94	0.08	0.10	0.09	0.11
Model used for model performance (Fig. 2.6; Supplementary Code A8)	246.14	<0.001	60	0.95	0.07	0.09	0.07	0.10
Acceptable threshold levels	Low chi-square relative to degrees of freedom with an insignificant p value (p > 0.05)			>0.90	<=0.08	<=0.07		
Literature	Grace, 2006			Hu & Bentler, 1999; Lefcheck, 2019	Hu & Bentler, 1999	Steiger, 2007		

Supplementary Table A8: Comparison of the two full models (Supplementary Fig. A13). Model 1 indicating the model without a direct effect of body size, Model 2 indicating the model with a direct effect of body size on survival.

Model	DF	AIC	BIC	Chisq	Chisq diff	DF diff	Pr(>Chisq)
Model 1 (Supplementary Fig. A13b & Code A6)	51	-5278.3	-5083.6	276.97			
Model 2 (Supplementary Fig. A13a & Code A7)	52	-5279.7	-5089.0	277.64	0.66635	1	0.4143

Supplementary Table A9: Steps that needs to be taken to analyse the model (Fig. 2.5) with conventional methods (MR=multiple regression, PCA=principal component analysis). Note that here we show 6 steps instead of 4 steps (as described in Fig. 2.6). Step 2 and 3 in this table relate to step 2 in Fig. 2.6 and step 5 and 6 in this table relate to step 4 in Fig. 2.6. The reason for this is that technically, extracting the residuals and running the PCA are two steps, but for easier visualization we showed it as one step (step 2) in Fig. 2.6. Explanatory variables (from step 1) were standardized (mean=0, sd=1) before analysis. Abbreviations: MS=mass, TL=tarsus length, WL=wing length, HL=head length, HT=handling time, BH=bill tip height, Cho=cholesterol, U=uric acid, B=buffy coat, Hct=haematocrit, Cort=corticosterone, Age=Age, Sex=Sex.

Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4	Step 5	Step 6
MR: condition variables as response variable with individual characteristics and confounding variables as independent variables	Extract residuals	PCA: run PCA and extract PC1	MR: regress confounding variables and individual characteristics on PC1	Extract residuals from PC1	MR: survival as response variable and residuals of all condition variables
MS~TL+WL+HL	Resid(MS)	PCA with Resid(MS) and Ratio	PC1 Energy store~Age+Sex+BH+HT	Resid(PC1 Energy reserve)	Survival ~ resid(PC1 Energy store)+ resid(Hue)+resid(Cho)+ resid(U)+resid(BC)+ resid(Hct)+resid(Cort)
Ratio					
Cho~Sex+HT+BH+Age	Resid(Cho)				
U~Sex+HT+BH+Age	Resid(U)				
B~Sex+HT+BH+Age	Resid(B)				
Hct~Sex+HT+BH+Age	Resid(Hct)				
Cort~Sex+BH+Age	Resid(Cort)				
Hue~ Sex+BH+Age	Resid(Hue)				

Supplementary Table A10: Pearson's correlation of different measuring points of the bill of an individual. Values in parentheses indicate the lower and upper 95% confidence interval. See for abbreviations and locations *sbm*, *som*, *sbb*, *sbe* Supplementary Fig. A22.

		Hue	Chroma	Luminance	n
Bill	<i>Right vs. left side (sbm)</i>	0.89 (0.86,0.92)	0.91 (0.88, 0.94)	0.89 (0.86,0.92)	160
	<i>Sbm vs. som on left side</i>	0.88 (0.84, 0.91)	0.86 (0.81, 0.89)	0.79 (0.72, 0.84)	167
	<i>Sbm vs. sbb on left side</i>	0.76 (0.67, 0.84)	0.65 (0.52, 0.75)	0.48 (0.30, 0.62)	94
	<i>Sbm vs. sbe on left side</i>	0.35 (0.21, 0.48)	0.84 (0.78, 0.88)	0.82 (0.76, 0.86)	166

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure A1: Study area in the Netherlands showing an overview of the catching locations across the Wadden Sea (a) and the Delta area (b) as well as the area-division used in the survival model. (c) indicates an overview map. Dots indicate catching events in the two winter periods (2016/2017 and 2017/2018). The size of the dots indicates the number of caught birds per catching event.

Supplementary Figure A2: Correlation matrix of all variables in the dataset. N=430

Appendix A

Supplementary Figure A3: Visualization of the energy-reserve-PCA. PCA visualization was conducted with the R-package *factoextra* (Kassambara & Mundt, 2020).

Supplementary Figure A4: Bill colour PCA for adults. PCA visualization was conducted with the R-package *factoextra* (Kassambara & Mundt, 2020).

Supplementary Figure A5: Bill colour PCA for sub-adults. PCA visualization was conducted with the R-package *factoextra* (Kassambara & Mundt, 2020).

Supplementary Figure A6: Relationships of the three colour parameters (hue, chroma and luminance) per age class. The relatively straight lines in all three panels in adults can be explained by the structure of the colour parameter chroma. Plotting the parameters in 3D results in a cylinder when using saturation (Fig. 26a), whereas, when plotting chroma instead of saturation it results in a biconical shape (Fig. 26b), which is also visible when plotting it two-dimensionally (Supplementary Fig. A7).

Appendix A

Supplementary Figure A7: Distribution of bill chroma (a), luminance (b) and hue (c). d-f) show bill colour range (circles) at changing luminance and chroma for minimum (d), mean (e) and maximum (f) hue values.

Supplementary Figure A8: Correlation of extracted values from PCA (PC1) and CFA for the energy reserve model (a) and the bill colour model for adults (b) and sub-adults (c). For explanation of the straight line in b, see figure description S6.

Supplementary Figure A9: The relationship between the condition index and the survival probability from the SEM (Fig. 2.5). Condition is explaining 18% of the variation in survival. Note that several individuals have the same condition value because multiple individuals were caught at the same location and year resulting in the same survival probability from the multistate live and dead recoveries model.

Appendix A

Supplementary Figure A10: The effect of oystercatcher density on the survival probability. Each dot represents one wintering area and year combination.

Supplementary Figure A11: Illustration of the a) full model (Fig. 2.5) indicating how bill colour was modelled and alternative structures to model bill colour (b-d). b) shows a model structure where only bill lightness is modelled as latent variable by luminance and chroma, which are highly correlated in both age classes. c) shows an example to integrate luminance and chroma as latent variable (bill lightness) and hue as a separate variable (observed and latent) describing the composite (bill colour). d) shows an alternative structure where all three variables are modelled separately describing the composite condition. Note that we use latent variables (e.g. hue') for hue to allow correction by confounding variables (e.g. sex) with the MIMIC method.

Appendix A

Supplementary Figure A12: The effect of a) the residuals of mass (corrected for size) and b) mass (in gram) on the survival probability. Dots show the raw data points, the red line indicate the fitted line and the grey shaded area around it is the confidence interval. c) shows the effect of residuals of mass on survival per age class (blue triangle=adults, orange dot=sub-adults). The large symbol indicates the mean with the standard error (horizontal bars) and the raw data with more transparent fill in the background. Summary statistics for panel a) are: $t\text{-value}=-7.62$, $DF=425$, $p<0.001$.

Supplementary Figure A13: SEM model including latent (circles), composite (squares) and measured (squares) variables (comparable to model of Fig. 2.5) with (a) and without (b) a direct effect of body size on survival which appears to be non-significant. Values indicate the standardized path strength (see Fig. 2.2 for explanation). Solid and dashed lines indicate a positive and negative significant ($p < 0.05$) path and are indicated by a star next to the standardized path strength, respectively. Dotted lines indicate non-significant pathways ($p > 0.05$). For simplicity we only documented the path strength of the condition, predictor and response variables. For the code of the models see Supplementary Code A6-A7. Note that as body size measure we only used tarsus length because the three structural sizes (tarsus length, wing length, head length) are not highly correlated so that it is not useful combining them in a latent variable. Combining the variables in a composite variable is not an option because there is no observed response variable. We can compare the effect of the direct vs. the indirect pathway (through mass) of tarsus length on condition by taking the product of all pathways. This results in a total (standardized) effect of -0.04 of tarsus on survival directly vs. a total effect of -0.1 through mass, energy stores and condition.

Appendix A

Supplementary Figure A14: Histogram of the effect of each condition variable on condition (estimate) of the simulated datasets for the SEM-approach. Red dashed line indicates the 'true' mean, whereas the blue dotted line is the mean of the simulated data.

Supplementary Figure A15: Histogram of the effect of each condition variable on condition (estimate) of the simulated datasets for the conventional approach. Red dashed line indicates the 'true' mean, whereas the blue dotted line is the mean of the simulated data.

Supplementary Figure A16: Relative bias (simulated estimate-true estimate divided by simulated estimate multiplied by 100) for three condition variables with strong effect on the condition index. SEM approach appears to be more unbiased than the conventional approach.

Appendix A

Supplementary Figure A17: Results from the simulation comparing biases in the estimation of the slopes of the condition variables using the SEM and the conventional approach. Simulation (with 1000 datasets of 1000 observations) was based on the covariance patterns found in the case study population (Fig. 2.6a) using the 'simulateData' function from lavaan (Rosseel, 2012). Dots and triangles indicate the mean simulated estimate for the conventional method and SEM, respectively, with the empirical standard error. Dashed grey horizontal line indicates the 'true' estimates. Note that standard error of the variable 'energy store' is really small and error bars are therefore hardly visible.

Supplementary Figure A18: Absolute bias for each condition variable for each approach. SEM being indicated by triangles and conventional approach by dots.

Appendix A

Supplementary Figure A19: Bias plotted against the empirical standard error for each condition estimate per approach. The SEM approach is clearly more unbiased compared to the conventional approach. In six of the seven variables the estimates are more precise than the estimates from the conventional approach. Only the variable energy store was estimated more precise with the conventional approach, however, this estimate was highly biased.

Supplementary Figure A20: Empirical standard error (precision) per variable and statistical approach.

Supplementary Figure A21: Holder for the capillaries for the blood samples to measure the haematocrit and buffy coat.

Appendix A

Supplementary Figure A22: a) showing the box where camera was placed on the side as well as from above to take a picture of the oystercatcher head. b) shows the box from inside with illumination, which ensured standardized light conditions for each picture. c) illustrates the different measuring points of each individual with the program PixelGrabber (d) where each individual is labelled on the picture next to the three reference cards for balancing the colour. e) shows an example of balanced colours on the right side corrected for the “real” white, on the left side the “original” colour.

Supplementary Figure A23: Seasonal survival probability for the different years, catching areas and age classes. Dots with bar indicate the estimate with the standard error. Year 2016 refers to winter 2016/2017.

Supplementary Figure A24: Corticosterone (pg/mg) measurements for the two different years of extraction (2016-2017 & 2017-2018).

Supplementary Figure A25: Schematic representation of the model by accounting for measurement errors (0.7 on each variable) by including latent variables (circles). The measured variables (squares) are tarsus length (TA), head length (TH) and wing length (WL) which are regressed on mass (MS) through the latent variables.

Supplementary Figure A26: Relationship of hue, lightness and a) saturation or b) chroma in a 3-dimensional setting. Picture credits: a) SharkD Talk - HSL_color_solid_cylinder.png, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=9801661>; b) SharkD Talk Hcl-hcv_models.svgHSL_color_solid_dblcone.png, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=9802536>

Supplementary Text

Supplementary Text A1: Choice, description and data collection of biometric and physiological measures included in the worked examples.

Blood samples (sex, haematocrit, buffy coat, cholesterol, uric acid)

Buffy coat, the fraction of white blood cells, is elevated if the body needs to fight against infections (Campbell et al., 2008). Haematocrit, the proportion of red blood cells with the main function of oxygen transportation, has been shown to be positively related to survival in Eurasian oystercatcher (*Haematopus ostralegus*) (Verhulst et al., 2004) and crimson fitches (*Neochmia phaeton*) (Milenkaya et al., 2015). Uric acid is a nitrogenous waste product of birds (Tsahar et al., 2006). The amount of nitrogenous waste produced by an individual can be linked to energy budget and diet (Campbell et al., 2008) and has been shown to be related to body mass loss in Yellow-legged gulls (*Larus cachinnans*) (Alonso-Alvarez et al., 2002). Cholesterol, a lipid, has been shown to best reflect body mass change in Yellow-legged gulls (*Larus cachinnans*) (Alonso-Alvarez et al., 2002). Griminger (1986) also suggested an influence of diet composition on cholesterol levels in birds.

Blood samples (approximately 0.35 ml per bird) were taken from the brachial vein. Sex was determined using molecular techniques from blood stored in cell lysis buffer at room temperature.

Two blood collection tubes of approximately 65 μL each were taken per individual bird and centrifuged 10 minutes at 9503g between 2 to 6 hours (mean \pm se = 3.6 ± 0.96 hrs) after blood extraction. Since this time delay did not significantly affect buffy coat and haematocrit, it was not included as a variable in the analysis. Buffy coat and haematocrit were measured by taking standardized pictures of the blood collection tube in a specific holder constructed for this purpose (Supplementary Fig. A21), and then measuring the length of the portion with red blood cells, white blood cells and plasma in pixels with the program Paint.NET. The haematocrit and buffy coat were calculated by taking the proportion of the length of red blood cells and white blood cells, respectively, to the total length (red blood cells + white blood cells + plasma). The reason for using pictures and measuring pixels instead of measuring proportions directly in the field was to minimize measuring bias due to more accurate measurements compared to a ruler/calliper. Repeatability (calculated by estimating the intra-class correlation coefficients (ICC) (and its 95% confidence interval) using the variance components from a one-way ANOVA with the R-package ICC (Wolak et al., 2012) between the two collection tubes of the same individual

Appendix A

of both haematocrit and buffy coat samples was high. Haematocrit: ICC (lower & upper confidence interval) = 0.984 (0.982, 0.986), n=758 duplicate samples. Buffy coat: ICC (lower & upper confidence interval) = 0.943 (0.931, 0.953), n = 390 duplicate samples). Number of observations for the buffy coat was smaller because samples were removed when edges were not sharp and/or diagonal.

The blood of two capillaries was transferred to tubes with heparin buffer and centrifuged at 6082g for 8 minutes. After centrifugation, the plasma (at least 50 μ L) was extracted and stored in a -80°C freezer. Cholesterol (mmol/L blood) and uric acid (μ mol/L blood) was determined (cholesterol: enzymatic method on discrete automatic analyser; uric acid: automatic and colorimetric method using uricase) by the University Veterinary Diagnostic Laboratory (UVDL) in Utrecht, the Netherlands, with Olympus AU-680 from the Beckman Coulter company.

Biometry

Biometric parameters, namely length of tarsus to toe (mm), wing length (mm), head length (mm), bill tip height (mm) and mass, were measured following the standard techniques described in Durell et al. (1993). Bill tip height (measured 3 mm from the bill tip using a calliper) was used as a proxy for the type of individuals' feeding specialization (individual characteristics; Fig. 2.1), ranging from worm specialists (indicated by a pointed bill and a low bill tip height) to shellfish specialists (indicated by a blunt bill and high bill tip height) (van de Pol et al., 2009a). Birds were aged on basis of their plumage, bill and leg characteristics (Cramp & Simmons, 1983) and the age was classified in 1st, 2nd, 3rd calendar year and adults (>3rd calendar year). We focussed only on sub-adults (2nd and 3rd calendar year) and adults (>3rd calendar year) in the case study because number of caught and sampled juveniles (1st calendar year) was small (n=28; Supplementary Table A1). Handling time (confounding variable; Fig. 2.1) was recorded to correct for time-dependent mass loss as well as possible effects on other physiological measures. Handling time (as a proportion of 24 hours) was defined as the time between capture and measuring (Fig. 2.1) to correct for seasonal effects on energy reserves and physiological parameters (Norte et al., 2009).

Feather sample (corticosterone)

Corticosterone, a steroid stress hormone, fulfils its main functions by mobilizing stored resources and up-regulating metabolism for coping with increased energetic challenges, resulting in higher corticosterone secretion in birds coping with harsh environments

(Jimeno et al., 2017b, 2017a, 2018; Marra & Holberton, 1998).

When a bird was caught, we took the 5th tail/flight feather from the left side of the bird and stored it in a paper envelope until it was sent to the laboratory of the Department of Evolutionary Ecology at the National Museum for natural Science (CSIS) in Spain for corticosterone extraction. We followed the methodology for steroid extraction from feathers described in Bortolotti et al. (2008). Feather samples were prepared by selecting the most proximal part of the feather, next to the calamus, which was least abraded, and cutting around 3.5 cm from there, taking white feather only. Feather samples were weighed to the nearest mg with an analytical scale (Sartorius). Average mass of feather material per sample was 32.4 mg (SD = 4.24). The vane plus rachis were cut in small pieces (<5 mm) with scissors. We added 6 ml of methanol to the tube with the feather particles, and left the tubes for 30 min in an ultrasound water bath. Then, tubes were capped and left overnight (around 19 hours) in a shaking water bath at 50°C. Samples were decanted in a clean tube and filtered using a nylon plug filter (0.45µ). Tubes were washed with 2 ml of methanol, which was added to the previous extract after a similar filtering. Samples were then placed in a heated tube rack (50°C) under a stream of nitrogen until evaporation (Techne, Germany). Dried extracts were suspended in 150 µl of steroid free buffer and vigorously vortexed for 10 min. Extracted samples were then assayed following kit inserts using a commercial corticosterone ELISAs (DRG, Germany), and optical density measured with a plate spectrophotometer (BioTek, USA).

Bill colour

Oystercatchers have orange bills, and presumably this is due to carotenoids. Carotenoids have been linked to antioxidant and immune status signalling (Perez-Rodriguez, 2009; Simons et al., 2012b; von Schantz et al., 1999) and may therefore be a signal of individuals' phenotypic quality. In male zebra finches, for instance, bill redness reflects recent environmental (Eraud et al., 2007) and immunological challenges (Cote et al., 2009), and has been shown to be positively correlated to immune functioning (Birkhead et al., 2006) and survival and reproduction (Simons et al., 2012a).

Bill colour measurements were performed using digital photography (Panasonic Lumix GX8) from each individuals' right and left side, which has been shown to be a valid method in ecology to study animal coloration (Simons et al., 2012a; Stevens et al., 2007; Villafuerte & Negro, 1998). The colour of an object is greatly influenced by the colour and brightness of the light source used to illuminate it. To minimise variation in light colour and brightness,

photographs were taken in a purpose-built photo-box to ensure standardized light conditions (Supplementary Fig. A22). To further compensate for variations in light source colour and brightness and allow captured colour and brightness information to be standardized in order to compare different pictures from different individuals, the colours white, grey and black were visible from a photo reference card on each picture (Supplementary Fig. A22). This allowed post-production colour and exposure balancing of the images. Camera settings were also standardized for all pictures. We used the program, PixelGrabber (Nienhuis, 2015) (Supplementary Fig. A22) to quantify the colours in a continuous scale of the conventional colour model developed for humans, amenable for statistical analyses. Colour measurements may be defined according to different systems (e.g. Munsell, Lab, HCL) but one of the most widely used is the HCL colour system, which provides independent values of hue, chroma and luminance which are the parameters generally used to define a colour. Hue corresponds to wavelength of light, chroma refers to spectral variance and therefore to colour purity so that the more monochromatic a colour is, the higher its chroma value. Luminance is correlated with physical light intensity and refers to the position on a grey-scale between black and white (Quesada & Senar, 2006).

This gives for each part of the bill measured for each individual three axes of the colour: Hue, Chroma and Luminance, where a higher “hue” indicates a more yellowish colour compared to a more orange colour (Supplementary Fig. A7). Pictures where the measuring points were damaged, dirty or blurry (3%) were excluded from analysis. Correlations of the right and left side of the bill as well as different parts of bill were correlated (Supplementary Table A10), so that we focussed on only one of the several bill measuring points for analysis.

For a random subset ($n=86$) of the total dataset ($n=598$), we repeated the measurement of the bill colour parameters (hue, chroma and luminance) to get an indication of the repeatability of the measurements. Repeatability was calculated by estimating the intra-class correlation coefficients (and its 95% confidence interval) using the variance components from a one-way ANOVA with the R-package ICC (Wolak et al., 2012). The results indicate high repeatability in the measurements (hue: 0.95 (0.92, 0.96); chroma: 0.94 (0.91, 0.96); luminance: 0.95 (0.92, 0.97)).

Survival estimates

We applied a multi-state live and dead recoveries model (MSLD) using RMark (Laake, 2013) with some adjustments to the model as described in Allen et al. (2019). An age effect was included in order to calculate survival estimates for different age classes: juveniles (1 year-

old individuals), sub-adults (2 -and 3-year-old individuals) and adults (being older than 3 years; Supplementary Fig. A23). Separating 2 -and 3-year-old birds in the analysis was not possible because of sample size issues. To improve parameter identifiability, we expanded the sampling period to include all oystercatchers ringed and observed between 2016 and 2019. This enabled estimates of seasonal survival for the different geographical states defined for our study area. We used seasonal (winter to summer) survival estimates, for the sampling period (of condition variables) between 2016 and 2018 (Supplementary Fig. A23) for all analyses. The reason we use over-winter survival estimates is that the condition of the birds was measured in winter. The state (geographical location) of the individual was coded according to one of the nine geographical locations (Supplementary Fig. A1): R = Rottum, S = Schiermonnikoog, T = Terschelling/Ameland, V = Texel/Vlieland, B = Balgzand/Texel, D = Delta, N = Inland North and P = Inland South. A state of A (Abroad) captured all observations outside the Netherlands (Allen et al., 2019a).

Competition

As environmental variable we used the density of oystercatchers in their wintering ground as a proxy for competition. Since 1975, high tide roost counts by volunteers are organized by the Dutch Centre for Field Ornithology (Sovon) in order to count waterbird species in the Dutch Wadden Sea and the Delta area (Hornman et al., 2012). These counts are done on a monthly basis throughout the winter.

We used the counts from the month November and January, since those were most complete for all catching locations. Within a buffer of 7 km-radius around each catching location, we summed the numbers of counted oystercatchers for the month November and January separately, weighted for the counted area, because not the whole buffer area was counted. This resulted in oystercatcher density in number of birds per km² for each month (November and January). Finally, we averaged the two densities to get a proxy of overall winter density. The 7 km-radius buffer was chosen based on information of GPS-tagged oystercatcher movement around several high tide roosts in the Netherlands (Bakker et al., 2021).

Supplementary Codes

The following codes and explanations aim to illustrate and explain the coding while reading the paper. Reproducing the codes with the data is possible with the available R Markdown file (Analyses.Rmd) and data file (data.csv) on Github and can be accessed via

<https://github.com/MagaliFr/QuantifyingBodyConditionWithSEM>.

Abbreviations for the variables in all R-codes:

ratio: ratio of mass divided by tarsus length

MS: mass

TA: tarsus length

TH: head length

WL: wing length

ES: Energy store

BCol: bill colour

LS: bill luminance

CS: bill chroma

HS: bill hue

Comp: composite variable=body condition

LogitSurvWS: Survival

Density: Oystercatcher density (number/km²)

SexN: Sex (numeric variable)

nBH: standardized bill tip height (mean=0, sd=1)

nHT: standardized handling time (mean=0, sd=1)

CortStd: Corticosterone

U_perVolBlood: Uric acid

Cho_perVolBlood: Cholesterol

LogitH: Haematocrit

LogitB: Buffy coat

AgeN: Age (1=sub-adults, 2=adults)

Residuals: Residuals of mass (Mass ~ wing length + tarsus length + head length)

All Statistical analyses in this paper were done in R (version 3.5.1) (R Core Team, 2019).

Libraries used for the following coding:

- lavaan version 0.6-5

- caret version 6.0-80

Operators used in lavaan:

=~ latent variable

<~ composite variable

~~ residual covariance

~ regression

All analysis were based on the co-variances between variables.

Supplementary Code A1: The code shows the code for Fig. 2.2a. The error variance of ratio turns out to be negative (but really close to 0) so that it is acceptable to fix the error variance of the variable ratio to 0. The R-package used for the analysis is lavaan (Rosseel, 2012).

```
lvmod.2 <-'
ES =~ ratio + Residuals # =~ annotation for defining latent variable
Residuals~~0*Residuals
'

lvmod.1.fit<-cfa(lvmod.1,data=f)          #fits the model
summary(lvmod.1.fit, rsq=T, standardized=T) #gives model output

## lavaan 0.6-5 ended normally after 20 iterations
##
## Estimator                      ML
## Optimization method            NLMINB
## Number of free parameters      3
##
## Number of observations         1021
##
## Model Test User Model:
##
## Test statistic                  0.000
## Degrees of freedom             0
##
## Parameter Estimates:
##
## Information                    Expected
## Information saturated (h1) model Structured
## Standard errors                 Standard
##
## Latent Variables:
##      Estimate   Std.Err  z-value  P(>|z|)  Std.lv  Std.all
## ES =~
## ratio      1.000
## Residuals  0.097      0.001   82.169  0.000   0.045   1.000
##
## Variances:
##      Estimate   Std.Err  z-value  P(>|z|)  Std.lv  Std.all
## .Residuals  0.000
## .ratio      0.032      0.001   22.594  0.000   0.032   0.131
## ES          0.211      0.011   19.798  0.000   1.000   1.000
##
## R-Square:
```


Appendix A

```
##          Estimate
## Residuals 1.000
## ratio     0.869

fitMeasures(lvmod.1.fit, c("chisq", "pvalue", "df", "cfi", "srmr", "rmsea", "rmsea.ci.lower", "rmsea.ci.upper"))
#gives model fit indices

##   chisq   pvalue   df    cfi   srmr
##    0     NA      0     1     0
##   rmsea  rmsea.ci.lower rmsea.ci.upper
##    0     0              0
```

Supplementary Code A2: SEM for bill colour analysis (Fig. 2a). The error variance of the variable LS (luminance) turns out to be slightly negative (close to 0) so that it is acceptable to fix the error variance of the variable LS to 0. We conducted a multi-group analysis of age class (group="Age"). Results show the outcome for each age class. The R-package used for the analysis is lavaan (Rosseel, 2012).

```
f$AgeN<-ifelse(f$Age=="Adult",2,1)
lvmod.2 <- '
BCol~LS+HS+CS      #define latent variable BCol=Bill colour
LS~0*LS           #fix error variance of luminance to 0
'

lvmod.2.fit<-cfa(lvmod.2,data=f, group="Age") #fit model
summary(lvmod.2.fit, rsq=T, standardized=T) #model output
## lavaan 0.6-5 ended normally after 66 iterations
##
## Estimator                      ML
## Optimization method            NLMINB
## Number of free parameters      16
##
## Number of observations per group:
##   Adult                        599
##   Sub-Adult                    163
##
## Model Test User Model:
##
## Test statistic                  1141.244
## Degrees of freedom              2
## P-value (Chi-square)           0.000
## Test statistic for each group:
##   Adult                        787.835
##   Sub-Adult                    353.409
##
## Parameter Estimates:
##
## Information                     Expected
## Information saturated (h1) model Structured
## Standard errors                  Standard
##
##
## Group 1 [Adult]:
##
```

```

## Latent Variables:
##      Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
## BCol =~
##   LS      1.000
##   HS      1.456    0.015  94.952  0.000    5.107  0.968
##   CS     -0.387    0.015 -25.357  0.000   -1.357 -0.720
##
## Intercepts:
##      Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
##   .LS      68.892  0.143  480.618  0.000   68.892 19.638
##   .HS      63.320  0.215  293.846  0.000   63.320 12.006
##   .CS      84.494  0.077 1096.179  0.000   84.494 44.789
##   BCol      0.000          0.000    0.000
##
## Variances:
##      Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
##   .LS      0.000
##   .HS      1.733    0.100  17.306  0.000    1.733  0.062
##   .CS      1.716    0.099  17.306  0.000    1.716  0.482
##   BCol     12.307    0.711  17.306  0.000    1.000  1.000
##
## R-Square:
##      Estimate
##   LS      1.000
##   HS      0.938
##   CS      0.518
##
##
## Group 2 [Sub-Adult]:
##
## Latent Variables:
##      Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
## BCol =~
##   LS      1.000
##   HS     -0.055    0.035  -1.550  0.121   -0.468 -0.121
##   CS      1.033    0.029  35.923  0.000    8.820  0.942
##
## Intercepts:
##      Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
##   .LS      53.267  0.668  79.687  0.000   53.267  6.242
##   .HS      65.298  0.304  214.763  0.000   65.298 16.822
##   .CS      67.158  0.733  91.599  0.000   67.158  7.175
##   BCol      0.000
##
## Variances:
##      Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
##   .LS      0.000
##   .HS     14.850  1.645  9.028  0.000  14.850  0.985
##   .CS      9.826  1.088  9.028  0.000  9.826  0.112
##   BCol     72.835  8.068  9.028  0.000  1.000  1.000
##
## R-Square:
##      Estimate
##   LS      1.000

```


Appendix A

```
## HS 0.015
## CS 0.888

fitMeasures(lvmod.2.fit, c("chisq", "pvalue", "df", "cfi", "srmr", "rmsea", "rmsea.ci.lower", "rmsea.ci.upper"))
# model fit indices

##      chisq      pvalue      df      cfi      srmr
## 1141.244    0.000    2.000    0.683    0.061
##      rmsea      rmsea.ci.lower  rmsea.ci.upper
##      1.223      1.164      1.283
```

Supplementary Code A3: Code for the composite variable model (Fig. 2.4). Note that in this example the model fit index (CFI) indicates poor fit. However, remember that this serves as a simple illustration for running a composite variable in SEM and is not yet biologically correct e.g. missing confounding variables. The first variable (determining the composite variable) should always be multiplied by 1 to set the scale (for other variables). We multiplied the first variable “ratio” by -1 because it has a negative effect on the condition. If we multiply it by 1 we get a negative effect of condition on survival which makes interpretation more difficult. The absolute number of the coefficients stay the same (when multiplying by 1 or -1). The R-package used for the analysis is lavaan (Rossee, 2012).

```
# Variable scaling
d1$MSK<-d1$MS/1000
d1$Dens<-d1$Density/1000
d1$TA100<-d1$TA/100
d1$TH100<-d1$TH/100
d1$WL100<-d1$WL/100
d1$Cho10<-d1$Cho_perVolBlood/10

Cmod.1 <- '
# define the composite variable
Comp <- -1*IMS+CortStd+U_perVolBlood+Cho10+LogitH+LogitB
IMS =~ MSK # create latent variable of mass
IMS~WL100+TA100+TH100 # regress structural sizes on latent mass
LogitSurvWS~Comp # regress the composite on survival
Comp~Dens # regress the density on the composite
'

Cmod.1.fit<-sem(Cmod.1,data=d1) # fit the model
summary(Cmod.1.fit, rsq=T, standardized=T) # get the output of the sem
## lavaan 0.6-5 ended normally after 68 iterations
##
## Estimator ML
## Optimization method NLMINB
## Number of free parameters 12
##
## Number of observations 447
##
## Model Test User Model:
##
## Test statistic 77.832
## Degrees of freedom 9
```

```

## P-value (Chi-square)          0.000
##
## Parameter Estimates:
##
## Information                    Expected
## Information saturated (h1) model Structured
## Standard errors                Standard
##
## Latent Variables:
##      Estimate   Std.Err   z-value   P(>|z|)   Std.lv   Std.all
## IMS =~
## MSK           1.000
##
## Composites:
##      Estimate   Std.Err   z-value   P(>|z|)   Std.lv   Std.all
## Comp <~
## IMS          -1.000
## CortStd      -0.028   0.009   -3.160   0.002   -0.412  -0.373
## U_perVolBlood -0.017   0.011   -1.561   0.119   -0.256  -0.185
## Cho10        -0.028   0.033   -0.833   0.405   -0.412  -0.110
## LogitH       0.044   0.077   0.568   0.570   0.654   0.076
## LogitB       0.028   0.027   1.029   0.304   0.420   0.112
##
## Regressions:
##      Estimate   Std.Err   z-value   P(>|z|)   Std.lv   Std.all
## IMS ~
## WL100        0.230   0.032   7.272   0.000   4.610   0.330
## TA100        0.337   0.071   4.770   0.000   6.762   0.213
## TH100        0.117   0.033   3.528   0.000   2.357   0.153
## LogitSurvWS ~
## Comp         2.887   0.410   7.040   0.000   0.193   0.412
## Comp ~
## Dens        -0.553   0.132   -4.183   0.000   -8.246  -0.571
##
## Variances:
##      Estimate   Std.Err   z-value   P(>|z|)   Std.lv   Std.all
## .MSK         0.000
## .LogitSurvWS 0.183   0.012   14.950   0.000   0.183   0.830
## .Comp        0.000
## .IMS         0.002   0.000   14.950   0.000   0.707   0.707
##
## R-Square:
##      Estimate
## MSK         1.000
## LogitSurvWS 0.170
## Comp        1.000
## IMS         0.293

```

Supplementary Code A4: Model from Fig. 2.4 (Supplementary Code A3) with an additional variable (squared residuals=ResidualsSc2) to test for a possible non-linear relationship of mass (corrected for size) on condition. Covariance structure (indicated by operator ~) was defined in the model because for the variable 'residuals' and 'squared residuals' we expect the error terms to be correlated.

Appendix A

```

d1$ResidualsSc<-d1$Residuals/100
d1$ResidualsSc2<-d1$ResidualsSc*d1$ResidualsSc
d1$Cho10<-d1$Cho_perVolBlood/10          # scaled cholesterol

Cmod.2 <- '
Comp <~ -1*ResidualsSc+ResidualsSc2+CortStd+U_perVolBlood+Cho10+LogitH+LogitB
# define the composite variable
LogitSurvWS~Comp                          # regress the composite on survival
Comp~Dens                                  # regress the density on the composite variable
ResidualsSc~~ResidualsSc2
'

Cmod.2.fit<-sem(Cmod.2,data=d1, fixed.x=F)  # fit the model
summary(Cmod.2.fit, rsq=T, standardized=T) # get the output of the sem

## lavaan 0.6-8 ended normally after 140 iterations
##
## Estimator                      ML
## Optimization method            NLMINB
## Number of model parameters     33
##
## Number of observations         447
##
## Model Test User Model:
##
## Test statistic                  77.188
## Degrees of freedom             12
## P-value (Chi-square)           0.000
##
## Parameter Estimates:
##
## Standard errors                Standard
## Information                    Expected
## Information saturated (h1) model Structured
##
## Composites:
##
##           Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
## Comp <~
## ResidualsSc   -1.000
## ResidualsSc2  0.390    0.215  1.818  0.069  0.745  0.197
## CortStd       -0.201    0.070 -2.863  0.004 -0.383 -0.346
## U_perVolBlood -0.121    0.088 -1.375  0.169 -0.230 -0.166
## Cho10         -0.327    0.267 -1.224  0.221 -0.624 -0.166
## LogitH        0.802    0.624  1.285  0.199  1.530  0.178
## LogitB        0.298    0.221  1.347  0.178  0.569  0.152
##
## Regressions:
##           Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
## LogitSurvWS ~
## Comp       0.359    0.051  7.100  0.000  0.188  0.401
## Comp ~
## Dens      -3.675    1.036 -3.549  0.000 -7.014 -0.486
##
## Covariances:
##           Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
## ResidualsSc ~~

```

```

## ResidualsSc2      0.031    0.005  5.693    0.000  0.031  0.280
## CortStd ~~
## U_perVolBlood    0.096    0.031  3.087    0.002  0.096  0.148
## Cho10            0.002    0.011  0.179    0.858  0.002  0.008
## LogitH           0.009    0.005  1.822    0.068  0.009  0.086
## LogitB           0.032    0.012  2.799    0.005  0.032  0.134
## Dens             -0.003    0.003  -1.167   0.243  -0.003 -0.055
## U_perVolBlood ~~
## Cho10            0.013    0.009  1.407    0.159  0.013  0.067
## LogitH           0.025    0.004  5.997    0.000  0.025  0.296
## LogitB           -0.019    0.009  -2.026   0.043  -0.019 -0.096
## Dens             -0.007    0.002  -3.102   0.002  -0.007 -0.148
## Cho10 ~~
## LogitH           0.017    0.002  10.051   0.000  0.017  0.540
## LogitB           -0.004    0.003  -1.227   0.220  -0.004 -0.058
## Dens             0.006    0.001  6.739    0.000  0.006  0.336
## LogitH ~~
## LogitB           -0.000    0.001  -0.329   0.742  -0.000 -0.016
## Dens             0.002    0.000  4.598    0.000  0.002  0.223
## LogitB ~~
## Dens             -0.002    0.001  -2.399   0.016  -0.002 -0.114
##
## Variances:
##               Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
## .LogitSurvWS    0.185    0.012  14.950  0.000  0.185  0.839
## ResidualsSc    0.175    0.012  14.950  0.000  0.175  1.000
## ResidualsSc2   0.070    0.005  14.950  0.000  0.070  1.000
## .Comp           0.000
## CortStd         0.818    0.055  14.950  0.000  0.818  1.000
## U_perVolBlood   0.519    0.035  14.950  0.000  0.519  1.000
## Cho10           0.071    0.005  14.950  0.000  0.071  1.000
## LogitH          0.014    0.001  14.950  0.000  0.014  1.000
## LogitB          0.071    0.005  14.950  0.000  0.071  1.000
## Dens            0.005    0.000  14.950  0.000  0.005  1.000
##
## R-Square:
##               Estimate
## LogitSurvWS    0.161
## Comp           1.000

```

Supplementary Code A5: R-code of the final model (Fig. 2.5) including latent variables (bill colour and energy reserve) and a composite variable (body condition). See Supplementary Code A3 for explanation of the -1 in front of ES (composite variable). Covariance structure (indicated by operator `~~`) was defined in the model because it is expected that the error term cholesterol and haematocrit are correlated. Cholesterol is determined in mmol/l blood which means that is related to the proportion of haematocrit in the blood. The R-package used for the analysis is *lavaan* (Rosseel, 2012).

```

# scaling of the variables
f$CortStd10<-f$CortStd/10
f$nBH10<-f$nBH/10
f$MSK<-f$MS/1000

```


Appendix A

```
f$LS<-f$LS/100
f$CS<-f$CS/100
f$HS<-f$HS/100
f$Density<-f$Density/100
f$TA<-f$TA/100
f$TH<-f$TH/100
f$WL<-f$WL/100
f$Cho_perVolBlood<-f$Cho_perVolBlood/10
f$nHT10<-f$nHT/10

# Bill colour
Cmod.3 <- '
BCol =~ HS          # latent variable bill colour

# Energy store
ES =~ IMS+ratio     # latent variable energy store
IMS =~ MSK          # latent variable mass
IMS ~ TA + TH +WL   # structural sizes regressed on mass
IMS~~0*IMS          # error variance=0

# cond variables: regress confounding and individual variables on the different condition measures
ICho =~ Cho_perVolBlood # latent variable cholesterol
IH =~ LogitH           # latent variable haematocrit
IB =~ LogitB           # latent variable buffy coat
IU =~ U_perVolBlood   # latent variable uric acid
ICort =~ CortStd10    # latent variable corticosterone
IB + IH + ICho + ES + IU ~ AgeN+SexN+nBH10+nHT10 # regress confounding variables on the latent variable
ICort + BCol ~ AgeN+SexN+nBH10 # same here (but other set of confounding variables)

# composite variable
Comp <~ -1*ES+ICort+BCol+IH+IB+ICho+IU # define the composite variable with the condition variables
LogitSurvWS ~ Comp # regress composite on survival
Comp ~ Density # regress density on composite

# add covariance structure
ICho~~IH
IU~~IH
'

Cmod.3.fit<-sem(Cmod.3,data=f) # fit the model
summary(Cmod.3.fit, rsq=T, standardized=T) # get model output

## lavaan 0.6-8 ended normally after 211 iterations
##
## Estimator ML
## Optimization method NLMINB
## Number of model parameters 49
##
## Number of observations 427
##
## Model Test User Model:
##
## Test statistic 363.725
## Degrees of freedom 68
## P-value (Chi-square) 0.000
```

```

##
## Parameter Estimates:
##
## Standard errors          Standard
## Information              Expected
## Information saturated (h1) model  Structured
##
## Latent Variables:
##      Estimate   Std.Err  z-value  P(>|z|)  Std.lv  Std.all
## BCol =~
## HS              1.000
## ES =~
## IMS             1.000
## ratio           10.313    0.016   637.548  0.000    0.476   0.999
## IMS =~
## MSK             1.000
## ICho =~
## Cho_perVolBlod  1.000
## IH =~
## LogitH          1.000
## IB =~
## LogitB          1.000
## IU =~
## U_perVolBlood   1.000
## ICort =~
## CortStd10       1.000
##
## Composites:
##      Estimate   Std.Err  z-value  P(>|z|)  Std.lv  Std.all
## Comp <~
## ES              -1.000
## ICort           -0.229    0.071   -3.234   0.001   -0.376  -0.376
## BCol            0.121    0.135    0.902   0.367    0.097   0.097
## IH              0.050    0.069    0.718   0.473    0.094   0.094
## IB              0.013    0.024    0.543   0.587    0.059   0.059
## ICho            -0.027    0.030   -0.921   0.357   -0.118  -0.118
## IU              -0.013    0.010   -1.367   0.172   -0.156  -0.156
##
## Regressions:
##      Estimate   Std.Err  z-value  P(>|z|)  Std.lv  Std.all
## IMS ~
## TA              0.577    0.003   225.302  0.000   11.610   0.363
## TH              -0.000    0.001   -0.340   0.734   -0.008  -0.001
## WL              -0.001    0.001   -0.499   0.618   -0.011  -0.001
## IB ~
## AgeN            -0.182    0.031   -5.907   0.000   -0.673  -0.276
## SexN             0.016    0.031    0.532   0.595    0.061   0.030
## nBH10           0.282    0.150    1.876   0.061    1.043   0.104
## nHT10           -0.219    0.128   -1.712   0.087   -0.811  -0.081
## IH ~
## AgeN            -0.051    0.014   -3.764   0.000   -0.441  -0.181
## SexN            -0.005    0.014   -0.369   0.712   -0.043  -0.021
## nBH10           -0.089    0.066   -1.343   0.179   -0.768  -0.077
## nHT10           -0.038    0.056   -0.672   0.502   -0.327  -0.033
## ICho ~

```


Appendix A

##	AgeN	0.052	0.031	1.689	0.091	0.198	0.081
##	SexN	-0.034	0.030	-1.131	0.258	-0.132	-0.065
##	nBH10	0.188	0.149	1.264	0.206	0.722	0.072
##	nHT10	0.468	0.127	3.690	0.000	1.795	0.179
##	ES ~						
##	AgeN	0.028	0.005	5.320	0.000	0.600	0.246
##	SexN	-0.014	0.005	-2.761	0.006	-0.311	-0.152
##	nBH10	0.009	0.025	0.373	0.709	0.205	0.020
##	nHT10	-0.079	0.022	-3.647	0.000	-1.708	-0.171
##	IU ~						
##	AgeN	-0.051	0.084	-0.600	0.549	-0.071	-0.029
##	SexN	-0.119	0.084	-1.420	0.156	-0.167	-0.082
##	nBH10	-0.437	0.411	-1.063	0.288	-0.612	-0.061
##	nHT10	-0.742	0.350	-2.120	0.034	-1.040	-0.104
##	lCort ~						
##	AgeN	-0.049	0.011	-4.276	0.000	-0.493	-0.202
##	SexN	0.008	0.011	0.674	0.500	0.077	0.038
##	nBH10	0.098	0.056	1.749	0.080	0.981	0.098
##	BCol ~						
##	AgeN	-0.026	0.005	-4.728	0.000	-0.530	-0.217
##	SexN	-0.025	0.005	-4.528	0.000	-0.504	-0.247
##	nBH10	0.108	0.027	4.064	0.000	2.218	0.222
##	LogitSurvWS ~						
##	Comp	3.222	0.453	7.119	0.000	0.196	0.415
##	Comp ~						
##	Density	-0.046	0.011	-4.100	0.000	-0.757	-0.526
##							
##	Covariances:						
##		Estimate	Std.Err	z-value	P(> z)	Std.lv	Std.all
##	.lCho ~						
##	.lH	0.016	0.002	10.329	0.000	0.561	0.561
##	.lH ~						
##	.lU	0.019	0.003	5.575	0.000	0.232	0.232
##							
##	Variances:						
##		Estimate	Std.Err	z-value	P(> z)	Std.lv	Std.all
##	.lMS	0.000				0.000	0.000
##	.lHS	0.000				0.000	0.000
##	.lratio	0.000	0.000	14.612	0.000	0.000	0.001
##	.lMSK	0.000				0.000	0.000
##	.lCho_perVolBlod	0.000				0.000	0.000
##	.lLogitH	0.000				0.000	0.000
##	.lLogitB	0.000				0.000	0.000
##	.lU_perVolBlood	0.000				0.000	0.000
##	.lCortStd10	0.000				0.000	0.000
##	.lLogitSurvWS	0.184	0.013	14.612	0.000	0.184	0.828
##	.lBCol	0.002	0.000	14.612	0.000	0.893	0.893
##	.lES	0.002	0.000	14.612	0.000	0.887	0.887
##	.lCho	0.065	0.004	14.612	0.000	0.958	0.958
##	.lH	0.013	0.001	14.866	0.000	0.961	0.961
##	.lB	0.066	0.005	14.612	0.000	0.907	0.907
##	.lU	0.496	0.034	14.612	0.000	0.974	0.974
##	.lCort	0.009	0.001	14.612	0.000	0.943	0.943
##	.lComp	0.000				0.000	0.000
##							

```
## R-Square:
##           Estimate
##  IMS           1.000
##   HS           1.000
##  ratio         0.999
##  MSK           1.000
## Cho_perVolBlod 1.000
##  LogitH        1.000
##  LogitB        1.000
## U_perVolBlood  1.000
## CortStd10     1.000
## LogitSurvWS   0.172
##  BCol         0.107
##   ES          0.113
##  ICho         0.042
##   IH          0.039
##   IB          0.093
##   IU          0.026
##  ICort        0.057
##  Comp        1.000

fitMeasures(Cmod.3.fit, c("chisq", "pvalue", "df", "cfi", "srmr", "rmsea", "rmsea.ci.lower", "rmsea.ci.upper"))
# get model fit indices

##      chisq      pvalue      df      cfi      srmr
##      363.725    0.000    68.000    0.922    0.077
##      rmsea    rmsea.ci.lower  rmsea.ci.upper
##      0.101    0.091          0.111
```

Supplementary Code A6: The full model (Fig. 2.5) with only one size structure (tarsus length) and an added direct effect of body size on survival. For model results in a figure see Supplementary Fig. A13. The R-package used for the analysis is lavaan (Rosseel, 2012).

```
Cmod.4 <- '
BCol =~ HS # latent variable bill colour

ES =~ MSK+ratio # latent variable energy store
MSK ~ TA # regress tarsus length on mass
MSK~~0*MSK # 0 error variance for mass

#condition variables
ICho =~ Cho_perVolBlood # latent cholesterol
IH =~ LogitH # latent haematocrit
IB =~ LogitB # latent buffy coat
IU =~ U_perVolBlood # latent uric acid
ICort =~ CortStd10 # latent corticosterone
IB + IH + ICho + ES + IU ~ AgeN+SexN+nBH10+nHT10 # regress confounding variables on latent variables
ICort + BCol ~ AgeN+SexN+nBH10 # same but with different set of variables

#composite
Comp <~ -1*ES+ICort+BCol+IH+IB+ICho+IU # composite variable
LogitSurvWS ~ Comp +TA # regress tarsus length and composite density on survival
Comp ~ Density # regress density on composite
```


Appendix A

```

#add covariance structure
ICho~~IH
IU~~IH
'

Cmod.4.fit<-sem(Cmod.4,data=f)
summary(Cmod.4.fit, standardized=T, rsq=T)

## lavaan 0.6-5 ended normally after 170 iterations
##
## Estimator                      ML
## Optimization method            NLMINB
## Number of free parameters      48
##
## Number of observations          427
##
## Model Test User Model:
##
## Test statistic                  276.972
## Degrees of freedom              51
## P-value (Chi-square)           0.000
##
## Parameter Estimates:
##
## Information                     Expected
## Information saturated (h1) model Structured
## Standard errors                  Standard
##
## Latent Variables:
##      Estimate   Std.Err  z-value  P(>|z|)  Std.lv  Std.all
## BCol =~
## HS              1.000              0.049  1.000
## ES =~
## MSK             1.000              0.046  0.928
## ratio          10.317    0.016  645.740  0.000  0.476  0.999
## ICho =~
## Cho_perVolBlod  1.000              0.261  1.000
## IH =~
## LogitH          1.000              0.116  1.000
## IB =~
## LogitB          1.000              0.270  1.000
## IU =~
## U_perVolBlood   1.000              0.714  1.000
## ICort =~
## CortStd10       1.000              0.100  1.000
##
## Composites:
##      Estimate   Std.Err  z-value  P(>|z|)  Std.lv  Std.all
## Comp <~
## ES              -1.000    -0.755  -0.755
## ICort           -0.228    0.071  -3.188  0.001  -0.372  -0.372
## BCol            0.130    0.136   0.957  0.339   0.104   0.104
## IH              0.043    0.070   0.620  0.535   0.082   0.082
## IB              0.014    0.024   0.562  0.574   0.061   0.061
## ICho           -0.027    0.030  -0.894  0.371  -0.115  -0.115
## IU             -0.014    0.010  -1.429  0.153  -0.164  -0.164

```

```

##
## Regressions:
##
## MSK ~
## TA      0.576    0.002   252.687  0.000    0.576    0.363
## IB ~
## AgeN   -0.182    0.031   -5.907   0.000   -0.673   -0.276
## SexN    0.016    0.031    0.532   0.595    0.061    0.030
## nBH10   0.282    0.150    1.876   0.061    1.043    0.104
## nHT10  -0.219    0.128   -1.712   0.087   -0.811   -0.081
## IH ~
## AgeN   -0.051    0.014   -3.764   0.000   -0.441   -0.181
## SexN   -0.005    0.014   -0.370   0.712   -0.043   -0.021
## nBH10  -0.089    0.066   -1.343   0.179   -0.768   -0.077
## nHT10  -0.038    0.056   -0.672   0.502   -0.327   -0.033
## ICho ~
## AgeN    0.052    0.031    1.689   0.091    0.198    0.081
## SexN   -0.034    0.030   -1.131   0.258   -0.132   -0.065
## nBH10   0.188    0.149    1.264   0.206    0.722    0.072
## nHT10   0.468    0.127    3.690   0.000    1.795    0.179
## ES ~
## AgeN    0.028    0.005    5.313   0.000    0.599    0.245
## SexN   -0.014    0.005   -2.752   0.006   -0.310   -0.151
## nBH10   0.009    0.025    0.373   0.709    0.205    0.020
## nHT10  -0.079    0.022   -3.648   0.000   -1.708   -0.171
## IU ~
## AgeN   -0.051    0.084   -0.600   0.549   -0.071   -0.029
## SexN   -0.119    0.084   -1.420   0.156   -0.167   -0.082
## nBH10  -0.437    0.411   -1.063   0.288   -0.612   -0.061
## nHT10  -0.742    0.350   -2.120   0.034   -1.040   -0.104
## ICort ~
## AgeN   -0.049    0.011   -4.276   0.000   -0.493   -0.202
## SexN    0.008    0.011    0.674   0.500    0.077    0.038
## nBH10   0.098    0.056    1.749   0.080    0.981    0.098
## BCol ~
## AgeN   -0.026    0.005   -4.728   0.000   -0.530   -0.217
## SexN   -0.025    0.005   -4.528   0.000   -0.504   -0.247
## nBH10   0.108    0.027    4.064   0.000    2.218    0.222
## LogitSurvWS ~
## Comp    3.185    0.452    7.040   0.000    0.194    0.413
## TA     -0.552    0.664   -0.832   0.406   -0.552   -0.037
## Comp ~
## Density -0.047    0.011   -4.095   0.000   -0.764   -0.531
##
## Covariances:
##
## .ICho ~
## .IH      0.016    0.002   10.329   0.000    0.561    0.561
## .IH ~
## .IU      0.019    0.003    5.575   0.000    0.232    0.232
##
## Variances:
##
## .MSK     0.000
## .HS      0.000

```


Appendix A

```
## .ratio      0.000    0.000   14.612    0.000    0.000    0.001
## .Cho_perVolBlod 0.000
## .LogitH      0.000
## .LogitB      0.000
## .U_perVolBlood 0.000
## .CortStd10   0.000
## .LogitSurvWS 0.183    0.013   14.612    0.000    0.183    0.828
## .BCol        0.002    0.000   14.612    0.000    0.893    0.893
## .ES          0.002    0.000   14.612    0.000    0.888    0.888
## .ICho        0.065    0.004   14.612    0.000    0.958    0.958
## .IH          0.013    0.001   14.866    0.000    0.961    0.961
## .IB          0.066    0.005   14.612    0.000    0.907    0.907
## .IU          0.496    0.034   14.612    0.000    0.974    0.974
## .ICort       0.009    0.001   14.612    0.000    0.943    0.943
## .Comp        0.000
##
```

R-Square:

```
## Estimate
## MSK          1.000
## HS           1.000
## ratio        0.999
## Cho_perVolBlod 1.000
## LogitH       1.000
## LogitB       1.000
## U_perVolBlood 1.000
## CortStd10    1.000
## LogitSurvWS  0.172
## BCol         0.107
## ES           0.112
## ICho         0.042
## IH           0.039
## IB           0.093
## IU           0.026
## ICort        0.057
## Comp         1.000
```

```
fitMeasures(Cmod.4.fit,c("chisq", "pvalue", "df", "cfi", "nfi", "srmr", "rmsea", "rmsea.ci.lower", "rmsea.ci.upper",
"AIC", "rmsea.pvalue"))
```

```
## chisq      pvalue      df      cfi      nfi
## 276.972    0.000     51.000    0.939    0.927
## srmr      rmsea      rmsea.ci.lower  rmsea.ci.upper  aic
## 0.079     0.102     0.090     0.114     -5278.346
## rmsea.pvalue
## 0.000
```

Supplementary Code A7: The full model (Fig. 2.5) with only one size structure (tarsus length) and only an indirect effect of body size on survival. For model results in a figure see Supplementary Fig. A13. The R-package used for the analysis is lavaan.

```
Cmod.5 <- '
BCol =~ HS

ES =~ MSK+ratio
```

```

MSK ~ TA
MSK~~0*MSK

#cond variables: regress confounding and individual variables on the different condition measures
ICho =~ Cho_perVolBlood
IH =~ LogitH
IB =~ LogitB
IU =~ U_perVolBlood
ICort =~ CortStd10
IB + IH + ICho + ES + IU ~ AgeN+SexN+nBH10+nHT10
ICort + BCol ~ AgeN+SexN+nBH10

#composite
Comp <~ -1*ES+ICort+BCol+IH+IB+ICho+IU #define the composite variable with the condition variables
LogitSurvWS ~ Comp
Comp~ Density

#add covariance structure
ICho~~IH
IU~~IH
'

Cmod.5.fit<-sem(Cmod.5,data=f)
summary(Cmod.5.fit, standardized=T, rsq=T)

## lavaan 0.6-8 ended normally after 163 iterations
##
## Estimator                      ML
## Optimization method            NLMINB
## Number of model parameters     47
##
## Number of observations         427
##
## Model Test User Model:
##
## Test statistic                  277.638
## Degrees of freedom             52
## P-value (Chi-square)           0.000
##
## Parameter Estimates:
##
## Standard errors                Standard
## Information                    Expected
## Information saturated (h1) model Structured
##
## Latent Variables:
##
##          Estimate  Std.Err  z-value  P(>|z|)  Std.lv  Std.all
## BCol =~
## HS              1.000
## ES =~
## MSK              1.000
## ratio           10.317   0.016  645.740  0.000   0.476  0.999
## ICho =~
## Cho_perVolBlod  1.000
## IH =~
## LogitH          1.000

```


Appendix A

```

## IB =~
## LogitB          1.000                      0.270  1.000
## IU =~
## U_perVolBlood  1.000                      0.714  1.000
## ICort =~
## CortStd10      1.000                      0.100  1.000
##
## Composites:
##              Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
## Comp <~
## ES          -1.000
## ICort       -0.229    0.071  -3.233   0.001  -0.376 -0.376
## BCol        0.121    0.135   0.901   0.368   0.097  0.097
## IH          0.050    0.069   0.719   0.472   0.095  0.095
## IB          0.013    0.024   0.544   0.586   0.059  0.059
## ICho       -0.027    0.030  -0.922   0.356  -0.118 -0.118
## IU         -0.013    0.010  -1.367   0.172  -0.156 -0.156
##
## Regressions:
##              Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
## MSK ~
## TA          0.576    0.002  252.694  0.000   0.576  0.363
## IB ~
## AgeN       -0.182    0.031  -5.907   0.000  -0.673 -0.276
## SexN        0.016    0.031   0.532   0.595   0.061  0.030
## nBH10       0.282    0.150   1.876   0.061   1.043  0.104
## nHT10      -0.219    0.128  -1.712   0.087  -0.811 -0.081
## IH ~
## AgeN       -0.051    0.014  -3.764   0.000  -0.441 -0.181
## SexN       -0.005    0.014  -0.370   0.712  -0.043 -0.021
## nBH10      -0.089    0.066  -1.343   0.179  -0.768 -0.077
## nHT10      -0.038    0.056  -0.672   0.502  -0.327 -0.033
## ICho ~
## AgeN        0.052    0.031   1.689   0.091   0.198  0.081
## SexN       -0.034    0.030  -1.131   0.258  -0.132 -0.065
## nBH10       0.188    0.149   1.265   0.206   0.722  0.072
## nHT10       0.468    0.127   3.690   0.000   1.795  0.179
## ES ~
## AgeN        0.028    0.005   5.313   0.000   0.599  0.245
## SexN       -0.014    0.005  -2.752   0.006  -0.310 -0.151
## nBH10       0.009    0.025   0.373   0.709   0.205  0.020
## nHT10      -0.079    0.022  -3.648   0.000  -1.708 -0.171
## IU ~
## AgeN       -0.051    0.084  -0.600   0.549  -0.071 -0.029
## SexN       -0.119    0.084  -1.420   0.156  -0.167 -0.082
## nBH10      -0.437    0.411  -1.063   0.288  -0.612 -0.061
## nHT10      -0.742    0.350  -2.120   0.034  -1.040 -0.104
## ICort ~
## AgeN       -0.049    0.011  -4.276   0.000  -0.493 -0.202
## SexN        0.008    0.011   0.674   0.500   0.077  0.038
## nBH10       0.098    0.056   1.749   0.080   0.981  0.098
## BCol ~
## AgeN       -0.026    0.005  -4.728   0.000  -0.530 -0.217
## SexN       -0.025    0.005  -4.528   0.000  -0.504 -0.247
## nBH10       0.108    0.027   4.064   0.000   2.218  0.222

```

```

## LogitSurvWS ~
## Comp      3.224    0.453  7.120    0.000    0.196  0.415
## Comp ~
## Density   -0.046    0.011 -4.099    0.000   -0.756 -0.526
##
## Covariances:
##           Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
## .lCho ~
## .lH      0.016    0.002  10.329  0.000    0.561  0.561
## .lH ~
## .lU      0.019    0.003  5.575   0.000    0.232  0.232
##
## Variances:
##           Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
## .MSK     0.000
## .HS      0.000
## .ratio   0.000    0.000  14.612  0.000    0.000  0.001
## .Cho_perVolBlod 0.000
## .LogitH  0.000
## .LogitB  0.000
## .U_perVolBlood 0.000
## .CortStd10 0.000
## .LogitSurvWS 0.184    0.013  14.612  0.000    0.184  0.828
## .BCol    0.002    0.000  14.612  0.000    0.893  0.893
## .ES      0.002    0.000  14.612  0.000    0.888  0.888
## .lCho    0.065    0.004  14.612  0.000    0.958  0.958
## .lH      0.013    0.001  14.866  0.000    0.961  0.961
## .lB      0.066    0.005  14.612  0.000    0.907  0.907
## .lU      0.496    0.034  14.612  0.000    0.974  0.974
## .lCort   0.009    0.001  14.612  0.000    0.943  0.943
## .Comp    0.000
##
## R-Square:
##           Estimate
## MSK      1.000
## HS       1.000
## ratio    0.999
## Cho_perVolBlod 1.000
## LogitH   1.000
## LogitB   1.000
## U_perVolBlood 1.000
## CortStd10 1.000
## LogitSurvWS 0.172
## BCol     0.107
## ES       0.112
## lCho     0.042
## lH       0.039
## lB       0.093
## lU       0.026
## lCort    0.057
## Comp     1.000

```

```

fitMeasures(Cmod.5.fit,
c("chisq", "pvalue", "df", "cfi", "nfi", "srmr", "rmsea", "rmsea.ci.lower",
"rmsea.ci.upper", "AIC", "rmsea.pvalue"))

```


Appendix A

```
##      chisq      pvalue    df          cfi          nfi
##      277.638      0.000    52.000      0.939      0.927
##      srmr       rmsea    rmsea.ci.lower  rmsea.ci.upper  aic
##      0.079      0.101    0.089      0.113      -5279.679
##      rmsea.pvalue
##      0.000
```

Supplementary Code A8: R-code and output for the SEM model used to compare the model performance for the SEM and conventional approach.

```
lvmod.6 <- '
#Bill colour
BCol =~ HS

#Energy store
ES =~ IMS+ratio
IMS =~ MSK
IMS ~ TA + TH +WL
IMS~~0*IMS

#condition variables
ICho =~ Cho_perVolBlood
IH =~ LogitH
IB =~ LogitB
IU =~ U_perVolBlood
ICort =~ CortStd10
IB + IH + ICho + ES + IU ~ AgeN+SexN+nBH10+nHT10
ICort + BCol ~ AgeN+SexN+nBH10

#composite
Comp <~ -1*ES+ICort+BCol+IH+IB+ICho+IU
LogitSurvWS ~ Comp

#add covariance structure
ICho~~IH
IU~~IH
'

lvmod.6.fit<-sem(lvmod.6,data=f)
summary(lvmod.6.fit, rsq=T, standardized=T)      #get model output

## lavaan 0.6-5 ended normally after 188 iterations
##
## Estimator                      ML
## Optimization method            NLMINB
## Number of free parameters       48
##
## Number of observations          427
##
## Model Test User Model:
##
## Test statistic                   246.143
## Degrees of freedom              60
## P-value (Chi-square)            0.000
##
```

```

## Parameter Estimates:
##
## Information                               Expected
## Information saturated (h1) model          Structured
## Standard errors                           Standard
##
## Latent Variables:
##
##      Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
## BCol =~
## HS      1.000
##      0.049 1.000
## ES =~
## IMS     1.000
## ratio  10.313 0.016 637.546 0.000 0.476 0.999
## IMS =~
## MSK     1.000
##      0.050 1.000
## ICho =~
## Cho_perVolBlod 1.000
##      0.261 1.000
## IH =~
## LogitH  1.000
##      0.116 1.000
## IB =~
## LogitB  1.000
##      0.270 1.000
## IU =~
## U_perVolBlood 1.000
##      0.714 1.000
## ICort =~
## CortStd10 1.000
##      0.100 1.000
##
## Composites:
##
##      Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
## Comp <~
## ES     -1.000
## ICort  -0.219 0.066 -3.299 0.001 -0.413 -0.413
## BCol   0.171 0.128 1.327 0.184 0.157 0.157
## IH     0.012 0.065 0.187 0.852 0.027 0.027
## IB     0.024 0.023 1.028 0.304 0.121 0.121
## ICho  -0.053 0.029 -1.842 0.065 -0.261 -0.261
## IU    -0.002 0.009 -0.274 0.784 -0.033 -0.033
##
## Regressions:
##
##      Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
## IMS ~
## TA     0.577 0.003 225.299 0.000 11.610 0.363
## TH    -0.000 0.001 -0.333 0.739 -0.008 -0.001
## WL    -0.001 0.001 -0.492 0.623 -0.011 -0.001
## IB ~
## AgeN  -0.182 0.031 -5.907 0.000 -0.673 -0.276
## SexN   0.016 0.031 0.532 0.595 0.061 0.030
## nBH10 0.282 0.150 1.876 0.061 1.043 0.104
## nHT10 -0.219 0.128 -1.712 0.087 -0.811 -0.081
## IH ~
## AgeN  -0.051 0.014 -3.764 0.000 -0.441 -0.181
## SexN  -0.005 0.014 -0.370 0.712 -0.043 -0.021
## nBH10 -0.089 0.066 -1.343 0.179 -0.768 -0.077
## nHT10 -0.038 0.056 -0.672 0.502 -0.327 -0.033
## ICho ~
## AgeN   0.052 0.031 1.689 0.091 0.198 0.081

```


Appendix A

```

## SexN      -0.034    0.030  -1.131    0.258   -0.132  -0.065
## nBH10     0.188    0.149   1.265    0.206    0.722   0.072
## nHT10     0.468    0.127   3.690    0.000    1.795   0.179
## ES ~
## AgeN      0.028    0.005   5.320    0.000    0.600   0.246
## SexN     -0.014    0.005  -2.761    0.006   -0.311  -0.152
## nBH10     0.009    0.025   0.373    0.709    0.205   0.020
## nHT10    -0.079    0.022  -3.647    0.000   -1.708  -0.171
## IU ~
## AgeN     -0.051    0.084  -0.600    0.549   -0.071  -0.029
## SexN     -0.119    0.084  -1.420    0.156   -0.167  -0.082
## nBH10    -0.437    0.411  -1.063    0.288   -0.612  -0.061
## nHT10    -0.742    0.350  -2.120    0.034   -1.040  -0.104
## lCort ~
## AgeN     -0.049    0.011  -4.276    0.000   -0.493  -0.202
## SexN      0.008    0.011   0.674    0.500    0.077   0.038
## nBH10     0.098    0.056   1.749    0.080    0.981   0.098
## BCol ~
## AgeN     -0.026    0.005  -4.728    0.000   -0.530  -0.217
## SexN     -0.025    0.005  -4.528    0.000   -0.504  -0.247
## nBH10     0.108    0.027   4.064    0.000    2.218   0.222
## LogitSurvWS ~
## Comp      3.489    0.463   7.536    0.000    0.184   0.388
##
## Covariances:
##           Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
## .lCho ~
## .lH      0.016    0.002  10.329  0.000    0.561   0.561
## .lH ~
## .lU      0.019    0.003   5.575  0.000    0.232   0.232
##
## Variances:
##           Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
## .IMS      0.000    0.000    0.000  0.000    0.000   0.000
## .HS       0.000    0.000    0.000  0.000    0.000   0.000
## .ratio    0.000    0.000  14.612  0.000    0.000   0.001
## .MSK      0.000    0.000    0.000  0.000    0.000   0.000
## .Cho_perVolBlod 0.000    0.000    0.000  0.000    0.000   0.000
## .LogitH   0.000    0.000    0.000  0.000    0.000   0.000
## .LogitB   0.000    0.000    0.000  0.000    0.000   0.000
## .U_perVolBlood 0.000    0.000    0.000  0.000    0.000   0.000
## .CortStd10 0.000    0.000    0.000  0.000    0.000   0.000
## .LogitSurvWS 0.192    0.013  14.612  0.000    0.192   0.850
## .BCol     0.002    0.000  14.612  0.000    0.893   0.893
## .ES       0.002    0.000  14.612  0.000    0.887   0.887
## .lCho     0.065    0.004  14.612  0.000    0.958   0.958
## .lH       0.013    0.001  14.866  0.000    0.961   0.961
## .lB       0.066    0.005  14.612  0.000    0.907   0.907
## .lU       0.496    0.034  14.612  0.000    0.974   0.974
## .lCort    0.009    0.001  14.612  0.000    0.943   0.943
## Comp      0.000    0.000    0.000  0.000    0.000   0.000
##
## R-Square:
##           Estimate
## IMS      1.000

```

```

## HS          1.000
## ratio       0.999
## MSK         1.000
## Cho_perVolBlod 1.000
## LogitH      1.000
## LogitB      1.000
## U_perVolBlood 1.000
## CortStd10   1.000
## LogitSurvWS 0.150
## BCol        0.107
## ES          0.113
## ICho        0.042
## IH          0.039
## IB          0.093
## IU          0.026
## ICort       0.057

fitMeasures(lvmod.6.fit, c("chisq", "pvalue", "df", "cfi", "srmr", "rmsea", "rmsea.ci.lower", "rmsea.ci.upper")) #get
model fit indices

##      chisq      pvalue      df      cfi      srmr
##      246.143  0.000      60.000    0.949  0.066
##      rmsea      rmsea.ci.lower  rmsea.ci.upper
##      0.085      0.074          0.096

```

Supplementary Code A9: R-code and output of the cross validation for the SEM approach (Fig. 2.6a) and the conventional (regression & PCA) approach (Fig. 2.6b) conducted with the R-package caret (Kuhn et al., 2018). method=repeatedcv means repeated cross validation, using 10 non-overlapping folds (groups; number=10). For each fold/group the dataset is split in training ($p=0.8$) and test dataset (being 80% training data and 20% test data). This process is repeated 3 times, meaning that 30 different sets/fits are used to estimate the performance.

```

#SEM approach (Fig. 2.6a)
set.seed(121)
train.control <- trainControl(method = "repeatedcv", number = 10, repeats = 3, p=.8)
SEMmodel <- train(LogitSurvWS~Comp, data = d, method = "lm", trControl = train.control)
print(SEMmodel)
## Linear Regression
##
## 427 samples
## 1 predictor
##
## No pre-processing
## Resampling: Cross-Validated (10 fold, repeated 3 times)
## Summary of sample sizes: 384, 384, 385, 384, 384, 384, ...
## Resampling results:
##
## RMSE      Rsquared    MAE
## 0.4383024  0.1769444  0.3340294

```


Appendix A

```
##
## Tuning parameter 'intercept' was held constant at a value of TRUE

#Conventional approach (PCA&MR; Fig. 2.6b)
set.seed(125)
train.control <- trainControl(method = "repeatedcv", number = 10, repeats = 3, p=.8)
PCAmodel <- train(LogitSurvWS~predict, data = d, method = "lm", trControl = train.control)
#“predict” is the predicted value of survival from the MR&PCA approach (Fig. 6b)
print(PCAmodel)

## Linear Regression
##
## 427 samples
## 1 predictor
##
## No pre-processing
## Resampling: Cross-Validated (10 fold, repeated 3 times)
## Summary of sample sizes: 383, 385, 384, 383, 385, 384, ...
## Resampling results:
##
## RMSE      Rsquared    MAE
## 0.4420557  0.1625398  0.3323978
##
## Tuning parameter 'intercept' was held constant at a value of TRUE

## RMSE of this (conventional approach) is higher than in the SEM and R2 is lower, indicating lower
## model performance. Also the MAE, the mean absolute error is lower in SEM, indicating better
## performance. MAE expresses similar to the RMSE the average model prediction error. However, since
## in RMSE the errors are squared before they are averaged, the RMSE gives a relatively high weight to
## large errors.
```

Supplementary Code A10: Example r-code to account for a measurement error (in a regression analysis; mass as response variable and three structural size measures as independent variables) by using latent variables in SEM. We assume a measurement repeatability (intra-class correlation coefficient) of 0.3 of the structural size measures TA, TH and WL meaning that the measurement error is 0.7. We add three latent variables ITA, ITH, IWL to the model. Instead of regressing the structural size measures directly on mass, we regress the latent variables of the structural size measures on mass (ITA, IWL, ITH). See Supplementary Fig. A25 for a schematic illustration of the model. By adding the latent variables to the model, we can distinguish between the error variance due to unexplained variation and due to measurement error. In the output of this model, we find the unexplained variation for each structural size variable (without any influence of measurement error). The R-package used for the analysis is lavaan (Rosseel, 2012). See chapter 4 in Grace (2006) for more information about accounting for measurement errors in SEM.

```
lvmod.3 <- '
ITA=~TA      # define the latent variable ITA
```

```

IWL=~WL      # define the latent variable IWL
ITH=~TH      # define the latent variable ITH
TA~~0.7*TA   # add error variance on TA
TH~~0.7*TH   # add error variance on TH
WL~~0.7*WL   # add error variance on WL
MS~ITA+ITH+IWL # regress the three latent variables on mass
'

lvmod.3.fit<-sem(lvmod.3,data=M2)      # fit the model; for reproducing the code see the R Markdown file
# (Analysis.Rmd) with the data file (data.csv)
summary(lvmod.3.fit, rsq=T, standardized=T) # get model output

## lavaan 0.6-5 ended normally after 62 iterations
##
## Estimator                      ML
## Optimization method            NLMINB
## Number of free parameters      10
##
##                               Used    Total
## Number of observations         1049    1061
##
## Model Test User Model:
##
## Test statistic                  0.000
## Degrees of freedom              0
##
## Parameter Estimates:
##
## Information                     Expected
## Information saturated (h1) model Structured
## Standard errors                  Standard
##
## Latent Variables:
##      Estimate   Std.Err  z-value  P(>|z|)  Std.lv  Std.all
## ITA =~
## TA              1.000                2.924  0.961
## IWL =~
## WL              1.000                7.035  0.993
## ITH =~
## TH              1.000                6.402  0.992
##
## Regressions:
##      Estimate  Std.Err  z-value  P(>|z|)  Std.lv  Std.all
## MS ~
## ITA           4.391   0.559   7.852   0.000   12.839  0.248
## ITH           1.349   0.245   5.514   0.000   8.636   0.167
## IWL           1.841   0.217   8.470   0.000  12.949  0.250
## gives the path strength (impact of TA, WL and TH) on mass (MS) accounting for imperfect measurements of
## TH, TA and WL, thus being lower than in previous SEMs (e.g. Supplementary Code A3).
## Covariances:
##      Estimate  Std.Err  z-value  P(>|z|)  Std.lv  Std.all
## ITA ~~
## IWL       7.027   0.700  10.042   0.000   0.342   0.342
## ITH       7.293   0.647  11.278   0.000   0.390   0.390
## IWL ~~
## ITH      14.386   1.481   9.717   0.000   0.319   0.319

```


Appendix A

```
##
## Variances:
##           Estimate Std.Err z-value P(>|z|) Std.lv Std.all
## .TA           0.700      0.700   0.700  0.076
## .TH           0.700      0.700   0.700  0.017
## .WL           0.700      0.700   0.700  0.014
## .MS          1999.265   88.045  22.707  0.000  1999.265  0.747
## ITA           8.548     0.404  21.168  0.000   1.000   1.000
## IWL          49.497     2.192  22.583  0.000   1.000   1.000
## ITH          40.982     1.820  22.517  0.000   1.000   1.000
##
## R-Square:
##           Estimate
## TA           0.924
## TH           0.983
## WL           0.986
## MS           0.253
```

R2 gives unexplained variation without the impact of measurement error.

Supplementary Code A11: Example r-code for a model with binomial response variable. In this example we defined a bird that was seen in the subsequent year (after catching) as 1 and otherwise as 0. We show here an example of a simple composite model (similar to Fig. 2.5) without any confounding variables. The R-package used for the analysis is lavaan (Rosseeel, 2012).

```
d$Seen1<-ordered(d$Seen)      # define the numeric binomial response variable "Seen" (1/0) to be ordered

Cmod.6 <- '
Comp <~ 1*MS+Cho_perVolBlood+LogitB+LogitH+U_perVolBlood+Cort
#define the composite variable
MS~TA                          # regress tarsus length on mass to correct for size effect on mass
Seen1~Comp                      # use Seen1 as binomial response variable
'

Cmod.6.fit<-sem(Cmod.6,data=d, ordered ="Seen1", estimator="WLSMV")
# estimator WLSMV needs to be used when dealing with binomial response variables, define ordered="Seen1" to
# tell the model that the response variable is binomial
summary(Cmod.6.fit, rsq=T, standardized=T)      #get model output

## lavaan 0.6-5 ended normally after 115 iterations
##
## Estimator                      DWLS
## Optimization method            NLMINB
## Number of free parameters       10
##
##                               Used      Total
## Number of observations          110      214
##
## Model Test User Model:
##                               Standard  Robust
## Test Statistic                  4.603    4.645
## Degrees of freedom               6        6
## P-value (Chi-square)            0.596    0.590
```

```

## Scaling correction factor          1.096
## Shift parameter                    0.445
## for the simple second-order correction
##
## Parameter Estimates:
##
## Information                        Expected
## Information saturated (h1) model   Unstructured
## Standard errors                    Robust.sem
##
## Composites:
##      Estimate  Std.Err  z-value  P(>|z|)  Std.lv  Std.all
## Comp <~
## MS            1.000
## Cho_perVolBlod -5.295   8.020   -0.660   0.509   -0.092  -0.228
## LogitB         88.799  76.314   1.164   0.245   1.541   0.416
## LogitH        123.789 207.183   0.597   0.550   2.148   0.219
## U_perVolBlood  0.819   41.349   0.020   0.984   0.014   0.006
## Cort          -14.552  9.206   -1.581   0.114   -0.252  -0.778
##
## Regressions:
##      Estimate  Std.Err  z-value  P(>|z|)  Std.lv  Std.all
## MS ~
## TA            4.639   1.075   4.316   0.000   4.639   0.407
## Seen1 ~
## Comp          0.008   0.003   2.387   0.017   0.441   0.414
##
## Intercepts:
##      Estimate  Std.Err  z-value  P(>|z|)  Std.lv  Std.all
## .MS           143.753 134.311   1.070   0.284   143.753 4.111
## .Seen1         0.000
## Comp           0.000
##
## Thresholds:
##      Estimate  Std.Err  z-value  P(>|z|)  Std.lv  Std.all
## Seen1|t1       2.651   5.553   0.477   0.633   2.651   2.489
##
## Variances:
##      Estimate  Std.Err  z-value  P(>|z|)  Std.lv  Std.all
## .MS           1019.968 144.232   7.072   0.000   1019.968 0.834
## .Seen1         0.940
## Comp           0.000
##
## Scales y*:
##      Estimate  Std.Err  z-value  P(>|z|)  Std.lv  Std.all
## Seen1          1.000
##
## R-Square:
##      Estimate
## MS             0.166
## Seen1          0.171

fitmeasures(Cmod.6.fit, c("chisq", "pvalue", "df", "cfi", "srmr", "rmsea", "rmsea.ci.lower", "rmsea.ci.upper"))
# get model fit indices

```


Appendix A

##	chisq	pvalue	df	cfi	srmr
##	4.603	0.596	6.000	1.000	0.018
##	rmsea	rmsea.ci.lower	rmsea.ci.upper		
##	0.000	0.000	0.107		

APPENDIX B

Supplementary material chapter 3

Body condition mediates carry-over effects of overwintering environment on reproductive success in a shorebird population

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table B1: Characteristics of catching events.

Date	Location name	Tidal basin (Fig. 3.2)	Longitude	Latitude	Period	Winter	Capture ID	Number of 1st year birds	Number of 2nd year birds	Number of 3rd year birds	Number of adults
23-1-2001	Emma Polder I	R	6.684	53.463	1	2000-2001	1	0	0	0	2
25-1-2001	Emma Polder II	R	6.764	53.464	1	2000-2001	3	0	0	0	8
30-1-2001	Wierum	T	6.022	53.406	1	2000-2001	4	11	0	0	25
1-2-2001	Balgzand, Normerven	B	4.927	52.902	1	2000-2001	5	15	7	0	47
6-2-2001	Mokbaai Texel, kazerne strandje	B	4.769	53.001	1	2000-2001	6	17	0	0	39
16-2-2001	Zwarte Haan	T	5.626	53.313	1	2000-2001	7	1	0	0	44
27-2-2001	Sexbierum	T	5.475	53.233	1	2000-2001	8	3	0	0	10
1-3-2001	Vlieland nieuwe kooi	V	5.017	53.279	1	2000-2001	9	15	8	0	56
9-3-2001	Paesens bandpolder	S	6.147	53.405	1	2000-2001	10	0	0	0	2
10-1-2002	Mokbaai Texel, kazerne strandje	B	4.771	52.999	1	2001-2002	92	11	30	1	64
26-3-2002	Mokbaai Texel, kazerne strandje	B	4.769	53.001	1	2001-2002	283	0	0	0	1
7-2-2003	Texel, Volharding	V	4.879	53.164	1	2002-2003	364	8	1	0	48
20-2-2003	Vlieland, Westerveld	V	5.062	53.266	1	2002-2003	387	2	4	0	49
26-2-2003	Texel, Mokbaai Kazernestrandje	B	4.769	53.001	1	2002-2003	389	5	5	0	82
5-3-2003	Wierum	T	6.022	53.406	1	2002-2003	392	34	3	0	103
11-3-2003	Balgzand, t Kuitje	B	4.796	52.931	1	2002-2003	395	6	6	0	32
14-3-2003	Texel, NIOZ strandje	B	4.795	53.009	1	2002-2003	396	5	0	0	27
16-1-2017	Vlieland, Vliehors hoek Posthuiswad	V	4.950	53.240	2	2016-2017	66900332	0	1	0	1
17-1-2017	Vliehors, Kazerne- oost	V	4.950	53.240	2	2016-2017	66900333	10	12	0	36

Supplementary Table B1: Continued.

Date	Location name	Tidal basin (Fig. 3.2)	Longitude	Latitude	Period	Winter	Capture ID	Number of 1st year birds	Number of 2nd year birds	Number of 3rd year birds	Number of adults
18-1-2017	Vliehors, Kazerne- oost	V	4.950	53.240	2	2016-2017	66900334	4	1	0	4
25-1-2017	Schiernomkoog 2e slenk	S	6.229	53.477	2	2016-2017	66900335	9	3	0	30
20-2-2017	Balgzand Normerven	B	4.944	52.910	2	2016-2017	66900349	10	6	0	20
24-2-2017	Eemshaven	R	6.785	53.460	2	2016-2017	66900364	3	1	0	10
28-2-2017	Molenkoik Texel	B	4.805	53.020	2	2016-2017	66900365	2	3	0	27
15-12- 2017	Vlieland, Vliehors, Kwelder ten zuiden van Kroonpolders	V	4.961	53.248	2	2017-2018	66902231	1	4	5	14
18-12- 2017	Vlieland, Vliehors, Kwelder ten zuiden van Kroonpolders	V	4.961	53.248	2	2017-2018	66902233	11	5	6	11
19-12- 2017	Vlieland, Vliehors, Tankdoelen Waddenkant	V	4.919	53.227	2	2017-2018	66902236	0	4	4	29
6-2-2018	Oosterend, Terschelling	T	5.386	53.402	2	2017-2018	66902246	0	0	0	3
26-1-2018	Balgzand, 't Kuitje, Den Helder	B	4.795	52.931	2	2017-2018	66902247	2	2	0	58
19-1-2018	Prunjepolder, Oosterschelde	D	3.848	51.685	2	2017-2018	66902248	3	10	0	62
21-1-2018	Ameland, Vogelpolle	T	5.672	53.424	2	2017-2018	66902249	4	16	0	60
16-2-2018	Strip, Terschelling	T	5.297	53.375	2	2017-2018	66902250	0	1	0	10
17-2-2018	Sehael, Terschelling	T	5.324	53.378	2	2017-2018	66902251	1	1	0	29
30-1-2018	Schor Wilhelminapolder, Zeeland	D	3.901	51.542	2	2017-2018	66902257	4	8	0	80
19-2-2018	Schiernomkoog, 2e Slenk	S	6.229	53.475	2	2017-2018	66902259	21	8	0	36
20-2-2018	Schiernomkoog, 2e Slenk	S	6.229	53.475	2	2017-2018	66902260	6	3	0	22
Total								224	153	16	1181

Appendix B

Supplementary Table B2: Distance from catching locations to the nearest by weather station.

Weather station	Mean distance (km)	SD	Number of catching locations
235 (red star; Figure 1)	9.3	6.8	11
251 (green star; Figure 1)	22.0	11.3	14
277 (blue star; Figure 1)	17.7	14.6	9
310 (orange star; Figure 1)	28.1	5.9	2

Supplementary Table B3: The repeatability was calculated by estimating the intra-class correlation coefficients (ICC) (and its 95% confidence interval) and using the variance components from a one-way ANOVA with the R-package ICC (Wolak et al., 2012). Number of observations for the buffy coat was smaller because samples were removed when edges were not sharp and/or diagonal.

Measure	Period	Mean	Lower 95% CI; upper 95% CI	Number of duplicated samples
Haematocrit	1	0.954	0.946, 0.960	252
	2	0.984	0.982, 0.986	758
Buffy coat	1	0.814	0.773, 0.848	232
	2	0.943	0.931, 0.953	390

Supplementary Table B4: Number and percentage of birds being sexed with DNA or biometric measures (classification tree) per sampling year.

	2000-2001	2001-2002	2002-2003	2016-2017	2017-2018	Total
DNA	80% (249)	3% (3)	1% (3)	98% (189)	100% (544)	63% (988)
Classification tree	20% (61)	97% (104)	99% (417)	2% (4)	0% (0)	37% (586)

Supplementary Table B5: Pearson correlation between the weather condition variables of one vs. two months before the catching event.

	Pearson correlation
Temperature	0.82
Precipitation	0.85
Precipitation anomaly	0.74
Windchill index	0.81
Winter severity	0.89

Supplementary Table B6: WAIC for model with linear term of mass, haematocrit and buffy coat as well as with additional quadratic term for mass, haematocrit and buffy coat. We run the model ones with only a linear term for each condition variable and once with a linear and a quadratic term for each condition variable. Finally, we compared the WAIC of both models.

Model	Linear term	Quadratic term
WAIC	44774.98	44997.65

Supplementary Table B7: WAIC for model with linear term of the environmental variables as well as for taking values of temperature and precipitation 1 month and 2 months prior the catching event.

Model	1 month	2 months
Linear terms	17559.77	19240.41
Quadratic terms	17563.35	19257.35

Supplementary Table B8: Number of individuals per age class in the encounter history (for the multi-state-model analysis).

Age	Number of birds	Percentage
1-year-old	5543	39.47
2-year-old	458	3.26
3-year-old	547	3.90
> 3 years	7495	53.37
Total	14043	100

Appendix B

Supplementary Table B9: Overview of the number of birds caught and resighted in the three winters from the first period to show how many resightings are missed due to excluding the resightings from 2005 to 2015 from the model as a result of computational power issues.

	Winter 2000	Winter 2001	Winter 2002	Total
Total number of birds caught	310	107	420	837
Number of birds seen in the next years (until summer 2005=2 winters after last catch in period 1) which are included in the model	169	72	194	435
Number of birds <u>not</u> seen until summer 2005	141	35	226	402
Number of birds not seen until summer 2005; but resighted after summer 2015 until the winter 2015/20016	27 (9%)	16 (15%)	83 (20%)	126 (15%)
Number of birds not resighted until summer 2005, not resighted in period (2005-2015), but are resighted in period 2 (2016-2018)	2	1	5	8
Total number of birds that are missed (not resighted) due to excluding the years 2005-2015 from analysis	25 (8%)	15 (14%)	78 (18%)	118 (14%)

Supplementary Table B10: Estimate, lower and upper 95% credible interval, R-hat, bulk and tail effective sample size estimated for each path of the path analysis with as response variable daily nest survival.

Path	Mean	lower 95% CI	upper 95% CI	R-hat	Bulk-ESS	Tail-ESS
intercept nest survival	3.320	2.889	3.716	1.0000	18900	15159
intercept lay date	0.078	-0.329	0.474	1.0000	29637	16069
condition -> nest survival	0.341	-0.004	0.675	1.0001	29084	17234
lay date -> nest survival	-0.287	-0.533	-0.008	1.0005	28529	16692
condition -> lay date	0.139	-0.279	0.5589	1.0001	29716	16133
sigma nest survival	22.341	11.356	36.950	1.0002	19233	15678
sigma lay date	1.147	0.889	1.501	1.0001	28795	15978

Supplementary Table B11: Estimate, lower and upper 95% credible interval, R-hat, bulk and tail effective sample size estimated for each path of the path analysis with as response variable chick survival (number of days).

Path	Mean	lower 95% CI	upper 95% CI	R-hat	Bulk-ESS	Tail-ESS
intercept chick survival	3.072	2.934	3.204	1.000	29994	17469
intercept lay date	- 0.503	-0.851	-0.155	1.000	30988	15390
condition -> chick survival	0.127	0.024	0.229	1.000	34579	16613
lay date -> chick survival	- 0.160	-0.321	0.000	1.000	27197	17823
crop -> chick survival	- 1.128	-1.443	-0.823	1.000	22815	18784
condition -> lay date	0.258	-0.045	0.559	1.000	22815	18784
crop -> lay date	0.780	0.163	1.389	1.001	22815	18784
sigma lay date	3.072	2.934	3.204	1.000	25635	16859

Appendix B

Supplementary Table B12: Overview of the (indirect) effect of each environmental variable on chick survival (through body condition).

Predictor variable	Mean (SD) of predictor variable	Increase in predictor variable (in original unit) by	Increase in predictor variable (in %) by	Results in increase in chick survival by
Grassland proportion	0.08 (0.05) proportion	0.01 proportion	13 %	1 day (=10%)
Conspecific density	113 (79) ind/km ²	0.98 ind/km ²	0.87 %	
Temperature	4.7 (2.45) °C	0.98 °C	21 %	
Cockle availability	5.4 (4.8) g AFDM/m ²	0.99 g AFDM/m ²	18 %	
Precipitation	65.3 (32.7) mm/month	0.99 mm/month	1.5 %	
Mussel availability	19.9 (28.1) g AFDM/m ²	1.00 g AFDM/m ²	5 %	

Supplementary Table B13: Between and within individual variation in haematocrit, buffy coat and size-corrected mass. Data come from individuals that were caught during two different winters. We used mixed models to quantify the between and within individual variation (van de Pol & Wright, 2009), whereas we accounted for confounding variables.

Variable	n	Between individual variation (%)	Within individual variation (%)	Confounding variables
Haematocrit	19	70	30	Age, Handling time, Sex, Time difference, DayCatching (in that season)
Buffy coat	19	28	72	Age, Handling time, Sex, Time difference, DayCatching (in that season)
Size-corrected mass	50	31	69	Age, Handling time, Time difference, DayCatching (in that season)

Supplementary Table B14: Distribution of age classes per feeding specialization.

	1-year-old	2-year-old	3-year-old	>3-year-old	Total
<i>Worm specialist (pointed bill shape)</i>	32 (14%)	34 (22%)	4 (25%)	303 (26%)	373 (24%)
<i>Shellfish specialists (blunt or chisel bill shape)</i>	62 (28%)	47 (31%)	2 (13%)	340 (29%)	451 (29%)
<i>Generalist feeder (pointed chisel or pointed blunt bill shape)</i>	130 (58%)	72 (47%)	10 (62%)	538 (45%)	750 (47%)
<i>Total</i>	224	153	16	1181	1574

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure B1: Holder for the capillaries for the blood samples to measure the haematocrit and buffy coat.

Appendix B

Supplementary Figure B2: Illustration of the results of the classification tree to sex the birds from biometric measures. BTipHeight meaning the bill tip height (mm); bill shapes distinguishes between blunt bill (B, H, HB), intermediate bill shape (PB, PH) and pointed bill shape (P); TOHE indicating total head length. For more details on bill shape measurements see (van de Pol et al., 2009a).

Supplementary Figure B3: Result from the confusion matrix for the prediction of the sex based on the classification tree (Supplementary Fig. B2). The figure shows that 115 females were predicted correctly as females. 10 were predicted as females but in reality, were males. 139 males were correctly predicted as males but 17 were predicted as males but should have been predicted as females. Black solid line indicates the 95% confidence interval.

Supplementary Figure B4: Distribution of the environmental variables concerning food and density: a) cockle and mussel food abundance accounting for condition loss during winter, b) exposure time (c) oystercatcher density, d) the proportion of available grassland within the buffer.

Supplementary Figure B5: Map showing the Wadden Sea area of the study with the spatial distribution of the variables collected to calculate food availability. Red squares indicate the catching location, blue circles show the 7km-radius buffer around the catching location which was used to calculate the food availability. Grey dots show the transects for sampling cockle and mussel abundance, orange lines indicate the areas where high tide roost counts were conducted each winter to calculate oystercatcher number and included as an index for competition. Green areas show potential terrestrial foraging areas (grasslands). Area shaded from yellow to red in the Wadden Sea shows the exposure time in proportion from no exposure (yellow) to higher exposure time (red). Background map of the Netherlands was downloaded from www.gadm.org.

Supplementary Figure B6: Distribution of (a, f) mean air temperature, (b, g) sum of precipitation, (c, h) precipitation anomaly, (d, i) winter severity index and (e, j) windchill index one month before the catching event for both periods.

Supplementary Figure B7: Distribution of (a, f) mean air temperature, (b, g) sum of precipitation, (c, h) precipitation anomaly, (d, i) winter severity index and (e, j) windchill index two months before the catching event for both periods.

Appendix B

Supplementary Figure B8: Loess (locally estimated scatterplot smoothing) for the relationship of the condition variables (body mass, haematocrit, buffy coat) and the body condition based on the model output.

Supplementary Figure B9: Correlation matrix of all environmental variables included in the model.

Appendix B

Supplementary Figure B10: Priors used for survival and resighting probability per age and state (based on the results from the R-mark model).

Supplementary Figure B11: Lay date of the first clutch for mainland and island breeding sites.

Supplementary Figure B12: (a) Body condition per habitat type, (b) chick survival per habitat type and (c) body condition in relation to chick survival per habitat type.

Supplementary Figure B13: (a) Body condition per habitat type, (b) daily nest survival per habitat type and (c) body condition in relation to daily nest survival probability per habitat type.

Appendix B

Supplementary Figure B14: Density plot (a-g) and trace plot (h-n) for each estimate from the nest survival model (path analysis).

Supplementary Figure B15: Density plot (a-g) and trace plot (h-n) for each estimate from the chick survival model (path analysis).

Appendix B

Supplementary Figure B16: Relationship between the three condition variables (mass, haematocrit, buffy coat) and condition per period (Period 1: 2000-2003; Period 2: 2016-2018). Note that the fitted line in (a) is exactly the same (equal to 1) for both periods, because the model uses by default the first condition variable in the model as reference variable (Frauendorf et al., 2021).

Supplementary Figure B17: The relationship of body condition and survival probability per age class.

Supplementary Figure B18: Standardized parameter estimates of the effect of feeding specialization on winter body condition. For an overview of the distribution of feeding specialization across the study population see Supplementary Table B14.

Appendix B

Supplementary Figure B19: Standardized parameter estimates of the effect of the environmental variables on body condition per feeding specialization: (a) for worm specialists, (b) for shellfish specialists and (c) for generalists (intermediate feeding specialization). These are the model results when including an interaction effect between feeding specialization (factor) and environmental variables in the model.

Supplementary Figure B20: Counted number of peregrine falcons per winter season (December-February) in the Wadden Sea based on an intensive and regular monitoring scheme. Data were available from Sovon, Dutch Centre for Field Ornithology.

Supplementary Figure B21: Daily mean temperature across the Netherlands averaged across the winter months December-February (KNMI, 2020a).

Supplementary Figure B22: The bay at Texel (state Texel-Balgzand (B); Fig. 3.2a) that has no exposure time in the intertides output. The raster shows the result from the manual calculated exposure time for the winter 2016/2017 (as example) (Supplementary Text B1). Increasing red colour indicates higher exposure time. Blue squares indicate the catching locations, green star shows the bay point (starting point for the calculations; Supplementary Text B1).

Supplementary Figure B23: Relationship of seafloor height and exposure time for four winter seasons for the ‘bay point’ (Supplementary Fig. B22). Relationships differ between years because water levels throughout the winter season differ. Dots indicate the calculated exposure time (Supplementary Text B1) and line indicate the fitted line.

Supplementary Text

Supplementary Text B1: Detailed description of exposure time extraction when InterTides was not used.

Bay: We took the point at the entrance of the bay (Supplementary Fig. B22) (seafloor height of -152cm) and calculated for each water level time point (10-minute interval) from November to February the depth (seafloor height-water level). If the depth is >0 , the seafloor is exposed so that the proportion of time was calculated where the seafloor is exposed. For the same winter and thus water level values of the bay point, we calculated the exposure time for different seafloor heights, ranging from -152 cm to +50 cm, which was also the range of the seafloor height in the bay (Supplementary Fig. B23). This process was repeated for each winter season (Supplementary Fig. B23). In total, for six catching locations the bay fell into the 7km-radius buffer. This concerned the winters 2000/2001, 2001/2002, 2002/2003 as well as 2016/2017. Based on this relationship (intercept and slope) we could calculate the exposure time for each winter and each cell in the bay.

Appendix B

Delta area: Two catches took place in the Delta area (Fig. 3.2b). Data on seafloor height were available from Rijkswaterstaat. In addition, a conversion table of exposure time and seafloor height was available from Deltares. The conversion table was created based on water level measures at Stavenisse (the Netherlands) by measuring the proportion of time that the water level stayed in a 1cm-water level-bin.

APPENDIX C

Supplementary material chapter 4

Love thy neighbour? – Spatial variation in density dependence of nest survival in relation to predator community

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table C1: Distribution of breeding density (pair/ha) for successful and unsuccessful nests across the populations.

Population	Total sample size (number of successful, unsuccessful nests)	Median (standard error) density for successful nests	Median (standard error) density for unsuccessful nests
<i>Island 1 population 1</i>	144 (26,118)	1.43 (0.49)	1.29 (0.44)
<i>Island 1 population 2</i>	70 (33,37)	0.64 (0.28)	0.96 (0.31)
<i>Island 2</i>	95 (19,76)	0.64 (0.34)	0.64 (0.34)
<i>Island 3 population 1</i>	20 (12,8)	1.38 (0.56)	1.60 (0.41)
<i>Island 3 population 2</i>	32 (21,11)	0.96 (0.47)	0.72 (0.30)
<i>Country-wide: low mammalian dominance</i>	96 (80,16)	0.32 (0.22)	0.32 (0.11)
<i>Country-wide: mid mammalian dominance</i>	170 (101,69)	0.32 (0.35)	0.36 (0.24)
<i>Country-wide: high mammalian dominance</i>	34 (9,25)	0.32 (0.17)	1.28 (0.82)

Supplementary Table C2: Out-of-bag prediction error (Supplementary Text C1) and the R² of each distribution model per species.

Type	Species	OOB prediction error	R²
Bird	Carrion crow	0.23	0.07
	Marsh harrier	0.04	0.18
	Common buzzard	0.21	0.10
	Lesser black-backed gull	0.01	0.43
	Herring gull	0.01	0.42
Mammal	Stoat	0.11	0.55
	Beech marten	0.10	0.59
	Red fox	0.11	0.27

Supplementary Table C3: Proportions multiplied by probability of presence values per species (from the distribution model) to add equal and unequal weight to the predation pressure.

Species	Proportion for equal weight	Proportion for unequal weight*
Common gull	1/6	0,111
Lesser black-backed gull	1/6	0,019
Herring gull	1/6	0,074
Western marsh harrier	1/6	0,370
Common buzzard	1/6	0,019
Carrion crow	1/6	0,407
Red fox	1/3	0,75
Stoat	1/3	0,08
Beech marten	1/3	0,17

* weight based on trap cam monitoring (Supplementary Fig. C3)

Supplementary Table C4: AIC-model selection to detect the best mammalian dominance index. Bold model represents the best fitting model. Mammalian and avian values were multiplied by 0.5 to ensure a proportion between 0 and 1. Mam_Pred and Mam_PredWeighted meaning the probability of all mammalian predators summed up after multiplying with its equal and unequal weight, respectively (Supplementary Table C3). Bird_Pred and Bird_PredWeighted meaning the probability of all avian predators summed up after multiplying with its equal and unequal weight, respectively (Supplementary Table C3).

WEIGHT	FORMULA TO CALCULATE THE MAMMALIAN DOMINANCE INDEX	AIC
EQUAL WEIGHT	$0.5 * Mam_Pred$	476.26
UNEQUAL WEIGHT	$0.5 * Mam_Pred + 0.5 * Bird_Pred$	481.22
	$0.5 * Mam_PredWeighted$	
	$0.5 * Mam_PredWeighted + 0.5 * Bird_PredWeighted$	

Appendix C

Supplementary Table C5: Number of nests per habitat type.

Habitat	Number of nests	Description
Agriculture	82	Agricultural land, not further defined
Agriculture crop	76	Crop field
Agriculture grassland	257	Grassland (permanent or temporary)
Nature dry	24	Inland nature area, dikes, beaches
Nature wet	344	Saltmarshes or inland wet nature area
“Tuinwal”	17	Landscape feature typical for North-Holland (province of the Netherlands). A type of fence made of earth and vegetation that rises out of the land and is maintained by farmers
Water inland	9	At the edge to lake/river

Supplementary Table C6: Comparison of the effect of density on nest success with two different proxies for density from two methods: breeding monitoring program (BMP) vs. active nests. N indicating the number of samples and Pearson correlation, the correlation between density measures based on the active nests and the BMP.

Area-Year combination	BMP (estimate)	Active nests (estimate)	N	Pearson correlation
Island 1 population 1 2017	1.822	0.03873	45	0.07
Island 1 population 1 2018	1.371	0.006371	48	0.29
Island 1 population 2 2017	- 3.9002	- 0.01419	42	0.19
Island 1 population 2 2018	-1.241	0.2145	19	-0.33

Supplementary Table C7: Model results from the GLMMs for the local population dataset ($n=361$) as well as for the country-wide dataset ($n=300$) with daily nest survival being the response variable (see equation 4.1 and 4.2). Island 3 population 2 was used as reference. Bold p -values indicate significant variables.

	Variable	Estimate	Standard error	p
Local (island) population dataset	Intercept	4.966	1.104	<0.001
	Distance to the coast	-1.212	0.516	0.019
	Density	1.199	0.825	0.146
	Island 1 Population 1	-2.002	1.059	0.059
	Island 1 Population 2	1.572	0.819	0.055
	Island 2	-1.522	1.072	0.156
	Island 3 Population 1	-0.834	1.619	0.606
	Density: Island 1 Population 1	-1.254	0.856	0.143
	Density: Island 1 Population 2	-2.208	0.96	0.021
	Density: Island 2	-1.954	0.906	0.031
	Density: Island 3 Population 1	-1.567	1.097	0.153
Country-wide dataset	Intercept	0.473	1.146	0.680
	Distance to the coast	-0.002	0.003	0.525
	Density	6.107	1.782	0.028
	Mammalian dominance	3.223	1.320	0.015
	Density: Mammalian dominance	-7.174	3.070	0.019

Appendix C

Supplementary Table C8: Model results for the effect of predator composition and heterospecific densities on nest survival (estimate, standard error, p-value and the AIC of the model). Model includes as response variable the daily nest survival (Mayfield calculation) and as predictor variables the distance to the sea, the mammalian dominance, the density and the interaction of the density and mammalian dominance. The different models illustrated in this table show different heterospecific density combinations of Eurasian oystercatcher (*Haematopus ostralegus*), black-tailed godwit (*Limosa limosa*), northern lapwing (*Vanellus vanellus*) and common redshank (*Tringa tetanus*). N=300.

Model	Variable	Estimate	Standard error	p-value	AIC
Oystercatcher density	Density:Mammalian dominance	-7.17	3.07	0.02	476.26
Oystercatcher + lapwing density		-2.22	0.72	0.002	470.49
Oystercatcher + godwit density		-4.80	1.33	0.0003	467.21
Oystercatcher + redshank density		-4.65	1.52	0.002	473.34
Oystercatcher + lapwing + godwit density		-1.82	0.62	0.003	467.25
Oystercatcher + lapwing + godwit + redshank density		-1.58	0.51	0.002	467.72

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure C1: Distribution maps of the predator species.

Appendix C

Supplementary Figure C2: Histogram of the frequency (number of focal nests) per circle area. The dashed line represents the 85% cut-off. All circles with an area of more than 2.669 ha (85% of total circle area, on the right side of the dashed line) were included in the analysis. If circles covered unmonitored water bodies, we assumed there were no birds breeding there.

Supplementary Figure C3: Annual population index per year and avian predator species. Data are derived from national annual bird survey (<https://stats.sovon.nl>). Note that you should not compare the index between species. For each species the index in the year 1990 is set to 100. It is only possible to compare the trend across years within species.

Supplementary Figure C4: Overview of the distribution of nest predation events recorded with trap cams. Sample size indicates the number of nests monitored with camera traps. The pie chart indicates the predation events in percentage and in parentheses the number of observations per species.

Appendix C

Supplementary Figure C5: Standardized residuals obtained by the regression model plotted versus their spatial coordinates: Variogram for a distance up to (a) 80 km and (b) 110 m indicating no clear spatial autocorrelation between the nest locations as points are horizontally scattered at the different distances. (c) Bubble plot where black dots are negative residuals, and grey dots are positive residuals. The size of the dots is proportional to the value of the residuals. This graph hardly shows any spatial pattern (e.g. groups of negative or positive residuals close to each other).

Supplementary Figure C6: The effect of oystercatcher breeding density on nest success for a) each local island population as well as b) for the country-wide dataset, which is split up in low (<0.62), medium and high (>0.89) mammalian dominance. Lines indicate the fitted line of the binomial model with the 95% confidence interval (shaded area). Predictions outside the range of observations is set transparent. Note that statistical analysis for panel b) were done using the continuous mammalian dominance index, the index was split in three categories only for visualization purposes. For a description of the distribution of the breeding density between successful and unsuccessful nests across the populations see Supplementary Table C1.

Appendix C

Supplementary Figure C7: Interaction plot (2d plot) of the model results for different meadow bird density combinations: a) oystercatcher density, b) oystercatcher + lapwing density, c) oystercatcher + godwit density, d) oystercatcher + lapwing + godwit density, e) oystercatcher + lapwing + godwit density and f) density of all four meadow birds together (oystercatcher, lapwing, godwit and redshank). Dots indicate a nest being successful (white) or unsuccessful (black). Yellow colour indicates high predicted nest success and red colour means low predicted nest success. Note that for visualization we used success as a 0/1 response variable, for the model results of the interaction effect (Supplementary Table C7), we used daily nest survival (Mayfield calculation) as response variable.

Supplementary Figure C8: Model estimates of the effect of conspecific breeding density on oystercatcher nest success (\pm SE as error bar) as a function of a) the probability of presence of mammalian predators and b) the probability of presence of avian predators. Note that the mammalian dominance index (see analysis, Fig. 4.4) is the ratio of the probability of presence of mammalian and avian predators. The figure illustrates that both mechanisms shown in Fig. 4.1c play a role, namely predator avoidance (a) as well as predator deterrence (b). Dashed horizontal lines represent the point at which no density-dependent nest success occurs. The solid line indicates the model fit of the interaction effect between probability of presence and breeding density based on the country-wide dataset showing a beta (sd) of -8.6 (2.76) and $p=0.002$ for (a) and a beta (sd) of 3.29 (1.68) and $p=0.05$ for (b). Horizontal error bars indicate the range (standard deviation) of the explanatory variable (probability of presence). The grey triangle is extracted from Bailey et al. (2017) and transformed to the density metric used in this study (Supplementary Text C2). Island 2 population 2 represents exactly the same area as population 1, but in a different year.

Supplementary Text

Supplementary Text C1: Detailed description of the distribution models.

Avian presence and absence data are collected according to a well-developed and long-term monitoring scheme developed and maintained by Sovon Dutch Centre for Field Ornithology. Unfortunately, this kind of well-developed monitoring scheme is not present for mammalian species. Therefore, mammalian presence/absence data needed some additional processing before they could be used in SDMaps. Mammal (presence only) data were available from the Dutch National Database on Flora and Fauna (www.ndff.nl), which is a database for all Dutch flora and fauna observations. However, the NDFF also includes how well (complete) a grid cell is monitored. In well-monitored cells with no encounter of a mammalian species, we assumed that the species is absent. Nevertheless, this added only few grid cells with the necessary absence data. Therefore, additionally, we used information on mammalian species being traffic victims and combined them with the traffic intensity in a grid (Teunissen et al., 2020). In total, this resulted in 30.075 traffic victims in the time period of 10 years (2009-2018) for the six mammalian species red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*), European polecat (*Mustela putorius*), beech marten (*Martes foina*), stoat (*Mustela erminea*), European badger (*Meles meles*) and European hedgehog (*Erinaceus europaeus*). We determined the median traffic intensity for the grid cells with traffic victims and then assumed that a species is absent in grid cells with a traffic intensity larger than the median (traffic intensity) but where no traffic victims were encountered (Teunissen et al., 2020).

Distribution maps were conducted with the R-package SDMaps (Kampichler et al., 2020) with Random forest models (Boulesteix et al., 2012) to link the absence/presence data to environmental (landscape) variables. This method is widely used to create Bird Atlases in different European countries like Netherlands (Sovon Vogelonderzoek Nederland, 2018), UK (Balmer et al., 2013) and Poland (Kuczyński & Chylarecki, 2012). Validation of the distribution map for each species has been done by calculating the out-of-bag-data estimate of error rate as described in Liaw & Wiener (2002) as well as the R^2 (Supplementary Table C2).

Supplementary Text C2: Method description for the use of the literature point.

Bailey et al. (2017) show in Fig. 4.3b (chapter 5; p. 149) a relationship between the predicted nest predation and nest density that we plotted as a point from “literature” in Fig. 4.4. Since mobbing intensity may differ between incubating and non-incubating pairs, Bailey et al. (2017) analysed the density effect based only on active nests instead of all nests present regardless of their status of activity. Nest activity status was not available on a large scale. Since data were available from two years and two populations where the active-nest density

was measured as well as the density with the BMP-method, we were able to compare the estimates (of the effect of density on the nest success) for both methods (Supplementary Table C6). We can conclude from this that in most cases, the direction (positive/negative) of the density-dependent nest success were similar.

The calculation was as followed:

Relationship of Fig. 3b from Bailey et al. (2017):

$$NS \sim \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \text{DensActive}$$

$$NS \sim -1.77972 + 1.14688 * \text{DensActive}$$

Relationship between DensActive and DensBMP based on data from (Supplementary Table C6):

$$\text{DensActive} \sim \beta_2 + \beta_3 * \text{DensBMP}$$

$$\text{DensActive} \sim 3.1584 + 0.4822 * \text{DensBMP}$$

Bringing both relationships together:

$$NS \sim \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \text{DensActive}$$

$$NS \sim \beta_0 + \beta_1 * (\beta_2 + \beta_3 * \text{DensBMP})$$

$$NS \sim \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \beta_2 + \beta_1 * \beta_3 * \text{DensBMP}$$

$$NS \sim -1.77972 + 1.14688 * 3.1584 + 1.14688 * 0.4822 * \text{DensBMP}$$

$$NS \sim -1.77972 + 0.553 * \text{DensBMP}$$

NS indicates the nest success, DensActive indicates the density of active nests and DensBMP indicates the density based on data from the breeding monitoring program (BMP).

We assumed that the standard error is the same as described in Table 1 (chapter 5; p.147) resulting in an estimate of $0.55(\pm 0.12)$.

APPENDIX D

Supplementary material chapter 5

The synergistic effects of environmental drivers of declining reproduction of a threatened meadow bird across the Netherlands

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table D1: Number of nests with the percentage in brackets that were protected and not protected per habitat type. For the remaining 6351 nests it was unknown if nest protection was applied or not.

Habitat	Nest protection		Total
	Yes	No	
Arable land	3347	50	3397 (31)
Natural grassland	349	20	369 (3)
Permanent grassland	6221	99	6320 (57)
Temporary grassland	1003	7	1010 (9)
Total	10920 (98)	176 (2)	11096 (100)

Supplementary Table D2: Results of the model visualized in Fig. 5.2, including nests found before and after clutch completion in the analysis compared to the model results, when the nests found before clutch completion are excluded.

	Nests found before and after clutch completion (Fig. 5.2)	Only nests found after clutch completion
Variable	Estimate (Std. Error)	Estimate (Std. Error)
Distance coast	0.02 (0.02)	0.01 (0.02)
Precipitation	0.05 (0.02)	0.07 (0.02)
Buzzard	-0.11 (0.02)	-0.12 (0.02)
Harrier	0.00 (0.02)	-0.04 (0.02)
Marten	-0.26 (0.02)	-0.25 (0.02)
Fox	-0.12 (0.02)	-0.11 (0.02)
Earthworm	-0.02 (0.02)	-0.02 (0.02)
Land use intensity	-0.03 (0.02)	-0.03 (0.02)
Nest protection	0.04 (0.03)	0.06 (0.03)
Lay date	-0.50 (0.04)	-0.50 (0.05)
Fox*Earthworm	-0.01 (0.02)	-0.01 (0.02)
Marten*Earthworm	-0.01 (0.02)	-0.01 (0.02)

Supplementary Table D2: Continued.

	Nests found before and after clutch completion (Fig. 5.2)	Only nests found after clutch completion
Harrier*Earthworm	-0.01 (0.03)	-0.01 (0.03)
Buzzard*Earthworm	0.03 (0.02)	0.04 (0.02)
Fox*Land use intensity	0.04 (0.02)	0.04 (0.02)
Marten* Land use intensity	-0.00 (0.02)	-0.00 (0.02)
Harrier* Land use intensity	-0.02 (0.03)	-0.02 (0.03)
Buzzard* Land use intensity	-0.05 (0.02)	-0.04 (0.02)

Supplementary Table D3: Comparison of the models with quadratic terms for precipitation shortage (PS2) and lay date (LD2). Bold model indicates the best fitting model with the lowest AIC that was used in the main analysis for Fig. 5.2 and 5.3.

Model	Nest model (Fig. 5.2)	Chick model (Fig. 5.3)
PS2, LD2	32231.36	2236.20
PS, LD	32265.53	2255.11
PS2, LD	32266.99	2234.66
PS, LD2	32229.56	2256.84

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure D1: Spatial distribution of the nests with information on daily clutch survival (blue dots; n=17447) and hatchling survival (orange dots; n=1890).

Supplementary Figure D2: Distribution of the monitored nests per habitat and year for each reproductive parameter: (a) daily clutch survival, (b) hatchling survival and (c) number of fledglings. Note that panel (c) is a separate response variable (number of fledglings) and not the product of clutch and hatchling survival.

Supplementary Figure D3: Lay date in Julian day per habitat type (for all clutch numbers combined). The boxes show the interquartile range and the lines include 95% of observations and points. Category agriculture unknown means agricultural breeding area but unknown if arable land or grassland. Because the effect in the full model was similar to arable land, we merged the two categories for the final full models.

Appendix D

Supplementary Figure D4: Lay date in Julian day per breeding area (coastal vs. inland) for (a) all clutch numbers combined and (b) only for first clutches. The boxes show the interquartile range and the lines include 95% of observations and points.

Supplementary Figure D5: Temporal variation of precipitation surplus (>0) / shortage (<0) for (a) the nest (egg) period and (b) the chick (hatchling) period. Variation was calculated by running two linear mixed models, with precipitation as response variable and year as a random effect. The first model was run with the clutch survival dataset (a) and the second model was run with the hatchling survival dataset (b).

Supplementary Figure D6: Annual population index per year and avian predator species. Data are derived from national annual bird survey (<https://stats.sovon.nl>). Note that you should not compare the index between species. For each species the index in the year 1990 is set to 100. It is only possible to compare the trend across years within species.

Supplementary Figure D7: Average number of white storks per year. The data comes from the Waterbird Monitoring Network (<https://stats.sovon.nl>).

Appendix D

Supplementary Figure D8: Lay date (in Julian day) for the three habitat categories (saltmarsh, agriculture and urban). Dots represent the median per year and the ribbons represent the 95% confidence interval.

Supplementary Figure D9: Correlation matrix of the clutch survival data set.

Appendix D

Supplementary Figure D10: Correlation matrix for the chick dataset.

Supplementary Figure D11: Relationship between daily clutch survival and lay date. Dots indicate the effect size of the binned raw lay date data points. The size of the dots is proportional to its sample size.

Appendix D

Supplementary Figure D12: Relationship between chick (hatchling) survival and lay date. Dots indicate the effect size of the binned raw lay date data points. The size of the dots is proportional to its sample size.

Supplementary Figure D13: Earthworm abundance per habitat type. Note that there is no boxplot for the coastal breeding habitats (dunes/sand, saltmarsh) because we only included the effect of earthworm abundance on the reproduction in agricultural and urban habitat types. The category 'agriculture unknown' means agricultural breeding area but it is unknown if it was arable land or grassland. Because the effect in the full model was similar to arable land, we merged the two categories for the final full models.

Appendix D

Supplementary Figure D14: Relative earthworm abundance in relation to daily clutch survival. Note that this relationship is based on raw data, without correcting for effects of other environmental variables or lay date. However, the relationship was also significantly positive in the model considering other variables (if the beech marten was excluded from analysis). For more information see the main text. The size of the dots is proportional to the sample size.

Supplementary Text

Supplementary Text D1: Detailed description of home range calculation.

Based on accelerometer data the behaviour (e.g. foraging, resting, flying) could be determined as described in van der Kolk et al. (2019). We calculated a 50% minimum convex polygon (MCP) around all points annotated as foraging behaviour (within the period from 1st April - 15th July) with the adehabitatHR R-package (Calenge, 2006). The mean area size of the 50% MCP was 0.09 km², resulting in a mean radius of 170 m assuming circular habitat use around the nest location.

Supplementary Text D2: Extended acknowledgement.

Albers, M .	Cottaar, F .
Arts, F .	Cremer, J .
Backsen, S .	Dallmeijer, D .
Bakker, S .	Das, P .
Beets, A .	de Boer, F .
Berghuis, A .	de Boer, P .
Bijlsma, R .	de Boer, T .
Boele, A .	de Haan, P .
Boerjan, L .	de Jager, K .
Bokje, M .	de Jong, E .
Bonthuis, S .	de Jong, M .
Bousché, B .	de Leeuw, J .
Bouwmeester, H .	de Vries, J .
Braaksma, S .	de Vries, P .
Brandenburg, E .	de Weerd, P .
Brandhorst, W .	Dijksten, L .
Breeuwsma, P .	Dijkstra, B .
Breukel, I .	Dillerop, R .
Breukel, L .	Dirksen, S .
Brinkman, C .	Douwma, E .
Brouwer, P .	Duiven, A .
Buesink, W .	Dunn, A .
Buijs, R .	Ebbingse, B .
Buiten, N .	Eijkelenboom, E .
Bulder, H .	Eising, M .

Appendix D

Erhart, F .
Feenstra, M .
Fito, F .
Fokker, C .
Gerritsen, G .
Gijsbertsen, J .
Godijn, N .
Grobbe, C .
Günther, K .
Hiemstra, D .
Hofeditz, F .
Horn, H .
Hotting, J .
Hotting, M .
Huizenga, J .
Hulder, A .
Hulshof, E .
Hustings, F .
Jager, K .
Jansen, J .
Jelle Hibma, R .
Kamer-van der Heijden, L .
Kamstra, G .
Kamstra-Werkhoven, J .
Kaspersma, W .
Keijser, H .
Kelder, L .
Klaassen, H .
Kleefstra, R .
Klein, W .
Kleemann, M .
Klok, C .
Kok, A .
Kok, W .
Koper, A .
Kreetz, T .
Kruk, M .
Kühn, M .
Kwint, N .
Langhans, S .
Leyrer, J .
Lichtenbeld, H .
Lieverdink, M .
Lilipaly, S .
Litovska, I .
Maes, K .
Majoor, F .
Manche, P .
Martig, R .
Meininger, P .
Middendorp, B .
Minnaar, K .
Moerman, M .
Mosselaar, J .
Musters, B .
Nagtegaal, J .
Noorman, C .
Oosterhuis, H .
Oosterhuis, R .
Oosterveld, E .
Ottens, H .
Parmentier, F .
Petter, G .
Plat, J .
Postma, J .
Pullen, E .
Radstake, Y .
Rehm, R .
Ribbers, E .
Roodbergen, M .
Schekkerman, H .
Schoonderwoerd, J .
Schoppers, J .
Schouten, N .

Seinstra, A .
Sijbrandij, A .
Sikkema, M .
Sluijter, M .
Tanger, D .
Tijssen, W .
Tramper, J .
Trimbos, K .
van Bokhoven, J .
van de Reep, M .
van Deelen, R .
van den Berg, T .
van der Hulst, B .
van der Kolk, H .
van der Laan, E .
van der Spek, V .
van der Vliet, R .
van der Vliet, R .
van Dijk, A .
van Dort, J .
van Dun, K .
van Eijk, J .
van Geneijgen, P .
van Kleunen, A .
van Kooten, L .
van Leeuwen, M .
van Lint, W .
van Manen, W .
van Mourik, D .
van Noorden, B .
van Ree, L .
van Stralen, J .
van Swelm, N .
van Wesel, M .
van Wijk, J .
Veenendaal, D .
Vegelin, J .
Venema, P .
Visser, R .
Voesten, R .
Voortman, T .
Vos, R .
Vroegindeweyj, B .
Waasdorp, S .
Weima, S .
Wessel, A .
Wieland, A .
Willemsen, M .
Zomer, H .
Zorgdrager, J .
Zuhorn, C .

APPENDIX E

Supplementary material chapter 6

Synthesis

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table E1: Proportion (with sample sizes in brackets) of birds with different feeding specializations caught during winter catches in two periods: early (2000-2003) and recent (2016-2018).

	Early period	Recent period
Worm specialist	0.27 (321)	0.19 (209)
Intermediate feeder	0.40 (473)	0.54 (579)
Shellfish specialist	0.33 (400)	0.27 (286)
Total	1 (1194)	1 (1074)

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure E1: Proportion of birds with different feeding specializations caught during winter catches in two periods: early (2000-2003) and recent (2016-2018).

BIBLIOGRAPHY

RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT

SUMMARY/SAMENVATTING

BIBLIOGRAPHY

A

- Abdi, H., & Williams, L. J. (2010). Principal component analysis. *WIREs Computational Statistics*, 2, 433–459. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wics.101>
- Aceves-Bueno, E., Adeleye, A. S., Feraud, M., Huang, Y., Tao, M., Yang, Y., & Anderson, S. E. (2017). The accuracy of citizen science data: A quantitative review. *The Bulletin of the Ecological Society of America*, 98(4), 278–290. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bes2.1336>
- Ackerman, J. T., Blackmer, A. L., & Eadie, J. M. (2004). Is predation on waterfowl nests density dependent?—Tests at three spatial scales. *Oikos*, 107(1), 128–140. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0030-1299.2004.13226.x>
- Aebischer, N. J. (1999). Multi-way comparisons and generalized linear models of nest success: extensions of the Mayfield method. *Bird Study*, 46(sup1), S22–S31. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00063659909477228>
- Allee, W. C. (1927). Animal aggregations. *The Quarterly Review of Biology*, 2(3), 367–398. <https://doi.org/10.1086/394281>
- Allen, A. M., Ens, B. J., van de Pol, M., van der Jeugd, H., Frauendorf, M., Oosterbeek, K., & Jongejans, E. (2019a). Seasonal survival and migratory connectivity of the Eurasian oystercatcher revealed by citizen science. *Auk*, 136(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1093/auk/uky001>
- Allen, A. M., Ens, B. J., van de Pol, M., van der Jeugd, H., Frauendorf, M., van der Kolk, H.-J., Oosterbeek, K., Nienhuis, J., & Jongejans, E. (2019b). Colour-ring wear and loss effects in citizen science mark-resighting studies. *Avian Research*, 10(11), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40657-019-0151-z>
- Allen, A. M., Jongejans, E., van de Pol, M., Ens, B. J., Frauendorf, M., van der Sluijs, M., & de Kroon, H. (2021). The demographic causes of population change vary across four decades in a long-lived shorebird. *Ecology*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ECY.3615>
- Alonso-Alvarez, C., Ferrer, M., & Velando, A. (2002). The plasmatic index of body condition in Yellow-legged Gulls *Larus cachinnans*: a food-controlled experiment. *Ibis*, 144, 147–149. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.0019-1019.2001.00023.x>
- Angelier, F., Wingfield, J. C., Weimerskirch, H., & Chastel, O. (2010). Hormonal

correlates of individual quality in a long-lived bird: a test of the 'corticosterone–fitness hypothesis'. *Biology Letters*, *6*, 846–849.

<https://doi.org/doi:10.1098/rsbl.2010.0376>

Araya-Ajoy, Y. G., & Dingemanse, N. J. (2014). Characterizing behavioural 'characters': an evolutionary framework. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1098/rspb.2013.2645>

Araya-Ajoy, Y. G., Ranke, P. S., Kvalnes, T., Rønning, B., Holand, H., Myhre, A. M., Pärn, H., Jensen, H., Ringsby, T. H., Sæther, B.-E., & Wright, J. (2019). Characterizing morphological (co)variation using structural equation models: Body size, allometric relationships and evolvability in a house sparrow metapopulation. *Evolution*, *73*(3), 452–466. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1111/evo.13668>

Atchley, W. R., & Anderson, D. (1978). Ratios and the statistical analysis of biological data. *Systematic Zoology*, *27*(1), 71. <https://doi.org/doi:10.2307/2412816>

Aubry, L. M., Rockwell, R. F., Cooch, E. G., Brook, R. W., Mulder, C. P., & Koons, D. N. (2013). Climate change, phenology, and habitat degradation: drivers of gosling body condition and juvenile survival in lesser snow geese. *Global Change Biology*, *19*(1), 149–160. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1111/gcb.12013>

Auger-Methe, M., Derocher, A. E., DeMars, C. A., Plank, M. J., Codling, E. A., & Lewis, M. A. (2016). Evaluating random search strategies in three mammals from distinct feeding guilds. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, *85*(5), 1411–1421. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1111/1365-2656.12562>

B

Bailey, L. D., Ens, B. J., Both, C., Heg, D., Oosterbeek, K., & van de Pol, M. (2019). Habitat selection can reduce effects of extreme climatic events in a long-lived shorebird. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, *88*(10), 1474–1485. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1111/1365-2656.13041>

Bailey, L. D., Langmore, N. E., & Van de Pol, M. (2017). *Negative density-dependent nest predation in a threatened mobbing bird species. In: Between the devil and the deep blue sea: Consequences of extreme climatic events in the Eurasian oystercatcher (Haematopus ostralegus)* [PhD thesis]. Australian National University.

Bakker, W., Ens, B. J., Dokter, A., van der Kolk, H.-J., Rappoldt, K., van de Pol, M., Troost, K., van der Veer, H. W., Bijleveld, A. I., van der Meer, J., Oosterbeek, K.,

- Jongejans, E., & Allen, A. M. (2021). Connecting foraging and roosting areas reveals how food stocks explain shorebird numbers. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 259, 107458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2021.107458>
- Balmer, D. E., Gillings, S., Caffrey, B., Swann, R. L., Downie, I. S., & Fuller, R. J. (2013). *Bird Atlas 2007–11: the breeding and wintering birds of Britain and Ireland*. BTO Books.
- Banda, E., & Blanco, G. (2009). Implications of nest-site limitation on density-dependent nest predation at variable spatial scales in a cavity-nesting bird. *Oikos*, 118(7), 991–1000. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0706.2009.17363.x>
- Barnosky, A. D., Hadly, E. A., Bascompte, J., Berlow, E. L., Brown, J. H., Fortelius, M., Getz, W. M., Harte, J., Hastings, A., Marquet, P. A., Martinez, N. D., Mooers, A., Roopnarine, P., Vermeij, G., Williams, J. W., Gillespie, R., Kitzes, J., Marshall, C., Matzke, N., ... Smith, A. B. (2012). Approaching a state shift in Earth's biosphere. *Nature*, 486(7401), 52–58. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature11018>
- Barry, K. L., & Wilder, S. M. (2013). Macronutrient intake affects reproduction of a predatory insect. *Oikos*, 122(7), 1058–1064. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0706.2012.00164.x>
- Bartoń, K. (2020). *MuMIn: Multi-Model Inference* (1.43.17) [Computer software]. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=MuMIn>
- Bates, D., Maechler, M., Bolker, B., & Walker, S. (2015). Fitting Linear Mixed-Effects Models Using lme4. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 67(1), 1–48. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v067.i01>
- Bearhop, S., Fiedler, W., Furness, R. W., Votier, S. C., Waldron, S., Newton, J., Bowen, G. J., Berthold, P., & Farnsworth, K. (2005). Assortative mating as a mechanism for rapid evolution of a migratory divide. *Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1115661>
- Bearhop, S., Hilton, G. M., Votier, S. C., & Waldron, S. (2004). Stable isotope ratios indicate that body condition in migrating passerines is influenced by winter habitat. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 271(4), S215–S218. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2003.0129>
- Beechler, B. R., Broughton, H., Bell, A., Ezenwa, V. O., & Jolles, A. E. (2015). Innate immunity in free-ranging African buffalo (*Syncerus caffer*): Associations with parasite infection and white blood cell counts. *Physiological and Biochemical*

- Zoology*. <https://doi.org/10.1086/665276>
- Beintema, A. J. (1994). Condition indices for wader chicks derived from bodyweight and bill-length. *Bird Study*, *41*(1), 68–75.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00063659409477199>
- Beintema, A. J., & Muskens, G. J. D. M. (1987). Nesting success of birds breeding in Dutch agricultural grasslands. *The Journal of Applied Ecology*, *24*(3), 743.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/2403978>
- Belovsky, G. E., Botkin, D. B., Crowl, T. A., Cummins, K. W., Franklin, J. F., Hunter, M. L., Joern, A., Lindenmayer, D. B., MacMahon, J. A., Margules, C. R., & Scott, J. M. (2004). Ten suggestions to strengthen the science of ecology. *Bioscience*, *54*(4), 345–351. [https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568\(2004\)054\[0345:Tststs\]2.0.Co;2](https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568(2004)054[0345:Tststs]2.0.Co;2)
- Bentham, K. J. van, Bruijning, M., Bonnet, T., Jongejans, E., Postma, E., & Ozgul, A. (2017). Disentangling evolutionary, plastic and demographic processes underlying trait dynamics: a review of four frameworks. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, *8*(1), 75–85. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12627>
- Bentler, P. M. (1990). Comparative fit indexes in structural models. *Psychological Bulletin*, *107*(2), 238–246. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.107.2.238>
- Benton, T. G., Vickery, J. A., & Wilson, J. D. (2003). Farmland biodiversity: is habitat heterogeneity the key? *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, *18*(4), 182–188.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347\(03\)00011-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347(03)00011-9)
- Bernard, C. J. (2004). *Animal behaviour: mechanism, development, function and evolution*. Pearson Education.
- Betini, G. S., Griswold, C. K., & Norris, D. R. (2013). Carry-over effects, sequential density dependence and the dynamics of populations in a seasonal environment. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *280*(1759), 7.
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2013.0110>
- Bêty, J., Gauthier, G., & Giroux, J.-F. (2003). Body condition, migration, and timing of reproduction in snow geese: A test of the condition-dependent model of optimal clutch size. *The American Naturalist*, *162*(1), 110–121.
<https://doi.org/10.1086/375680>
- Beukema, J., & Dekker, R. (2006). Annual cockle *Cerastoderma edule* production in the Wadden Sea usually fails to sustain both wintering birds and a commercial fishery. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, *309*, 189–204.

<https://doi.org/10.3354/meps309189>

- Beukema, J., Dekker, R., & Jansen, J. (2009). Some like it cold: populations of the tellinid bivalve *Macoma balthica* (L.) suffer in various ways from a warming climate. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 384, 135–145.
<https://doi.org/10.3354/meps07952>
- BirdLife International. (2021). *IUCN Red List for birds*. <http://www.birdlife.org>
- Birkhead, T. R., Pellatt, E. J., Matthews, I. M., Roddis, N. J., Hunter, F. M., McPhie, F., & Castillo-Juarez, H. (2006). Genic capture and the genetic basis of sexually selected traits in the zebra finch. *Evolution*, 60(11), 2389–2398.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0014-3820.2006.tb01873.x>
- Bison, M., Yoccoz, N. G., Carlson, B. Z., & Delestrade, A. (2019). Comparison of budburst phenology trends and precision among participants in a citizen science program. *International Journal of Biometeorology*, 63(1), 61–72.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00484-018-1636-x>
- Blanco, G., & Bertellotti, M. (2002). Differential predation by mammals and birds: implications for egg-colour polymorphism in a nomadic breeding seabird. *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 75, 137–146.
<https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1095-8312.2002.00026.x>
- Blaustein, A. R., & Kiesecker, J. M. (2002). Complexity in conservation: lessons from the global decline of amphibian populations. *Ecology Letters*, 5(4), 597–608.
<https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1461-0248.2002.00352.x>
- Bollen, K. A. (2002). Latent variables in psychology and the social sciences. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 53(1), 605–634.
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.53.100901.135239>
- Bolton, M., Tyler, G., Smith, K. E. N., & Bamford, R. O. Y. (2007). The impact of predator control on lapwing *Vanellus vanellus* breeding success on wet grassland nature reserves. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 44(3), 534–544.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2007.01288.x>
- Both, C., Van Turnhout, C. A. M., Bijlsma, R. G., Siepel, H., Van Strien, A. J., & Foppen, R. P. B. (2010). Avian population consequences of climate change are most severe for long-distance migrants in seasonal habitats. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 277(1685), 1259–1266.
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2009.1525>

- Boulesteix, A.-L., Janitza, S., Kruppa, J., & König, I. R. (2012). Overview of random forest methodology and practical guidance with emphasis on computational biology and bioinformatics. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*, 2(6), 493–507. <https://doi.org/10.1002/widm.1072>
- Bouwens, S. (2017). *Handreiking Kleine Marters in relatie tot soortbescherming* (2017.32.; p. 32). Zoogdierverseniging.
- Boyd, I. L. (2004). Migration of Marine Mammals. In D. Werner (Ed.), *Biological Resources and Migration* (pp. 203–210). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-06083-4_20
- Briedis, M., Krist, M., Kral, M., Voigt, C. C., & Adamik, P. (2018). Linking events throughout the annual cycle in a migratory bird-non-breeding period buffers accumulation of carry-over effects. *Behavioral Ecology and Sociobiology*, 72(6), 12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00265-018-2509-3>
- Briggs, K. (1984). The breeding ecology of coastal and inland oystercatchers in north Lancashire. *Bird Study*, 31(2), 141–147. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00063658409476832>
- Broekhuizen, S., Spoelstra, K., Thissen, J. B. M., Canters, KJ., & Buys, J. C. (2016). *Atlas van de Nederlandse zoogdieren. – Natuur van Nederland 12*. Naturalis Biodiversity Center & EIS.
- Brook, B. W., Sodhi, N. S., & Bradshaw, C. J. (2008). Synergies among extinction drivers under global change. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 23(8), 453–460. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2008.03.011>
- Brown, D. J., Ribic, C. A., Donner, D. M., Nelson, M. D., Bocetti, C. I., & Deloria-Sheffield, C. M. (2017). Using a full annual cycle model to evaluate long-term population viability of the conservation-reliant Kirtland's warbler after successful recovery. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 54(2), 439–449. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12776>
- Brown, M. E. (1996). Assessing body condition in birds. In V. Nolan & E. D. Ketterson (Eds.), *Current Ornithology* (pp. 67–135). Springer US. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4615-5881-1_3
- Brown, M. L., & Murphy, B. R. (2004). Seasonal dynamics of direct and indirect condition indices in relation to energy allocation in largemouth bass *Micropterus salmoides* (Lacèpede). *Ecology of Freshwater Fish*, 13(1), 23–36.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0906-6691.2004.00031.x>

- Bürkner, P.-C. (2017). brms: An R package for Bayesian multilevel models using Stan. *Journal of Statistical Software*, *80*(1), 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v080.i01>
- Bürkner, P.-C. (2018). Advanced Bayesian multilevel modeling with the R package brms. *The R Journal*, *10*(1), 395. <https://doi.org/10.32614/RJ-2018-017>
- Burnham, K. P., & Anderson, D. R. (1998). Practical use of the information-theoretic approach. In *Model selection and inference* (pp. 75–117). Springer.

C

- Caldow, R. W. G., Goss-Custard, J. D., Stillman, R. A., Durell, S. E. A. L. V. D., Swinfen, R., & Bregnballe, T. (1999). Individual variation in the competitive ability of interference-prone foragers: the relative importance of foraging efficiency and susceptibility to interference. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, *68*(5), 869–878. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2656.1999.00334.x>
- Calenge, C. (2006). The package adehabitat for the R software: tool for the analysis of space and habitat use by animals. *Ecological Modelling*, *297*, 1035. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2006.03.017>
- Calvert, A. M., Walde, S. J., & Taylor, P. D. (2009). Nonbreeding-season drivers of population dynamics in seasonal migrants: conservation parallels across taxa. *Avian Conservation and Ecology*, *4*(2), 27. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ACE-00335-040205>
- Campbell, N. A., Reece, J. B., Urry, L. A., Cain, M. L., Wasserman, S. A., Minorsky, P. V., & Jackson, R. B. (2008). *Biology* (8th edition). Pearson Benjamin Cummings.
- Camphuysen, C. J., Ens, B. J., Heg, D., Hulscher, J. B., Van der Meer, J., & Smit, C. J. (1996). Oystercatcher *Haematopus ostralegus* winter mortality in The Netherlands: the effect of severe weather and food supply. *Ardea*, 469–492.
- Cardillo, M., Mace, G. M., Jones, K. E., Bielby, J., Bininda-Emonds, O. R. P., Sechrest, W., Orme, C. D. L., & Purvis, A. (2005). Multiple causes of high extinction risk in large mammal species. *Science*, *309*(5738), 1239–1241. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1116030>
- Carroll, C. (2007). Interacting effects of climate change, landscape conversion, and harvest on carnivore populations at the range margin: marten and lynx in the northern Appalachians. *Conservation Biology*, *21*(4), 1092–1104.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2007.00719.x>

- Catry, P., Dias, M. P., Phillips, R. A., & Granadeiro, J. P. (2013). Carry-over effects from breeding modulate the annual cycle of a long-distance migrant: an experimental demonstration. *Ecology*, *94*(6), 1230–1235. <https://doi.org/10.1890/12-2177.1>
- CBS. (2021). *Data from: CBS Bestand Bodemgebruik*. Central Bureau voor Statistiek. <https://www.pdok.nl/introductie/-/article/cbs-bestand-bodemgebruik>
- CBS, PBL, RIVM, & WUR. (2021). *Land- en tuinbouw: ruimtelijke spreiding, grondgebruik en aantal bedrijven, 1980-2020 (indicator 2119, versie 10, 8 juli 2021)*. Centraal Bureau Voor de Statistiek (CBS). <https://www.clo.nl>
- Chang, C., Gardiner, J., Houang, R., & Yu, Y.-L. (2020). Comparing multiple statistical software for multiple-indicator, multiple-cause modeling: an application of gender disparity in adult cognitive functioning using MIDUS II dataset. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, *20*(1), 275. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-020-01150-4>
- Cīrule, D., Krama, T., Vrublevska, J., Rantala, M. J., & Krams, I. (2012). A rapid effect of handling on counts of white blood cells in a wintering passerine bird: a more practical measure of stress? *Journal of Ornithology*, *153*(1), 161–166. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10336-011-0719-9>
- Converse, S. J., Royle, J. A., & Urbanek, R. P. (2012). Bayesian analysis of multi-state data with individual covariates for estimating genetic effects on demography. *Journal of Ornithology*, *152*(S2), 561–572. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10336-011-0695-0>
- Cote, J., Arnoux, E., Sorci, G., Gaillard, M., & Faivre, B. (2009). Age-dependent allocation of carotenoids to coloration versus antioxidant defences. *Journal of Experimental Biology*, *213*(2), 271–277. <https://doi.org/10.1242/jeb.035188>
- Cox, R. M., & Calsbeek, R. (2015). Survival of the fattest? Indices of body condition do not predict viability in the brown anole (*Anolis sagrei*). *Functional Ecology*, *29*(3), 404–413. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2435.12346>
- Cramp, S., & Simmons, K. E. L. (1983). *Birds of the Western Palearctic. Waders to gulls: Vol. III*. Oxford University Press.
- Cresswell, W. (1994). Flocking is an effective anti-predation strategy in redshanks, *Tringa totanus*. *Animal Behaviour*, *47*(2), 433–442. <https://doi.org/10.1006/anbe.1994.1057>
- Cresswell, W., & Quinn, J. L. (2011). Predicting the optimal prey group size from

predator hunting behaviour. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, *80*(2), 310–319.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2656.2010.01775.x>

Crossin, G. T., Phillips, R. A., Trathan, P. N., Fox, D. S., Dawson, A., Wynne-Edwards, K. E., & Williams, T. D. (2012). Migratory carryover effects and endocrinological correlates of reproductive decisions and reproductive success in female albatrosses. *General and Comparative Endocrinology*, *176*(2), 151–157.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ygcen.2012.01.006>

Cubaynes, S., Doutrelant, C., Grégoire, A., Perret, P., Faivre, B., & Gimenez, O. (2012). Testing hypotheses in evolutionary ecology with imperfect detection: capture–recapture structural equation modeling. *Ecology*, *93*(2), 248–255.
<https://doi.org/10.1890/11-0258.1>

Cuthill, I. C., Maddocks, S. A., Weall, C. V., & Jones, E. K. M. (2000). Body mass regulation in response to changes in feeding predictability and overnight energy expenditure. *Behavioral Ecology*, *11*(2), 189–195.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/beheco/11.2.189>

Czarniecka-Wiera, M., Szymura, T. H., & Kącki, Z. (2020). Understanding the importance of spatial scale in the patterns of grassland invasions. *Science of The Total Environment*, *727*, 138669. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138669>

D

Darling, E. S., & Cote, I. M. (2008). Quantifying the evidence for ecological synergies. *Ecology Letters*, *11*(12), 1278–1286. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2008.01243.x>

Darlington, R. B., & Smulders, T. V. (2001). Problems with residual analysis. *Animal Behaviour*, *62*, 599–602. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.1006/anbe.2001.1806>

Daunt, F., Reed, T. E., Newell, M., Burthe, S., Phillips, R. A., Lewis, S., & Wanless, S. (2014). Longitudinal bio-logging reveals interplay between extrinsic and intrinsic carry-over effects in a long-lived vertebrate. *Ecology*, *95*(8), 2077–2083.
<https://doi.org/10.1890/13-1797.1>

Davies, K. F., Margules, C. R., & Lawrence, J. F. (2004). A synergistic effect puts rare, specialized species at greater risk of extinction. *Ecology*, *85*(1), 265–271.
<https://doi.org/10.1890/03-0110>

de Little, S. C., Bradshaw, C. J., McMahon, C. R., & Hindell, M. A. (2007). Complex interplay between intrinsic and extrinsic drivers of long-term survival trends in

- southern elephant seals. *BMC Ecology*, 7(1), 3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6785-7-3>
- de Valpine, P., Turek, D., Paciorek, C., Anderson-Bergman, C., Temple Lang, D., & Bodik, R. (2017). Programming with models: writing statistical algorithms for general model structures with NIMBLE. *Journal of Computational and Graphical Statistics*, 26(2), 403–413. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10618600.2016.1172487>.
- Deredec, A., & Courchamp, F. (2006). Combined impacts of Allee effects and parasitism. *Oikos*, 112(3), 667–679. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0030-1299.2006.14243.x>
- Devictor, V., Whittaker, R. J., & Beltrame, C. (2010). Beyond scarcity: citizen science programmes as useful tools for conservation biogeography. *Diversity and Distributions*, 16(3), 354–362. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1472-4642.2009.00615.x>
- Dickinson, J. L., Zuckerberg, B., & Bonter, D. N. (2010). Citizen science as an ecological research tool: challenges and benefits. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics*, 41(1), 149–172. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ecolsys-102209-144636>
- Didham, R. K., Tylianakis, J. M., Gemmell, N. J., Rand, T. A., & Ewers, R. M. (2007). Interactive effects of habitat modification and species invasion on native species decline. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 22(9), 489–496. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2007.07.001>
- Dijkstra, B., & Dillerop, R. (2016). *Jaarbericht Scholeksteronderzoek Assen en omstreken 2015*.
- Dingemanse, N. J., Dochtermann, N., & Wright, J. (2010). A method for exploring the structure of behavioural syndromes to allow formal comparison within and between data sets. *Animal Behaviour*, 79(2), 439–450. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anbehav.2009.11.024>
- Dochtermann, N. A., & Jenkins, S. H. (2007). Behavioural syndromes in Merriam's kangaroo rats (*Dipodomys merriami*): a test of competing hypotheses. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 274, 2343–2349. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2007.0622>
- Dufty, A. M. (1989). Testosterone and survival: A cost of aggressiveness? *Hormones and Behavior*, 23, 185–193. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0018-506X\(89\)90059-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0018-506X(89)90059-7)
- Dunn, J. C., Hamer, K. C., & Benton, T. G. (2015). Anthropogenically-mediated density

dependence in a declining farmland bird. *PLoS ONE*, *10*(10), e0139492.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0139492>

Durell, S. E. A. L. V. D., Goss-Custard, J. D., & Caldow, R. W. G. (1993). Sex-related differences in diet and feeding method in the oystercatcher *Haematopus ostralegus*. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, *62*, 205–215. <https://doi.org/10.2307/5495>

Durell, S. E. A. L. V. D., Goss-Custard, J. D., Caldow, R. W. G., Malcolm, H. M., & Osborn, D. (2001a). Sex, diet and feeding method related differences in body condition in the oystercatcher *Haematopus ostralegus*. *Ibis*, *143*, 107–119. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1474-919X.2001.tb04175.x>

Durell, S. E. A. L. V. D., Goss-Custard, J. D., Stillman, R. A., & West, A. D. (2001b). The effect of weather and density-dependence on oystercatcher *Haematopus ostralegus* winter mortality. *Ibis*, *143*, 498–499. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1474-919X.2001.tb04952.x>

Duriez, O., Ens, B. J., Choquet, R., Pradel, R., & Klaassen, M. (2012). Comparing the seasonal survival of resident and migratory oystercatchers: carry-over effects of habitat quality and weather conditions. *Oikos*, *121*(6), 862–873. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0706.2012.20326.x>

Duriez, O., Ferrand, Y., Binet, F., Corda, E., Gossmann, F., & Fritz, H. (2005). Habitat selection of the Eurasian woodcock in winter in relation to earthworms availability. *Biological Conservation*, *122*(3), 479–490. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2004.08.011>

E

Edmonson, A. J., Lean, I. J., Weaver, L. D., Farver, T., & Webster, G. (1989). A body condition scoring chart for holstein dairy cows. *Journal of Dairy Science*, *72*(1), 68–78. [https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302\(89\)79081-0](https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(89)79081-0)

Edwards, C. A., & Lofty, J. R. (1978). The influence of arthropods and earthworms upon root growth of direct drilled cereals. *The Journal of Applied Ecology*, *15*(3), 789. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2402776>

Ekman, J. B., & Liliendahl, K. (1993). Using priority to food access: fattening strategies in dominance-structured Willow Tit (*Parus montanus*) flocks. *Behavioral Ecology*, *4*(3), 232–238.

Ellis, E. C., Kaplan, J. O., Fuller, D. Q., Vavrus, S., Klein Goldewijk, K., & Verburg, P. H. (2013). Used planet: A global history. *Proceedings of the National Academy of*

- Sciences*, 110(20), 7978–7985. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1217241110>
- Ens, B. J. (1991). Guarding your mate and losing the egg: an oystercatcher's dilemma. *Wader Study Group Bulletin*, 61, 69–70.
- Ens, B. J., Aarts, B., Hallmann, C., Oosterbeek, K., Sierdsema, H., Slaterus, R., Troost, G., Van Turnhout, C., Wiersma, P., Van Winden, E., & Nienhuis, J. (2011). *Scholeksters in de knel: onderzoek naar de oorzaken van de dramatische achteruitgang van de Scholekster in Nederland*. SOVON Vogelonderzoek Nederland.
- Ens, B. J., Briggs, K. B., Safriel, U. N., Smit, C. J., & Goss-Custard, J. D. (1996). Life history decisions during the breeding season. In J. D. Goss-Custard (Ed.), *The Oystercatcher: From Individuals to Populations* (pp. 186–218). Oxford University Press.
- Ens, B. J., & Cayford, J. T. (1996). Feeding with other Oystercatchers. In J. D. Goss-Custard (Ed.), *The Oystercatcher: From Individuals to Populations*. (pp. 77–104). Oxford University Press.
- Ens, B. J., & Underhill, L. G. (2014). Synthesis of oystercatcher conservation assessments: general lessons and recommendations. *International Wader Studies*, 20, 5–22.
- Eraud, C., Devevey, G., Gaillard, M., Prost, J., Sorci, G., & Faivre, B. (2007). Environmental stress affects the expression of a carotenoid-based sexual trait in male zebra finches. *Journal of Experimental Biology*, 210(20), 3571–3578. <https://doi.org/10.1242/jeb.005496>
- Evans, K. L. (2004). The potential for interactions between predation and habitat change to cause population declines of farmland birds. *Ibis*, 146(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1474-919X.2004.00231.x>

F

- Feddema, J. J., Oleson, K. W., Bonan, G. B., Mearns, L. O., Buja, L. E., Meehl, G. A., & Washington, W. M. (2005). The importance of land-cover change in simulating future climates. *Science*, 310(5754), 1674–1678. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1118160>
- Felici, L. D., Piersma, T., & Howison, R. A. (2019). Abundance of arthropods as food for meadow bird chicks in response to short- and long-term soil wetting in Dutch dairy grasslands. *PeerJ*, 7, e7401. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.7401>

- Fink, D., Auer, T., Johnston, A., Ruiz-Gutierrez, V., Hochachka, W. M., & Kelling, S. (2020). Modeling avian full annual cycle distribution and population trends with citizen science data. *Ecological Applications*, *30*(3), e02056. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.2056>
- Foley, J. A., DeFries, R., Asner, G. P., Barford, C., Bonan, G., Carpenter, S. R., Chapin, F. S., Coe, M. T., Daily, G. C., Gibbs, H. K., Helkowski, J. H., Holloway, T., Howard, E. A., Kucharik, C. J., Monfreda, C., Patz, J. A., Prentice, I. C., Ramankutty, N., & Snyder, P. K. (2005). Global consequences of land use. *Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1111772>
- Foley, J. A., Ramankutty, N., Brauman, K. A., Cassidy, E. S., Gerber, J. S., Johnston, M., Mueller, N. D., O'Connell, C., Ray, D. K., West, P. C., Balzer, C., Bennett, E. M., Carpenter, S. R., Hill, J., Monfreda, C., Polasky, S., Rockström, J., Sheehan, J., Siebert, S., ... Zaks, D. P. M. (2011). Solutions for a cultivated planet. *Nature*, *478*(7369), 337–342. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature10452>
- Forsman, J. T., Mikko Mönkkönen, M., Inkeröinen, J., & Reunanen, P. (1998). Aggregate dispersion of birds after encountering a predator: experimental evidence. *Journal of Avian Biology*, *29*(1), 44–48.
- Franks, S. E., Roodbergen, M., Teunissen, W., Carrington Cotton, A., & Pearce-Higgins, J. W. (2018). Evaluating the effectiveness of conservation measures for European grassland-breeding waders. *Ecology and Evolution*, *8*(21), 10555–10568. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.4532>
- Fransson, T., Jansson, L., Kolehmainen, T., Kroon, C., & Wenninger, T. (2017). *EURING list of longevity records for European birds*. <https://euring.org/data-and-codes/longevity-list>
- Frauendorf, M., Allen, A. M., Jongejans, E., Ens, B. J., Teunissen, W., Kampichler, C., van Turnhout, C. A. M., Bailey, L. D., de Kroon, H., Cremer, J., Kleyheeg, E., Nienhuis, J., & van de Pol, M. (2022). Love thy neighbour? – Spatial variation in density dependence of nest survival in relation to predator community. *Diversity and Distributions*, *28*(4), 624–635. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.13457>
- Frauendorf, M., Allen, A. M., Verhulst, S., Jongejans, E., Ens, B. J., van der Kolk, H.-J., de Kroon, H., Nienhuis, J., & van de Pol, M. (2021). Conceptualizing and quantifying body condition using structural equation modelling: A user guide. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, *90*(11), 2478–2496. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2656.13578>
- Freckleton, R. P. (2002). On the misuse of residuals in ecology: regression of residuals

vs. multiple regression. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, 71(3), 542–545.
<https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2656.2002.00618.x>

Froy, H., Phillips, R. A., Wood, A. G., Nussey, D. H., & Lewis, S. (2013). Age-related variation in reproductive traits in the wandering albatross: evidence for terminal improvement following senescence. *Ecology Letters*, 16(5), 642–649.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12092>

G

Gelman, A. (1996). Inference and monitoring convergence. In W. R. Gilks, S. Richardson, & D. J. Spiegelhalter (Eds.), *Markov chain Monte Carlo in practice* (pp. 131–143). Chapman and Hall.

Gelman, A., Goodrich, B., Gabry, J., & Vehtari, A. (2019). R-squared for Bayesian regression models. *The American Statistician*, 73(3), 307–309.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00031305.2018.1549100>

German, A. J., Holden, S. L., Moxham, G. L., Holmes, K. L., Hackett, R. M., & Rawlings, J. M. (2006). A simple, reliable tool for owners to assess the body condition of their dog or cat. *The Journal of Nutrition*, 136(7), 2031S–2033S.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jn/136.7.2031S>

Gibbens, J., & Arnould, J. P. Y. (2009). Interannual variation in pup production and the timing of breeding in benthic foraging Australian fur seals. *Marine Mammal Science*, 25(3), 573–587. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1748-7692.2008.00270.x>

Gleeson, D. J., Blows, M. W., & Owens, I. P. (2005). Genetic covariance between indices of body condition and immunocompetence in a passerine bird. *BMC Evolutionary Biology*, 5, 61. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2148-5-61>

Gochfeld, M. (1984). Shorebirds. In J. Burger & B. L. Olla (Eds.), *Antipredator behavior: aggressive and distraction displays of shorebirds* (pp. 289–377). Springer.

Goss-Custard, J. D. (1984). Intake rate and food supply in migrating and wintering shorebirds. In J. Burger & B. L. Olla (Eds.), *Behaviour of Marine Animals* (Vol. 6, pp. 233–270). Plenum Press.

Goss-Custard, J. D. (1996). *The Oystercatcher: from individuals to populations* (1st edition). Oxford University Press.

Goss-Custard, J. D., & Durell, S. E. A. L. V. dit. (1983). Individual and age differences in the feeding ecology of Oystercatchers *Haematopus ostralegus* wintering on the

- Exe Estuary, Devon. *Ibis*, 125(2), 155–171. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1474-919X.1983.tb03096.x>
- Goss-Custard, J. D., Le V. dit Durell, S. E. A., Sitters, H. P., & Swinfen, R. (1982). Age-structure and survival of a wintering population of Oystercatchers. *Bird Study*, 29(2), 83–98. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00063658209476743>
- Goss-Custard, J. D., le V., S., Clarke, R. T., Beintema, A. J., Caldow, R. W. G., Meininger, P. L., & Smit, C. J. (1996). Population dynamics: predicting the consequences of habitat change at the continental scale. In J. D. Goss-Custard (Ed.), *The Oystercatcher: from individuals to populations*. Oxford University Press.
- Grace, J. B. (2006). *Structural Equation Modeling and Natural Systems*. Cambridge University Press.
- Grace, J. B., Anderson, T. M., Olf, H., & Scheiner, S. M. (2010). On the specification of structural equation models for ecological systems. *Ecological Monographs*, 80(1), 67–87. <https://doi.org/10.1890/09-0464.1>
- Grace, J. B., Anderson, T. M., Seabloom, E. W., Borer, E. T., Adler, P. B., Harpole, W. S., Hautier, Y., Hillebrand, H., Lind, E. M., Partel, M., Bakker, J. D., Buckley, Y. M., Crawley, M. J., Damschen, E. I., Davies, K. F., Fay, P. A., Firn, J., Gruner, D. S., Hector, A., ... Smith, M. D. (2016). Integrative modelling reveals mechanisms linking productivity and plant species richness. *Nature*, 529, 390–393. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature16524>
- Grace, J. B., & Bollen, K. A. (2008). Representing general theoretical concepts in structural equation models: the role of composite variables. *Environmental and Ecological Statistics*, 15(2), 191–213. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10651-007-0047-7>
- Grace, J. B., & Keeley, J. E. (2006). A structural equation model analysis of postfire plant diversity in California shrublands. *Ecological Applications*, 16(2), 503–514. [https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761\(2006\)016\[0503:asemao\]2.0.co;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761(2006)016[0503:asemao]2.0.co;2)
- Green, A. J. (2001). Mass/length residuals: measures of body condition or generators of spurious results? *Ecology*, 82(5), 1473–1483. [https://doi.org/10.1890/0012-9658\(2001\)082\[1473:MLRMOB\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/0012-9658(2001)082[1473:MLRMOB]2.0.CO;2)
- Greenwood, J. J. D. (2007). Citizens, science and bird conservation. *Journal of Ornithology*, 148(S1), 77–124. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10336-007-0239-9>
- Griminger, P. (1986). Lipid metabolism. In P. D. Sturkie (Ed.), *Avian Physiology*. Springer.

- Guan, L., Jia, Y., Saintilan, N., Wang, Y., Liu, G., Lei, G., & Wen, L. (2016). Causality between abundance and diversity is weak for wintering migratory waterbirds. *Freshwater Biology*, *61*(2), 206–218. <https://doi.org/10.1111/fwb.12694>
- Gunnarsson, G., & Elmberg, J. (2008). Density-dependent nest predation—an experiment with simulated mallard nests in contrasting landscapes. *Ibis*, *150*(2), 259–269. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1474-919X.2007.00772.x>
- Gunnarsson, T. G., Gill, J. A., Atkinson, P. W., Gélinaud, G., Potts, P. M., Croger, R. E., Gudmundsson, G. A., Appleton, G. F., & Sutherland, W. J. (2006). Population-scale drivers of individual arrival times in migratory birds. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, *75*(5), 1119–1127. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2656.2006.01131.x>
- Gunnarsson, T. G., Gill, J. A., Newton, J., Potts, P. M., & Sutherland, W. J. (2005). Seasonal matching of habitat quality and fitness in a migratory bird. *Proceedings. Biological sciences*, *272*(1578), 2319–2323. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2005.3214>

H

- Hanssen, S. A., Hasselquist, D., Folstad, I., & Erikstad, K. E. (2005). Cost of reproduction in a long-lived bird: incubation effort reduces immune function and future reproduction. *Proceedings. Biological sciences*, *272*(1567), 1039–1046. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2005.3057>
- Harrison, X. A., Blount, J. D., Inger, R., Norris, D. R., & Bearhop, S. (2011). Carry-over effects as drivers of fitness differences in animals. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, *80*(1), 4–18. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2656.2010.01740.x>
- Hartig, F. (2021). *DHARMA: Residual Diagnostics for Hierarchical (Multi-Level / Mixed) Regression Models* (0.4.4) [Computer software]. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=DHARMA>
- Hegemann, A., Marra, P. P., & Tieleman, B. I. (2015). Causes and consequences of partial migration in a passerine bird. *American Naturalist*, *186*(4), 531–546. <https://doi.org/10.1086/682667>
- Heppleston, P. B. (1971). The feeding ecology of oystercatchers (*Haematopus ostralegus* L.) in winter in Northern Scotland. *The Journal of Animal Ecology*, *40*(3), 651. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3443>
- Hogstad, O. (1995). Do avian and mammalian nest predators select for different nest dispersion patterns of Fieldfares *Turdus pilaris*? A 15-year study. *Ibis*, *137*, 484–

489.

- Hooper, D., Coughlan, J., & Mullen, M. R. (2008). Structural Equation Modelling: Guidelines for determining model fit. *The Electronic Journal of Business Research Methods*, 6(1), 53–60. <https://doi.org/10.21427/D7CF7R>
- Hopcraft, J. G., Anderson, T. M., Perez-Vila, S., Mayemba, E., & Olff, H. (2012). Body size and the division of niche space: food and predation differentially shape the distribution of Serengeti grazers. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, 81(1), 201–213. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2656.2011.01885.x>
- Hornman, M., Hustings, F., Koffijberg, K., & Klaassen, O. (2012). *Handleiding Sovon Watervogel- en Slaapplaatstellingen* (p. 28). Sovon Vogelonderzoek Nederland.
- Hothorn, T., Hornik, K., & Zeileis, A. (2012). Unbiased recursive partitioning: A conditional inference framework. *Journal of Computational and Graphical Statistics*. <https://doi.org/10.1198/106186006X133933>
- Hothorn, T., & Zeileis, A. (2015). partykit: a modular toolkit for recursive partytioning in R. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 16(118), 3905–3909.
- Hötker, H. (2010). Correction factors for hatching success rates of meadow birds not derived by the Mayfield method. *Wader Study Group Bulletin*, 117(1), 59–61.
- Hu, L., & Bentler, P. M. (1999). Cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 6(1), 1–55. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10705519909540118>
- Hulscher, J. B. (1996). Food and feeding behaviour. In J. D. Gross-Custard (Ed.), *The Oystercatcher: from individuals to populations*. (pp. 7–29). Oxford University Press.
- Hulscher, J. B., & Verhulst, S. (2003). The rise and fall of the breeding population of oystercatchers *Haematopus ostralegus* in Friesland 1966–2000. *Limosa*, 76, 11–22.
- I
- Ijnsen, F. (1988). Het karakteriseren van winters: koudegetallen en wintercijfers. *Zenit*, 15(2), 50–55.
- J
- Jablonszky, M., Szász, E., Krenhardt, K., Markó, G., Hegyi, G., Herényi, M., Laczi, M., Nagy, G., Rosivall, B., Szöllösi, E., Török, J., & Garamszegi, L. Z. (2018). Unravelling the relationships between life history, behaviour and condition under the pace-of-

- life syndromes hypothesis using long-term data from a wild bird. *Behavioral Ecology and Sociobiology*, 72(3), 52. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00265-018-2461-2>
- Jackson, A. S., Stanforth, P. R., Gagnon, J., Rankinen, T., Leon, A. S., Rao, D. C., Skinner, J. S., Bouchard, C., & Wilmore, J. H. (2002). The effect of sex, age and race on estimating percentage body fat from body mass index: The Heritage Family Study. *International Journal of Obesity*, 26(6), 789–796. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.ijo.0802006>
- Jager, T. D., Hulscher, J. B., & Kersten, M. (2000). Egg size, egg composition and reproductive success in the Oystercatcher *Haematopus ostralegus*. *Ibis*, 142, 603–613. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1474-919X.2000.tb04460.x>
- Jak, S., & Jorgensen, T. D. (2017). Relating measurement invariance, cross-level invariance, and multilevel reliability. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8, 1640. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.01640>
- Jakob, E. M., Marshall, S. D., & Uetz, G. W. (1996). Estimating fitness: A comparison of body condition indices. *Oikos*, 77(1), 61–67. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3545585>
- James, G., Witten, D., Hastie, T., & Tibshirani, R. (2013). *An introduction to statistical learning - with applications in R* (Vol. 103). Springer New York. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-7138-7>
- Janssen, M. H., Arcese, P., Kyser, T. K., Bertram, D. F., & Norris, D. R. (2011). Stable isotopes reveal strategic allocation of resources during juvenile development in a cryptic and threatened seabird, the Marbled Murrelet (*Brachyramphus marmoratus*). *Canadian Journal of Zoology*, 89(9), 859–868. <https://doi.org/10.1139/z11-058>
- Jean-Gagnon, F., Legagneux, P., Gilchrist, G., Bélanger, S., Love, O. P., & Bêty, J. (2018). The impact of sea ice conditions on breeding decisions is modulated by body condition in an arctic partial capital breeder. *Oecologia*, 186(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-017-4002-5>
- Jiguet, F. (2020). The Fox and the Crow. A need to update pest control strategies. *Biological Conservation*, 248, 108693. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2020.108693>
- Jiguet, F., Gadot, A.-S., Julliard, R., Newson, S. E., & Couvet, D. (2007). Climate envelope, life history traits and the resilience of birds facing global change. *Global Change Biology*, 13(8), 1672–1684. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365->

2486.2007.01386.x

- Jimeno, B., Briga, M., Verhulst, S., & Hau, M. (2017a). Effects of developmental conditions on glucocorticoid concentrations in adulthood depend on sex and foraging conditions. *Hormones and Behavior*, *93*, 175–183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yhbeh.2017.05.020>
- Jimeno, B., Hau, M., & Verhulst, S. (2017b). Strong association between corticosterone levels and temperature-dependent metabolic rate in individual zebra finches. *The Journal of Experimental Biology*, *220*(23), 4426–4431. <https://doi.org/10.1242/jeb.166124>
- Jimeno, B., Hau, M., & Verhulst, S. (2018). Corticosterone levels reflect variation in metabolic rate, independent of 'stress'. *Scientific Reports*, *8*(1), 13020. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-31258-z>
- Johnston, A., Fink, D., Hochachka, W. M., & Kelling, S. (2018). Estimates of observer expertise improve species distributions from citizen science data. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, *9*(1), 88–97. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12838>

K

- Kampichler, C., Hallmann, C., & Sierdsema, H. (2020). *SDMaps: an R package for the analysis of species abundance and distribution data. Extended Manual*. Sovon Vogelonderzoek Nederland. <https://www.sovon.nl/nl/content/trimmaps>
- Kampichler, C., Sierdsema, H., Roodbergen, M., & Ens, B. J. (2013). *Ruimtelijke analyses van dichtheden en trends van binnendijks broedende Scholeksters*. Sovon Vogelonderzoek Nederland.
- Kassambara, A., & Mundt, F. (2020). *factoextra: extract and visualize the results of multivariate data analyses. R package version 1.0.7*.
- Kellner, K. (2019). *jagsUI: A Wrapper Around 'rjags' to Streamline 'JAGS' Analyses. R package version 1.5.1*.
- Kentie, R., Both, C., Hooijmeijer, J. C. E. W., & Piersma, T. (2015). Management of modern agricultural landscapes increases nest predation rates in Black-tailed Godwits *Limosa limosa*. *Ibis*, *157*(3), 614–625. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ibi.12273>
- Kentie, R., Coulson, T., Hooijmeijer, J. C. E. W., Howison, R. A., Loonstra, A. H. J., Verhoeven, M. A., Both, C., & Piersma, T. (2018). Warming springs and habitat alteration interact to impact timing of breeding and population dynamics in a

- migratory bird. *Global Change Biology*, 24(11), 5292–5303.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14406>
- Kentie, R., Hooijmeijer, J. C. E. W., Trimbos, K. B., Groen, N. M., & Piersma, T. (2013). Intensified agricultural use of grasslands reduces growth and survival of precocial shorebird chicks. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 50(1), 243–251.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12028>
- Kersten, M. A. J. M. (1997). *Living leisurely should last longer: Energetic aspects of reproduction in the oystercatcher* [PhD thesis]. University of Groningen.
- Kersten, M., & Piersma, T. (1987). High levels of energy expenditure in shorebirds; metabolic adaptations to an energetically expensive way of life. *Ardea*, 55(1–2), 175–187. <https://doi.org/10.5253/arde.v75.p175>
- King, C. M., & Powell, R. A. (2006). *The natural history of weasels and stoats: ecology, behavior, and management*. Oxford University Press.
- Kirk, D. A., & Gosler, A. G. (1994). Body condition varies with migration and competition in migrant and resident South American vultures. *Auk*, 111(4), 933–944. <https://doi.org/10.2307/4088825>
- Kitaysky, A. S., Kitaiskaia, E. V., Piatt, J. F., & Wingfield, J. C. (2003). Benefits and costs of increased levels of corticosterone in seabird chicks. *Hormones and Behavior*, 43(1), 140–149. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0018-506x\(02\)00030-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0018-506x(02)00030-2)
- Kitaysky, A. S., Wingfield, J. C., & Piatt, J. F. (1999). Dynamics of food availability, body condition and physiological stress response in breeding Black-legged Kittiwakes. *Functional Ecology*, 13, 577–584. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2435.1999.00352.x>
- Kitikidou, K., Papakosta, M., Bakaloudis, D., & Vlachos, C. (2014). Dietary variation of the stone marten (*Martes foina*): A meta-analysis approach. *Wildlife Biology in Practice*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.2461/wbp.2014.10.11>
- Kleijn, D., Schekkerman, H., Dimmers, W. J., van Kats, R. J. M., Melman, D., & Teunissen, W. A. (2010). Adverse effects of agricultural intensification and climate change on breeding habitat quality of Black-tailed Godwits *Limosa l. limosa* in the Netherlands. *Ibis*, 152(3), 475–486. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1474-919X.2010.01025.x>
- Kline, R. B. (2011). *Principles and Practice of Structural Equation Modeling* (3rd ed.). The Guilford Press.

- Knipl, D., & Rost, G. (2016). Spatially heterogeneous populations with mixed negative and positive local density dependence. *Theoretical Population Biology*, *109*, 6–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tpb.2016.01.001>
- KNMI. (2020a). *Daggegevens van het weer in Nederland - Download*. <https://www.knmi.nl/nederland-nu/klimatologie>
- KNMI. (2020b). *Langjarige gemiddelde maandsom van de neerslag*.
- Kobori, H., Dickinson, J. L., Washitani, I., Sakurai, R., Amano, T., Komatsu, N., Kitamura, W., Takagawa, S., Koyama, K., Ogawara, T., & Miller-Rushing, A. J. (2016). Citizen science: a new approach to advance ecology, education, and conservation. *Ecological Research*, *31*(1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11284-015-1314-y>
- Koffijberg, K., de Boer, P., Geelhoed, S. C. V., Nienhuis, J., Schekkerman, H., Oosterbeek, K., & Postma, J. (2021). *Broedsucces van kustbroedvogels in de Waddenzee in 2019* (WOt-technical report No. 209). Wettelijke Onderzoekstaken Natuur & Milieu. <https://doi.org/10.18174/553633>
- Kouwenberg, A.-L., Hipfner, J. M., McKay, D. W., & Storey, A. E. (2013). Corticosterone and stable isotopes in feathers predict egg size in Atlantic Puffins *Fratercula arctica*. *Ibis*, *155*(2), 413–418. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ibi.12030>
- Kramer, A. M., Dennis, B., Liebhold, A. M., & Drake, J. M. (2009). The evidence for Allee effects. *Population Ecology*, *51*(3), 341–354. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10144-009-0152-6>
- Kramer, A. M., Sarnelle, O., & Yen, J. (2011). The effect of mating behavior and temperature variation on the critical population density of a freshwater copepod. *Limnology and Oceanography*, *56*(2), 707–715. <https://doi.org/10.4319/lo.2011.56.2.0707>
- Krams, I., Bērziņš, A., & Krama, T. (2009). Group effect in nest defence behaviour of breeding pied flycatchers, *Ficedula hypoleuca*. *Animal Behaviour*, *77*(2), 513–517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anbehav.2008.11.007>
- Krams, I., Vrublevska, J., Cirule, D., Kivleniece, I., Krama, T., Rantala, M. J., Kaasik, A., Hõrak, P., Sepp, T., & Fusani, L. (2013). Stress, behaviour and immunity in wild-caught wintering great tits (*Parus major*). *Ethology*, *119*(5), 397–406. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eth.12075>
- Kruger, L. E., & Shannon, M. A. (2000). Getting to know ourselves and our places through participation in civic social assessment. *Society & Natural Resources*,

13(5), 461–478. <https://doi.org/10.1080/089419200403866>

Kuczyński, L., & Chylarecki, P. (2012). *Atlas pospolitych ptaków lęgowych Polski. Rozmieszczenie, wybiórczość siedliskowa, trendy*. GIOŚ.

Kuhn, M., Contributions from Wing, J., Weston, S., Williams, A., Keefer, C., Engelhardt, A., Cooper, T., Mayer, Z., Kenkel, B., R Core Team, Benesty, M., Lescarbeau, R., Ziem, A., Scrucca, L., Tang, Y., Candan, C., & Hunt, T. (2018). *caret: classification and regression training*.

L

Laake, J. L. (2013). *RMark: an R interface for analysis of capture – recapture data with MARK*. AFSC Processed Report.

Landschapsbeheer Nederland. (2009). *Maatregelencatalogus ter verbetering van het leefgebied van de steenuil*. <https://www.steenuil.nl/userfiles/Handboek.pdf>

Larivière, S., & Messier, F. (1998). Effect of density and nearest neighbours on simulated waterfowl nests: can predators recognize high-density nesting patches? *Oikos*, 83(1), 12–20. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3546541>

Larsen, T., & Grundetjern, S. (1997). Optimal choice of neighbour: predator protection among tundra birds. *Journal of Avian Biology*, 303–308. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3676943>

Le, S., Josse, J., & Husson, F. (2008). FactoMineR: An R Package for Multivariate Analysis. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 25(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v025.i01>

Lea, A. J., Barrera, J. P., Tom, L. M., & Blumstein, D. T. (2008). Heterospecific eavesdropping in a nonsocial species. *Behavioral Ecology*, 19(5), 1041–1046. <https://doi.org/10.1093/beheco/arn064>

Lebeuf, A. P., & Giroux, J.-F. (2014). Density-dependent effects on nesting success of temperate-breeding Canada geese. *Journal of Avian Biology*, 45(6), 600–608. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jav.00320>

Lefcheck, J. S. (2016). piecewiseSEM: Piecewise structural equation modeling in R for ecology, evolution, and systematics. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 7(5), 573–579. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12512>

Lefcheck, J. S. (2019). *Structural Equation Modeling in R for Ecology and Evolution*. https://jslefeche.github.io/sem_book/index.html

- Leuthold, W. (2012). *African ungulates: a comparative review of their ethology and behavioral ecology*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Liaw, A., & Wiener, M. (2002). Classification and Regression by randomForest. *R News*, 2, 18–22.
- Lin, D. Y., Psaty, B. M., & Kronmal, R. A. (1998). Assessing the sensitivity of regression results to unmeasured confounders in observational studies. *Biometrics*, 54(3), 948–963. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2533848>
- Linszen, H., van de Pol, M., Allen, A. M., Jans, M., Ens, B. J., Krijgsveld, K. L., Frauendorf, M., & van der Kolk, H.-J. (2019). Disturbance increases high tide travel distance of a roosting shorebird but only marginally affects daily energy expenditure. *Avian Research*, 10(31), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40657-019-0171-8>
- Lode, T. (2000). Functional response and area-restricted search in a predator: seasonal exploitation of anurans by the European polecat, *Mustela putorius*. *Austral Ecology*, 25, 223–231. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1442-9993.2000.01024.x>
- Lombardi, L., Fernández, N., Moreno, S., & Villafuerte, R. (2003). Habitat-related differences in rabbit (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) abundance, distribution, and activity. *Journal of Mammalogy*, 84(1), 26–36. [https://doi.org/10.1644/1545-1542\(2003\)084<0026:HRDIRO>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1644/1545-1542(2003)084<0026:HRDIRO>2.0.CO;2)
- Loss, S. R., Will, T., & Marra, P. P. (2013). The impact of free-ranging domestic cats on wildlife of the United States. *Nature Communications*, 4(1), 1396. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms2380>
- Low, M., Arlt, D., Pärt, T., & Öberg, M. (2015). Delayed timing of breeding as a cost of reproduction. *Journal of Avian Biology*, 46(4), 325–331. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jav.00623>
- Lukyanenko, R., Parsons, J., & Wiersma, Y. F. (2016). Emerging problems of data quality in citizen science. *Conservation Biology*, 30(3), 447–449. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12706>
- Lundberg, P. (1988). The evolution of partial migration in birds. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 3(7), 172–175. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-5347\(88\)90035-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-5347(88)90035-3)
- Luque, G. M., Vayssade, C., Facon, B., Guillemaud, T., Courchamp, F., & Fauvergue, X. (2016). The genetic Allee effect: a unified framework for the genetics and demography of small populations. *Ecosphere*, 7(7), e01413.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/ecs2.1413>

M

- MacCracken, J. G., & Stebbings, J. L. (2012). Test of a body condition index with amphibians. *Journal of Herpetology*, *46*(3), 346–350. <https://doi.org/10.1670/10-292>
- MacKay, A. E., Forsyth, D. M., Coulson, G., & Festa-Bianchet, M. (2017). Maternal resource allocation adjusts to timing of parturition in an asynchronous breeder. *Behavioral Ecology and Sociobiology*, *72*(1), 7. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00265-017-2419-9>
- Magrath, R. D., Haff, T. M., Fallow, P. M., & Radford, A. N. (2015). Eavesdropping on heterospecific alarm calls: from mechanisms to consequences. *Biological Reviews of the Cambridge Philosophical Society*, *90*(2), 560–586. <https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.12122>
- Major, R. E., & Kendal, C. E. (1996). The contribution of artificial nest experiments to understanding avian reproductive success: a review of methods and conclusions. *Ibis*, *138*(2), 298–307. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1474-919X.1996.tb04342.x>
- Makowski, D., Ben-Shachar, M. S., & Lüdtke, D. (2019). bayestestR: describing effects and their uncertainty, existence and significance within the Bayesian framework. *Journal of Open Source Software*, *4*(40), 1541. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.01541>
- Malpas, L. R., Kennerley, R. J., Hirons, G. J. M., Sheldon, R. D., Ausden, M., Gilbert, J. C., & Smart, J. (2013). The use of predator-exclusion fencing as a management tool improves the breeding success of waders on lowland wet grassland. *Journal for Nature Conservation*, *21*(1), 37–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnc.2012.09.002>
- Marchand, P., Loretto, M.-C., Henry, P.-Y., Duriez, O., Jiguet, F., Bugnyar, T., & Itty, C. (2018). Relocations and one-time disturbance fail to sustainably disperse non-breeding common ravens *Corvus corax* due to homing behaviour and extensive home ranges. *European Journal of Wildlife Research*, *64*(5), 57. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10344-018-1217-7>
- Marra, P. P., Cohen, E. B., Loss, S. R., Rutter, J. E., & Tonra, C. M. (2015). A call for full annual cycle research in animal ecology. *Biology Letters*, *11*(8), 4. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2015.0552>
- Marra, P. P., Hobson, K. A., & Holmes, R. T. (1998). Linking winter and summer events in a migratory bird by using stable-carbon isotopes. *Science*, *282*(5395), 1884–

1886.

- Marra, P. P., & Holberton, R. L. (1998). Corticosterone levels as indicators of habitat quality: effects of habitat segregation in a migratory bird during the non-breeding season. *Oecologia*, *116*, 284–292.
- Martay, B., & Pearce-Higgins, J. W. (2020). Opening a can of worms: Can the availability of soil invertebrates be indicated by birds? *Ecological Indicators*, *113*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.106222>
- Martig, R. (2017). *Negative density dependent nest predation in a wader breeding community with declining populations [MSc. thesis]*. Leiden University.
- Mason, L. R., Smart, J., & Drewitt, A. L. (2018). Tracking day and night provides insights into the relative importance of different wader chick predators. *Ibis*, *160*(1), 71–88. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ibi.12523>
- Mayer, M., Frank, S. C., Zedrosser, A., & Rosell, F. (2019). Causes and consequences of inverse density-dependent territorial behaviour and aggression in a monogamous mammal. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, *89*, 577–588. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2656.13100>
- Mayfield, H. (1975). Suggestions for calculating nesting success. *Wilson Bulletin*, *87*, 456–466.
- McCandless, L. C., Gustafson, P., & Levy, A. (2007). Bayesian sensitivity analysis for unmeasured confounding in observational studies. *Statistics in Medicine*, *26*(11), 2331–2347. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sim.2711>
- McDonald, R. A., Webbon, C., & Harris, S. (2000). The diet of stoats (*Mustela erminea*) and weasels (*Mustela nivalis*) in Great Britain. *Journal of Zoology*, *252*(3), 363–371. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7998.2000.tb00631.x>
- McGregor, H., Moseby, K., Johnson, C. N., & Legge, S. (2020). The short-term response of feral cats to rabbit population decline: Are alternative native prey more at risk? *Biological Invasions*, *22*(2), 799–811. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-019-02131-5>
- McGuire, L. P., Kelly, L. A., Baloun, D. E., Boyle, W. A., Cheng, T. L., Clerc, J., Fuller, N. W., Gerson, A. R., Jonasson, K. A., Rogers, E. J., Sommers, A. S., & Guglielmo, C. G. (2018). Common condition indices are no more effective than body mass for estimating fat stores in insectivorous bats. *Journal of Mammalogy*, *99*(5), 1065–1071. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jmammal/gyy103>
- McNamara, J. M., & Houston, A. I. (2008a). Introduction. Adaptation to the annual

- cycle. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London B: Biological Sciences*, 363(1490), 209–210. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2007.2192>
- McNamara, J. M., & Houston, A. I. (2008b). Optimal annual routines: behaviour in the context of physiology and ecology. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 363(1490), 301–319. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2007.2141>
- Metón, I., Mediavilla, D., Caseras, A., Cantó, E., Fernández, F., & Baanante, I. V. (1999). Effect of diet composition and ration size on key enzyme activities of glycolysis–gluconeogenesis, the pentose phosphate pathway and amino acid metabolism in liver of gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*). *British Journal of Nutrition*, 82(3), 223–232. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0007114599001403>
- Milenkaya, O., Catlin, D. H., Legge, S., & Walters, J. R. (2015). Body condition indices predict reproductive success but not survival in a sedentary, tropical bird. *PLOS ONE*, 10(8), e0136582. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0136582>
- Moiron, M., Araya-Ajoy, Y. G., Mathot, K. J., Mouchet, A., & Dingemanse, N. J. (2019). Functional relations between body mass and risk-taking behavior in wild great tits. *Behavioral Ecology*, 30(3), 617–623. <https://doi.org/10.1093/beheco/ary199>
- Møller, A. P., Thorup, O., & Laursen, K. (2018). Predation and nutrients drive population declines in breeding waders. *Ecological Applications*, 28(5), 1292–1301. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.1729>
- Montreuil-Spencer, C., Schoenemann, K., Lendvai, Á. Z., & Bonier, F. (2019). Winter corticosterone and body condition predict breeding investment in a nonmigratory bird. *Behavioral Ecology*, 30(6), 1642–1652. <https://doi.org/10.1093/beheco/arz129>
- Mora, C., Metzger, R., Rollo, A., & Myers, R. A. (2007). Experimental simulations about the effects of overexploitation and habitat fragmentation on populations facing environmental warming. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 274(1613), 1023–1028. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2006.0338>
- Moritz, C., & Agudo, R. (2013). The future of species under climate change: resilience or decline? *Science*, 341(6145), 504–508. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.123719>
- Morris, T. P., White, I. R., & Crowther, M. J. (2019). Using simulation studies to evaluate statistical methods. *Statistics in Medicine*, 38(11), 2074–2102. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sim.8086>

- Moyer-Horner, L., Smith, M. M., & Belt, J. (2012). Citizen science and observer variability during American pika surveys. *The Journal of Wildlife Management*, 76(7), 1472–1479. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jwmg.373>
- Muff, S., Nilsen, E. B., O’Hara, R. B., & Nater, C. R. (2021). Rewriting results sections in the language of evidence. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2021.10.009>
- Murphy, R. K., Michaud, I. M. G., Prescott, D. R. C., Ivan, J. S., Anderson, B. J., & French-Pombier, M. L. (2003). Predation on adult piping plovers at predator exclosure cages. *Waterbirds*, 26(2), 150–155. [https://doi.org/10.1675/1524-4695\(2003\)026\[0150:POAPPA\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1675/1524-4695(2003)026[0150:POAPPA]2.0.CO;2)
- Musil, C. M., Jones, S. L., & Warner, C. D. (1998). Structural equation modeling and its relationship to multiple regression and factor analysis. *Research in Nursing & Health*, 21, 271–281. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1098-240X\(199806\)21:3<271::AID-NUR10>3.0.CO;2-G](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1098-240X(199806)21:3<271::AID-NUR10>3.0.CO;2-G)

N

- Nams, V. O. (1997). Density-dependent predation by skunks using olfactory search images. *Oecologia*, 110(3), 440–448.
- Neff, B. D., & Cargnelli, L. M. (2004). Relationships between condition factors, parasite load and paternity in bluegill sunfish, *Lepomis macrochirus*. *Environmental Biology of Fishes*, 71, 297–304. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10641-004-1263-8>
- Nespolo, R. F., Arim, M., & Bozinovic, F. (2003). Body size as a latent variable in a structural equation model: thermal acclimation and energetics of the leaf-eared mouse. *Journal of Experimental Biology*, 206(13), 2145–2157. <https://doi.org/10.1242/jeb.00396>
- Netwerk Ecologische Monitoring, Sovon, provinces & CBS. (2021). *Sovon Vogelonderzoek | Vind informatie over vogelsoorten*. <https://stats.sovon.nl/stats>
- Newman, C., Buesching, C. D., & Macdonald, D. W. (2003). Validating mammal monitoring methods and assessing the performance of volunteers in wildlife conservation—“Sed quis custodiet ipsos custodiet?” *Biological Conservation*, 113(2), 189–197. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3207\(02\)00374-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3207(02)00374-9)
- Nichols, J. D., Kendall, W. L., & Runge, M. C. (2004). Estimating survival and movement. In W. J. Sutherland, I. Newton, & R. E. Green (Eds.), *Bird Ecology and Conservation - A Handbook of Techniques*. Oxford University Press.

- Nie, Y., Zhang, Z., Raubenheimer, D., Elser, J. J., Wei, W., Wei, F., & Kay, A. (2014). Obligate herbivory in an ancestrally carnivorous lineage: the giant panda and bamboo from the perspective of nutritional geometry. *Functional Ecology*, *29*(1), 26–34. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2435.12302>
- Nienhuis, J. (2015). *Pixel Grabber, version 1.4*.
- Nolet, B. A., Bauer, S., Feige, N., Kokorev, Y. I., Popov, I. Y., & Ebbinge, B. S. (2013). Faltering lemming cycles reduce productivity and population size of a migratory Arctic goose species. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, *82*(4), 804–813. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2656.12060>
- Noon, B. R., & Dale, V. H. (2002). Broad-scale ecological science and its application. In K. J. Gutzwiller (Ed.), *Applying Landscape Ecology in Biological Conservation* (pp. 34–52). Springer New York. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4613-0059-5_3
- Nordberg, E. J., & Schwarzkopf, L. (2019). Predation risk is a function of alternative prey availability rather than predator abundance in a tropical savanna woodland ecosystem. *Scientific Reports*, *9*(1), 7718. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-44159-6>
- Norris, D. R., & Marra, P. P. (2007). Seasonal interactions, habitat quality, and population dynamics in migratory birds. *The Condor*, *109*(3), 535–547. <https://doi.org/10.1093/condor/109.3.535>
- Norris, D. R., Marra, P. P., Kyser, K. T., Sherry, T. W., & Ratcliffe, L. M. (2004). Tropical winter habitat limits reproductive success on the temperate breeding grounds in a migratory bird. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series B: Biological Sciences*, *271*(1534), 59–64. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1098/rspb.2003.2569>
- Norte, A. C., Ramos, J. A., Sousa, J. P., & Sheldon, B. C. (2009). Variation of adult Great Tit *Parus major* body condition and blood parameters in relation to sex, age, year and season. *Journal of Ornithology*, *150*(3), 651. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10336-009-0387-1>
- Nummela, S., Pihlstrom, H., Puolamaki, K., Fortelius, M., Hemila, S., & Reuter, T. (2013). Exploring the mammalian sensory space: co-operations and trade-offs among senses. *Journal of Comparative Physiology A: Neuroethology, Sensory, Neural, and Behavioral Physiology*, *199*(12), 1077–1092. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00359-013-0846-2>
- Nummi, P., & Saari, L. (2003). Density-dependent decline of breeding success in an

introduced, increasing mute swan *Cygnus olor* population. *Journal of Avian Biology*, 34(1), 105–111. <https://doi.org/10.1034/j.1600-048X.2003.02801.x>

Nusair, K., & Hua, N. (2010). Comparative assessment of structural equation modeling and multiple regression research methodologies: E-commerce context. *Tourism Management*, 31(3), 314–324. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2009.03.010>

Nuttall, F. Q. (2015). Body mass index: obesity, BMI, and health: A critical review. *Nutrition Today*, 50(3), 117–128. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NT.0000000000000092>

O

Oldekop, J. A., Bebbington, A. J., Berdel, F., Truelove, N. K., Wiersberg, T., & Preziosi, R. F. (2011). Testing the accuracy of non-experts in biodiversity monitoring exercises using fern species richness in the Ecuadorian Amazon. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 20(12), 2615–2626. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-011-0094-0>

Olivier, F., Franeker, J. A. van, Creuwels, J. C. S., & Woehler, E. J. (2005). Variations of snow petrel breeding success in relation to sea-ice extent: detecting local response to large-scale processes? *Polar Biology*, 28(9), 687–699. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00300-005-0734-5>

Olson, R. S., Haley, P. B., Dyer, F. C., & Adami, C. (2015). Exploring the evolution of a trade-off between vigilance and foraging in group-living organisms. *Royal Society Open Science*, 2(9), 150135. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.150135>

Onrust, J., Wymenga, E., Piersma, T., & Olff, H. (2019). Earthworm activity and availability for meadow birds is restricted in intensively managed grasslands. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 56(6), 1333–1342. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13356>

Oro, D., Martinez-Abraín, A., Paracuellos, M., Nevado, J. C., & Genovart, M. (2006). Influence of density dependence on predator-prey seabird interactions at large spatio-temporal scales. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 273(1584), 379–383. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2005.3287>

Ouyang, J. Q., Sharp, P. J., Dawson, A., Quetting, M., & Hau, M. (2011). Hormone levels predict individual differences in reproductive success in a passerine bird. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 278(1717), 2537–2545. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2010.2490>

P

- Palmer, W. E., Carroll, J. P., Sisson, D. C., Wellendorf, S. D., Terhune, T. M., Ellis-Felege, S. N., & Martin, J. A. (2019). Reduction in meso-mammal nest predators improves northern bobwhite demographics. *Journal of Wildlife Management*, *83*(3), 646–656. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jwmg.21627>
- Pavliška, P. L., Riegert, J., Grill, S., & Šálek, M. (2018). The effect of landscape heterogeneity on population density and habitat preferences of the European hare (*Lepus europaeus*) in contrasting farmlands. *Mammalian Biology*, *88*, 8–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mambio.2017.11.003>
- Peig, J., & Green, A. J. (2009). New perspectives for estimating body condition from mass/length data: the scaled mass index as an alternative method. *Oikos*, *118*(12), 1883–1891. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0706.2009.17643.x>
- Peig, J., & Green, A. J. (2010). The paradigm of body condition: a critical reappraisal of current methods based on mass and length. *Functional Ecology*, *24*(6), 1323–1332. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2435.2010.01751.x>
- Perez, C., Granadeiro, J. P., Dias, M. P., & Catry, P. (2016). Sex and migratory strategy influence corticosterone levels in winter-grown feathers, with positive breeding effects in a migratory pelagic seabird. *Oecologia*, *181*(4), 1025–1033. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-016-3625-2>
- Perez-Rodriguez, L. (2009). Carotenoids in evolutionary ecology: re-evaluating the antioxidant role. *Bioessays*, *31*(10), 1116–1126. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bies.200900070>
- Philip, S. Y., Kew, S. F., van der Wiel, K., Wanders, N., & Jan van Oldenborgh, G. (2020). Regional differentiation in climate change induced drought trends in the Netherlands. *Environmental Research Letters*, *15*(9), 094081. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ab97ca>
- Picman, J. (1988). Experimental study of predation on eggs of ground-nesting birds: effects of habitat and nest distribution. *The Condor*, *90*(1), 124–131.
- Piersma, T., Everaarts, J. M., & Jukema, J. (1996). Build-up of red blood cells in refuelling Bar-Tailed Godwits in relation to individual migratory quality. *The Condor*, *98*(2), 363–370. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1369154>
- Plard, F., Bruns, H. A., Cimiotti, D. V., Helmecke, A., Hötcker, H., Jeromin, H., Roodbergen, M., Schekkerman, H., Teunissen, W., Jeugd, H., & Schaub, M. (2019). Low productivity and unsuitable management drive the decline of central

- European lapwing populations. *Animal Conservation*, 23(3), 286–296.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/acv.12540>
- Poole, D. W., & McKillop, I. G. (2002). Effectiveness of two types of electric fence for excluding the Red Fox (*Vulpes vulpes*). *Mammal Review*, 32(1), 51–57.
<https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2907.2002.00095.x>
- Preininger, D., Schoas, B., Kramer, D., & Boeckle, M. (2019). Waste disposal sites as all-you-can eat buffets for carrion crows (*Corvus corone*). *Animals*, 9(5), 215.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/ani9050215>
- Prop, J., & Quinn, J. L. (2003). Constrained by available raptor hosts and islands: density-dependent reproductive success in red-breasted geese. *Oikos*, 102(3), 571–580. <https://doi.org/10.1034/j.1600-0706.2003.12244.x>
- Provoost, S., Jones, M. L. M., & Edmondson, S. E. (2011). Changes in landscape and vegetation of coastal dunes in northwest Europe: a review. *Journal of Coastal Conservation*, 15(1), 207–226. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11852-009-0068-5>
- Pugesek, B. H., & Tomer, A. (1995). Determination of selection gradients using multiple regression versus structural equation models (SEM). *Biometrical Journal*, 37(4), 449–462. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bimj.4710370406>
- Pugesek, B. H., & Tomer, A. (1996). The Bumpus house sparrow data: a reanalysis using structural equation models. *Evolutionary Ecology*, 10, 387–404.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/bf01237725>
- Q**
- Quesada, J., & Senar, J. C. (2006). Comparing plumage colour measurements obtained directly from live birds and from collected feathers: the case of the great tit *Parus major*. *Journal of Avian Biology*, 37, 609–616. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0908-8857.2006.03636.x>
- Quinn, J. L., & Ueta, M. (2008). Protective nesting associations in birds. *Ibis*, 150, 146–167. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1474-919X.2008.00823.x>
- R**
- R Core Team. (2019). *R: A language and environment for statistical computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria.
- Rangen, S. A., Clark, R. G., & Hobson, K. A. (2000). Visual and olfactory attributes of artificial nests. *Auk*, 117(1), 136–146.

- Rangen, S. A., Clark, R. G., & Hobson, K. A. (2001). Predator responses to similarity and dispersion of artificial nest sites: implications for the structure of boreal forest songbird communities. *Auk*, *118*(1), 105–115. <https://doi.org/10.2307/4089761>
- Rappoldt, C., Roosenschoon, O. R., & van Kraalingen, D. W. G. (2014). *InterTides; maps of the intertidal by interpolation of tidal gauge data*. (p. 36). EcoCurves BV.
- Reppert, S. M., & de Roode, J. C. (2018). Demystifying monarch butterfly migration. *Current Biology*, *28*(17), R1009–R1022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2018.02.067>
- Reséndiz-Infante, C., Gauthier, G., & Souchay, G. (2020). Consequences of a changing environment on the breeding phenology and reproductive success components in a long-distance migratory bird. *Population Ecology*, *62*(2), 284–296. <https://doi.org/10.1002/1438-390x.12046>
- Rickenbach, O., Grüebler, M. U., Schaub, M., Koller, A., Naef-Daenzer, B., & Schifferli, L. (2011). Exclusion of ground predators improves Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus* chick survival. *Ibis*, *153*(3), 531–542. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1474-919X.2011.01136.x>
- Rijksoverheid. (2021). *Data from: Basisregistratie Gewaspercelen (BRP)*. Rijksoverheid. <https://www.pdok.nl/introductie/-/article/basisregistratie-gewaspercelen-brp>
- Rijkswaterstaat. (2021). *Data from: Dataregister Rijkswaterstaat*. Rijkswaterstaat. <https://maps.rijkswaterstaat.nl/dataregister/srv/dut/catalog.search#/metadata/0bb7f390-7761-41da-b341-828c1bc74b5c?tab=contact>
- Ringelman, K. M. (2014). Predator foraging behavior and patterns of avian nest success: What can we learn from an agent-based model? *Ecological Modelling*, *272*, 141–149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2013.09.028>
- Ringelman, K. M., Eadie, J. M., & Ackerman, J. T. (2012). Density-dependent nest predation in waterfowl: the relative importance of nest density versus nest dispersion. *Oecologia*, *169*(3), 695–702. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-011-2228-1>
- Ritchie, E. G., & Johnson, C. N. (2009). Predator interactions, mesopredator release and biodiversity conservation. *Ecology Letters*, *12*(9), 982–998. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2009.01347.x>
- Rivers, J. W., Liebl, A. L., Owen, J. C., Martin, L. B., Betts, M. G., & Grindstaff, J. (2012). Baseline corticosterone is positively related to juvenile survival in a migrant passerine bird. *Functional Ecology*, *26*(5), 1127–1134.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2435.2012.02025.x>

- Roberson, L. L., Aneni, E. C., Maziak, W., Agatston, A., Feldman, T., Rouseff, M., Tran, T., Blaha, M. J., Santos, R. D., Sposito, A., Al-Mallah, M. H., Blankstein, R., Budoff, M. J., & Nasir, K. (2014). Beyond BMI: The 'Metabolically healthy obese' phenotype & its association with clinical/subclinical cardiovascular disease and all-cause mortality - a systematic review. *BMC Public Health*, *14*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-14-14>
- Robinson, O. J., Ruiz-Gutierrez, V., & Fink, D. (2018). Correcting for bias in distribution modelling for rare species using citizen science data. *Diversity and Distributions*, *24*(4), 460–472. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12698>
- Roche, J. R., Friggens, N. C., Kay, J. K., Fisher, M. W., Stafford, K. J., & Berry, D. P. (2009). Invited review: Body condition score and its association with dairy cow productivity, health, and welfare. *Journal of Dairy Science*, *92*(12), 5769–5801. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2009-2431>
- Rock, P., Camphuysen, C. J., Shamoun-Baranes, J., Ross-Smith, V. H., & Vaughan, I. P. (2016). Results from the first GPS tracking of roof-nesting Herring Gulls *Larus argentatus* in the UK. *Ringing & Migration*, *31*(1), 47–62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03078698.2016.1197698>
- Rockström, J., Steffen, W., Noone, K., Persson, Å., Chapin, F. S., Lambin, E. F., Lenton, T. M., Scheffer, M., Folke, C., Schellnhuber, H. J., Nykvist, B., de Wit, C. A., Hughes, T., van der Leeuw, S., Rodhe, H., Sörlin, S., Snyder, P. K., Costanza, R., Svedin, U., ... Foley, J. A. (2009). A safe operating space for humanity. *Nature*, *461*(7263), 472–475. <https://doi.org/10.1038/461472a>
- Rödel, H. G., & Stubbe, M. (2006). Shift in food availability and associated shifts in space use and diet in stone marten. *Lutra*, *49*(1), 67–72.
- Roodbergen, M., & Teunissen, W. (2014). Meadow bird conservation in The Netherlands – lessons from the past and future developments. *Vogelwelt*, *135*, 29–34.
- Roodbergen, M., & Teunissen, W. (2019). Meadow birds in The Netherlands. *Wader Study*, *126*(1), 7–18. <https://doi.org/10.18194/ws.00134>
- Roodbergen, M., van der Werf, B., & Hötker, H. (2012). Revealing the contributions of reproduction and survival to the Europe-wide decline in meadow birds: review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Ornithology*, *153*(1), 53–74.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10336-011-0733-y>

- Roos, S., Smart, J., Gibbons, D. W., & Wilson, J. D. (2018). A review of predation as a limiting factor for bird populations in mesopredator-rich landscapes: a case study of the UK. *Biological Reviews of the Cambridge Philosophical Society*, *93*(4), 1915–1937. <https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.12426>
- Rosenberg, K. V., Lowe, J. D., & Dhondt, A. A. (1999). Effects of forest fragmentation on breeding tanagers: a continental perspective. *Conservation Biology*, *13*(3), 568–583. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1523-1739.1999.98020.x>
- Rosseel, Y. (2012). lavaan: An R Package for Structural Equation Modeling. *Journal of Statistical Software*, *48*(2), 1–36. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v048.i02>
- Rothschild, B. J., Sharov, A. F., Kearsley, A. J., & Bondarenko, A. S. (1997). Estimating growth and mortality in stage-structured populations. *Journal of Plankton Research*, *19*(12), 1913–1928. <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/19.12.1913>
- Russel, A. J. F., Doney, J. M., & Gunn, R. G. (1969). Subjective assessment of body fat in live sheep. *The Journal of Agricultural Science*, *72*(3), 451–454. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021859600024874>
- Rutgers, M., Orgiazzi, A., Gardi, C., Römbke, J., Jänsch, S., Keith, A. M., Neilson, R., Boag, B., Schmidt, O., Murchie, A. K., Blackshaw, R. P., Pérès, G., Cluzeau, D., Guernion, M., Briones, M. J. I., Rodeiro, J., Piñeiro, R., Cosín, D. J. D., Sousa, J. P., ... Zwart, D. de. (2016). Mapping earthworm communities in Europe. *Applied Soil Ecology*, *97*, 98–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2015.08.015>

S

- Sæther, B.-E. (1997). Environmental stochasticity and population dynamics of large herbivores: a search for mechanisms. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, *12*(4), 143–149. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347\(96\)10068-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347(96)10068-9)
- Sæther, B.-E., & Bakke, Ø. (2000). Avian life history variation and contribution of demographic traits to the population growth rate. *Ecology*, *81*(3), 642–653. [https://doi.org/10.1890/0012-9658\(2000\)081\[0642:ALHVAC\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/0012-9658(2000)081[0642:ALHVAC]2.0.CO;2)
- Saino, N., & Møller, A. P. (1995). Testosterone correlates of mate guarding, singing and aggressive behaviour in male barn swallows, *Hirundo rustica*. *Animal Behaviour*, *49*, 465–472. <https://doi.org/10.1006/anbe.1995.0060>
- Sarychev, V., & Mischenko, A. (2014). Conservation assessment of *Haematopus*

ostralegus longipes. *International Wader Studies*, 20, 33–40.

- Schekkerman, H., & Beintema, A. J. (2007). Abundance of Invertebrates and Foraging Success of Black-Tailed Godwit *Limosa limosa* Chicks in Relation to Agricultural Grassland Management. *Ardea*, 95(1), 39–54.
<https://doi.org/10.5253/078.095.0105>
- Schekkerman, H., Teunissen, W., & Oosterveld, E. (2009). Mortality of Black-tailed Godwit *Limosa limosa* and Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus* chicks in wet grasslands: influence of predation and agriculture. *Journal of Ornithology*, 150(1), 133. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10336-008-0328-4>
- Schmeller, D. S., Henry, P.-Y., Julliard, R., Gruber, B., Clobert, J., Dziock, F., Lengyel, S., Nowicki, P., Déri, E., Budrys, E., Kull, T., Tali, K., Bauch, B., Settele, J., van Swaay, C., Kobler, A., Babij, V., Papastergiadou, E., & Henle, K. (2009). Advantages of volunteer-based biodiversity monitoring in Europe. *Conservation Biology*, 23(2), 307–316. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2008.01125.x>
- Schmidt, K. A., & Whelan, C. J. (1999). Nest predation on woodland songbirds: when is nest predation density dependent? *Oikos*, 65–74.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/3546997>
- Schoech, S. J., Bowman, R., & Reynolds, S. J. (2004). Food supplementation and possible mechanisms underlying early breeding in the Florida Scrub-Jay (*Aphelocoma coerulescens*). *Hormones and Behavior*, 46(5), 565–573.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yhbeh.2004.06.005>
- Schulte-Hostedde, A. I., Zinner, B., Millar, J. S., & Hickling, G. J. (2005). Restitution of mass-size residuals: validating body condition indices. *Ecology*, 86(1), 155–163.
<https://doi.org/10.1890/04-0232>
- Schultner, J., Moe, B., Chastel, O., Tartu, S., Bech, C., & Kitaysky, A. S. (2014). Corticosterone mediates carry-over effects between breeding and migration in the kittiwake *Rissa tridactyla*. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 496, 125–U382.
<https://doi.org/10.3354/meps10603>
- Schwemmer, P., Hälterlein, B., Geiter, O., Günther, K., Corman, V. M., & Garthe, S. (2014). Weather-related winter mortality of Eurasian oystercatchers (*Haematopus ostralegus*) in the Northeastern Wadden Sea. *Waterbirds*, 37(3), 319–330.
<https://doi.org/10.1675/063.037.0310>
- Seibold, S., Gossner, M. M., Simons, N. K., Bluthgen, N., Muller, J., Ambarli, D.,

- Ammer, C., Bauhus, J., Fischer, M., Habel, J. C., Linsenmair, K. E., Naus, T., Penone, C., Prati, D., Schall, P., Schulze, E. D., Vogt, J., Wollauer, S., & Weisser, W. W. (2019). Arthropod decline in grasslands and forests is associated with landscape-level drivers. *Nature*, *574*(7780), 671–674. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-019-1684-3>
- Semeniuk, C. A. D., & Dill, L. M. (2006). Anti-predator benefits of mixed-species groups of cowtail stingrays (*Pastinachus sephen*) and whiplays (*Himantura uarnak*) at rest. *Ethology*, *112*(1), 33–43. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0310.2006.01108.x>
- Seymour, A. S., Harris, S., Ralston, C., & White, P. C. L. (2003). Factors influencing the nesting success of Lapwings *Vanellus vanellus* and behaviour of Red Fox *Vulpes vulpes* in Lapwing nesting sites. *Bird Study*, *50*(1), 39–46. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00063650309461288>
- Sheriff, M. J., Krebs, C. J., & Boonstra, R. (2009). The sensitive hare: sublethal effects of predator stress on reproduction in snowshoe hares. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, *78*(6), 1249–1258. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2656.2009.01552.x>
- Shipley, B. (2016). *Cause and Correlation in Biology - A User's Guide to Path Analysis, Structural Equations and Causal Inference with R* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Simons, M. J. P., Briga, M., Koetsier, E., Folkertsma, R., Wubs, M. D., Dijkstra, C., & Verhulst, S. (2012a). Bill redness is positively associated with reproduction and survival in male and female zebra finches. *PLoS ONE*, *7*(7), e40721. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0040721>
- Simons, M. J. P., Cohen, A. A., & Verhulst, S. (2012b). What does carotenoid-dependent coloration tell? Plasma carotenoid level signals immunocompetence and oxidative stress state in birds-A meta-analysis. *PLoS ONE*, *7*(8), e43088. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0043088>
- Skarpaas, O., Silverman, E. J., Jongejans, E., & Shea, K. (2011). Are the best dispersers the best colonizers? Seed mass, dispersal and establishment in *Carduus*. *Evolutionary Ecology*, *25*(1), 155–169. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10682-010-9391-4>
- Smith, D. H. V., Moller, H., Wilson, D. J., & Murphy, E. C. (2010). Prey switching by stoats (*Mustela erminea*): a supplemental food experiment. *Wildlife Research*, *37*(7), 604–611. <https://doi.org/10.1071/WR10088>

- Smith, P. A., Tulp, I., Schekkerman, H., Gilchrist, H. G., & Forbes, M. R. (2012). Shorebird incubation behaviour and its influence on the risk of nest predation. *Animal Behaviour*, *84*(4), 835–842. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.anbehav.2012.07.004>
- Smith, R. K., Pullin, A. S., Stewart, G. B., & Sutherland, W. J. (2011). Is nest predator exclusion an effective strategy for enhancing bird populations? *Biological Conservation*, *144*(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2010.05.008>
- Sönnichsen, L., Bokje, M., Marchal, J., Hofer, H., Jędrzejewska, B., Kramer-Schadt, S., & Ortmann, S. (2013). Behavioural responses of European roe deer to temporal variation in predation risk. *Ethology*, *119*(3), 233–243. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eth.12057>
- Sorensen, M. C., Hipfner, J. M., Kyser, T. K., & Norris, D. R. (2009). Carry-over effects in a Pacific seabird: stable isotope evidence that pre-breeding diet quality influences reproductive success. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, *78*(2), 460–467. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2656.2008.01492.x>
- Souchay, G., Gauthier, G., & Pradel, R. (2013). Temporal variation of juvenile survival in a long-lived species: the role of parasites and body condition. *Oecologia*, *173*(1), 151–160. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-013-2613-z>
- Souchay, G., van Wijk, R. E., Schaub, M., & Bauer, S. (2018). Identifying drivers of breeding success in a long-distance migrant using structural equation modelling. *Oikos*, *127*(1), 125–133. <https://doi.org/10.1111/oik.04247>
- Sousa, S. I. V., Martins, F. G., Alvim-Ferraz, M. C. M., & Pereira, M. C. (2007). Multiple linear regression and artificial neural networks based on principal components to predict ozone concentrations. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, *22*(1), 97–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2005.12.002>
- Sovon Vogelonderzoek Nederland. (2018). *Vogelatlas van Nederland. Broedvogels, wintervogels en 40 jaar verandering*. Kosmos Uitgevers.
- Sprenger, D., Dingemanse, N. J., Dochtermann, N. A., Theobald, J., & Walker, S. P. W. (2012). Aggressive females become aggressive males in a sex-changing reef fish. *Ecology Letters*, *15*(9), 986–992. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2012.01819.x>
- Stan Development Team. (2020). *RStan: the R interface to Stan. R package version 2.19.3*.

- Steffen, W., Crutzen, P. J., & McNeill, J. R. (2007). The anthropocene: are humans now overwhelming the great forces of nature. *AMBIO: A Journal of the Human Environment*, 36(8), 614–621. [https://doi.org/10.1579/0044-7447\(2007\)36\[614:TAAHNO\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1579/0044-7447(2007)36[614:TAAHNO]2.0.CO;2)
- Steiger, J. H. (2007). Understanding the limitations of global fit assessment in structural equation modeling. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 42(5), 893–898. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2006.09.017>
- Stephens, P. A., & Sutherland, W. J. (1999). Consequences of the Allee effect for behaviour, ecology and conservation. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 14(10), 401–405. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347\(99\)01684-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347(99)01684-5)
- Stevens, M., Partridge, J., Párraga, C. A., Troscianko, T. S., & Innes, C. (2007). Using digital photography to study animal coloration. *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 90, 211–237. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-8312.2007.00725.x>
- Stevenson, R. D., & Woods, J. W. A. (2006). Condition indices for conservation: new uses for evolving tools. *Integrative and Comparative Biology*, 46(6), 1169–1190. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icb/icl052>
- Stirling, I., & Derocher, A. E. (2012). Effects of climate warming on polar bears: a review of the evidence. *Global Change Biology*, 18(9), 2694–2706. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2012.02753.x>
- Strijkstra, R. J. (1986). *Oosterkwelder: het broedseizoen van de scholekster*. University of Groningen.
- Swanson, D. L., Liknes, E. T., & Dean, K. L. (1999). Differences in migratory timing and energetic condition among sex/age classes in migrant ruby-crowned kinglets. *The Wilson Bulletin*, 61–69.
- Swennen, C. (1984). Differences in quality of roosting flocks of Oystercatchers. In P. R. Evans, J. D. Goss-Custard, & W. G. Hale (Eds.), *Coastal waders and wildfowl in winter*. (pp. 177–189). Cambridge University Press.
- Swift, R. J., Rodewald, A. D., Johnson, J. A., Andres, B. A., & Senner, N. R. (2020). Seasonal survival and reversible state effects in a long-distance migratory shorebird. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, 89(9), 2043–2055. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2656.13246>
- Szabo, J. K., Vesk, P. A., Baxter, P. W. J., & Possingham, H. P. (2010). Regional avian species declines estimated from volunteer-collected long-term data using List

Length Analysis. *Ecological Applications*, 20(8), 2157–2169.
<https://doi.org/10.1890/09-0877.1>

T

- Taillon, J., Sauvé, D. G., & Côté, S. D. (2006). The effects of decreasing winter diet quality on foraging behavior and life-history traits of white-tailed deer fawns. *The Journal of Wildlife Management*, 70(5), 1445–1454. [https://doi.org/10.2193/0022-541x\(2006\)70\[1445:Teodwd\]2.0.Co;2](https://doi.org/10.2193/0022-541x(2006)70[1445:Teodwd]2.0.Co;2)
- Tamario, C., Sunde, J., Petersson, E., Tibblin, P., & Forsman, A. (2019). Ecological and evolutionary consequences of environmental change and management actions for migrating fish. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 7, 271.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2019.00271>
- Terhune II, T. M., Palmer, W. E., & Wellendorf, S. D. (2019). Northern bobwhite chick survival and effects of weather. *The Journal of Wildlife Management*, 83(4), 963–974. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jwmg.21655>
- Tête, N., Fritsch, C., Afonso, E., Coeurdassier, M., Lambert, J.-C., Giraudoux, P., & Scheifler, R. (2013). Can body condition and somatic indices be used to evaluate metal-induced stress in wild small mammals? *PLoS ONE*, 8(6), e66399.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0066399>
- Teunissen, W., Kampichler, C., Majoor, F., Roodbergen, M., & Kleyheeg, E. (2020). *Predatieproblematiek bij weidevogels*. Sovon Vogelonderzoek Nederland.
- Teunissen, W., Schekkerman, H., & Willems, F. (2005). *Predatie bij weidevogels. Op zoek naar de mogelijke effecten van predatie op de weidevogelstand*. Sovon-onderzoeksrapport, Alterra-Document.
- Teunissen, W., Schekkerman, H., Willems, F., & Majoor, F. (2008). Identifying predators of eggs and chicks of Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus* and Black-tailed Godwit *Limosa limosa* in the Netherlands and the importance of predation on wader reproductive output. *Ibis*, 150, 74–85. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1474-919X.2008.00861.x>
- Timmerman, A., Bos, D., Ouweland, J., & de Goede, R. G. M. (2006). Long-term effects of fertilisation regime on earthworm abundance in a semi-natural grassland area. *Pedobiologia*, 50(5), 427–432. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedobi.2006.08.005>
- Tobin, P. C., Whitmire, S. L., Johnson, D. M., Bjornstad, O. N., & Liebhold, A. M. (2007). Invasion speed is affected by geographical variation in the strength of Allee effects.

- Ecology Letters*, 10(1), 36–43. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2006.00991.x>
- Townsend, C. R., Begon, M., & Harper, J. L. (2008). *Essentials of Ecology* (3rd ed.). Blackwell Publishing.
- Tracey, L. (1980). *Some comparative effects of earthworms and leather jackets on upland improved soils* [PhD thesis]. Durham University.
<http://etheses.dur.ac.uk/7568/>
- Travis, S. E., & Grace, J. B. (2010). Predicting performance for ecological restoration: a case study using *Spartina alterniflora*. *Ecological Applications*, 20(1), 192–204.
<https://doi.org/10.1890/08-1443.1>
- Troost, K., Asch, M. van, Brummelhuis, E., Ende, D. van den, Es, Y. van, Perdon, K. J., Pool, J. van der, Zweeden, C. van, & Zwol, J. van. (2021). *Schelpdierbestanden in de Nederlandse kustzone, Waddenzee en zoute deltawateren in 2020*.
<https://doi.org/10.18174/538895>
- Troost, K., Van Asch, M., & Van Zweeden, C. (2017). *Het kokkelbestand in de Nederlandse kustwateren in 2017: CVO Report 17.013*. Stichting Wageningen Research, Centrum voor Visserijonderzoek (CVO).
- Tsahar, E., Arad, Z., Izhaki, I., & Guglielmo, C. G. (2006). The relationship between uric acid and its oxidative product allantoin: a potential indicator for the evaluation of oxidative stress in birds. *Journal of Comparative Physiology B*, 176(7), 653–661.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00360-006-0088-5>
- Tulloch, A. I. T., Possingham, H. P., Joseph, L. N., Szabo, J., & Martin, T. G. (2013). Realising the full potential of citizen science monitoring programs. *Biological Conservation*, 165, 128–138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2013.05.025>

U

- Ullman-Culler, M. H. (1999). Body condition scoring: a rapid and accurate method for assessing health status in mice. *Laboratory Animal Science*, 49(3), 5.

V

- van de Pol, M., Atkinson, P., Blew, J., Crowe, O., Delany, S., Duriez, O., Ens, B. J., Hälterlein, B., Hötker, H., Laursen, K., Oosterbeek, K., Petersen, A., Thorup, O., Tjørve, K., Triplet, P., & Yésou, P. (2014). A global assessment of the conservation status of the nominate subspecies of Eurasian oystercatcher *Haematopus ostralegus ostralegus*. *International Wader Studies*, 20, 47–61.

- van de Pol, M., Ens, B. J., Oosterbeek, K., Brouwer, L., Verhulst, S., Tinbergen, J. M., Rutten, A. L., & de Jong, M. (2009a). Oystercatchers' bill shapes as a proxy for diet specialization: More differentiation than meets the eye. *Ardea*, *97*(3), 335–347. <https://doi.org/10.5253/078.097.0309>
- van de Pol, M., Oosterbeek, K., Rutten, A. L., Ens, B. J., Tinbergen, J. M., & Verhulst, S. (2009b). Biometric sex discrimination is unreliable when sexual dimorphism varies within and between years: an example in Eurasian oystercatchers *Haematopus ostralegus*. *Ibis*, *151*, 171–180. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1474-919X.2008.00891.x>
- van De Pol, M., & Pettifor, R. A. (2006). *Identifying the main causes of phenotypic variation and covariation in life-history traits in a long-lived species*. In: *State-dependent life-history strategies* [PhD thesis]. University of Groningen.
- van de Pol, M., Vindenes, Y., Sæther, B.-E., Engen, S., Ens, B. J., Oosterbeek, K., & Tinbergen, J. M. (2010). Effects of climate change and variability on population dynamics in a long-lived shorebird. *Ecology*, *91*(4), 1192–1204. <https://doi.org/10.1890/09-0410.1>
- van de Pol, M., & Wright, J. (2009). A simple method for distinguishing within- versus between-subject effects using mixed models. *Animal Behaviour*, *77*(3), 753–758. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anbehav.2008.11.006>
- van der Kolk, H.-J., Allen, A. M., Ens, B. J., Oosterbeek, K., Jongejans, E., & van de Pol, M. (2020). Spatiotemporal variation in disturbance impacts derived from simultaneous tracking of aircraft and shorebirds. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, *57*(12), 2406–2418. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13742>
- van der Kolk, H.-J., Ens, B. J., Oosterbeek, K., Bouten, W., Allen, A. M., Frauendorf, M., Lameris, T. K., Oosterbeek, T., Deuzeman, S., de Vries, K., Jongejans, E., & van de Pol, M. (2019). Shorebird feeding specialists differ in how environmental conditions alter their foraging time. *Behavioral Ecology*, *31*(2), 371–382. <https://doi.org/10.1093/beheco/arz189>
- van der Meer, J., Dankers, N., Ens, Bruno. J., van Stralen, M., Troost, K., & Waser, A. M. (2019). The birth, growth and death of intertidal soft-sediment bivalve beds: no need for large-scale restoration programs in the Dutch Wadden Sea. *Ecosystems*, *22*(5), 1024–1034. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-018-0320-7>
- van der Meer, J., & Piersma, T. (1994). Physiologically inspired regression models for estimating and predicting nutrient stores and their composition in birds. *Physiological Zoology*, *67*(2), 305–329.

- <https://doi.org/10.1086/physzool.67.2.30163851>
- van Dijk, A. J., Noback, M., Troost, G., Vergeer, J.-W., Sierdsema, H., & van Turnhout, C. (2013). De introductie van Autocluster in het Broedvogel Monitoring Project. *Limosa*, *86*, 94–102.
- van Turnhout, C. A. M. (2010). *Birding for science and conservation - Explaining temporal changes in breeding bird diversity in the Netherlands* [PhD thesis]. Radboud University.
- van Turnhout, C. A. M., Foppen, R. P. B., Leuven, R. S. E. W., Van Strien, A., & Siepel, H. (2010). Life-history and ecological correlates of population change in Dutch breeding birds. *Biological Conservation*, *143*, 173–181.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2009.09.023>
- VanderWeele, T. J., & Arah, O. A. (2011). Unmeasured confounding for general outcomes, treatments, and confounders. *Epidemiology*, *22*(1), 42–52.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/EDE.0b013e3181f74493>
- Veldman, J., Troost, C., & Klink, A. (2021). *Brochure Soortenbescherming in Overijssel* (No. 2021/0035915; p. 33). Provincie Overijssel.
- Verboven, N., Ens, B. J., & Dechesne, S. (2001). Effect of investigator disturbance on nest attendance and egg predation in Eurasian oystercatchers. *Auk*, *118*(2), 503–508. <https://doi.org/10.1093/auk/118.2.503>
- Verhulst, S. (1998). Multiple breeding in the Great Tit; II. The costs of rearing a second clutch. *Functional Ecology*, *12*, 132–140. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2435.1998.00165.x>
- Verhulst, S., & Hogstad, O. (1996). Social dominance and energy reserves in flocks of willow tits. *Journal of Avian Biology*, *27*(3), 203–208.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/3677223>
- Verhulst, S., Oosterbeek, K., Rutten, A. L., & Ens, B. J. (2004). Shellfish fishery severely reduces condition and survival of oystercatchers despite creation of large marine protected areas. *Ecology and Society*, *9*(1), 17. <https://doi.org/10.5751/es-00636-090117>
- Villafuerte, R., & Negro, J. J. (1998). Digital imaging for colour measurement in ecological research. *Ecology Letters*, *1*, 151–154. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1461-0248.1998.00034.x>
- Visser, M. D., Muller-Landau, H. C., Schnitzer, S. A., Kroon, H., Jongejans, E., & Wright,

- S. J. (2018). A host–parasite model explains variation in liana infestation among co-occurring tree species. *Journal of Ecology*, *106*(6), 2435–2445.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.12997>
- Vitousek, M. N., Adelman, J. S., Gregory, N. C., & Clair, J. J. H. S. (2007). Heterospecific alarm call recognition in a non-vocal reptile. *Biology Letters*, *3*(6), 632–634.
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2007.0443>
- Vogelbescherming Nederland. (2017, May 9). *Muizenruiter*.
<https://www.vogelbescherming.nl/beleefdemente/blog/lezen/muizenruiter>
- von Engelhardt, N., Carere, C., Dijkstra, C., & G. G. Groothuis, T. (2006). Sex-specific effects of yolk testosterone on survival, begging and growth of zebra finches. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *273*(1582), 65–70.
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2005.3274>
- von Schantz, T., Bensch, S., Grahn, M., Hasselquist, D., & Wittzell, H. (1999). Good genes, oxidative stress and condition-dependent sexual signals. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *266*(1414), 1–12.
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.1999.0597>
- W**
- Walter, J. A., Johnson, D. M., & Haynes, K. J. (2017). Spatial variation in Allee effects influences patterns of range expansion. *Ecography*, *40*(1), 179–188.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/ecog.01951>
- Warton, D. I., & Hui, F. K. (2011). The arcsine is asinine: the analysis of proportions in ecology. *Ecology*, *92*(1), 3–10. <https://doi.org/10.1890/10-0340.1>
- Waser, A. M., Deuzeman, S., Kangeri, A. K. wa, van Winden, E., Postma, J., de Boer, P., van der Meer, J., & Ens, B. J. (2016). Impact on bird fauna of a non-native oyster expanding into blue mussel beds in the Dutch Wadden Sea. *Biological Conservation*, *202*, 39–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2016.08.007>
- Weisshaupt, N., Lehikoinen, A., Mäkinen, T., & Koistinen, J. (2021). Challenges and benefits of using unstructured citizen science data to estimate seasonal timing of bird migration across large scales. *PLOS ONE*, *16*(2), e0246572.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0246572>
- White, G. C., & Burnham, K. P. (1999). Program MARK: survival estimation from populations of marked animals. *Bird Study*, *46*(sup1), S120–S139.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00063659909477239>

- Wiersma, P., & Piersma, T. (1994). Effects of microhabitat, flocking, climate and migratory goal on energy expenditure in the annual cycle of red knots. *The Condor*, 96(2), 257–279. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1369313>
- Wiersma, P., & Piersma, T. (1995). Scoring abdominal profiles to characterize migratory cohorts of shorebirds: an example with red knots. *Journal of Field Ornithology*, 66(1), 12.
- Wilder, S. M., Raubenheimer, D., & Simpson, S. J. (2016). Moving beyond body condition indices as an estimate of fitness in ecological and evolutionary studies. *Functional Ecology*, 30(1), 108–115. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2435.12460>
- Williams, C. T., Kitaysky, A. S., Kettle, A. B., & Buck, C. L. (2008). Corticosterone levels of tufted puffins vary with breeding stage, body condition index, and reproductive performance. *General and Comparative Endocrinology*, 158(1), 29–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ygcen.2008.04.018>
- Wilson, A. J., & Nussey, D. H. (2010). What is individual quality? An evolutionary perspective. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 25(4), 207–214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2009.10.002>
- Wolak, M. E., Fairbairn, D. J., & Paulsen, Y. R. (2012). Guidelines for estimating repeatability. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 3(1), 129–137. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2041-210X.2011.00125.x>
- World Bank Group. (2021). *Population density - Netherlands | Data*. <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/EN.POP.DNST?locations=NL>

Y

- Yahner, R. H., & Mahan, C. G. (1996). Depredation of artificial ground nests in a managed, forested landscape. *Conservation Biology*, 10(1), 285–288. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1523-1739.1996.10010285.x>

Z

- Zielonka, N. B., Hawkes, R. W., Jones, H., Burnside, R. J., & Dolman, P. M. (2019). Placement, survival and predator identity of Eurasian Curlew *Numenius arquata* nests on lowland grass-heath. *Bird Study*, 66(4), 471–483. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00063657.2020.1725421>
- Zwarts, L. (1991). Seasonal variation in body weight of the bivalves *Macoma balthica*, *Scrobicularia plana*, *Mya arenaria* and *Cerastoderma edule* in the Dutch Wadden

sea. *Netherlands Journal of Sea Research*, 28(3), 231–245.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/0077-7579\(91\)90021-R](https://doi.org/10.1016/0077-7579(91)90021-R)

- Zwarts, L., Ens, B. J., Goss-Custard, J. D., Hulscher, J. B., & Durell, S. E. A. I. V. dit. (1996a). Causes of variation in prey profitability and its consequences for the intake rate of the oystercatcher *Haematopus ostralegus*. *Ardea*, 84A, 229–268.
- Zwarts, L., Hulscher, J. B., Koopman, K., Piersma, T., & Zegers, P. M. (1996b). Seasonal and annual variation in body weight, nutrient stores and mortality of oystercatchers *Haematopus ostralegus*. *Ardea*, 84A, 327–356.
- Zwarts, L., Hulscher, J. B., Koopman, K., & Zegers, P. M. (1996c). Discriminating the sex of oystercatchers *Haematopus ostralegus*. *Ardea*, 84A, 1–12.
- Zwarts, L., & Wanink, J. H. (1993). How the food supply harvestable by waders in the Wadden Sea depends on the variation in energy density, body weight, biomass, burying depth and behaviour of tidal-flat invertebrates. *Netherlands Journal of Sea Research*, 31, 441–476.

RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT

This thesis research has been carried out under the research data management policy of the Radboud Institute for Biological and Environmental Sciences, version 10-Dec-2021 accessed at <https://www.ru.nl/ribes/organisation/data-management>.

This is an overview of where data has been archived per chapter:

Chapter 1 - No data or code has been produced.

Chapter 2 - Data are available in Zonodo: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5153492>

Chapter 3 - Data are available in Zonodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5831867>

Chapter 4 - Data are available in Zonodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5718466>

Chapter 5 - Data are available in Zonodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5831867>

Chapter 6 - Data are available in Zonodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5831867>

SUMMARY

The increasing world population and associated growing needs caused that humans drastically altered their environment; consequently, putting enormous pressure on the natural ecosystems of the globe. Populations respond differently to these environmental changes and farmland birds are one of the species groups that showed, consequently, a drastic decline all across Europe. Understanding how anthropogenic impacts affect population dynamics at a large spatial scale is crucial to be able to explain why species are threatened, and also to be able to turn the tide.

With this thesis, I aim to get better insight in the factors driving the population dynamics of the Eurasian oystercatcher (*Haematopus ostralegus*) in the Netherlands with a focus on the reproduction parameters and inland breeding grounds. The oystercatcher is an ideal model species because the Dutch population showed a dramatic decline in the last decades. In addition, we already have a broad knowledge about its ecology and behaviour, but mainly from long-term monitoring and research on the Wadden Sea island Schiermonnikoog (a coastal breeding ground). Furthermore, there is a considerable citizen science network that collects a large amount of data on reproduction and survival (through resightings). This research is part of the CHIRP (Cumulative Human Impact on biRd Populations) project, which has the overall goal to quantify the cumulative impact of all potential human pressures on reproductive success and survival of oystercatchers in the Netherlands.

With the help of resighting data and field observations (from volunteers and professionals) and by using advanced statistical approaches, this thesis advances our understanding of the spatiotemporal variation in the reproductive performance of oystercatchers in the Netherlands. I hereby address three main knowledge gaps (**chapter 1**): (i) studying multiple threats and their synergistic effects on a large spatial scale (**chapter 4 & 5**) and (ii) quantifying body condition in an appropriate way (**chapter 2**) to (iii) investigate how body condition mediates the effect of winter environment on the reproductive performance in the subsequent season (**chapter 3**).

To assess environmental impacts on populations, body condition is often used as a proxy of an individual's performance. Although body condition potentially

encompasses a wide range of health state dimensions (nutritional, immune or hormonal status), in practice most studies operationalize body condition using a single (univariate) measure, such as fat storage. One reason for excluding additional axes of variation may be that multivariate descriptors of body condition impose statistical and analytical challenges. Structural equation modelling (SEM) is used in many fields to study questions relating multidimensional concepts, and we show in **chapter 2** how SEM is a useful and powerful analytical tool to describe the multivariate nature of body condition.

In **chapter 3**, we apply and expand the model approach (from **chapter 2**) to investigate how body condition is influenced by environmental drivers in winter and how it affects subsequent reproductive success (carry-over effect). It is challenging to identify the main drivers of population dynamics in migratory species, as animals can be affected at different stages of the annual cycle that are geographically separated. Furthermore, the impact of environmental drivers at overwintering sites may not be directly apparent if they carry-over to the reproductive season. Therefore, quantifying carry-over effects can help in identifying which drivers play a role in causing population decline. We quantify body condition (as shown in **chapter 2**) since it is thought to be the state variable that mediates carry-over effects. We find that the winter body condition predicted the reproductive success, indicating a carry-over effect. Clutches as well as hatchlings from parents with high preceding winter body condition survive longer in spring. The body condition in winter is positively associated with the proportion of grassland around the wintering ground. However, there is no evidence that other environmental variables in winter (shellfish availability, weather condition) affect the winter body condition.

Next to environmental conditions in winter, there may be environmental drivers during the breeding season that cause the low reproductive success in the oystercatcher population. In meadow bird research, anthropogenic factors such as agricultural intensification, predation and climate change are often mentioned as causes for population decline. However, it is also likely that different threats interact and understanding potential synergistic effects can improve our understanding of the ongoing population decline and help to identify appropriate management actions. In **chapter 5**, we identify the relative impact of environmental factors (predator species,

weather, food abundance and land use intensity) on the reproductive success and investigate their potential interacting effects. The overall average reproductive success is 0.1 fledglings/pair, which is well below what is needed for a stable population. The main bottleneck is the low hatchling survival (rather than the clutch survival). Predator abundance plays an important role in explaining variation in reproductive output and less favourable habitat (with less food) results in higher vulnerability to predation.

Another challenge in ecological research is that not only environmental drivers may interact, but also intrinsic (density-regulated) factors interacting with extrinsic (environmental) factors. It is known that density-dependent effects on reproduction can be an important driver of population dynamics. However, it is rarely considered that the direction of density-dependence is expected to vary over space and time depending on the predator community. While aggregation of prey species may allow for effective group mobbing against avian nest predators, aggregation may also attract mammalian predators, causing negative density dependent clutch survival. In **chapter 4**, we show that the spatial variation in the composition of the predator community explains the effects of neighbour (conspecific and heterospecific) density, showing decreasing clutch survival when both breeding density and mammalian dominance increases.

Chapter 6 synthesizes the contribution of this thesis to the broad ecological research and to our understanding of the spatiotemporal variation of the reproductive performance of oystercatchers in the Netherlands. With this thesis, I emphasize that a large-scale ecological approach is important to understand population dynamics because (i) different mechanisms may act at different places and (ii) that if the same mechanism acts at many places, we may still need to sample substantial spatiotemporal variation to detect and quantify relationships in a reliable way.

For the Dutch oystercatcher population, we conclude that the reproductive success is too low to keep the population stable and that we should focus on increasing hatchling survival to increase the overall reproductive output. Most important drivers of the oystercatcher reproductive performance during the breeding season are the abundance and composition of predator species. In addition, alternative foraging grounds in winter are an important determinant of hatchling survival. Based on our results from the different chapters, I provide some ideas for effective management

implications to increase the reproductive output of oystercatchers across the Netherlands.

SAMENVATTING

De groei van de wereldbevolking en de daarmee samenhangende groeiende behoeften zorgden ervoor dat de mens zijn omgeving drastisch veranderde. Als gevolg hiervan wordt er een enorme druk uitgeoefend op de natuurlijke ecosystemen van de wereld. Populaties reageren verschillend op deze veranderingen in de omgeving. Weidevogels zijn een van de soortgroepen die als gevolg hiervan in heel Europa een drastische achteruitgang laten zien. Het begrijpen van hoe antropogene effecten de populatiedynamiek op grote ruimtelijke schaal beïnvloeden, is cruciaal om te kunnen verklaren waarom soorten worden bedreigd, en ook om het tij te kunnen keren.

Met dit proefschrift wil ik een beter inzicht krijgen in de factoren die de populatiedynamiek van de scholekster (*Haematopus ostralegus*) in Nederland beïnvloeden, met de focus op het broedsucces van in het binnenland broedende scholeksters. De scholekster is een ideale studiesoort omdat de Nederlandse populatie de laatste decennia sterk achteruit is gegaan. Daarnaast hebben we al een brede kennis over de ecologie en het gedrag van scholeksters in Nederland, vooral door decennialange monitoring en onderzoek op het Waddeneiland Schiermonnikoog, waar scholeksters langs de kust (op de kwelder en de polder) broeden. Verder is er een aanzienlijk netwerk van burgerwetenschap (citizen science) dat een grote hoeveelheid gegevens verzamelt over het broedsucces en overleving (door middel van ringaflezingen). Dit onderzoek maakt deel uit van het CHIRP-project (Cumulative Human Impact on biRd Populations), dat als algemeen doel heeft om de cumulatieve invloed van alle potentiële menselijke drukfactoren op broedsucces en overleving van scholeksters in Nederland te kwantificeren.

Met behulp van ringaflezingen en veldwaarnemingen (van vrijwilligers en professionals) en door gebruik te maken van geavanceerde statistische analyses, vergroot dit proefschrift ons begrip over de ruimtelijke en temporele variatie van de reproductie van scholeksters in Nederland. Hierbij ga ik in op drie belangrijke kennishiaten (**hoofdstuk 1**): (i) het bestuderen van meerdere drukfactoren en hun synergetische effecten op grote ruimtelijke schaal (**hoofdstuk 4 & 5**) en (ii) het kwantificeren van de lichaamsconditie (**hoofdstuk 2**) (iii) om te onderzoeken hoe

lichaamsconditie het effect van de winteromgeving op het broedsucces in het volgende seizoen beïnvloedt (**hoofdstuk 3**).

Om het effect van omgevingsvariabelen op populaties te onderzoeken, wordt de lichaamsconditie vaak gebruikt als een maatstaaf voor de prestatie van een individu. Hoewel lichaamsconditie mogelijk een breed scala van dimensies van de gezondheidstoestand omvat (zoals voedings-, immuun- of hormonale status), maken de meeste onderzoeken de lichaamsconditie in de praktijk meetbaar met behulp van een enkele (univariate) maatstaaf, zoals vetopslag. Een reden om extra variatieassen uit te sluiten kan zijn dat multivariate karakteristieken van lichaamsconditie statistische en analytische uitdagingen met zich meebrengen. Structural equation modelling (SEM) wordt in veel onderzoeksgebieden gebruikt om vragen met betrekking tot multidimensionale concepten te bestuderen, en we laten in **hoofdstuk 2** zien hoe SEM een nuttig en krachtig analytisch hulpmiddel is om de multivariate aard van lichaamsconditie te beschrijven.

In **hoofdstuk 3** passen we deze analysetechniek (uit **hoofdstuk 2**) toe om te onderzoeken hoe de lichaamsconditie door omgevingsfactoren in de winter wordt beïnvloed en hoe dit het latere broedsucces beïnvloedt (een zo genaamd carry-over effect). Het is vooral een uitdaging om de belangrijkste oorzaken van populatiedynamiek bij migrerende soorten te identificeren, aangezien de individuen in verschillende stadia van de jaarlijkse cyclus die geografisch gescheiden zijn door verschillende factoren beïnvloedt kunnen worden. Daardoor is het effect van mogelijke omgevingsfactoren op de overwinteringslocaties mogelijk niet direct duidelijk en zichtbaar als ze doorspelen naar het broedseizoen. Het kwantificeren van carry-over effecten kan daarom helpen de oorzaken van de teruggang van een populatie te identificeren. We kwantificeren lichaamsconditie (zoals beschreven in **hoofdstuk 2**), omdat dit een belangrijke toestandsvariabele is die bij carry-over effecten een rol speelt. Onze resultaten laten zien dat de lichaamsconditie in de winter invloed heeft op het daaropvolgende broedsucces, wat wijst op een carry-over-effect. De overleving van de eieren en de kuikens in het voorjaar was groter bij ouders die in de voorafgaande winter een goede lichaamsconditie hadden. De lichaamsconditie in de winter liet een positief verband zien met het aandeel grasland rond het overwinteringsgebied. Andere omgevingsvariabelen in de winter (zoals beschikbaarheid van schelpdieren of

weersomstandigheden) hadden echter geen impact op de lichaamsconditie in de winter.

Naast de omgeving in de winter, kunnen er ook tijdens het broedseizoen drukfactoren zijn die het lage broedsucces in de scholeksterpopulatie veroorzaken. In weidevogelonderzoek worden vaak antropogene factoren zoals landbouwintensivering, predatie en klimaatverandering genoemd als oorzaken voor de teruggang van de populatie. Het is echter ook waarschijnlijk dat verschillende factoren op elkaar inwerken (en samenspelen). Het begrijpen van de werking van mogelijke zogenoemde synergetische effecten kan ons helpen een beter idee te krijgen van de oorzaken van de aanhoudende populatieafname. Daarmee kunnen mogelijk passende beheersmaatregelen gevonden worden. In **hoofdstuk 5** kwantificeren we de relatieve invloed van verschillende drukfactoren (roofdiersoorten, weeromstandigheden, voedselbeschikbaarheid en intensiteit van landbouw) op het broedsucces en bestuderen we de mogelijke interacties tussen deze factoren. Het gemiddelde broedsucces is 0,1 jongen/paar, wat ver onder het niveau ligt dat nodig is voor een stabiele populatie. Het belangrijkste knelpunt ligt in de overleving van de kuikens (in plaats van in de overleving van de eieren). Het voorkomen van roofdieren (predatoren) speelt een belangrijke rol bij het verklaren van variatie in het broedsucces en een minder geschikt habitat (door minder voedsel) leidt tot een grotere kwetsbaarheid voor predatie.

Een andere uitdaging in ecologisch onderzoek is dat niet alleen omgevingsfactoren elkaar wederzijds kunnen beïnvloeden, maar ook intrinsieke (dichtheid regulerende) factoren die interageren met extrinsieke (omgevings)factoren. Het is bekend dat dichtheidsafhankelijke effecten op voortplanting een belangrijke sturende factor kunnen zijn van de populatiedynamiek. Er wordt echter zelden over nagedacht dat de richting van het dichtheidsafhankelijke effect in ruimte en tijd kan variëren, afhankelijk van de roofdiergemeenschap. Hoewel groepsvorming van prooi-soorten het mogelijk maakt samen als groep vliegende predatoren te verjagen, kan het ook grondpredatoren aantrekken. Daardoor zou de overleving van nesten (eieren) dan als gevolg lager zijn, als de broedvogeldichtheid hoog is. In **hoofdstuk 4** laten we zien dat de ruimtelijke variatie in de samenstelling van de roofdiergemeenschap (vliegende vs. grondpredatoren) impact heeft op het effect van broedvogeldichtheid (zowel van

soortgenoten als ook andere soorten) op de nestoverleving van scholeksters. Als in een gebied meer grondpredatoren dan vliegende predatoren aanwezig zijn, is het nadelig om veel broedende burens dichtbij te hebben omdat de nesten dan minder lang overleven.

Hoofdstuk 6 vat de bijdrage van dit proefschrift samen in de context van het brede ecologische onderzoek en aan ons begrip over de ruimtelijke en temporele variatie van de reproductie van scholeksters in Nederland. Met dit proefschrift benadruk ik dat een grootschalige ecologische benadering belangrijk is om de populatiedynamiek te begrijpen, omdat (i) verschillende mechanismen in verschillende gebieden kunnen plaatsvinden en (ii) dat als hetzelfde mechanisme op veel gebieden werkt, we nog steeds data met substantiële ruimtelijke en temporele variatie moeten verzamelen om mogelijke relaties op een betrouwbare manier te kunnen detecteren en kwantificeren.

Voor de Nederlandse scholeksterpopulatie concluderen we dat het broedsucces te laag is om de populatie stabiel te houden en dat we ons moeten concentreren op het vergroten van de kuikenoverleving om de algehele reproductie te vergroten. De belangrijkste sturende factoren van de scholekster reproductie tijdens het broedseizoen zijn het voorkomen en de samenstelling van predatoren. Daarnaast zijn alternatieve foerageergebieden voor de adulte scholeksters in de winter een belangrijke bepalende factor voor de overleving van de kuikens (in het daaropvolgend voorjaar). Op basis van onze resultaten uit de verschillende hoofdstukken, geef ik enkele ideeën voor effectieve managementimplicaties om de reproductie van scholeksters in Nederland te verhogen.

CURRICULUM VITAE

LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

PE&RC TRAINING AND EDUCATION STATEMENT

CURRICULUM VITAE

Magali Frauendorf was born on the 29th of April 1988 in Eckernförde, Germany. Her interest in nature grew at a young age and in 2008 she started her study in Wildlife Management at Van Hall Larenstein in Leeuwarden, where she obtained a Bachelor of Applied Sciences in 2012. During her study she got during internships various opportunities to gain practical experiences in conducting scientific research (across several species groups like lynx, bats, birds) at different institutes in Costa Rica, Norway and Germany.

She then started as research assistant at the Institute for Terrestrial and Aquatic Wildlife Research, where she collected telemetry data to gain insight in habitat range and use of wild boar (*Sus scrofa*). Her interest for ecological research increased and therefore she decided to start the Master study Forest and Nature Conservation at Wageningen University in 2014, where she graduated cum laude in 2016. During her master thesis, she investigated the influence of environmental and physiological factors as well as hunting on the reproductive success of wild boar using a long-term dataset. During her master internship at Wageningen Environmental Research, she studied the effectiveness of different non-invasive methods (trap cam, video surveillance and track pads) to encounter the usage of crossing structures by ungulates at the Hoge Veluwe National Park.

In December 2016 she started her PhD in the project CHIRP (Cumulative Human Impact on BiRd Populations). She used long-term and large-scale datasets, a substantial citizen science network and fieldwork in combination with novel statistical techniques to investigate the causes of spatial and temporal variation in the reproductive performance of oystercatchers, which resulted in the present thesis. She was supervised by Hans de Kroon, Martijn van de Pol, Bruno Ens and Eelke Jongejans, and

she conducted her research at the Department of Animal Ecology the Netherlands Institute of Ecology (NIOO-KNAW) in collaboration with Radboud University in Nijmegen and Sovon, the Dutch Centre for Field Ornithology.

Currently, Magali works at Altenburg & Wymenga ecological research, where she is mainly involved in projects concerning meadow birds, shorebirds and goose management.

LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

Peer-reviewed

- Frauendorf, M.**, Allen, A. M., Jongejans, E., Ens, B. J., Teunissen, W., Kampichler, C., van Turnhout, C. A. M., Bailey, L. D., de Kroon, H., Cremer, J., Kleyheeg, E., Nienhuis, J., & van de Pol, M. (2022). Love thy neighbour?—Spatial variation in density dependence of nest survival in relation to predator community. *Diversity and Distributions*, *28*(4), 624–635. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.13457>
- Allen, A. M., Jongejans, E., van de Pol, M., Ens, B. J., **Frauendorf, M.**, van der Sluijs, M., & de Kroon, H. (2022). The demographic causes of population change vary across four decades in a long-lived shorebird. *Ecology*, *103*(4), e3615. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecy.3615>
- van Irsel, J., **Frauendorf, M.**, Ens, B. J., van de Pol, M., Troost, K., Oosterbeek, K., de Kroon, H., Jongejans, E., & Allen, A. M. (2022). State-dependent environmental sensitivity of reproductive success and survival in a shorebird. *Ibis*, *164*(3), 692–710. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ibi.13038>
- Frauendorf, M.**, Allen, A. M., Verhulst, S., Jongejans, E., Ens, B. J., van der Kolk, H.-J., de Kroon, H., Nienhuis, J., & van de Pol, M. (2021). Conceptualizing and quantifying body condition using structural equation modelling: A user guide. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, *90*(11), 2478–2496. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2656.13578>
- van der Kolk, H.-J., Ens, B. J., **Frauendorf, M.**, Jongejans, E., Oosterbeek, K., Bouten, W., & van de Pol, M. (2021). Why time-limited individuals can make populations more vulnerable to disturbance. *Oikos*, *130*(4), 637–651. <https://doi.org/10.1111/oik.08031>
- Allen, A. M., Ens, B. J., van de Pol, M., van der Jeugd, H., **Frauendorf, M.**, Oosterbeek, K., & Jongejans, E. (2019). Seasonal survival and migratory connectivity of the Eurasian Oystercatcher revealed by citizen science. *Auk*, *136*(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1093/auk/uky001>
- Allen, A. M., Ens, B. J., van de Pol, M., van der Jeugd, H., **Frauendorf, M.**, van der Kolk, H.-J., Oosterbeek, K., Nienhuis, J., & Jongejans, E. (2019). Colour-ring wear

and loss effects in citizen science mark-resighting studies. *Avian Research*, 10(11), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40657-019-0151-z>

- Linssen, H., van de Pol, M., Allen, A. M., Jans, M., Ens, B. J., Krijgsveld, K. L., **Frauendorf, M.**, & van der Kolk, H.-J. (2019). Disturbance increases high tide travel distance of a roosting shorebird but only marginally affects daily energy expenditure. *Avian Research*, 10(31), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40657-019-0171-8>
- van der Kolk, H.-J., Ens, B. J., Oosterbeek, K., Bouten, W., Allen, A. M., **Frauendorf, M.**, Lameris, T. K., Oosterbeek, T., Deuzeman, S., de Vries, K., Jongejans, E., & van de Pol, M. (2019). Shorebird feeding specialists differ in how environmental conditions alter their foraging time. *Behavioral Ecology*, 31(2), 371–382. <https://doi.org/10.1093/beheco/arz189>
- van der Kolk, H.-J., Krijgsveld, K. L., Linssen, H., Diertens, R., Dolman, D., Jans, M., **Frauendorf, M.**, Ens, B. J., & van de Pol, M. (2019). Cumulative energetic costs of military aircraft, recreational and natural disturbance in roosting shorebirds. *Animal Conservation*, 23(4), 359–372. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acv.12546>
- Frauendorf, M.**, Gethoffer, F., Siebert, U., & Keuling, O. (2016). The influence of environmental and physiological factors on the litter size of wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) in an agriculture dominated area in Germany. *Science of the Total Environment*, 541, 877–882. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.09.128>

In preparation

- Frauendorf, M.**, Allen, A. M., van der Kolk, H.-J., Cubaynes S., Ens, B. J., Verhulst, S., Jongejans, E., de Kroon, H., Oosterbeek, K., Troost, K., van de Pol, M. Body condition mediates carry-over effects of overwintering environment on reproductive success in a shorebird population.
- Frauendorf, M.**, Ens, B. J., Allen, A. M., Jongejans, E., de Kroon, H., Teunissen, W., Kampichler, C., Kleyheeg, E., Nienhuis, J., Oosterbeek, K., van de Sluijs, M., de Jong, M., de Jong, J., van de Pol, M. The synergistic effects of environmental drivers of declining reproduction of a threatened meadow bird across the Netherlands.

PE&RC TRAINING AND EDUCATION STATEMENT

With the training and education activities listed below the PhD candidate has complied with the requirements set by the C.T. de Wit Graduate School for Production Ecology and Resource Conservation (PE&RC), which comprises of a total of 44 ECTS exceeding the minimum total of 32 ECTS (= 22 weeks of activities).

Review of literature (4.5 ECTS)

- Behavioural and reproductive flexibility under changing environmental risks in Eurasian Oystercatcher (*Haematopus ostralegus*)

Post-graduate courses (4.7 ECTS)

- Integral projection models; online; Transmitting Science (2017)
- Structural equation modelling; PE&RC, the Netherlands (2018)
- Applied spatial modelling with R; KU Leuven (2018)
- Bayesian inference of animal demography; CEFE, Montpellier (2021)

Invited review of (unpublished) journal manuscripts (3 ECTS)

- Royal Society Open Science: wildlife management, population dynamics, habitat selection (2020)
- Biological Conservation: conservation, human disturbance, shorebird (2020)
- Wader study: disturbance, conservation (2020)

Deficiency, refresh, brush-up courses (2.1 ECTS)

- Modelling population dynamics, estimating demographic parameters for wildlife conservation; University of Debrecen, Hungary (2020)

Competence strengthening / skills courses (2.3 ECTS)

- Conference workshop, work–life balance in real life; British Ecological Society (2019)
- Conference workshop, getting social for science communication; British

- Ecological Society (2019)
- Conference workshop, transfer your science into news; Netherlands Annual Ecology Meeting (2019)
- PhD Workshop, the floor is yours: how to present your research online; Royal Belgian Zoological Society (2020)
- PhD Workshop, make me fly: manage stress during your PhD; Royal Belgian Zoological Society (2020)
- The journey of your career: PhD and Postdoc career development event; KNAW (2020)
- Coaching stress-management; KNAW (2021)
- Reviewing scientific manuscript; Wageningen Graduate School (WGS) (2021)

Scientific integrity / ethics in science activity (4.8 ECTS)

- Laboratory animal science designing procedures & projects and bird specific module; KNAW (2017)
- Scientific integrity course; NIOO-KNAW (2019)

PE&RC Annual meetings, seminars or weekends (3.95 ECTS)

- Netherlands Annual Ecology Meeting, Lunteren (2016)
- Netherlands Annual Ecology Meeting, Lunteren (2019)
- Netherlands Annual Ecology Meeting; oral presentation, Lunteren (2020)
- PE&RC Afternoon event (2011)

Discussion groups / local seminars or scientific meetings (4.5 ECTS)

- NIOO Seminars (2017-2020)
- NIOO Journal club (2017-2020)
- WEES Workshop (2019)
- Symposium: connecting rewilding science and practice (2020)
- International wader study group conference (2021)

International symposia, workshops and conferences (12.3 ECTS)

- International ornithological society conference; oral presentation; Vancouver, Canada (2018)
- International wader study group conference; oral presentation; Workum, the Netherlands (2018)
- European ornithological union conference; oral presentation; Cluj-Napoca,

Romania (2019)

- British ecological society meeting; oral presentation; Belfast, Ireland (2019)
- III Elvonal shorebird conference; oral presentation; Debrecen, Hungary (2020)
- International wader study group conference; oral presentation; online (2020)

Societally relevant exposure (2.1 ECTS)

- Speur dit voorjaar mee naar scholeksters met kleurringen; NatureToday (2017)
- Interview op Omrop Fryslân: scholekster met gps zender gezien meld het de onderzoekers (2017)
- Scholeksters zoeken, hoe komt het dat de scholekster zo fel achteruit gaat?; Mens&Vogel (2017)
- Interessant en dramatisch broedseizoen voor Nederlandse scholeksters; NatureToday (2017)
- Bedreiging scholekster komt van alle kanten; Artikel in Bionieuws (2017)
- Pilot broedsucces metingen van de scholekster in Noord-Holland; Jaarboek Boerenlandvogels Noord-Holland (2018)
- Scholeksters op daken; Natuurlijk Zoey, RTV Utrecht (2018)

Lecturing / supervision of practicals / tutorials (0.9 ECTS)

- Conservation biology, 1st year master students; Radboud University (2017)
- Conservation biology, 2nd year bachelor students; Wageningen University (2018)
- Conservation biology, 1st year master students; Radboud University (2018)

BSc / MSc thesis supervision (9 ECTS)

- Land management practices and predation affecting the reproductive success of Eurasian oystercatcher
- Incubation pattern in Eurasian oystercatcher
- Breeding ecology of inland breeding oystercatchers
- Nest site preferences of oystercatchers breeding in urban areas

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Acknowledgements

And here I am, reaching the end of my PhD journey, realizing that suddenly it is over and trying to condense many memories. I look back on a pile of work and a life-changing experience, with many downs but also major ups, being grateful for every single moment that helped me to grow personally and professionally. However, this work would have been impossible without the support of great people around me that have been offering their advice and help along the way.

First of all, thank you to each individual **oystercatcher** that we had in our hand for scientific purpose. You never asked for being a study species. It was an absolute pleasure to work with you, learning so much about the nature of your species and letting new fascinating scientific questions arise.

Next, thank you to my team of supervisors **Martijn van de Pol**, **Hans de Kroon**, **Bruno Ens** and **Eelke Jongejans**. **Martijn**, you are a fantastic mentor. Thank you for all your effort, patience, motivation and enthusiasm along the whole way of my PhD. Your door was always open to discuss ideas, no matter how big or small. Your input often made things so much clearer to me and your encouragement made a big difference when things went wrong. You supported me in developing my own research ideas and taught me so much about the various facets of doing research, to think big and never give up. I especially owe you my steep learning curve on a statistical level. Thank you for being my daily supervisor the last couple of years. It has been an invaluable experience. **Hans**, thank you for providing me with the opportunity to test myself in science. You had a good feeling at which point I needed some positive feedback and kind words to keep me motivated. Thank you for all your support, the learning moments and discussions during the last years. **Bruno**, you have an incredible passion for oystercatchers and your endurance to continue the research on oystercatchers in the Netherlands is amazing. Science involves building upon the previous achievements of others and that is very apparent in this oystercatcher work. Thank you for all your support in the past years that made this work possible and for sharing your broad network, of both researchers and volunteers, with me. **Eelke**, thank you for always having an open door to discuss any issue. You often offered me a different perspective and much inspiration, for my project and research questions, but also for science in general.

I also want to thank all co-authors. Your efforts substantially improved the quality

of this thesis. Sharing your knowledge and/or data helped to advance our understanding of this research field. Thank you **Christian Kampichler, Chris van Turnhout, Erik Kleyheeg, Jan de Jong, Jenny Cremer, Jeroen Nienhuis, Karin Troost, Kees Oosterbeek, Liam Bailey, Martijn van de Sluijs, Martin de Jong, Simon Verhulst** and **Wolf Teunissen** for great ideas and your vital contribution. **Sarah Cubaynes**, your help with the Bayesian CR-SEM model was immense. I am grateful to have met such a passionate and supportive researcher. Unfortunately because of the pandemic we could not meet in real life, but I really hope that our paths will cross again (in real life) in the near future. **Henk-Jan van der Kolk** and **Andrew Allen**. It was an inspiration to work with you together in the CHIRP project. Thank you! Who knows, maybe there will be some future collaborations.

Thanks to all my colleagues at the department of Animal Ecology at NIOO for their company and discussions during lunch time, coffee breaks or beer o'clocks: **Antica, Barbara, Bart van L., Bart N., Bernice, Cas, Chiel, Christa, Claire, Davide B., Davide D., Eva, Filipe, Götz, Gretchen, Henk, Henk-Jan, Irene, Jip, Judith, Kamiel, Kees S., Kees van O., Krista, Liam, Louis, Marcel, Melanie, Melissah, Mo, Monique, Nathalie, Nelleke, Nina B., Nina M., Rascha, Thomas, Tjomme** and **Veronica. Morrison** and **Jurrian**, thank you for being great PhD colleagues and especially for supporting me during the last stretch as “paranymphs”. I was extremely lucky to work in such a great place as the NIOO, where I had support for varied tasks, from building a box for taking standardized photographs from oystercatcher bills to arranging a ‘working’ caravan for the students staying on Texel and organizing volunteer days. I am grateful to the whole NIOO staff and I just would like to name some people that I constantly went to for help: **Elly, Gerrie, Wim, Jeroen** and **Gilles**. Thank you all!

Thank you, **Karen Krijgsveld, Hans van Gasteren, Luca van Duren, Gerrit Dommerholt, Jeroen Jansen, Erik Jansen, Mirka Marcel, Maarten Platteeuw, Meinte Engelmoer** and **Evert Jan Lammerts**, for the feedback and input you provided during our half-yearly project meetings.

I would like to take this opportunity to also thank **Ruud Foppen, Ryan Norris, Irene Tieleman, Jan van Gils, David Kleijn, Bart Nolet** and **Roos Kentie** for agreeing to be part of the Doctoral Examination Board and assessing my thesis.

A very special thank you to **Kees Oosterbeek** for sharing your years of knowledge

Acknowledgements

and field experience. The winter catches would not have been such a success without you! Also a big thank to **Symen Deuzeman, Martijn van de Sluijs, Peter de Vries, Rafael Martig and Nadia Hijner** for supporting us during the catches in winter and/or monitoring the breeding success in summer. **Jeroen Onrust**, thank you for sharing your experience and knowledge on all 'worm-related' topics. Even though I did not manage to include all the effort (of collected soil samples) in this thesis, I will work on writing it up in the future. **Greta van Hoorn**, een goede administratie is het halve werk. Dank je wel voor al je inzet rond de kleur -en metalen ringen. Ik vond het altijd gezellig samen de strengen voor het broedseizoen klaar te maken.

I would also like to thank all the students who worked with me and helped A LOT, both in the field during summer and winter as well as indoors, making this project possible. I will start at the beginning try to not forget anyone: **Lisenka de Vries, Kelly de Vries, Daisey van Biezem, Manon van Wesel, Kathelijne Maes, Alfred Kok, Marc Stadman, Jurrian van Irsel, Foteini Balafa, Katrin Schifferle, Rianne van Deelen, Els Ribbers, Iryna Litovska, Audrey Dunn, Ferran Fitó and Anna Wessel**. I hoped that you enjoyed the time and had the chance to learn a lot during your internship or thesis. I wish you success in your future careers!

Mijn grote dank gaat uit naar alle vrijwilligers die die zich ingezet hebben om het project op deze manier mogelijk te maken door het monitoren van het broedsucces en het delen van hun gegevens, het doorgeven van ringaflezingen en het vangen van de scholeksters in de winter en hun kennis en ervaringen te delen. Speciaal benoemen wil ik hierbij **Aad van Paassen, Andries Berghuis, Bart Ebbinge, Benny Middendorp, Carl Zuhorn, Chris Grobbe, Cor Smit, Derick Hiemstra, Dick Veenendaal, Dirk Tanger, Doortje Dallmeijer, Ed Weijburg, Eddie Douwma, Egbert Zorgdrager, Els Marijs, Evert Eijkelenboom, Floor Arts, Frank Majoor, Fred Cottaar, Freerk de Boer, Gerard Westerhuis, Gerben Krösschell, Gert Jan Verbeek, Hans Hasper, Hans Keijzer, Harmke de Hoogh, Harry Horn, Hein Vogt, Henri Zomer, Jacob Jan de Vries, Jan Boos, Jan de Jong, Jan Vegelin, Jaap Booij, Jeffrey Huizenga, Jeroen Nachtegaal, Johan Bos, Johan Tuls, John Brands, Joop Scheijbeler, Joop van Wijk, Jos Tramper, Jouke Altenburg, Kees de Jager, Kees Venneker, Klaas van Dijk, Koos Minnaar, Koos van Es, Leon Kelder, Maarten Hottig, Maarten Sluijter, Maarten van Kleinwee, Mario Huizinga, Martin van de Reep, Miranda Berghuis, Peter Das, Peter de Boer, Peter de Klein, Petra**

Mansche, Rafaella Porcu, René Vos, Roland-Jan Buijs, Sander Lilipaly, Siebe Bonthuis, Sylvana Harmsen, Sytze Algera, Theunis Banga, Tijs van den Berg, Tim Raats, Tom Voortman, Toos Hulshoff en Wil Segboer. Dank je wel!

Laurens en Tonny van Kooten, zonder jullie hulp en steun hadden we nooit zoveel gegevens kunnen verzamelen. **Laurens**, je inzet is ongelooflijk en ik ben je heel erg dankbaar voor je altijd gezellige bijzijn tijdens het veldwerk. Bij elke wintervangst konden we op je rekenen en of het nu om het vangen van de scholeksters in het broedseizoen ging, bodemmonsters nemen of de BMP doen, je was er altijd klaar voor, zonder vermoeidheid en altijd met een gezellig verhaaltje. Dank jullie wel ook voor jullie gastvrijheid. Er was altijd een slaapplek voor me klaar in jullie huisje toen ik weer twee dagjes naar Texel moest. En Tonny, jij zorgde altijd voor een warme maaltijd na een lange velddag, en ook al kwam ik weer te laat voor het eten, jullie hebben altijd op me gewacht. Dank je wel ook voor de ontzettend leuke scholekster die je voor me gehaakt hebt. Hij staat altijd op mijn bureau en geeft me heel veel mooie herinneringen. Jullie hebben me ook uit de brand geholpen door onverwacht Iryna een tijd op te nemen. Ik ben heel erg dankbaar jullie te mogen hebben ontmoeten en samen te mogen werken. Het was een heel erg leuke tijd waar ik graag naar terug kijk.

Bert Dijkstra en Rinus Dillerop, dank jullie wel voor al jullie inzet in het scholekster onderzoek rond Assen. De lange termijn gegevens die jullie ondertussen verzameld hebben zijn heel waardevol. Ik denk graag terug aan onze actie van het nemen van de bodemmonsters in en rond Assen. Helaas is dat deel geen onderdeel van mijn proefschrift geworden, maar er zal zeker nog een artikel over aankomen!

Ik herinner me nog goed hoe ik na een dagje veldwerk op Texel stopte bij het Normerven om met jou, **Wim Tijssen**, nog een aantal scholeksters op het nest te vangen en ringen. We hadden een scholekster bij de 'boerin' gevangen en je benadrukte nog dat je een foto wilde maken voor haar van de geringde scholekster en ik hem per ongeluk op het eind al losliet voordat je de kans had een foto te maken. En natuurlijk de kluten pulletjes, die bij de ijsbaan rondliepen en een ringetje kregen van jou. Uiteraard ook heel erg bedankt voor je hulp bij de wintervangsten bij het Normerven en dat je na de vangst nog de schuur bij je thuis ter beschikking stelde zodat we de bloedmonsters nog konden centrifugereren en meten (bij wat meer licht en warmte met lekker koffie en thee) tot vroeg in de ochtend.

Acknowledgements

Marc van Leeuwen en Sjerp Weima, dank voor jullie hulp met het scholekster ringwerk rond Houten. Hoe goed herinner ik me nog Sjerp, dat we op Hemelsvaartdag samen langs de Lek stonden te wachten (met een koffie en thee en leuke verhalen) dat de scholeksters op het nest gingen zitten. Hierbij ontstond ook het idee dat we in hoofdstuk 4 hebben onderzocht. Marc, wat voor een verassing was het toch toen je belde en vroeg of ik het goed vond als Eddy Zoëy (van Natuurlijk Zoey) mij zou interviewen als we het scholekster paartje op het Van der Valk Hotel gingen ringen. Pas toen ik ophing kwam ik erachter hoe 'bekend' hij eigenlijk is. Misschien had ik anders geen ja gezegd. Het was een leuke ervaring en ik ben je er dankbaar voor en uiteraard ook al het ring en monitor werk dat jullie, Sjerp en Marc, samen in het ringgebied Houten verrichten.

Siebold van Breukelen, dank je wel voor de mogelijkheid om op de Hoge Berg onderzoek naar scholeksters te mogen doen. Je regelde dat er genoeg agrariërs akkoord waren met het idee de scholeksters op de Hoge Berg intensief te gaan monitoren met alles wat erbij hoort, zoals studenten die op hun percelen rondlopen. Ik ben heel blij dat het monitoren (in minder intensieve mate) nog wel doorgaat op de Hoge Berg en ook hier over de jaren heen nog hele interessante ontdekkingen gedaan kunnen worden.

Ineke en Leen Breukel, dank jullie wel dat we 'Piet' jaar in jaar uit opnieuw mochten volgen op jullie dak en jullie er alles voor deden dat de kuikens niet van het dak af vielen. We waren altijd welkom en de koffie stond klaar. Dank jullie!

Gerhard Luehning, Helmut Bähr und Hans-Joachim Hoff, auch euch möchte ich für die tolle Zusammenarbeit und Hilfe bei der Beobachtung unseres ‚Jailbird‘, der auf dem Dach der Justizvollzugsanstalt brütet, danken.

Grote dank ook aan alle **agrariërs** en **organisaties** die ons toegang tot hun land hebben gegeven om de scholeksters te volgen en/of te vangen.

Luzie, Danke auch dir für deine gestalterische Unterstützung. Ohne zu zögern hast du es auf dich genommen, mir Austernfischer (mit Küken) zu gestalten, die ich bei vielzähligen Konferenzen in den letzten Jahren eingesetzt habe und die in dieser Arbeit als ‚Headings‘ zum Einsatz kommen. Und natürlich auch die Gestaltung des Covers in den letzten Monaten (im Endspurt). Es hat Spaß gemacht, mit dir zusammen Ideen aus zu tauschen und es war natürlich mit mir als Kunde unvermeidlich, dass noch ein paar

detailgetreue Verbesserungen nötig waren. Ich bin zufrieden mit dem Ergebnis!

Abschließend möchte ich die Gelegenheit nutzen, meiner Familie zu danken. Viele wichtige Entwicklungen im Leben beginnen bei den Eltern. Ihr habt mir als Kind schon die Natur Nahe gebracht wie zum Beispiel in den Ferien in Dänemark oder in den Alpen. Und wer weiß, wo ich heute wäre, wenn ich die Liebe zur Natur und den Tieren nicht schon als Kind hätte entwickeln können. **Mama** und **Papa**, ohne eure Liebe, Weisheit, Rat und Unterstützung in all den Jahren wäre ich heute nicht an diesem Punkt. Ich denke noch oft an den Tag zurück, an dem meine Reise in den Niederlanden begann, als wir, Mama, zusammen nach Leeuwarden gefahren sind, um uns ganz unverbindlich beim Van Hall Larenstein zu informieren. Ihr habt mich ermutigt, diesen Schritt zu wagen und auch wenn ich weiter weg war, wusste ich, dass ihr da seid, wenn ich euch brauche. Ihr habt immer hinter meinen Entscheidungen gestanden und auch wenn ihr vielleicht nicht immer ganz verstanden habt, womit ich mich bei meiner Doktorarbeit nun schon wieder beschäftige und ihr euch gefragt habt wie das alles nur so lange dauern kann oder ich (wieder) am Wochenende keine Zeit fand, den langen Weg nach Felde auf mich zu nehmen, ich konnte immer auf euch zählen. Für die kalten Tage und Nächte beim Fangen im Winter wurde ich immer wieder gut versorgt mit warmer selbst-gestrickter Kleidung. Danke!

Anabel, ich bin sehr dankbar, dass du meine Schwester bist. Du warst immer für mich da, wenn ich mal wieder eine Down-Phase hatte. Regelmäßig kamen Survival Pakete hier an, um mich zum Durchhalten zu motivieren und auch unsere kleine Auszeiten zwischendurch nach Schiermonnikoog oder Rom habe ich sehr genossen.

Je veux également remercier ma famille française. Surtout **Mami** et **Papi**, vous m'avez appris à aimer et à apprécier la nature quand j'étais petite. Mami, je me souviens bien comment nous avons séché et collé ensemble les feuilles de la flore dans un cahier pour que je les apprenne. J'en garde le souvenir. Malheureusement tu n'auras pas pu vivre ma décision de prendre la filière de la biologie après mon bac et par la suite mon travail dans la recherche écologique. Papi, tu aimais faire les photos de nature et de faune sauvage (terrestre et aquatique en faisant de la plongée sous-marine) et tu m'en as fait profiter aussi. Tu m'as beaucoup soutenu dans le choix de mes études et tu m'as accompagné sur mon chemin jusqu'ici. Tu savais que j'allais commencer cette aventure de recherche doctorale, mais malheureusement tu ne pourras pas être

Acknowledgements

témoin de mon soutien de thèse. Je sais que tu serais très fier de ce résultat. Merci!

Marc, merci pour ta passion, pour les récits de tes aventures sur tout le globe et pour tes photos de la faune sauvage. C'est impressionnant et encourageant à la fois. Je suis très heureuse de partager cette passion avec toi.

Henny en Arie, ook al heb je je schoonouders niet voor het uitkiezen, ik mag zeker niet klagen. Dank jullie voor al de steun in de afgelopen jaren. Er was steeds tijd voor een kopje koffie en een luisterend oor. De 'bordjes waren altijd warm' voor een onderbreking van mijn werk.

En tot slot **Matthijs**, mijn grootste dank ben ik aan jouw verschuldigd. Jij hebt zeker het meeste meegekregen, en het het moeilijkst gehad, met mij als onderzoeker en promovenda in huis. Jouw steun is onmisbaar geweest in al deze jaren om deze mijlpaal te behalen; jij bent 'mein Fels in der Brandung'. Daarom wil ik jou speciaal bedanken voor de mooie tijd, je liefde, loyaliteit en begrip. We delen de passie voor de natuur en daar geniet ik enorm van en ik ben benieuwd waar onze gezamenlijke reis in de toekomst nog naar toe gaat. Thank you for being with me all this time; you are such an important part of my life!

